

School of Education and Social Sciences

**Home and Away: The Lived Experiences of UK-based Algerian Doctoral
Graduates on Returning Home to Algeria**

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Author's Declaration

This is to certify that to the best of my knowledge, the content of this thesis is my original work, but for quotations and citations which have been acknowledged. This thesis has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other university.

Signed: AMZ

29/11/2024

Dedication

In the name of Allah, the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful. All praise is due to Allah, the source of wisdom, knowledge, and strength. I am profoundly grateful for the resilience, patience, and determination that Allah has granted me throughout this challenging and deeply transformative journey of seeking knowledge.

This work is dedicated to myself for the perseverance, strength, patience, and courage I demonstrated throughout my PhD journey; a journey that was far from easy and was marked by profound challenges and personal losses that tested my strength in ways I never imagined.

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Abstract

Studying abroad has long been recognised as a vital component of higher education, offering opportunities for knowledge acquisition and fostering global perspectives. For developing countries like Algeria, sending students abroad for advanced education is a key strategy for capacity building. Exposure to diverse academic systems and cultural contexts equips scholars with skills and insights to drive national development upon their return. In 2014, the Algerian government launched an international scholarship programme, funding five hundred Master's students from English language departments to pursue doctoral studies in the UK. Contractually obligated to return, these scholars were tasked with strengthening Algeria's higher education sector.

While much research has examined the experiences of students abroad, the post-return phase remains underexplored. This phenomenological study addresses this gap by investigating the lived experiences of Algerian academics who completed their doctorates in the UK and reintegrated into the Algerian higher education system. Using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), this qualitative research captures the personal and professional challenges and opportunities experienced by returnees, highlighting their efforts to adapt and apply their international experiences within local academic institutions. Through in-depth interviews, the study prioritises the voices of returning scholars, shedding light on the transformative impact of their global exposure and its implications for Algeria's higher education.

The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and researchers. Key recommendations include mentorship programmes for returning academics, networking platforms, and cross-cultural training to enhance collaboration. By addressing the challenges of reintegration, this research highlights the need for robust support systems to maximise the contributions of returning scholars. It also enriches the broader discourse on international education and knowledge transfer, offering actionable solutions to empower returning academics as agents of change within Algeria's higher education sector.

Keywords: Studying Abroad, Algerian Doctoral Graduates, Reintegration, Higher Education, Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), International Education, Knowledge Transfer.

Table of Contents

Author's Declaration.....	ii
Dedication	iii
Acknowledgement	v
Abstract.....	vi
List of Tables.....	xii
List of Figures	xiii
List of Abbreviations and Acronyms.....	xiv
Chapter One	1
General Introduction	1
Significance of the Study.....	1
Global Mobility of Higher Education	5
The Role of International Education in Personal and Professional Development.....	6
Specific Focus on Algerian Students in the UK.....	7
Research Motivation	8
Research Problem and Rationale.....	10
The Gap in Existing Literature.....	10
Research Aims and Objectives	11
Research Questions	12
Methodology Overview.....	13
Overview of Study Participants	14
Conclusion.....	14
Chapter Two.....	15
Contextual Background.....	15
A Brief Introduction to Algeria and its History	15
Demography of Algeria.....	15
Linguistic Diversity in the Pre-colonial era	16
French Colonialism and Its Impact on Algerian Life	18
Education in Algeria.....	20
Outline of the Algerian Educational System.....	20
The Status of English as a Foreign Language in Algeria.....	21
Higher Education in Algeria	22
Algerian Doctoral Mobility	23
British Council Scheme.....	24
Algerians Studying Abroad	25
Conclusion.....	26
Chapter Three.....	27
Literature Review	27

Internationalisation of Higher Education.....	27
Degree Mobility and Doctoral Education	29
Impact of International Experience on International Students	31
Critical Perspectives on International Experience	32
Transnational Education	34
Professional Dimensions: Knowledge Transfer and Professional Development	36
Knowledge Transfer.....	36
Professional Development	37
Academic Returnees.....	39
Identity and Culture: Conceptual Perspectives.....	41
Cultural Identity, Acculturation, and Re-entry	42
Cultural Distance and Re-entry Adjustment.....	44
Professional Identity in Transnational Academic Contexts.....	46
Identity Shifts at the Intersection of Cultural and Professional Domains	47
Transformative Learning Model.....	48
Key Components of Transformative Learning	49
Transformative Learning in the Context of Study Abroad	49
Schlossberg’s Transition Model.....	51
Psychological Dimensions of Re-entry.....	53
Understanding Readjustment in the Re-entry Context.....	55
Institutional and Professional Reintegration	56
Models of Re-entry Adjustment.....	57
Culture Shock and Reverse Culture Shock	58
Critical Perspectives on Stage Models of Re-entry	60
Experiencing Re-entry: Emotional and Social Challenges	62
Emotional Disruption and Sense of Loss	62
Relational Tensions and Identity Repositioning	63
Global Disruptions and the COVID-19 Pandemic: Implications for Returnees	64
Adaptation and Coping Strategies	65
Conclusion.....	66
Chapter Four.....	68
Research Methodology.....	68
Theoretical assumptions underpinning the study	68
Research Design and Rationale.....	70
Qualitative Research Design.....	71
Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA).....	72
Phenomenology.....	72
Hermeneutics	73

Idiography	73
Strengths of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis	73
Limitations and Critical Considerations of IPA	74
The Rationale for Choosing IPA.....	75
Reflexivity.....	76
Data Collection Methods.....	78
Pilot Study.....	78
Reflection on Pilot Interviews.....	79
Semi-Structured Interviews	80
Online Interviews.....	82
Interview Questions Development	83
Participants Recruitment.....	84
Participants Profile Table Explanation.....	89
Facing the Recruitment Challenge: Insights from the Field.....	90
Steps for IPA Analysis	91
Step 1: Reading and Rereading	91
Stage 2: Exploratory Noting (EN).....	91
Step 3: Constructing Experiential Statements (ES)	91
Step 4: Searching for Connections Across Experiential Statements (ES)	92
Step 5: Moving to the Next Case.....	92
Step 6: Looking for Patterns Across Cases	92
Principles to Ensure IPA Validity	93
Sensitivity to context.....	94
Commitment and Rigour	95
Transparency and Coherence	95
Importance and Impact.....	96
Ethics consideration	96
Human Subjects' Safety.....	98
Conclusion.....	99
Chapter Five	100
Findings and Discussion: Personal Journeys of Return.....	100
Participant Profiles	100
From Participant Accounts to Group Experiential Themes.....	104
GET1: Cultural and Social Re-adaptation	105
Subtheme 1: Navigating Transition and Cultural Reconnection	105
GET 2: Personal Growth	110
Subtheme 1: Broadening Perspectives and Social Growth	111
Subtheme 2: Building Resilience and Independence.....	119

GET 3: Psychological Well-being and Coping in Re-entry	121
Sub-theme 1: Coping with Transition and Emotional Toll.....	121
Subtheme 2: The Impact of COVID-19 on Emotional Wellbeing.....	127
Conclusion.....	130
Chapter Six.....	132
Findings and Discussion: Professional Reintegration	132
GET 1: Academic Reintegration and Adaptation	133
Subtheme 1: Academic Disconnect and Tension with Colleagues	133
Subtheme 2: Managing Expectations and Academic Realities	142
GET 2: Innovation and Resistance in Academic Practice.....	147
Subtheme 1: Overcoming Resistance and Implementing Progressive Teaching Methods	148
Subtheme 2: support Networks and Positive Workplace	151
GET 3: Bureaucratic and Credential Challenges	155
Subtheme 1: Navigating Bureaucratic Barriers	155
Subtheme 2: Credential Recognition Challenges	158
GET 4: Professional Growth and Resources Constraints.....	163
Subtheme 1: Application of Experiences and Skills.....	164
Subtheme 2: Limited Resources and Teaching Infrastructure	166
Subtheme 3: Navigating Professional Challenges Amidst COVID-19	169
Conclusion.....	172
Chapter Seven	174
Synthesis	174
Re-entry as Disorientation and Self-Reconstruction.....	175
Navigating Professional Realities: Clashing Professional Identities and Institutional Culture.....	177
Reverse Culture Shock: Beyond National Culture	180
A Journey of Transformation: Gratitude and Lasting Impact.....	181
Relating the Findings to the Research Questions	182
Re-entry as Layered Negotiation and Ongoing Becoming.....	185
Chapter Eight.....	190
General Conclusion.....	190
Summary of the Process	190
Contribution to Knowledge	191
Recommendations Arising from the Study	192
Challenges of the Study.....	193
Areas for Future Research Arising from the Research	195
Dissemination of Research	196
Practical Engagement and Support Initiatives.....	197
Reflections on using IPA.....	198

Reflections on Personal and Professional Growth.....	199
Bibliography.....	202
Appendices.....	218

List of Tables

Table 1: The Selection Criteria of Selected Students Competing in the National PhD Competition (Algerian Ministry of Higher Education, 2014).

Table 2: Participants Profile Table.

List of Figures

Figure 1: Overview of the interrelationship Between the Building Blocks of Research (Grix, 2004, p.68).

Figure 2: Screenshot of Participant Interaction

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

E.N: Exploratory Noting

ES: Experiential Statements

GET: Group Experiential Statement

HE: Higher Education

IPA: Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis

LMD: License, Master, Doctorate

MENA: Middle East and North Africa

PET: Personal Experiential Statement

Ph.D.: Doctor of Philosophy

RCS: Reverse Culture Shock

TL: Transformative Learning

UK: United Kingdom

UNESCO: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

Chapter One

General Introduction

Introduction

This thesis explores the lived experiences of Algerian PhD graduates who pursued their doctoral studies in the United Kingdom and subsequently returned to Algeria. I examine how these individuals navigated the personal, social, cultural, and professional dimensions of reintegration following an extended period of international academic mobility. While international education is widely recognised for its transformative potential, I argue that return to the home country is often marked by complex processes of re-adjustment, identity re-negotiation, and professional re-positioning.

Situated within wider debates on international student mobility, return migration, and transnational academic careers, I adopt an interpretative phenomenological approach to provide an in-depth, experience-based understanding of what return ‘means’ for Algerian doctoral returnees. Through close engagement with participants’ narratives, I focus on how return is experienced emotionally, culturally, and professionally, rather than treating reintegration as a purely structural or economic transition.

In this chapter, I begin by establishing the significance of the study and providing an executive overview of the thesis structure. I then situate the research within the broader context of global higher education mobility and international education before narrowing to the specific case of Algerian doctoral students in the UK. Finally, I outline the research problem, aims, and questions, my positionality as researcher, and an overview of the methodological approach.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant at three interrelated levels: academic, practical, and socio-economic, offering original insight into the under-researched experiences of doctoral return migration in the Algerian and wider Global South context. While extensive research explores the experiences of international students during their time abroad (Knight, 2012; Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015), there is limited understanding of what happens once these individuals return to their home countries, particularly in regions like North Africa. Tran and Gomes (2017) highlight that international doctoral returnees are often neglected in current academic discussions, further emphasising the importance of this research.

By focusing on the lived experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees, this study provides a detailed perspective on return migration and reintegration. It extends the understanding of international education by offering a more holistic perspective that includes academic and cultural adaptation abroad and the complexities of reintegration upon return. It contributes to theoretical discourses on identity, belonging, and the concept of 'home', examining how returning graduates negotiate their sense of self within socio-cultural and institutional contexts that differ markedly from their host countries.

Moreover, it addresses the broader research gap concerning post-return experiences in the Arab world. Return migration studies have been conducted in countries such as Australia, China, Indonesia, Malaysia, Turkey, Finland, Greece, Kazakhstan, Korea, Singapore, the USA, Iran, Kurdistan, and Vietnam, yet research focusing specifically on the Arab region is scarce as I am arguing throughout my thesis. Within this region, most studies have concentrated on Saudi Arabia (e.g. Alandejasni, 2013; Almuarik, 2019; Alsulami, 2021; Winkel, Strachan, and Aamir, 2021; Alkhalaf, Al-Krenawi, and Elbedour, 2024), leaving other contexts such as Algeria largely unexplored. This study addresses this imbalance by focusing on Algerian PhD returnees and offering original insights into the unique dynamics of their re-entry experiences.

This study holds practical significance, particularly for developing countries like Algeria, where the return of highly skilled individuals is critical for national development and capacity building (Nour, 2019). Algeria's scholarship programmes, initiated in the 1970s under the Late President Houari Boumediene, were designed to educate students abroad to contribute to national reconstruction and progress (Smaili and Benamara, 2022). By examining the challenges and successes of returning graduates, this research provides valuable insights into the broader implications of international education for knowledge transfer, institutional development, and capacity building. The historical and policy context underpinning these programmes is discussed in greater detail in Chapter two.

The practical implications extend to stakeholders in both Algeria and the UK. For UK institutions, understanding the post-return experiences of their international graduates can inform the development of extended support services that go beyond graduation, such as alumni networks, career counselling, and re-entry workshops. For Algerian policymakers and institutions, the study sheds light on professional and cultural barriers faced by returning graduates, including limited research resources, bureaucratic hurdles, resistance to change, and social and cultural challenges, which have also been documented in studies of returnees across different national contexts (Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019; Alsulami, 2021). These findings emphasise the

importance of targeted reintegration policies, mentorship schemes, access to research grants, and institutional reforms to maximise the contributions of returnees.

Beyond its academic and policy contributions, this study holds broader socio-economic significance, particularly in relation to 'brain gain', 'brain circulation' within national development strategies. Brain gain refers to the potential benefits associated with the return or engagement of highly skilled migrants, including knowledge transfer, innovation, and capacity building in home-country institutions (Migration Research, 2009). Closely related, brain circulation emphasises the dynamic and ongoing movement of skills, ideas, and professional networks across national borders, rather than a one-directional loss or return of talent (Migration Research, 2009).

By examining the factors that influence the success of returning graduates, the research highlights the potential of internationally educated individuals to contribute meaningfully to their home countries. This aligns with evidence suggesting that skilled migration and return can generate positive development effects through knowledge transfer, investment, and innovation (Chen, 2017; De Wit and Altbach, 2021). Such contributions, however, depend upon conducive institutional and policy environments that enable returnees to act as agents of change within their societies (Cassarino, 2004; Meyer, 2011).

This is particularly relevant for Algeria, where the effective utilisation of human capital has been identified as a key national priority to address ongoing socio-economic challenges and enhance development outcomes (Nour, 2019; EUDiF, 2020). Returning graduates possess the potential to introduce innovative teaching practices, advanced research methodologies, and global networks that can enrich local academia and professional sectors (Knight, 2012; Karakaş, 2020). Yet systemic barriers such as institutional rigidity, bureaucratic inefficiencies, and societal resistance to change often constrain these contributions (Pikos-Sallie, 2018; Alsulami, 2021).

By focusing on both the challenges and opportunities of return migration, this study provides a nuanced understanding of how institutional structures and societal attitudes can either foster or hinder the integration and impact of returning scholars. It situates Algeria within the broader global narrative of 'brain circulation' rather than 'brain drain' (Sussman, 2002; Altbach, 2014), highlighting the interplay between individual experiences and systemic factors. In doing so, it contributes to a more inclusive and comprehensive understanding of return migration and its implications for development (Docquier and Rapoport, 2012).

Structure of My Thesis

Having outlined the significance of the study, this section presents an overview of how the thesis is organised. This thesis is organised into eight chapters, which together examine the personal, social, cultural, and professional experiences of UK-trained Algerian doctoral graduates following their return to Algeria. The study shows that return is rarely a simple ‘homecoming’; rather, it is characterised by experiences of reverse culture shock, identity disruption and re-negotiation, institutional constraints, and tensions between globally shaped academic identities and local professional cultures, alongside opportunities for personal growth, resilience, and professional agency.

- **Chapter 1: General Introduction** – Sets the stage for the research by outlining the key themes, research problem, significance, and objectives of the study. It presents the research questions that guide the investigation and introduces the methodological approach adopted. This chapter provides an overview of the study’s scope and purpose, helping the reader understand the relevance and direction of the research.
- **Chapter 2: Contextual Background** – Provides a foundational overview of Algeria, focusing on its history, linguistic and cultural landscape, and the impact of French colonialism. It outlines the Algerian educational system, including the status of English in Algeria and the current landscape of doctoral programmes. This chapter situates the study within the wider national and institutional context into which doctoral graduates return.
- **Chapter 3: Literature Review** – Reviews existing literature on international student mobility, return migration, and the experiences of returning graduates, with particular attention to doctoral returnees and the limited work on Algeria. It identifies key conceptual lenses and gaps in the literature that this study seeks to address.
- **Chapter 4: Methodology** – Outlines the research design, methods, and analytical approach used in the study. It details the qualitative approach adopted, including participant selection, data collection through semi-structured interviews, the use of IPA, and ethical considerations. The chapter also discusses the researcher’s positionality and the strategies employed to ensure rigour and trustworthiness.
- **Chapter 5: Findings – Personal and Social Perspectives** – Presents the findings related to the personal, emotional, and social dimensions of return among UK-based Algerian doctoral graduates. This chapter examines how participants experienced re-entry not

simply as physical relocation, but as a process of cultural and identity negotiation. It explores themes including reverse culture shock within family and community contexts, shifts in belonging, identity re-positioning, psychological wellbeing, and personal growth. The chapter highlights how return involved layered processes of sense-making shaped by both continuity and transformation.

- **Chapter 6: Findings – Professional and Academic Perspectives** – Focuses on the professional reintegration of returning graduates within Algerian higher education institutions. It examines how participants negotiated workplace cultures, institutional constraints, bureaucratic structures, and resistance to pedagogical change. Particular attention is given to tensions between internationally shaped professional identities and locally embedded academic norms, as well as the gendered dimensions of some workplace challenges. The chapter foregrounds how professional reintegration involved ongoing negotiation of legitimacy, authority, and agency within institutional contexts.
- **Chapter 7: Synthesis Chapter** – Synthesises the findings from Chapters 5 and 6, integrating the personal, social, and professional perspectives of the returning graduates. It draws on the study’s theoretical lenses to discuss how culture, identity, reverse culture shock, and institutional power intersect in shaping return experiences, and articulates the core contributions of the thesis.
- **Chapter 8: Conclusions and Recommendations** – Provides a concise overview of the entire research project, summarising the main findings in relation to the research questions. It outlines the study’s contributions to knowledge, reflects on its limitations, and suggests directions for future research. The chapter concludes with practical recommendations for policymakers, educational institutions, and other stakeholders involved in supporting returning graduates.

With the structure and scope of the thesis established, the chapter now turns to the broader context of global mobility in higher education, within which international doctoral study and subsequent return are situated.

Global Mobility of Higher Education

Students crossing international borders to pursue higher education is not a new phenomenon that has emerged as a prominent feature of the 21st century (Chen, 2017; Knight, 2018; Deardorff, 2023). UNESCO reports that the number of students studying abroad has increased by over 100% in the last 20 years, surpassing 5 million in recent years (Simonds *et al.*, 2023). This growth has

been driven by increasing global interconnectedness, advances in communication technologies, and the recognition of higher education as a key pathway to socio-economic development.

Historically, western nations, most notably the United Kingdom, the United States, and Australia have appeared as a leading destination for international students, owing to their prestigious institutions, varied range of academic offerings, and the perceived professional advantages associated with degrees from these systems (Van Mol, Cleven, and Mulvey, 2024). Among these, the United Kingdom holds a particularly prominent position. Each year, it attracts over half a million international students, with a substantial proportion arriving from ‘developing countries’ (British Council, 2018; Universities UK, 2021).

The appeal of the United Kingdom for international students has traditionally extended beyond institutional prestige. Its role as a global centre of research and the status of English as a lingua franca have long positioned the UK as an attractive destination for students seeking advanced academic training and enhanced international mobility (Altbach and De Wit 2017; De Wit and Altbach, 2021; Deardorff *et al.*, 2023). For students from countries such as Algeria, studying in the UK has offered opportunities to access high-quality doctoral education, experience different academic and cultural environments, and build international networks that may support future academic and professional trajectories (Ghodbane, 2020; Lechekheb, 2022; Zidouni, 2023; Guerriche and Grimshaw, 2024). This broader context provides an essential conceptual and contextual framing for examining the specific experiences of Algerian doctoral students in the UK and, crucially, the complexities they encounter upon returning home.

The Role of International Education in Personal and Professional Development

The significance of international education extends beyond its academic dimension, as it is widely acknowledged to be a transformative experience that profoundly impacts individuals on personal and professional levels. As emphasised by Altbach *et al.* (2019) and De Wit and Altbach (2021), studying abroad involves more than formal learning; it exposes students to new cultural contexts, diverse perspectives, and opportunities for critical self-reflection.

Such exposure is particularly important in an increasingly interconnected world, where the ability to navigate cultural differences is central to both personal and professional success. Research demonstrates that intercultural competence, developed through international education and diverse learning environments, enhances students’ abilities to interact effectively and empathetically with people from various cultural backgrounds (Anderston *et al.*, 2006; Deardorff, 2006; Deardorff *et al.*, 2023). Engagement with peers from diverse cultural and academic

backgrounds helps students to recognise and evaluate contrasting viewpoints, thereby strengthening their cultural sensitivity and understanding (Leask, 2009). This is also reflected in the findings of my study, particularly in participants' accounts of intercultural engagement during their doctoral training abroad discussed in chapter six and seven.

Beyond interpersonal development, international education encourages students to adopt broader global perspectives and a sense of responsibility beyond national boundaries (Montgomery, 2013; Stein, 2017). Studies suggest that such experiences foster sustained global engagement and a commitment to addressing complex international challenges (Knight, 2012; Knight, 2020; De Wit and Altbach, 2021). A British Council (2019) report similarly notes that international exposure enhances graduates' global competence and preparedness for contemporary societal demands.

Taken as a whole, international education offers a holistic developmental experience that combines academic training with personal growth and professional skill formation. Higher education institutions increasingly aim to cultivate graduates who possess not only disciplinary expertise but also intercultural competence and adaptability (British Council, 2018). While these benefits are widely acknowledged, their realisation varies across national contexts (Altbach and Knight, 2007). In Algeria, where substantial investment has been made in international scholarship programmes to support capacity building and knowledge transfer, it is therefore essential to examine how such international experiences translate into the lived realities of returning doctoral graduates. To ground these broader discussions, the following section narrows the focus to Algerian doctoral students in the United Kingdom, situating their mobility within specific historical, political, and institutional frameworks.

Specific Focus on Algerian Students in the UK

Algerian students are increasingly pursuing higher education opportunities in foreign countries, with the United Kingdom emerging as a particularly favoured choice (Chellia, 2018). This trend shaped both by the historical ties between Algeria and the UK, and by the perceived prestige of British education (Belmihoub, 2018; Jacob, 2019).

In 2014, Algeria embarked on a strategic initiative to strengthen diplomatic and educational connections with English-speaking countries, notably the UK, through the establishment of international mobility partnerships. Central to this effort was a joint initiative between the British Council and the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education: an international postgraduate scholarship scheme designed to fund up to 500 Algerian doctoral students to study in the UK over a five-year period (British Council, 2014, 2020). Targeted particularly at English language and related

disciplines, the scheme aims to build advanced academic capacity while promoting cultural exchange and supporting the internationalisation of Algerian higher education (British Council, 2014).

The decision to pursue doctoral study abroad is also shaped by domestic conditions within Algeria. Economic constraints, limited research infrastructure, and restricted opportunities for advanced academic training encourage many students to seek alternatives overseas. As Karakaş (2020) highlights, studying in the UK represents far more than the acquisition of a degree: it provides an escape from structural limitations at home and an opportunity to redefine identities in a more open and diverse environment.

Scholarship initiatives facilitated through partnerships between the Algerian government and the British Council therefore play a crucial role in enabling this mobility (British Council, 2014; Bouherar and Salem, 2025). Beyond facilitating access to prestigious UK institutions, these schemes aim are intended long-term academic and professional linkages between Algeria and the UK. By prioritising fields aligned with national development goals, they aim to equip graduates with expertise relevant to Algeria's broader economic and educational strategies, equipping future graduates with the expertise needed to address pressing national challenges.

Crucially, these initiatives are not designed solely to support outward mobility but also to ensure that returning graduates can contribute meaningfully to Algeria's academic and professional landscape (Bouherar and Salem, 2025). With appropriate institutional support, the challenges of reintegration may be reframed as opportunities for innovation, leadership, and reform within higher education. This broader context provides the foundation for the present study, which examines how Algerian doctoral graduates interpret and navigate their return following UK-based doctoral training. The complexity of these experiences is developed further in the findings chapter six and seven, where detailed interpretative analysis of participants' narratives reveals how return is lived, negotiated, and understood.

Beyond its structural and policy dimensions, this study is also informed by the researcher's own academic journey and reflective engagement with international doctoral mobility. The following section outlines the motivations that shaped the development of this research.

Research Motivation

My interest in exploring the experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees was first sparked by a conversation with a fellow Algerian scholar who expressed a strong desire to return home after completing her studies abroad. This conversation, alongside similar discussions with friends

about our own futures after graduation, prompted deeper reflection on my personal academic journey and the broader implications of return.

My aspiration to pursue a PhD began when I entered university in Algeria, although the dream itself dated back to my childhood, when I first imagined studying abroad at the age of twelve. This ambition was eventually realised through a scholarship to study in the United Kingdom. Becoming an English language lecturer and obtaining a PhD had long been central to my academic goals, and the opportunity to specialise in education a field I am deeply passionate about was particularly motivating. With the knowledge and skills, I hoped to acquire abroad, I envisaged returning to Algeria to contribute meaningfully to my home institution, advance the field of education, and inspire others to pursue similar paths.

When I embarked on my doctoral journey in the United Kingdom, I did so with optimism and determination. Studying in the UK provided access to advanced research resources and exposure to a culturally diverse academic environment, which broadened my perspectives both personally and professionally. These experiences strengthened my interest in understanding how international education shapes individuals and how, upon return, these individuals may influence their home academic and social contexts.

My motivation for focusing specifically on Algerian doctoral returnees is also grounded in a clear gap in the existing literature. While a growing body of research has examined returnee experiences in other national contexts (Fanari, Wright, and Foerester, 2021), Algerian doctoral graduates remain largely absent from empirical scholarship. As discussed earlier in the section of the significance of the study, this absence is particularly striking given Algeria's long-standing practice of sending students abroad through government-funded scholarship programmes, initiated in the 1970s following independence (Benamara, 2022). Although these initiatives were designed to foster knowledge transfer and national development, the lived experiences of returnees and their reintegration into Algerian academic and professional environments remain underexplored. By addressing this gap, the present study seeks to illuminate the challenges returnees face, the strategies they employ to adapt, and the contributions they seek to make upon return.

In addition, this research aims to critically examine the effectiveness of the scholarship programme that enabled me, and many others, to study abroad. Exploring how well such schemes prepare scholars for return and reintegration offers valuable insights for both policy and practice. For policymakers, the study provides evidence to inform more effective reintegration strategies

and support mechanisms. For returnees, it offers an informed account of the complexities of re-entry and the conditions that enable personal, professional, and academic flourishing.

While my personal experiences shaped the initial motivation for this study, they also pointed towards a wider structural and scholarly gap in how doctoral return is understood and researched. The following section therefore outlines the research problem and rationale underpinning this study.

Research Problem and Rationale

This section presents the research problem and rationale, outlining the gaps in existing literature on the reintegration experiences of internationally trained graduates in Algeria. It highlights why it is important for advancing academic understanding of return migration and for informing policies that support doctoral returnees' transitions into their home-country contexts.

The Gap in Existing Literature

Part of the framing for this study emerged from sustained engagement with the literature on international student mobility, return migration, and doctoral education. Through this engagement, it became evident that while certain dimensions of international education have been extensively examined, there remain significant research opportunities that have yet to be fully explored. Rather than providing a comprehensive review at this stage, this section outlines the key gaps in existing scholarship that this thesis directly addresses, with further conceptual and empirical discussion developed in Chapter Three.

Despite the growing body of research on international student mobility, there remains a significant gap in the literature concerning the post-return experiences of graduates from developing and postcolonial contexts (Wadhwa, 2018; Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019; Pham, 2020; Alkubaidi and Alzhrani, 2020). Existing scholarship has extensively explored students' motivations for studying abroad, their adjustment in host countries, and the academic outcomes of international education. Studies focusing on Algerian doctoral students, for instance, have examined sociocultural, psychological, and academic adjustment during the period of study abroad (e.g., Housni, 2025), thereby contributing valuable insights into in-mobility experiences. However, these studies largely conclude their analysis at the point of degree completion, leaving the post-return phase comparatively unexamined. This imbalance is particularly evident in North Africa, and in Algeria specifically, where empirical research on returnee experiences remains limited (Marquis, 2019; Ghodbane, 2020; Lechkhab, 2022; Guerriche and Grimshaw, 2024).

Much of the available literature continues to be framed through macro-level paradigms such as ‘brain drain’ and ‘brain gain’, which focus primarily on patterns of mobility and knowledge circulation (Cao, 2008; Lee and Kim, 2010; Nour, 2019; Mok, Zhang, and Bao, 2022). While these frameworks offer valuable insights into the structural and economic dimensions of mobility, they frequently overlook the personal, emotional, and identity-related dimensions of return, as well as the everyday challenges involved in re-establishing professional and social lives in home contexts.

Recent scholarship has begun to acknowledge this limitation. Notably, Abdulazeez, Reppa, and Mok (2025), for example, highlight the lack of empirical evidence on the long-term career trajectories and identity development of Arab students after graduating from UK universities. In particular, they note limited understanding of how international education shapes professional identities, employment opportunities, and reintegration into home labour markets. Their findings underline the need for context-specific, post-graduation research that moves beyond host-country experiences and examines the outcomes of international education from the perspective of the home country.

This gap is further reinforced by Mehreen *et al.* (2025) in their recent systematic review of 129 peer-reviewed studies on repatriation. While the review identifies key themes such as readjustment, coping strategies, identity change, knowledge transfer, organisational support, and post-return career trajectories, it also reveals that repatriation research remains heavily dominated by corporate expatriate and multinational enterprise contexts. As a result, the experiences of academic returnees particularly doctoral graduates returning to public higher education systems in Global South contexts remain largely underexplored. Despite growing recognition of repatriation as a complex process involving identity negotiation and adjustment, the specific realities of doctoral academic return therefore remain under-researched.

Research Aims and Objectives

The following section outlines the aims and objectives of this study, focusing on understanding the personal and professional reintegration experiences of UK-based Algerian doctoral returnees and their broader implications for academia and society.

Research Aim

The primary aim of this study is to explore the lived experiences of UK-based Algerian doctoral graduates as they transition back to Algeria. It seeks to examine how these individuals navigate

the multifaceted process of reintegration, both professionally and personally, while identifying the key factors that shape and influence their experiences.

Research Objectives

- To examine the personal, professional, and cultural challenges encountered by returning Algerian doctoral graduates.
- To understand the coping mechanisms and strategies employed by these graduates to navigate the complexities of reintegration.
- To evaluate the impact of their return on the academic and research landscape in Algeria.

Research Questions

This research is guided by the following overarching research question:

- How do UK-based Algerian doctoral graduates experience their transition to Algeria, and what are the personal and professional implications of their return?
- How do these graduates navigate the professional landscape in Algeria upon their return?
- In what ways do their international academic experiences shape their contributions to academia, research, and professional practice in Algeria?

The research questions for this study emerged through an iterative process shaped by three interrelated influences: the existing literature, the researcher's personal and academic experience, and constant engagement with the broader field of international education and return migration.

The literature highlighted a growing body of research on international student mobility and doctoral education but also revealed a persistent lack of empirical work focused on the post-return experiences of doctoral graduates, particularly within Algerian and wider Arab contexts (as discussed in earlier section of the gap in existing literature). This gap prompted a need to explore not only structural outcomes of return but also the lived emotional, cultural, and professional dimensions of reintegration.

Alongside this, the researcher's positionality as an Algerian doctoral student in the UK and a future returnee provided a heightened awareness of the uncertainties, expectations, and anxieties associated with returning home after prolonged international study. Informal conversations with

fellow Algerian doctoral graduates further reinforced the sense that return was experienced as a complex and often unsettling transition rather than a simple 'homecoming'.

These academic and experiential influences were brought together through the process of literature review, reflexive engagement, and methodological alignment with Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). As a result, the research questions were designed to remain open, exploratory, and experience-centred, allowing participants' own sense-making of return to remain central to the inquiry. Given the study's focus on lived experience and sense-making, it is important to briefly outline the methodological approach guiding this inquiry before introducing the participants involved in the study.

Methodology Overview

While a full account of the methodological framework is presented in Chapter Four, an overview is provided here to situate the study within its interpretative and phenomenological orientation. This research adopts a qualitative, interpretative research design to explore the lived experiences of UK-based Algerian doctoral graduates who returned to Algeria following the completion of their PhD studies. Given the study's focus on meaning making and subjective experience, the research is informed by Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), which is particularly suited to examining how individuals make sense of significant life transitions.

Data were generated through semi-structured online interviews with 18 Participants. Recruitment followed purposive and snowball sampling strategies to ensure that all participants had direct experience of the phenomenon under investigation. Interviews were conducted online to accommodate participants' geographical dispersion across different Algerian cities and to ensure accessibility and flexibility. All interviews were audio-recorded with informed consent and transcribed verbatim prior to analysis.

Data were analysed using the systematic stages of IPA, involving detailed, case-by-case engagement with each participant's account before moving to cross-case analysis. This process enabled the identification of shared experiential themes while preserving the distinctiveness of each participant's narrative. The analysis focused on participants' experiences of return, reintegration, identity re-negotiation, reverse culture shock, and professional adaptation. Ethical approval for the study was obtained prior to data collection. All participants received full information about the research and provided informed consent. Pseudonyms are used throughout the thesis to protect anonymity, and all data have been stored securely in line with institutional ethical guidelines.

Overview of Study Participants

This study focuses on Algerian doctoral graduates who completed their PhD studies in the United Kingdom and subsequently returned to Algeria. Participants shared a common experiential trajectory characterised by prolonged academic and cultural immersion within UK higher education, followed by reintegration into Algerian academic and professional contexts shaped by different institutional, cultural, and professional expectations. This shared pathway forms the phenomenological basis of the study, enabling an in-depth exploration of how return is experienced, interpreted, and negotiated.

Although participants represented a range of disciplinary backgrounds and institutional affiliations across Algeria, their common experience of international doctoral mobility and return provided a coherent experiential focus for analysis. A detailed account of participant recruitment, inclusion criteria, and demographic characteristics is presented in Chapter Four.

Conclusion

This chapter has set the foundation for the thesis by introducing the focus of the study and establishing its academic, practical, and socio-economic significance. I situated the research within the broader landscape of global higher education mobility and international education before narrowing the discussion to Algerian doctoral students in the United Kingdom. In doing so, I demonstrated how international doctoral study, return migration, and reintegration intersect within the Algerian context. I also outlined the motivation for the study, drawing on both personal academic experience and identified gaps in the existing literature. The research problem and rationale were articulated, highlighting the limited empirical attention given to the post-return experiences of Algerian doctoral graduates. The research aim, objectives, and questions were then presented to clarify the direction of the inquiry.

In addition, I provided a brief overview of the methodological approach and study participants to contextualise the research design, with detailed discussion deferred to Chapter Four. Together, these elements establish a coherent framework for the thesis. The next chapter presents the contextual background to the study, situating it within Algeria's historical, linguistic, cultural, and educational landscape, which is essential for understanding the institutional and societal environment into which doctoral graduates return and for interpreting the lived experiences explored in the chapters that follow.

Chapter Two

Contextual Background

Introduction

In this chapter, I provide the foundational context necessary to understand the focus of this research: the lived experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees who completed their studies abroad. I begin by exploring the historical and cultural influences that have shaped contemporary Algerian society, including the enduring impact of French colonial rule. The chapter also examines the evolving status of the English language in Algeria, highlighting its growing prominence as a tool for academic and professional development in a multilingual context traditionally dominated by Arabic and French.

In addition, I discuss key initiatives aimed at fostering international educational mobility, including the scholarship programmes under which the participants of this study pursued their doctoral studies. These programmes represent a critical effort by Algeria to invest in the development of human capital and promote knowledge transfer. By addressing these historical, cultural, and educational dimensions, I establish the broader framework within which this study is situated, offering insights into the complex environment Algerian doctoral returnees navigate upon their return.

A Brief Introduction to Algeria and its History

Algeria, the largest country in Africa, boasts a rich and complex history that has significantly shaped its cultural and social foundation. From its Berber roots to Arab-Islamic influences and its long struggle for independence from French colonial rule, Algeria's historical trajectory has left an enduring mark on its identity and development. This diverse historical and cultural backdrop provides important context for understanding the country's demographic profile, which reflects the interplay of its historical, social, and economic dynamics.

Demography of Algeria

Algeria is a North African country- second in size in the African continent and part of the Maghreb `the Berber world` (Belmihoub, 2018). It shares borders from west to east with Morocco, Western Sahara, Mauritania, Mali, Niger, Libya and Tunisia. This country is well known for its geographical location, cultural diversity, ample size, and varied natural resources. These major factors have shaped its distinctiveness and uniqueness. Algeria has the longest

Mediterranean coastline and contains the world's fifth-largest natural gas reserves (Stora, 2004). According to the World Bank (2016, July 1) list of economies, Algeria's economy relies immensely on profits from hydrocarbons, such as gas and oil which make up 60% of the nation's budget revenues and 95% of export incomes. However, Oil and gas production has been dropping since 2015, as have their prices on international markets. Speaking about its inhabitants, historians assume that Amazigh or Imazighen people constitute the original population (Nickerson, 1968; Ruedy, 1992). According to (Tiliouine and Achoui, 2018) only 20% of the population speaks Tamazight dialects. The remaining Algerians who are "Arabised Berbers" speak Arabic dialects, whereas the dominant languages in Algeria are Arabic and French, which is considered.

Linguistic Diversity in the Pre-colonial era

The socio-cultural context of Algeria and its sociolinguistic repertoire were formulated throughout a series of drastic conquests and colonisation, which has led to linguistic pluralism or multilingualism (Benrabah, 2014). Due to its geographical position, Algeria has been prey to different invasions and colonial rules from Romans to the Arabo-Muslims to the Ottomans to the French who eventually established its borders (Meynier, 2017), which has shaped its fluctuated linguistic repertoire. Dating back to 4000 B.C.E, the history affirms the "Berber" - a word indicating the native people of Algeria (Nickerson, 1968; Ruedy, 1992). They are also known as "Imazighen" (Ilahiane, 2017, p. ix). These people refer to their language group as Tamazight because it denotes their ethnic identity; in a more stressed way, Imazighen means "free people (Belmihoub, 2012; Bagui, 2014).

Imazighen was a proud ethnic community that was relatively known for their nobility and attachment to their lands regardless of the numerous invasions they endured. However, despite their resistance to foreign invasions, they did not succeed in ruling their lands (Benrabeh, 2013). According to Storta (2004), numerous invading groups took control of the peninsula. Respectively, Eastern and Western invaders were attracted by their prosperous land; it is geographically- advantaged location triggered them, subsequently, six major invasions occurred before the French coloniser did (Stora, 2004). Firstly, for a long period, the Phoenicians-Carthaginians invasion, from 110 to 147 B.C.E, added the Libyco-Berber language variety (Benrabeh, 2013). Afterwards, the Romans from 146 B.C.E to 432 C.E. According to (Ennaji, 2005) the Roman invasion did not enable Latin's integration into Algeria's linguistic environment since the Romans were more concerned with trading than with integration in the community and imposing their language.

The decline of the Roman Maghreb occurred in 455 with the Vandal occupation, during which the Vandals employed their Germanic language and Gothic script alongside Latin in legislative and diplomatic contexts from 432 to 533. The Vandals were eliminated by the Byzantines, resulting in their near-total disappearance with minimal evidence of their existence. The Byzantine Empire existed from 533 to 633, followed by Arab rule from 755 to 1516 (Benrabah, 2014). Arabs occupied the Christian Byzantine Empire in the Maghreb and the locals partly were Arabised throughout the centuries of Arabic sovereignty (Ennaji, 2005; Belmihoub, 2015). Meanwhile, Islam was brought to Algeria in the 7th century. The Islamic movement began with the invasion of North African countries during the medieval period, which was a defining feature of the period. According to (Chebchoub, 1985; Storta, 2004), the Arab mission was not only to spread Islam but to Arabise the country as well. At the linguistic level, Classical Arabic grew in popularity as a result of Islam, which was the religion of the vast majority of Berbers during the period (Belmihoub, 2012). Thus, the Arabic invasion can be regarded as a pivotal point in Algerian history because the introduction of the Arabic language has a significant sociolinguistic impact and the long-term potential to fully arabise Algeria in the coming centuries (Stora, 2004; Aitsiselmi and Marley, 2008).

Subsequently, the Turkish came from 1516 to 1830, at that time, Algeria became a province of the Ottoman Empire (Chebchoub, 1985; Oakes, 2008). Turkish leaders incited splits between different tribes, which has intensified the linguistic variety. Consequently, the country became an open state for a variety of cultural models, ethnic groups, and languages (Benrabeh, 2013). Arabic, in this respect, was the most common liturgical language. The varieties of the Berber language denoted a significant symbol of ethnic and social identity that built a strong rebellious resistance towards the Ottoman Empire. Nevertheless, the Turkish did not contribute to the development of arts and literature in the language, but they allowed the internal regions to become more Islamised and Arabised than they were before (Rahmoun-Mrabet, 2018).

In this respect, it is worth mentioning that the sociolinguistic landscape tended to be as complicated and heterogeneous as the society (Chebchoub, 1985). As a result, the Algerian linguistic repertoire went through diversification due to the outcome of language contact with the aforementioned conquests have shaped the country's linguistic history, but more precisely the Arabs and the French invading groups had a significant effect on Algeria's linguistic profile (Benrabeh, 2014).

French Colonialism and Its Impact on Algerian Life

Algerian history marked the most critical era at the beginning of 1830, the French colonial conquest. French colonialism's goal was not only limited to the economic exploitation of Algeria's natural resources and political dominance, but also the total invasion to eradicate its language, and culture and also, the deprivation of the Algerians from their Berber, Arab, and Islamic identity (Maamri, 2009, Ball and Marley, 2016). Algeria would become administratively a fundamental part of French territory also known as 'L'Algérie française' (Eldridge, 2010, p. 124). This appellation was more than just a phrase; it was an undeniable fact that Algeria was an integral division of the French colonizer (Benrabeh, 2013). Algeria has been deeply influenced by French civilisation, culture, and language after more than a century of French administration, this impact, however, remains extremely powerful despite efforts to decrease and reduce it (Chebchoub, 1985).

The Linguistic and Cultural Impact of French Colonialism

Algeria underwent radical linguistic changes after French troops seized power in 1848, and still, French has claimed the official language of government, and a French law made Arabic a foreign language in 1938. As a result, Algerians were compelled to regard French as their official language (Ahmed Sid, 2008). In other words, France introduced several political and administrative institutions, which had a considerable impact on Algeria's identity, education, way of life, and how they interacted with one another. The alienation of language was the major aim of colonial rule in Algeria.

The French colony had far-reaching linguistic consequences. Even though it did so in a relatively short period, it resulted in a completely fragmented society (Benrabah, 2013), besides its attempt to steady application of the policy of 'Frenchification' in Algerian educational curricula. Furthermore, such policies which were introduced by the French, envisaged converting the Algerian society to a French one by imposing the use of their language in many fields including education, administration, economy, commerce, and even public life (Benrabah, 2005; Suleiman, 2013).

Henceforth, by the end of the 20th century, Algeria was considered the world's second-biggest French-speaking population (Benrabeh, 2014). The result of the coexistence of Arabic and French in Algerian society has led to the emergence of Bilingualism (Benrabeh, 2013; Belmihoub, 2012; Adder and Bagui, 2020). Bilingualism, however, refers to the use of two languages by the same individual or within the same speech group (Fishman, 1980).

Since language and culture are like two facets of the same coin, one cannot go without the other. Throughout colonial history, culture and language were deliberately used as instruments of domination and subjugation (Memmi, 1965). In the Algerian context, the French colonial policy, clearly illustrates this practice. Arabic literacy and education were restricted, and by the decree of 8 March 1938, Arabic was officially classified as a foreign language in Algeria (Cherrad-Benchehra, 2021). This process contributed to the deep deculturation and deracination of the Algerian people (Benrabah, 2013). French was imposed as the dominant language of administration and education, while local languages such as Arabic and Berber were marginalised and devalued (Benrabah, 2013). The French decolonial process enforced a cruel acculturation system that defined French as the official language of its colonies and expelled local languages such as Arabic and Berber. Algerians, however, were deeply impregnated by French culture and were alienated from the values of their own identity. (Edward, 1999) in this respect claimed:

“The long French attempt to crush anything but French culture in Algeria, culminating in a murderous war that finally brought independence, surely contributed to the extremist tendencies seen there today”.

Edward's (1999) statement highlights the lasting effects of French colonialism in Algeria, particularly the suppression of indigenous culture and the violent struggle for independence. His claim linking this history to modern extremist tendencies shed light on how colonial oppression can leave deep sociopolitical and cultural scars, though such connections must be examined within the broader context of Algeria's post-independence challenges.

Benrabeh (2014) notes that French colonialism profoundly altered Algerian society's cultural profile, leaving a lasting impact that ensured it would never return to its pre-colonial state. Similarly, Edward (1999) emphasises how the French suppression of non-French culture and the brutal independence war shaped Algeria's sociopolitical landscape, even suggesting a link between this colonial legacy and contemporary extremist tendencies. Together, these perspectives highlight the deep and far-reaching consequences of French colonial rule on Algeria's cultural and political identity.

Language and culture are widely recognised as central to the of shaping of identity (Hall, 1996); when that identity is undermined through the compulsory use of a foreign language such as French in education, individuals may experience cultural alienation and detachment from their homeland. In Algeria, the French colonial administration deliberately sought to suppress local languages and Islamic–Arab culture for more than 130 years, creating deep tensions in the

construction of national identity (Ageron, 1991; Benrabah, 2013; Sahel, 2017). Following the full annexation of Algeria in 1848, French was declared the official language of administration, and colonial authorities imposed its use at the expense of Arabic and Berber (Benrabah, 2007; Maamri, 2009). In 1938, a French decree officially classified Arabic as a foreign language, symbolising the depth of linguistic and cultural marginalisation (Ahmed Sid, 2008). According to Mami (2020), the destructive nature of this policy was evident in the systematic exclusion of Algerian cultural identity through the eradication of language, the restructuring of educational programmes, and the imposition of new instructional methods. Such processes reflect Hall's (1990) conceptualisation of cultural identity as historically constructed and continually reshaped through social and political forces, a concept that will be discussed in greater detail in the following chapter (see p. 41-42).

The colonial language policy thus went beyond communication; it became a tool for shaping consciousness and redefining belonging. By displacing Arabic and Berber and elevating French as the language of power and prestige, colonial authorities disrupted the transmission of cultural values and collective memory across generations. Several studies (Bennoune, 2000; Stora, 2000; Mami, 2020) have demonstrated how these transformations reshaped not only Algeria's political and social structures but also the very foundations of cultural identity.

Education in Algeria

Algeria's education system has undergone significant transformations since its independence in 1962, evolving as a cornerstone of national development. Rooted in the country's cultural and historical context, the system aims to balance traditional values with modern advancements, shaping the educational landscape and policies that continue to influence generations.

Outline of the Algerian Educational System

Most countries have undertaken a series of educational reforms at all levels that are ongoing throughout the world to meet the demands imposed by rapid socioeconomic change, Algeria cannot be an exception (Gasmi, 2020; Smaili and Benamara, 2022). Algeria's Ministry of Education and Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research underwent a series of changes in the field of education, beginning with the country's independence in 1962 and ending with the most recent reforms in the early 2000s, the Algerian government has pursued a series of reforms aimed at improving the country's educational system (Benrabeh, 2007; Bouazid and Le Roux 2014). From a historical standpoint, according to Benrabah (2007) and Djebbari (2016), three significant phases have influenced Algerian language policy; he claimed that the characteristics of the first phase were the dominance of the colonial legacy which comprised a

network of schools and an educational system dominated by the French language, with Arabic progressively gaining significance. The second phase, known as the `nationalist transition`, lasted from the late 1960s through the late 1990s and was linked to the socialist-era central planning economy, this period was characterised by the steady implementation of the Arabic as it has witnessed an extreme form of exclusive nationalism influenced by the 19th-century European ideal of language convergence. The third phase began in the early 2000s, which was in coincidence with the move to a free-market economy and less strident Arabisation efforts.

The Status of English as a Foreign Language in Algeria

Historically, French has had a greater impact on Algerians in both spoken and written forms because it was compulsory to learn French beginning in primary school; however, since independence, Algerian policymakers have selected English to the position of being integrated in schools (Miliani, 2001; Benrabeh, 2014). As a result, English as a foreign language is now taught in Algerian middle schools. However, the use of English in the Algerian linguistic setting has expanded dramatically due to the recent educational and a more globalised society (Belmihoub, 2017; Smaili and Benamara, 2022). In this regard, Abid Houcine (2007) and Chemami (2011) postulated that while the French language is still dominant because of French colonisation, English has become extremely popular and interesting for Algerians. The English language has earned significant importance as a foreign language in Algeria because of its growing presence in the nation. Nevertheless, the position of English in the country's linguistic landscape has shifted throughout the years due to political and pedagogical factors, before achieving such a prominent position in the Algerian linguistic landscape. After Algeria took independence in 1962.

According to Brutt-Griffler (2002), English is regarded as the most useful language in the world and is referred to as “a world language” (Mair, 2003). Likewise, Baker (2003), believes that English has imposed itself as the universal language of all domains; the English language today encompasses every facet of life. As a result, Algerian authorities attempted to improve access to this global language and to prepare Algerians to join the global community of English speakers. Nowadays, there is a growing awareness to develop the English language in Algeria to become a member of the globalised world and also as an attempt to establish mobility and exchange programmes with Anglophone nations (British Council, 2014; Belmihoub, 2017; 2018a).

According to Mami (2013), English holds a prominent position in the Algerian educational system; it was promoted from the status of a second foreign language in the 1990s to the first foreign language in 2000 to help enhance the status of science and technology. Meanwhile, he

also postulated that since the introduction of the English language in the Algerian curriculum, it has been increasingly prominent and has obtained a significant demand at all levels of education.

Higher Education in Algeria

Since Algeria's independence, significant policies have shaped the country's higher education system since the French system had a significant impact on the Algerian postsecondary system. The latter has undergone considerable changes that are demonstrated by many reforms, notably the launch of the LMD system in Algerian universities (Benouar, 2013; Smaili and Benamara, 2022). This system was preceded by the classical system that used to last four years. The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education decision-makers decided in 2004 and 2005 to adopt a new higher education system known as LMD, which could be regarded as a necessary step toward globalisation (Hamadi, 2019; Khelifa and Abdelaziz, 2021).

According to Metatla (2016), the initiative of this process has evolved through previous attempts from different European countries to stimulate the mobility and employability of citizens, the overall development of the continent, and constructing a shared belief that urges the preservation of common European identity. Within the Algerian context, the ultimate aim of such reforms was to integrate the Bologna processes into the Algerian higher educational system (Benouar, 2013; Hamzaoui, 2021). In this regard, Mami (2013), Reguig (2014), and Eta and Mngo (2021) concluded that the purpose of the Bologna process is to promote European education by making the educational system adaptable to the challenges, that are imposed by globalisation and to make the higher education more accessible and competitive in the worldwide market, by which students and academics work together and interact with their counterparts overseas.

In addition, this process aims at facilitating cross-national mobility of instructors, students, and workers (Buckner, 2011), as it was envisaged for the Bologna process in Europe in the early 2000s. Rose (2015) and Meriem and Bouyakoub (2020) observed that Algerian tertiary education has experienced significant growth and expansion in recent decades. This rapid development has been driven by increased investments in higher education infrastructure, the establishment of new universities, and a growing emphasis on producing skilled graduates to meet the country's socio-economic demands. Such expansion reflects Algeria's commitment to fostering a knowledge-based economy and increasing access to education for a broader segment of the population. However, this growth has also brought challenges, including overcrowded institutions, resource limitations, and the need to improve the quality of education to align with international standards.

Algerian Doctoral Mobility

Internationalisation has long had an impact on higher education through academic collaboration among institutions and the movement of academics and knowledge. As it might be denoted that globalisation has a great influence on higher education (Altbach, 2004; Kim, 2009; Knight, 2014; Chen and Li, 2019; De Wit, and Altbach, 2021). During the last decade, Internationalisation has promoted change and growth in several areas including economics, politics, and education, resulting in the transformation of local and national institutions via the establishment of various policies that aimed at promoting internationalisation (De Wit et al., 2015; De Wit and Altbach, 2021).

According to Altbach and Umakoshi (2004), the challenge for most universities, whether in Europe, Asia, or elsewhere, is to find ways to engage with the globalisation of education, driven by the increasing number of students seeking to study abroad to enhance their ability to perform in a global context. Recognising the positive impacts of study abroad programmes, higher education institutions and policymakers continue to invest in internationalisation initiatives (Grimshaw and Guerriche, 2024). Algeria, too, has long understood the value of such global integration, particularly as part of its post-independence nation-building efforts.

Following Algeria's independence in 1962, President Houari Boumediene, who led the country from 1965 to 1978, implemented significant educational reforms aimed at national development. A key component of these reforms was the establishment of scholarship programmes in the 1970s, designed to send Algerian students abroad for higher education. These initiatives were part of Boumediene's broader strategy to build a skilled workforce capable of contributing to Algeria's industrialisation and modernisation efforts. By investing in the education of its citizens, the Algerian government sought to reduce reliance on foreign expertise and promote self-sufficiency in various sectors (Smaili and Benamara, 2022). These scholarship programmes not only enhanced individual educational opportunities but also played a crucial role in the nation's socio-economic development during the post-independence era.

Building on these foundational efforts, Algeria has continued to prioritise international mobility as a means of fostering global citizenship and enhancing its higher education system. Various bottom-up initiatives have been implemented to stimulate student mobility programmes within Algerian universities (Chellia, 2018; Morley and Kosbar, n.d.). France, historically tied to Algeria, has played a significant role in supporting these efforts by establishing numerous financial assistance programmes for Algerian students. In 2014, for instance, over 80% of the 20,695 Algerian students studying abroad were in France (Ulrich, 2016). Beyond this

Francophone connection, Algeria has also expanded its global educational partnerships. The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research awarded 500 funded PhD scholarships to UK universities over five years starting in 2014. This initiative aimed to develop English-language capacities across Algerian universities and strengthen relationships with English-speaking countries, reflecting Algeria's ongoing commitment to diversifying its international collaborations and enhancing its global academic presence. The establishment of mobility and exchange programmes with Anglophone nations is one attempt to improve the position of English in Algeria (Belmihoub, 2012; Belmihoub, 2018; Jacob, 2019; Morley and Kosbar, n.d.).

British Council Scheme

Since the French imperialism in Algeria had commercial links between the two nations, there was a high degree of collaboration between the two countries. Following the implementation of the Bologna process paradigm, the French developed various financial aid programmes for Algerian students. The Franco-Algerian scholarship initiative (2009), for example, provided a chance for Algerian students. Only 40% of the payments are needed by the Algerian government, whereas 60% are funded by the French government in this scheme. Around 300 Algerian PhD students enrolled at French universities in 2009 as part of this programme (Chellia, 2018).

To improve the quality of higher education, Algeria and the United Kingdom signed a five-year contract in 2014 to send 500 Algerian students to the United Kingdom to pursue their PhD studies abroad as the first significant step in the Algerian British higher education partnership (Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, 2014, British council, 2014, Belmihoub, 2018). According to the Algerian-UK agreement (2014), students are chosen based on their qualifications. The Algerian Ministry of Higher Education is in charge of organising a nationwide competition in March of each academic year, with the first 100 successful candidates being accepted (Ministry of Higher Education, 2014). Candidates must meet a set of standards established by the Ministry of Higher Education to compete. The selection criteria are summarised in the table below (table 1).

Criterion	Definition
Academic discipline	-Students must be enrolled in the English studies discipline. Two academic subject areas exist at the Algerian universities' departments of English: Language Sciences (often referred to as linguistics), and Literature and Civilization Studies.
Age	-Students must be 25 or under by the time they sit for the national contest.
The academic study system	-Students must be enrolled within the LMD new system: The LMD system stands for <i>Licence</i> (3 years), <i>Master</i> (2 years), and <i>Doctorat</i> (3 years). The system's application in universities started in 2010 after the end of the Classical study system.
Academic records	-Students must: - Have excellent academic records during the 5 years of their study. - Be the top of their classes (the first six classified students in each university's English department who meet all the other criteria are taken) - Have never taken a re-sit exam and have never had a mark that is below average in any of the academic subjects.

Table 1: The selection criteria of selected students competing in the national PhD competition (Algerian Ministry of Higher Education, 2014).

Algerians Studying Abroad

Algeria has 29,718 students studying abroad according to UNESCO (Jughurtha, 2022). Algeria is considered a country that has a sizable unexplored international student population. Due to the un-competitiveness of the educational system and the crowded local employability, both present potential advantages for overseas institutions and linguistic study programmes. In 2018, Algeria sent 25,700 students overseas, according to the UNESCO Institute for Statistics. This figure pales in comparison to Morocco, which sent 51,100 students overseas during the same year. Algeria's foreign student statistics currently mirror those of Tunisia, its neighbour to the east, which has a fifth of Algeria's population but sends a nearly equivalent 22,400 students overseas. However, even though Algeria has few from its students abroad compared to Morocco, it is undergoing a political upheaval that might result in a major increase in international student numbers in the future years. Algeria in this concern has the potential to match or perhaps surpass Morocco as the second largest contributor of international students in North Africa, owing to greater per capita income levels.

To be specific, the United Kingdom (UK) has essentially a longstanding experience and an international reputation by being the hub of international higher education (HE) which makes it a popular destination for students from nations where there are considerable 'push' criteria, such as the likelihood of becoming mobile (Bourne *et al.*, 2013; Lomer, 2018). Taking the case of Algeria, with the spread of English in Algeria, various English graduate programmes have been established, however, it appears that English doctoral programmes have just lately begun to be examined. The example of the United States might be instructive (Chellia, 2018). The Fulbright and Youth Leadership Programme were among the programmes offered by the US embassy in Algeria to Algerian residents (Belmihoub, 2012).

In a more focused sense, Algeria has unveiled an ambitious goal to form international alliances with the Anglophone world. The UK government and the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education reached an agreement to send up to 500 PhD students to the UK over five years, who receive a fully supported scholarship to pursue their doctoral higher education (The British Council, 2014). The long-term goals of this academic exchange are to strengthen cultural ties between the two nations and to internationalise Algeria's higher education system (The British Council, 2014).

Conclusion

This chapter has established the contextual foundations necessary for understanding the environment within which this study is situated. By examining Algeria's historical, linguistic, cultural, and educational landscape, I have highlighted the structural and socio-cultural factors shaping the lived experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees. These contextual dynamics provide essential insight into the institutional and societal conditions influencing processes of reintegration, identity negotiation, and professional adaptation upon return.

Building on this contextual grounding, the following chapter turns to a review of the existing literature on international study programmes, doctoral mobility, and return migration. In that chapter, I examine key debates surrounding the benefits of study abroad, processes of knowledge transfer, and the complex challenges faced by returning graduates across diverse contexts. This literature review situates the experiences of Algerian returnees within broader scholarly discussions, thereby establishing the theoretical and empirical framework that informs the analysis presented in the subsequent chapters.

Chapter Three

Literature Review

Introduction

The purpose of this review is to situate the study within the wider context of international doctoral mobility and return migration while identifying the theoretical and empirical debates that inform its analysis. It explores how global trends in internationalisation, transnational education, and knowledge transfer intersect with processes of re-entry, identity reconstruction, and professional reintegration. In doing so, the review establishes the conceptual foundation for understanding the lived experiences of Algerian PhD returnees and highlights the research gaps this study seeks to address.

I begin by examining internationalisation and doctoral mobility, followed by an examination of transnational education, knowledge transfer, and professional development as central aspects of the international experience. I then consider return migration and re-entry, drawing on acculturation and adaptation theories, before addressing the emotional and identity-related dimensions of return. Informed by iterative engagement with the research process and early analytical insights, I also give particular attention to the impact of COVID-19, which is crucial in the development of my thesis arguments. The chapter concludes with a summary that synthesises the reviewed literature and positions the study within existing debates.

Although recent studies have been included, some earlier works remain relevant due to the limited research on re-entry experiences (Knocke and Schuster, 2017). This gap highlights the continuing need for research that explores return migration in under-studied contexts such as Algeria. Through this review, I show that understanding the experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees requires situating their narratives within broader global developments in higher education. Accordingly, this chapter moves from the international landscape of doctoral mobility and transnational education to the cultural and professional complexities of return, reflecting the evolving conceptual focus from global academic mobility to the lived realities of reintegration.

Internationalisation of Higher Education

The internationalisation of higher education has become a defining feature of the global academic landscape. This shift has been largely driven by the mass expansion of tertiary education and the growing importance of higher education and research in producing global knowledge (Tran and

Gomes, 2017; De Wit and Altbach, 2021). According to the OECD (2019), almost five million students are now studying abroad, which is twice as many as a decade ago, with projections suggesting that this number may increase to around eight million in the coming years, although the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic may have slowed this growth (OECD, 2020; UNESCO, 2021). The competition among countries to attract international students continues to intensify as education becomes a key driver of global engagement (De Wit and Altbach, 2021).

within this context, the term student mobility refers to the movement of students who travel to another country to study full degree programmes, take part in semester exchanges, or enrol in joint or collaborative academic schemes such as twinning programmes (Knight, 2018). In recent years, mobility has become a global phenomenon, particularly in English-speaking countries such as the United Kingdom and Ireland, where international students play an important role both financially and academically (Byram, 2006; Perna *et al.*, 2014). The leading destinations for internationally mobile students continue to be the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, and Australia (Project Atlas, 2018).

Altbach and Engberg (2014) note that “student mobility is at the heart of higher education globalisation” (p. 11), drawing attention to the vital role of movement in shaping international academic relations and intercultural understanding. Mobility provides opportunities for students to experience new learning environments and to develop cross-cultural awareness, which is increasingly valued in today’s interconnected world. Byram (2006) points out that opportunities for study abroad have expanded far beyond Europe and North America, extending to Asia, Africa, and Latin America. However, he also observes that this expansion is often linked to the financial goals of host institutions and countries. Georgiev (2014) and Coleman (2015) and Curtis and Ledgerwood (2018) argue that beyond such institutional benefits, mobility encourages new social connections and fresh perspectives, both of which enhance students’ academic and personal growth. It can therefore be seen as a key means of fostering intercultural learning and shaping new attitudes that later influence professional life.

Importantly, international experiences also affect how students understand themselves and their place in the world. Transnational mobility can influence identity formation, belonging, and relationships with both home and host environments (Tran and Gomes, 2017). These experiences often have a lasting influence on students’ wellbeing, confidence, and future plans (Tran, 2011; Tran and Pham, 2015).

Although internationalisation encompasses a wide range of cross-border activities, student mobility takes several distinct forms. Degree mobility refers to students who travel abroad to

complete a full qualification such as a bachelor's, master's, or doctoral degree. Credit mobility involves shorter periods abroad typically a semester or year during which students transfer credits back to their home institution. Certificate mobility includes brief overseas programmes designed to develop specific linguistic or professional skills without leading to a formal qualification (Knight, 2018). Given the aims of this study, the focus is specifically on degree mobility at the doctoral level, which carries unique academic, professional, and identity implications for returning scholars.

Overall, internationalisation and student mobility reflect both global trends and local realities, shaping how knowledge, people, and educational opportunities circulate across borders. Understanding these broader dynamics provides an essential foundation for examining more specific forms of mobility. The following section therefore narrows the focus to degree mobility at the doctoral level, where internationalisation intersects with professional identity development, research training, and long-term academic trajectories.

Degree Mobility and Doctoral Education

Building on the broader processes of internationalisation discussed above, doctoral education represents a particularly significant form of degree mobility within global higher education. The sector is increasingly shaped by collaboration among institutions, researchers, and students, supported by government policies that view higher education as essential to national development and global competitiveness (OECD, 2008). Over the past three decades, doctoral education in the United Kingdom has gone through important changes, including the diversification of doctoral programmes, the emergence of new providers, and a stronger focus on research impact and professionalisation (McGloin and Wynne, 2015). These developments reflect a broader understanding of doctoral education as a driver of innovation and economic growth in the global knowledge economy (Cuthbert and Molla, 2015).

The United Kingdom continues to attract large numbers of international doctoral students (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015; Hubble and Bolton, 2021). Doctoral study is not only an academic pursuit but also a period of personal and professional transformation that shapes identity and future aspirations (Austin and McDaniels, 2006; Lu, 2024). Many governments actively encourage students to pursue doctoral studies abroad, believing that on their return they will strengthen national research capacity and contribute to innovation through the knowledge and relationships they have developed during their studies (Cantwell, 2011).

However, recent evidence suggests that the attractiveness of the United Kingdom as a study destination can no longer be assumed as stable or uniform. Changes to immigration policy, including restrictions on student dependants, alongside rising tuition fees and living costs, have contributed to declining student visa applications and growing uncertainty among prospective international students (Institute for Fiscal Studies, 2024; Sondhi, 2025). Critical scholarship has also highlighted how contemporary international mobility may involve structural precarity and unequal institutional conditions, challenging dominant narratives that present international education as uniformly beneficial (Highet, 2025). These developments indicate a shifting landscape of international student mobility in which policy frameworks, financial considerations, and post-study prospects increasingly shape destination choices. Within this evolving context, understanding not only the period of study but also the longer-term trajectories of doctoral graduates become particularly important.

Despite the rich literature on international student experiences, there remains limited understanding of what happens after doctoral students return to their home countries. This process, sometimes described as reverse mobility (Lee and Kim, 2010), is often overlooked in favour of studies focusing on undergraduates or short-term exchange participants (Sengupta and Kapur, 2020; Fanari, Wright, and Foerster, 2021; Winkel, Strachan and Aamir, 2021). There is therefore a significant gap in knowledge about how doctoral graduates re-adjust both personally and professionally after completing their studies abroad.

Recent research has begun to explore these post-return experiences. Karakaş (2020), for example, examined Turkish academics who completed their MA and/or PhD studies overseas and analysed how international experiences influenced their professional identity and personal development. Similarly, Kuzhabekova, Sparks and Temerbayeva (2019) investigated the adaptation of Kazakhstani doctorate returnees through the lens of agency theory, while Alkubaidi and Alzhrani (2020) drew on transformative learning theory to explore Saudi returnees' experiences of reverse culture shock. (While reverse culture shock is introduced here through prior empirical work, a fuller conceptual and empirical discussion is provided in the section 'Culture Shock and Reverse Culture Shock' later in this chapter). Lee and Kim (2010) also studied Korean academics who returned home after completing doctorates in the United States, focusing on how they re-established their careers and integrated into their institutions. Together, these studies show that international doctoral experiences can be both empowering and demanding, as returnees often face institutional, social, and cultural challenges that influence how effectively they can apply the knowledge and skills gained abroad.

Doctoral study aims to develop independent researchers capable of generating new knowledge and contributing meaningfully to their academic and professional communities (Austin and McDaniels, 2006). Yet the experiences of doctoral returnees, particularly those from less researched contexts such as Algeria, remain insufficiently examined. Understanding how these graduates adapt, reconstruct their professional identities, and transfer knowledge to their local contexts is essential to assess the wider impact of international doctoral mobility on national higher education systems. To understand why return can become complex for doctoral graduates, it is first necessary to consider how international study shapes students during the period abroad. The next section therefore explores the impact of international experience on international students.

Impact of International Experience on International Students

Building on the broader discussion of internationalisation and doctoral mobility presented earlier, this section shifts attention to the individual-level impact of international experience on students themselves. The rapid expansion of international student mobility has been shaped by increased global interconnectedness, ease of travel, economic pressures, and evolving political and cultural dynamics (Altbach, 2004; Byram, 2006; Alsharari, 2018). Beyond its strategic importance for higher education systems, studying abroad has been widely associated with the acquisition of cultural capital, the development of global relationships, and enriched educational pathways. Within this context, international experiences are frequently linked to students' academic development, personal growth, and evolving sense of self.

A substantial body of research demonstrates that international experiences contribute to academic, linguistic, and personal development. Scholars such as Coleman (2015), Karakaş (2020), Deardorff *et al.* (2023), and Wang *et al.* (2024) show that international experiences foster adaptability, enhanced self-awareness, and improved intercultural communication skills. These outcomes reflect the transformative potential of mobility in shaping students' learning trajectories, professional aspirations, and intercultural competence. From this perspective, international study is not simply an academic endeavour but a formative experience that influences how students engage with diversity, knowledge, and global citizenship.

Research also highlights that international experiences reshape how students perceive identity, belonging, and their relationship to home and host cultures (Tran and Gomes, 2017). Exposure to different academic traditions and social norms often prompts reflection on previously taken-for-granted assumptions, leading to shifts in values, confidence, and future orientations (Tran, 2011; Tran and Pham, 2015). However, these benefits are not uniformly experienced. Studies

increasingly emphasise that the impact of international study is mediated by social background, linguistic capital, institutional support, and broader structural conditions, meaning that mobility can generate both opportunities and challenges for students.

While much of this literature draws on broader international contexts, these insights become particularly significant when examined within specific national settings such as Algeria. Within the Algerian context, international study has long been positioned as a pathway for developing advanced expertise and strengthening national capacity. Since the late 1970s, government-sponsored schemes have enabled Algerian students to pursue higher education abroad, initially in the United States and later through a range of bilateral agreements (Arfi, 2008; Belmihoub, 2015). Despite these efforts, France remains the primary destination for Algerian students, largely due to historical and linguistic ties, while Anglophone destinations such as the United Kingdom attract fewer students because of language and financial barriers (Chaouch, 2006; Benrabah, 2013, 2014; Morley and Kosbar, n.d.).

More recently, English has gained symbolic value as a language of global engagement and academic prestige, prompting gradual shifts towards Anglophone study destinations (Jacob, 2019). The United Kingdom has become an increasingly important partner in Algeria's internationalisation strategy, particularly through government-funded doctoral scholarship programmes introduced in 2014. These initiatives aimed to enhance English proficiency, foster research collaboration, and align Algerian higher education with international standards (British Council, 2014).

While these developments demonstrate the promise of international study, research consistently shows that international experiences do not affect all students in the same way (Brooks and Waters, 2011; Marginson, 2016). The outcomes of studying abroad are shaped by intersecting social, cultural, and institutional factors, which influence how students adapt, learn, and later reintegrate into their home contexts. Recognising these differentiated trajectories is essential for interpreting the lived experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees examined in this study and for situating their return journeys within broader debates on mobility, identity, and reintegration. The following section therefore adopts a critical lens to examine the limitations and inequalities that shape international experience.

Critical Perspectives on International Experience

While international study is frequently presented as a transformative and empowering experience, a growing body of research cautions against portraying international mobility as uniformly

beneficial. Scholars increasingly argue that the outcomes of studying abroad are shaped by unequal social, linguistic, and institutional conditions, which influence who benefits from international education and how those benefits are realised (Brooks and Waters, 2011; Madge, Raghuram, and Noxolo, 2015; Azram *et al.*, 2025). From this perspective, international mobility does not offer equal opportunities to all students, even when framed as a pathway to academic and personal development.

Empirical studies highlight the uneven nature of international experiences. Drawing on interviews with mobile students, Tavares (2024) found that levels of belonging, academic integration, and confidence varied considerably, with students from non-Western or less privileged backgrounds reporting greater difficulties navigating unfamiliar academic systems. These findings challenge dominant narratives of mobility by showing that international experience can also involve exclusion, uncertainty, and emotional stress. While such findings highlight disparities at the individual level, broader scholarship situates these uneven outcomes within systemic structures of inequality operating across global higher education.

Scholars further argue that internationalisation often reproduces global inequalities within higher education. Brooks and Waters (2013) and Marginson (2016) suggest that international mobility tends to privilege students with financial resources, linguistic capital, and familiarity with Western academic norms. Building on this, Kommers and Bista (2021) demonstrate that structural inequalities shape not only access to study abroad but also how international experiences are valued upon return, particularly for students from the Global South. Recent evidence reinforces these concerns. In a systematic review, Lomer *et al.* (2024) identified persistent inequalities in participation and outcomes, with students from lower-income or non-Western contexts facing greater barriers both during study abroad and after return.

Research also documents experiences of marginalisation, cultural misunderstanding, and academic exclusion among international students, especially those from non-dominant linguistic or geopolitical contexts (Lee and Rice, 2007; Montgomery, 2013). These challenges are not solely interpersonal but are embedded within broader power relations that shape global higher education. Within broader critiques of global higher education, Stein (2021) argues that international education often privileges Western knowledge systems, compelling students from the Global South to adapt to dominant norms while their own epistemologies remain undervalued. Beyond academic hierarchies, scholars have also drawn attention to the political and economic infrastructures that shape contemporary mobility systems.

Recent critical scholarship has further highlighted how international students are positioned within broader political and economic structures shaping contemporary higher education systems. Hight (2025), for example, argues that international mobility within the UK has increasingly become embedded within neoliberal governance frameworks, where institutions' reliance on international tuition fees intersects with restrictive immigration policies and regulatory pressures. This dynamic can generate tensions between the promotion of internationalisation and the lived realities of students navigating shifting policy environments, financial pressures, and structural vulnerabilities. Such critiques reinforce the need to examine international study not only as an individual developmental experience but as one shaped by wider institutional and policy contexts.

In the Algerian context, these global inequalities intersect with local structural challenges in distinctive ways. Students face limited access to scholarships, linguistic hierarchies privileging French and English, and institutional constraints that restrict meaningful international engagement (Benrabah, 2014; Mami, 2020). Such conditions shape both the experience of studying abroad and the possibilities for reintegration upon return. As a result, international mobility may simultaneously offer opportunities for growth and generate new forms of tension, frustration, and dislocation. Taken together, these critical perspectives highlight that international experience cannot be understood solely at the level of individual transformation. Instead, it must be situated within broader structural, institutional, and historical contexts that shape access, experience, and outcomes.

Transnational Education

Building on the preceding discussion of international mobility and its structural inequalities, transnational education (TNE) provides a broader institutional framework for understanding how international partnerships facilitate academic exchange and knowledge circulation across borders. Transnational education provides a broader institutional framework for understanding how international partnerships facilitate academic exchange and knowledge circulation across borders. TNE refers to the cross-border movement of students, academics, programmes, and research collaborations, often with the aim of strengthening institutional capacity and fostering mutual development (Knight, 2016; Jöns, 2018). These activities include joint and dual degree programmes, franchised curricula, distance-learning provision, and government-funded scholarship schemes that connect higher education systems in both the Global North and South.

Within this framework, transnational academic mobility is widely recognised for its potential to generate long-term benefits for individuals and institutions (Hugo, 2009; Shields, 2019). Doctoral students and academics who train internationally frequently contribute to their home universities

by introducing new knowledge, pedagogical approaches, and research expertise. Exposure to diverse academic cultures allows individuals to engage with alternative epistemologies and professional norms, fostering global outlooks that enhance intercultural awareness and adaptability (Hamza, 2010). For many returnees, these experiences reinforce their academic identity and expand their professional networks, positioning them as active contributors to the internationalisation of their local institutions.

However, critical scholarship highlights that the advantages of TNE are not evenly distributed. Scholars such as Altbach and Knight (2007) and Madge, Raghuram, and Noxolo (2015) emphasise that international academic partnerships often reflect uneven power relations, where institutions in the Global North exert greater influence over what is recognised as legitimate knowledge and acceptable academic standards. While TNE can support capacity building in developing contexts, it may also reproduce patterns of dependence by privileging Euro-American models of higher education and overshadowing local knowledge traditions. These dynamics are particularly evident in postcolonial settings such as Algeria, where collaboration with Anglophone universities is shaped by linguistic hierarchies, financial pressures, and differing academic cultures.

From this perspective, Algeria's partnership with the United Kingdom to fund doctoral study abroad represents both an important investment in research development and an example of these uneven transnational relationships. On one hand, the scholarship scheme seeks to build national academic capacity and promote English-medium scholarship. On the other, it exposes returnees to structural challenges during reintegration, particularly where institutional mechanisms for supporting knowledge transfer, research collaboration, or pedagogical reform remain underdeveloped. As Cassarino (2004) and Gu and Schweisfurth (2015) argue, return migration should be understood not as a final return stage but as an ongoing process of negotiation and adaptation within wider transnational networks.

Within this transnational framework, knowledge transfer emerges as a central mechanism through which international doctoral mobility is expected to generate academic and institutional benefit. The following section therefore examines knowledge transfer as a key professional dimension of return.

Professional Dimensions: Knowledge Transfer and Professional Development

Knowledge Transfer

Within the context of transnational education and international doctoral mobility, Knowledge transfer refers to the process through which individuals acquire, share, and apply knowledge gained from one context to another (De Wit and Altbach, 2021). Within international mobility, it encompasses the skills, insights, and practices that returning students and academics bring back to their home institutions after studying or working abroad (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015). It is widely recognised as one of the central aims of global mobility, given its potential to enhance research capacity, stimulate pedagogical innovation, and contribute to broader institutional development (De Wit and Altbach, 2021). However, the effectiveness of this process is neither automatic nor guaranteed. It depends on the presence of an enabling institutional environment, alignment of expectations, and the capacity of returnees to navigate the challenges that often accompany re-entry.

Szkudlarek (2010) and Alanedjani (2013) argue that knowledge transfer constitutes one of the most significant outcomes of successful re-entry, yet the transition home is frequently marked by emotional, cultural, and structural barriers that can limit this transfer. Studies have shown that returnees often experience reverse culture shock, frustration, and difficulty adjusting to local institutional norms when attempting to implement practices acquired abroad (Presbitero, 2016; Alkubaidi and Alzhrani, 2020; Winkel, Strachan, and Aamir, 2021; Kuzhabekova, 2025). These challenges can constrain the translation of global insights into local academic environments, resulting in underutilised expertise.

Despite these challenges, recent scholarship emphasises that international academic experiences can be powerful catalysts for knowledge exchange. Chen and Li (2019) note that global exposure introduces individuals to alternative epistemologies, pedagogical approaches, and research cultures, enabling them to enrich their professional settings upon return. For instance, Gu (2015) found that Chinese students returning from UK institutions described their overseas learning as an emotional journey of identity transformation, shaping their personal and professional lives in the context of return. Similar contributions are highlighted within the “brain circulation” literature, where returning scholars play a significant role in fostering innovation, international collaboration, and the development of new disciplinary perspectives (Jonkers and Tijssen, 2008; Ortega *et al.*, 2018).

However, while these perspectives highlight the transformative potential of mobility, knowledge transfer is shaped not only by the capabilities and motivation of returnees but also by the degree to which home institutions are prepared to absorb and integrate new ideas. Factors such as institutional resistance, limited resources, hierarchical structures, and deeply embedded pedagogical norms can significantly restrict the extent to which innovative practices take root. Lam and Rui (2023) vividly illustrate this challenge, showing how returning academics in China struggled to apply internationally acquired expertise in environments where organisational priorities and routines were slow to change. Their findings highlight that the success of knowledge transfer hinges on the absorptive capacity of the receiving institution, not merely the efforts of the returnees themselves. As Geeraert, Ward, and Hanel (2022) argue, reintegration is more likely to be constructive when returnees' expectations are realistic and aligned with local institutional realities, enabling them to negotiate constraints while still contributing meaningfully to their academic settings.

These dynamics become particularly significant in postcolonial contexts, where structural conditions for knowledge transfer may be uneven or underdeveloped (Altbach, 2014; Kuzhabekova, 2025). In Algeria, government-funded mobility schemes aim to cultivate internationally trained academics capable of contributing to national higher education reform (British Council, 2014; Bouherar and Salem, 2025). Yet the extent to which this potential is realised depends heavily on the reintegration phase. Understanding how Algerian doctoral returnees negotiate institutional constraints, adapt global practices, and position themselves within their local academic communities offers valuable insight into how international mobility translates into both individual growth and national academic capacity. Such an analysis is crucial for understanding how returnees develop professionally after their return, and how they negotiate their roles, aspirations, and academic identities within their home contexts.

Professional Development

Building on the discussion of knowledge transfer, professional development refers to the continuous process through which individuals expand their skills, knowledge, and competencies within their career contexts. For academics, it involves not only the enhancement of disciplinary expertise but also the cultivation of broader intellectual, pedagogical, and intercultural capacities. Studying or working abroad can play a pivotal role in this process, offering opportunities to engage with new academic environments, encounter diverse perspectives, and develop innovative practices that contribute to both intellectual and professional growth (Rumbley, Altbach, and Reisberg, 2012; De Wit and Altbach, 2021).

The effectiveness of professional development for internationally educated academics is closely tied to the successful transfer and adaptation of knowledge gained abroad. This process depends not only on individual capability but also on the institutional and cultural contexts into which returnees reintegrate (Szkudlarek, 2010; Pham and Saito, 2020). Extending the discussion of knowledge transfer, returning scholars must negotiate how newly acquired skills are integrated into evolving professional trajectories, often within institutional environments that differ from those in which they were trained (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015; Chen, 2017). Reintegration, therefore, is not a passive stage but a critical period that shapes how returnees consolidate their learning, navigate workplace expectations, and contribute to institutional change (Black, Gregersen, and Mendenhall, 1992; Presbitero, 2016). This stage also marks the beginning of an evolving process of professional identity negotiation, as academics seek to align the values, practices, and knowledge gained abroad with those of their home institutions (Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019; Pham, 2008).

Despite the growing number of returnees in developing economies, there remains a limited understanding of their professional development trajectories within home-country institutions (Pham and Saito, 2020). This gap is particularly noteworthy given the increasing emphasis on the potential of returning scholars to drive innovation and reform within local higher education systems (Li *et al.*, 2012). Returnees represent an important human capital resource capable of enriching their academic environments with global knowledge and cross-cultural insights, yet their professional experiences and contributions remain insufficiently explored.

Empirical research suggests that international experiences can profoundly shape both personal and professional orientations. Hadis (2005) found that time spent abroad often fosters renewed enthusiasm for learning and academic achievement, while Benson and Pattie (2008) observed that returnees frequently enjoy enhanced career prospects as a result of their expanded worldviews and skill sets. However, the positive potential of these experiences is not always fully realised upon return. Pham and Saito's (2020) study of Vietnamese returnees, for instance, revealed obstacles such as rigid workplace cultures and stereotypes about foreign qualifications, which limited the professional advancement of internationally trained academics. Similarly, Pikos-Sallie (2018) identified reverse culture shock, institutional resistance to change, and difficulties in producing high-quality research among Saudi academic returnees. These findings illustrate that structural and cultural barriers within home institutions can constrain the translation of international experience into professional growth.

Therefore, the professional development of returning academics cannot be understood solely in terms of individual capability or motivation. It also depends on the institutional and socio-cultural conditions that enable or hinder the application of knowledge and expertise acquired abroad. Researchers note that the effectiveness of reintegration is shaped by institutional openness, leadership attitudes, and the availability of structures that support innovation (Pikos-Sallie, 2018; Pham and Saito, 2020). To maximise the impact of international doctoral mobility, academic environments must support returnees through recognition of their expertise, opportunities for collaboration, and clear pathways for applying their international learning (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015; Kuzhabekova, Sparks and Temerbayeva, 2019). These dynamics are particularly visible among academic returnees, whose transitions from international doctoral students to lecturers and researchers illustrate how global learning becomes recontextualised within local institutional cultures. The following section therefore examines academic returnees in more detail, focusing on how their skills, identities, and expectations are renegotiated upon return.

Academic Returnees

The term returnee encompasses a wide spectrum of individuals whose experiences and motivations vary considerably. These include migrants who return to their home countries for social or political reasons, temporary labour migrants who complete overseas contracts, and academic returnees who study or gain professional experience abroad, often through state or institutional sponsorship and are expected to bring back their acquired knowledge and skills (Altbach and Knight, 2007; Potts, 2016). Among these categories, academic returnees occupy a distinctive position because their mobility is closely linked to national strategies for human capital development and educational reform.

In Algeria, academic returnees are typically doctoral students funded by the government to pursue studies abroad with the expectation that they will contribute to the development of the higher education system upon their return. Potts (2016) notes that many of the personal and professional benefits of international study only become fully apparent after repatriation, as returnees begin to apply their newly acquired knowledge within local contexts. These benefits often manifest in the form of new pedagogical approaches, research collaborations, and expanded intellectual perspectives (Altbach and Knight, 2007). Yet despite this potential, limited research explores how these processes unfold in practice, particularly in developing contexts such as Algeria.

The Forum on Education Abroad (2011) defines an academic returnee as “an education abroad participant who has returned to the home institution after completion of her or his programme” (p. 12). Beyond this formal definition, academic returnees engage in complex processes of

renegotiating their academic and professional identities within their home institutions (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015). This process is especially significant in contexts where academic traditions, languages of instruction, and educational expectations differ between host and home countries, requiring returnees to reconcile what they learned abroad with the realities of their local institutions. Research suggests that these processes often have long-term personal and institutional effects, as returnees act as bridges between global academic networks and local scholarly communities (Wielkiewicz and Turkowski, 2010; Chen and Li, 2019).

Building on this conceptual framing, empirical studies highlight that academic returnees can contribute significantly to innovation and reform in higher education. For instance, Chen and Li (2019) found that returned Chinese academics were instrumental in institutional transformation, using their transnational capital and global connections to promote reform and research excellence. However, such contributions are strongly shaped by the institutional environment of the receiving university, which can either enable or restrict their impact. Similar findings have been reported in other contexts, where overseas-trained academics attempt to integrate international pedagogies and research practices into their home institutions (Ortiga *et al.*, 2018; Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019; Karakaş, 2020).

These studies also reveal that reintegration is not always smooth. Returnees frequently encounter institutional rigidity, resistance to change, and misalignment between expectations formed abroad and realities at home (Lee and Kim, 2010; Khanal and Gaulee, 2019). Emotional and professional challenges such as reverse culture shock and loss of status are also common (Brown and Brown, 2009; Savicki and Price, 2021). From this study's perspective, these experiences illustrate that re-entry should be conceptualised as a dynamic, multidimensional process rather than a single stage of adaptation. It involves not only logistical and emotional adjustment but also the ongoing reconstruction of identity and professional agency.

Despite these challenges, the potential contributions of academic returnees remain substantial. They constitute a valuable form of transnational human capital individuals equipped with international experience, advanced skills, and diverse perspectives that can drive academic innovation and institutional growth (Rosen and Zweig, 2006; Lam and Rui, 2024). From this study's standpoint, such returnees are not merely knowledge carriers but active agents of change, capable of bridging global and local academic cultures and fostering intellectual exchange within their home institutions.

In countries such as Algeria, these dynamics are especially relevant. Previous studies suggest that while academic returnees often bring innovative ideas, linguistic competence, and global

networks, they may encounter institutional structures that are not always receptive to change or innovation (Altbach and Knight, 2007; Karakaş, 2020; Pham and Saito, 2020). These conditions highlight the importance of examining how returning scholars negotiate the application of their international learning within the realities of their home academic systems.

Once again as I argue throughout my thesis, there remains a notable gap in the literature regarding the lived experiences of academic returnees in North Africa, particularly Algeria. Existing research has largely focused on Asian and Western contexts. Although Algeria has a sizable population of students studying abroad approximately 31,288 according to UNESCO (Jughurtha, 2022) the experiences of these returnees, especially PhD holders trained in the United Kingdom, remain largely unexplored. These dynamics highlight that academic return cannot be understood solely in structural or professional terms. Rather, the experiences of returnees are closely tied to evolving understandings of self, belonging, and professional identity, as individuals negotiate the relationship between internationally shaped perspectives and local institutional contexts. Building on this insight, the following section examines identity and culture as key conceptual lenses for understanding re-entry experiences.

Identity and Culture: Conceptual Perspectives

Understanding how individuals reconstruct their sense of self during and after re-entry is therefore essential for interpreting the lived experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees. Within this thesis, identity is understood as dynamic, relational, and continually negotiated through individuals' interactions within their social and cultural environments (Hall, 1996; Jenkins, 2008). While Hall emphasises the fluid and shifting nature of cultural identity, Jenkins highlights how identity is formed and reformed through ongoing social interaction. In professional settings, these processes also extend to how individuals interpret their academic roles, practices, and relationships upon return. Culture, likewise, is approached not as a fixed or homogeneous entity but as a system of meanings, values, and practices that individuals engage with, interpret, and reshape throughout their everyday experiences (Geertz, 1973; Holliday, 2011). Together, these perspectives provide a conceptual foundation for exploring how Algerian doctoral returnees navigate and reconstruct their personal and professional identities within shifting cultural and institutional landscapes.

Identity is a contested concept across the social sciences and has been theorised in multiple ways. From a psychological perspective, Erikson (1968) viewed identity as a sense of personal continuity and coherence across time, providing a foundation for self-understanding. In sociology, identity is seen as socially constructed, formed through interaction and recognition by others (Mead, 1934; Jenkins, 2008). From the standpoint of cultural studies, scholars such as Hall

(1996) have moved away from fixed or stable understandings of identity, emphasising the fluid, fragmented, and negotiated nature of identity across contexts and over time. Anthropological and intercultural approaches often link identity to processes of belonging, ethnicity, and cultural affiliation (Phinney and Alipuria, 1990), while in educational and professional research, identity is conceptualised as emerging through participation, practice, and role negotiation within specific communities (Wenger, 1998; Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop, 2004).

These diverse perspectives reveal that identity is multi-layered, context-dependent, and continually evolving (Hall, 1996; Jenkins, 2008). Rather than being fixed or universal, identity is understood as lived, relational, and situated, developing through individuals' ongoing interactions with their social and cultural environments (Mead, 1934; Jenkins, 2008) and being continually reshaped through experience and reflection (Hall, 1996).

Building on this conceptual understanding, the present study approaches identity as a dynamic and negotiated process that unfolds across cultural and professional contexts. This perspective reflects the lived realities of Algerian doctoral returnees, whose experiences are shaped by movement between two academic and cultural systems: the United Kingdom and Algeria. Their re-entry experiences involve both a re-negotiation of cultural belonging, as theorised in re-entry and repatriation literature (Sussman, 2001), and an evolving sense of professional selfhood within their home academic communities (Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop, 2004). Framing identity in this way enables the study to examine how returning scholars reconstruct their academic, cultural, and personal identities upon re-entering their home institutions.

Cultural Identity, Acculturation, and Re-entry

Cultural identity forms a central dimension of how individuals understand themselves in relation to their social and cultural environments. It refers to a sense of belonging shaped through shared values, language, traditions, and social practices (Phinney and Alipuria, 1990). However, contemporary scholarship has consistently rejected essentialist understandings of cultural identity, emphasising instead its dynamic, negotiated, and context-dependent nature. Hall (1996) conceptualises cultural identity as a continuous process of "becoming" rather than a fixed state of "being," while Sussman (2002) and Jenkins (2008) highlight how identity is reshaped through social interaction and movement across cultural contexts.

For individuals who engage in international mobility, such as Algerian doctoral students studying in the United Kingdom, cultural identity is often constructed across multiple cultural systems. Exposure to new academic norms, social practices, and value frameworks can prompt individuals

to reassess previously taken-for-granted assumptions about home, self, and belonging (Ward, Bochner, and Furnham, 2001). As a result, returnees may develop hybrid or liminal identities that draw simultaneously on elements of both host and home cultures. This process can enrich self-understanding but may also generate tension, particularly when returning to environments that have not undergone similar change (Gaw, 2000; Kartoshkina, 2014).

Berry's (1997) acculturation framework offers a useful lens for understanding how such identity negotiations unfold. Although originally developed to explain immigrant adaptation, the framework has been widely applied in international education and re-entry research (Szkudlarek, 2010). Berry identifies four acculturation strategies; integration, assimilation, separation, and marginalisation, based on the degree to which individuals maintain their home culture while engaging with a new one. Integration, which involves sustaining connections to both cultural contexts, is generally associated with more positive psychological outcomes (Berry and Sam, 2006).

Importantly, acculturation does not end upon return. During re-entry, individuals often undergo a process of reverse acculturation, renegotiating their relationship with the home culture after internalising aspects of the host culture (Sussman, 2002). This can result in a "cultural identity shift" whereby the home environment feels unexpectedly unfamiliar, and previously stable markers of belonging are disrupted (Gaw, 2000). Such experiences are frequently reported in re-entry literature as a core component of reverse culture shock, particularly when expectations of familiarity clash with altered social norms and institutional realities.

These processes are especially salient in postcolonial contexts such as Algeria, where historical, linguistic, and educational hierarchies continue to shape how global and local identities are valued and negotiated (Benrabah, 2014; Mami, 2020). The symbolic capital associated with English-language education and Western academic training can further complicate re-entry, influencing how returning scholars perceive their cultural and professional positioning within home institutions (Jacob, 2019). For Algerian doctoral returnees, re-entry represents a critical moment in which identity is actively renegotiated, shaped by the interaction between personal transformation and the cultural, institutional, and historical realities of the home context. This understanding provides an essential foundation for examining professional identity, where similar processes of negotiation and tension become visible within academic workplaces. While acculturation theory offers a conceptual foundation for understanding these cultural and identity negotiations during re-entry, the psychological dimensions of this process are discussed later in

this chapter, where the affective, behavioural, and cognitive aspects of readjustment are examined in greater depth.

Cultural Distance and Re-entry Adjustment

Building on acculturation and re-entry perspectives discussed above, the degree of cultural distance between host and home environments represents one of the most widely discussed contextual influences on re-entry adjustment, affecting both personal and professional reintegration. Cultural distance refers to the disparities between the cultural settings of the host country and the home nation, and it has been revealed to significantly impact the adjustment process upon returning home (Ward *et al.*, 2001; Godart *et al.*, 2015; Rickley, 2019). Differences in societal norms, values, behaviours, and institutional structures can create a gap that returnees must bridge upon returning home. The greater this distance, the more challenging the adjustment tends to be, as individuals attempt to reconcile the values and practices acquired abroad with those of their home culture. Berry (2005) argues that successful adaptation depends on the ability to integrate aspects of both cultural systems; where such integration is constrained by structural or normative rigidity, psychological stress may intensify during re-entry.

Alandejani (2013), Butcher (2002), and La Brack (2006) provide detailed accounts of the challenges faced by international students upon their return, particularly those resulting from the internalisation of attitudes and behaviours that are not easily accommodated by their home cultures. These challenges often manifest as feelings of alienation, rejection, or even conflict within their social circles. For instance, returnees may adopt a more individualistic mindset after spending time in a country that values independence, only to find that their home culture continues to lay emphasis on collectivism and interdependence. Such tensions illustrate how cultural distance is experienced not only as external difference but as an internal negotiation of values and expectations shaped through mobility.

Adjustment difficulties associated with cultural distance are frequently intensified by unrealistic expectations. Many returnees anticipate a smooth reintegration, assuming that home will feel entirely familiar, only to discover that both they and their environments have changed. Ward *et al.* (2001) suggests that the greater the divergence between host and home cultural values, the more disorienting the re-entry experience can become. This mismatch often contributes to reverse culture shock, where individuals struggle to feel “at home” in a once-familiar setting. In this sense, re-entry involves both practical adaptation and psychological recalibration as returnees reassess their relationship with home culture.

Beyond personal adjustment, cultural distance can also shape experiences within institutional contexts. The academic and professional practices learned abroad may not align with local norms and institutional cultures. Rickley (2019) notes that returnees frequently encounter barriers when attempting to apply their international skills and knowledge, as these may be viewed as incompatible with established domestic practices. For example, an Algerian PhD returnee might have adopted collaborative and egalitarian academic practices from their host institution, only to return to a hierarchical and more rigid academic system. Such incongruence can constrain the application of internationally acquired practices within local institutional settings. Rather than treating these challenges solely as individual difficulties, scholars emphasise the role of structural and cultural expectations in shaping how internationally acquired practices are received within home environments.

The impact of cultural distance extends beyond professional and institutional contexts to interpersonal relationships. Butcher (2002) and Van Gorp *et al.* (2017) found that returning students often experience difficulty reconnecting with friends and family members who have not shared their experiences abroad. The values, beliefs, and worldviews acquired during their international education may not align with those of their social networks, creating emotional distance within familiar relationships. La Brack (2006) similarly observed that this can lead to misunderstanding or estrangement, as returnees struggle to articulate their transformative experiences to others who lack comparable cultural reference points. These interpersonal dimensions further demonstrate that re-entry is experienced across multiple relational levels rather than confined to institutional settings alone.

Cultural distance also shapes processes of identity reconstruction. Godart *et al.* (2015) argue that exposure to different cultural systems can foster a transnational or hybrid identity, in which returnees integrate elements of both host and home cultures. While this can enhance adaptability, it may also produce feelings of in-betweenness, as individuals perceive themselves as belonging fully to neither context. This perspective reinforces the importance of examining re-entry through an identity-focused lens, linking cultural adjustment to broader processes of self-redefinition.

To mitigate the challenges posed by cultural distance, several scholars emphasise the importance of structured re-entry support. Furnham and Bochner (1982) highlight the value of programmes that promote reflection on cultural adjustment, identity transformation, and coping strategies. Such initiatives can enable returnees to articulate their experiences, build understanding with peers, and integrate their new perspectives in ways that align with home-culture expectations.

Institutional measures such as mentoring schemes and re-entry workshops can further facilitate smoother psychological and professional adaptation.

While cultural distance provides a valuable framework for understanding contextual pressures shaping re-entry adjustment, these external differences alone do not fully capture how returnees interpret their experiences. Instead, the negotiation of cultural expectations becomes particularly visible through evolving professional identities, where returning academics reinterpret their roles, practices, and sense of belonging within local academic environments. The following section therefore turns to professional identity in transnational academic contexts, extending the discussion from structural adjustment toward identity formation within professional practice.

Professional Identity in Transnational Academic Contexts

Professional identity refers to how individuals define themselves within their occupational roles, encompassing their values, beliefs, and sense of belonging within a professional community (Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop, 2004; Henkel, 2005). For academics, it is closely tied to their teaching philosophies, research practices, collegial relationships, and institutional expectations. Wenger's (1998) notion of "communities of practice" further illuminates this, suggesting that identity is shaped through participation in shared academic and professional practices. For internationally educated scholars, professional identity is profoundly influenced by transnational experiences and the process of reintegration upon return. Gu and Schweisfurth (2015) argue that overseas study exposes scholars to new epistemological frameworks, pedagogical styles, and professional norms, which may not always align with those of their home institutions. Trede, Macklin and Bridges (2012) and Mackay (2017) similarly note that professional identity development is not linear but an evolving negotiation between personal values, institutional cultures, and wider social expectations.

Informed by literature and my study's data analysis, I see that the re-entry phase for Algerian PhD returnees represents a critical point at which professional identity is both challenged and reshaped. Returning scholars may aspire to implement innovative teaching methods or collaborative research practices learned abroad, yet they may encounter resistance within bureaucratic or traditional academic systems. This tension demonstrates that professional identity formation is relational: it depends not only on individual agency but also on institutional and cultural structures that either support or constrain professional growth. Understanding these dynamics provides insight into how returnees position themselves within their academic communities, balancing their globally shaped learning with the local realities of their professional environments. However, professional positioning represents only one dimension of identity

negotiation. Re-entry also involves broader shifts in how individuals understand themselves at the intersection of cultural and professional domains.

Identity Shifts at the Intersection of Cultural and Professional Domains

Building on the discussion of professional identity, it is important to consider how cultural and professional identities intersect and how this intersection may generate deeper shifts in self-understanding during and after re-entry. Cultural and professional identities are deeply intertwined, influencing and reshaping one another through the process of mobility and return. Cultural values inform how individuals perceive and enact their professional roles, while professional experiences can alter their sense of cultural belonging. This interplay reinforces Hall's (1996) and Jenkins's (2008) argument that identity is negotiated at the intersection of the personal and the social, continually redefined through interaction.

For Algerian doctoral returnees, the convergence of these two identity dimensions is particularly salient. Their return home involves reconciling professional identities shaped within Western academic environments with the expectations and realities of Algerian higher education. This ongoing negotiation reflects both adaptation and agency: adapting to institutional norms while attempting to maintain academic values, independence, and critical thinking practices acquired abroad. This relational view of identity highlights that re-entry is not a simple return but a process of transformation and re-situating the self within shifting cultural and professional contexts. These evolving identity dynamics provide a crucial context for understanding how returning scholars interpret change and self-development.

Extending this relational perspective, identity shifts during re-entry can be understood as processes of deeper self-reconfiguration rather than simple role adjustment. Recent scholarship highlights that identity is not static but continuously reshaped through cross-cultural encounters and re-entry experiences (Ma, Tan, and Lic, 2023; Dai and Hardy, 2024). Exposure to different value systems, norms, and academic traditions abroad often leads to a redefinition of self, both personally and professionally. For example, Alfurayh and Burns (2020) found that Saudi women returning from doctoral study in Australia experienced identities that were altered, evolved, and reinterpreted as a result of engaging with new cultural and social possibilities.

Similarly, Kohonen (2008) identified three broad patterns among Finnish returnees: identity shifters, balanced identities, and non-shifters illustrating that such transformations vary in depth and form. These findings align with Sussman's (2002) typology of cultural identity responses,

where some individuals internalise aspects of the host culture “additive” identities, while others experience internal conflict or identity disintegration upon return.

Within this context, cultural identity change is not a simple transition but an interpretive process of reconciling multiple frames of reference. Exposure to new cultural knowledge, languages, and professional norms often prompts returnees to critically evaluate their home cultures, developing more complex or hybrid self-conceptions (Rosa Gonzalez, 2022).

For many returnees, particularly those from postcolonial contexts such as Algeria, this process may provoke tension between evolving globalised identities and local cultural expectations. Studies such as Alandejani (2013) illustrate how women returning from Western education often confront conflicting pressures between the independence cultivated abroad and the conformity expected at home. This tension stresses the challenges of re-entry as both a personal and cultural negotiation. These evolving identity dynamics form an essential setting for understanding how returning scholars interpret change and self-development. Taken together, these perspectives demonstrate that identity shifts during re-entry are multidimensional, shaped by cultural distance, institutional context, and individual agency. One theoretical perspective that helps illuminate this process is Transformative Learning, which explains how encounters with new cultural and educational contexts can lead to deep shifts in values, beliefs, and worldviews.

Transformative Learning Model

Transformative Learning, first conceptualised by Jack Mezirow in the 1970s, explains how individuals fundamentally change their perspectives through critical reflection and new experiences. Originating from his study of adult learners particularly middle-aged women returning to education after a prolonged absence this theory is grounded in adult education and highlights the process of questioning existing beliefs, assumptions, and worldviews to foster deeper understanding and personal growth.

Subsequent scholars, such as Edward W. Taylor (1997, 2007), have expanded Mezirow’s work by emphasising that transformation is not solely a rational or cognitive process, but one that also encompasses emotional, social, and cultural dimensions. This broader understanding is particularly relevant to the experiences of international doctoral returnees, whose learning and re-entry transitions occur within complex intercultural and institutional environments. As a result, Transformative Learning has been widely applied across diverse populations and educational contexts, including study-abroad programmes (Brock, 2010; Hamza, 2010; Smith, McAuliffe, and Rippard, 2014; Stone *et al.*, 2017).

Mezirow (2000, p. 8) defined TL as “The process by which we transform our taken-for-granted frames of reference (meaning schemes, habits of mind, mindsets) to make them more inclusive, discriminating, open, emotionally capable to change, and reflective so that they will prove truer or justified to guided action”. At the heart of Mezirow's definition lies the concept of a "frame of reference" a structure formed by culture and language that shapes how individuals interpret their experiences. Transformative learning, as Mezirow (1990) explains, is the process through which people alter these frames of reference by questioning and restructuring the assumptions that guide their understanding of the world. This transformation allows individuals to either deepen and differentiate their existing views or adopt new ways of making meaning.

Key Components of Transformative Learning

Mezirow’s theory of transformative learning involves several core components that facilitate deep, lasting change:

1. **Disorienting Dilemma:** A significant life event or experience that challenges an individual’s existing beliefs and assumptions, leading to critical reflection.
2. **Critical Reflection:** The process of examining deeply held beliefs, which allows individuals to question and evaluate their previously unexamined assumptions.
3. **Rational Discourse:** Engaging in open and honest conversations with others to explore and validate new perspectives.
4. **Reintegration:** Integrating the newly acquired perspectives into one’s worldview and daily practices.

These components illustrate how transformative learning is driven by engagement with new environments, experiences, and social contexts, conditions often experienced by those studying abroad.

Transformative Learning in the Context of Study Abroad

Study abroad programmes are prime contexts for transformative learning as they often expose students to entirely different cultural norms, societal values, and educational systems, which act as disorienting dilemmas. These experiences challenge students to reassess their values and assumptions. For instance, Mossberg (1990) and Wang *et al.*, (2024) concluded that studying

abroad has a transformative influence not only on individuals' academic pursuits but also on the institutions to which they return.

In this study, Mezirow (1978, 1991, 2000) framework is adopted as a conceptual lens helps illuminate how returnees may reconstruct their perspectives through reflection and learning. My reading of Mezirow's framework maps well onto the experiences of returning doctoral students, whose intercultural engagement and professional transitions often involve re-examining previously held assumptions and integrating new ways of understanding. This process often involves choosing between abandoning former perspective or reconciling them with a newly formed insights to develop a more comprehensive worldview; an outcome evident in the experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees who have acquired new knowledge, values, and academic practices abroad.

However, while transformative learning is empowering, it also presents challenges, particularly during the re-entry phase. Studies by Alandejani (2013), Le Ha and Mohamad (2020), and Alkhalaf, Al-Krenawi, and Elbedour (2024) revealed that returnees often struggle to reintegrate into their home institutions due to hierarchical structures and differing expectations. For Saudi Arabian women returning from education overseas, the adjustment to a highly structured work environment was a source of frustration, particularly when juxtaposed with the autonomy they experienced abroad.

Moreover, transformative learning does not only impact individual returnees but can also create tension in their social and professional environments. Kitchenham (2008) notes that Mezirow's ten-phase model does not necessarily occur in order or completeness for transformation to take place, which means that individuals may experience different aspects of transformation depending on their unique circumstances and environments.

Broader Implications and Supporting Transformative Learning

The effects of transformative learning extend beyond individuals and carry important implications for home institutions and wider educational systems (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015). Returnees who experience such transformation often bring back new pedagogical ideas, values, and cultural insights that can enrich their professional environments. However, their reintegration depends on the degree to which institutions recognise and support these changes (Pham and Saito, 2020).

Institutional structures such as mentorship schemes, reflective workshops, and peer dialogue platforms can help returnees process their experiences and apply their learning effectively

(Kitchenham, 2008; Le Ha and Mohamad, 2020). These spaces promote critical reflection and continued adaptation rather than assuming that transformation is a single moment of change.

Recent research shows that returning academics often attempt to introduce innovative teaching and research practices but may encounter institutional resistance (Chen and Li, 2019; Pham and Saito, 2020). Although such findings provide valuable insight, little is known about how these dynamics unfold within Algerian higher education, highlighting the need for further investigation into the experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees.

Sustaining transnational research links and professional collaborations can also support returnees in consolidating their learning (Cassarino, 2004). Continued engagement with international networks enables them to integrate global perspectives while grounding their contributions in local realities, thereby strengthening both personal growth and institutional development (Karakas, 2020).

In summary, Transformative Learning offers a useful conceptual perspective for understanding how exposure to new cultural, educational, and social contexts can prompt significant shifts in values, beliefs, and self-perception. Recognising and supporting these transformative processes is essential for strengthening both individual reintegration and the broader vitality of higher education in Algeria.

While Transformative Learning explains how individuals critically reflect on and reconstruct their worldviews, it does not fully account for the practical and emotional navigation that follows such transformation. For this reason, Schlossberg's Transition Model provides a complementary lens that focuses on how individuals manage and adjust to major life changes during re-entry.

Schlossberg's Transition Model

To further understand Algerian doctoral graduates' transition experiences back home, it is necessary to define what I mean by 'transition' in this study. Following the discussion of Transformative Learning, which focuses on how individuals undergo personal and cognitive shifts in perspective, Schlossberg's (1989, 1995) Transition Theory offers a valuable conceptual framework for understanding how people experience and adapt to major life changes. She defines transitions as events or non-events that alter life circumstances, requiring individuals to reorient their sense of self and develop new coping strategies. These transitions can be anticipated such as completing a PhD or unanticipated, such as the unforeseen emotional and professional challenges that accompany reintegration (Kotewa, 1995). Central to Schlossberg's model is the

individual's capacity to make sense of change and to mobilise both internal and external resources to manage it effectively.

Building on earlier discussions of identity transformation and cultural negotiation, research on international academic mobility demonstrates that scholars who complete their studies abroad often acquire new disciplinary knowledge, research skills, and intercultural competencies that reshape both professional practices and self-understanding (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015; Le Ha and Mohamad, 2020; Marginson, 2014; Montgomery, 2013). Upon return, however, these individuals encounter multiple layers of transition not only geographical relocation but also the shift from doctoral student to academic professional each requiring significant adaptation (Martin, 1984; Szkudlarek, 2010).

Rather than reintroducing identity change as a separate concept, Schlossberg's model enables these previously discussed processes to be interpreted through a transition lens, emphasising how returnees reconcile internationally shaped expectations with the pedagogical norms, institutional structures, and cultural environments of their home context (Cox, 2008; Alandejani, 2013). The transition from doctoral student to teacher-researcher can thus be understood as both a professional transformation and a process of identity renegotiation within evolving cultural and institutional environments.

In the context of academic mobility, transitions are rarely linear. Individuals studying abroad must adapt to unfamiliar academic systems, cultural norms, and communication styles (Sussman, 2002; Ward *et al.*, 2001). Upon returning home, they face a different yet equally complex challenge as they re-enter environments that may no longer align with their transformed perspectives. Martin (1984, 1986) observed that this return phase is often more psychologically demanding than the initial adaptation abroad because individuals must bridge the gap between their evolved identities and the unchanged realities of home. The shift from student to academic professional therefore extends beyond practical adjustment and requires reconfiguring one's self-concept and professional identity (Szkudlarek, 2010; Tomlinson and Jackson, 2021).

Schlossberg's model emphasises that transitions are not passive occurrences but active meaning-making processes, in which individuals interpret change, assess available support, and decide how to respond (Schlossberg, 1995). Wortham (2006) adds that people bring pre-existing identities into new contexts, which can both enable and constrain adjustment a notion particularly relevant to doctoral returnees who must reconcile internationally shaped academic identities with local institutional expectations.

As discussed earlier in the section on cultural identity, acculturation and re-entry, drawing on Berry's (1997) acculturation framework, re-entry may also be viewed as a reverse process of adaptation, in which returnees renegotiate their attachment to home cultures while accommodating the internalised influences of host ones. Schlossberg's theory complements this perspective by emphasising the psychological and situational dimensions of transition. Her "4 S's" model; Situation, Self, Support, and Strategies offer a comprehensive means of analysing how individuals evaluate change, draw on personal strengths and social networks, and employ coping mechanisms to restore balance.

Within this study, Schlossberg's model is used as an interpretive tool because its focus on how individuals manage change aligns closely with the experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees. It helps illuminate how they interpret and respond to the challenges of re-entry while balancing personal agency with institutional and cultural constraints.

In summary, Schlossberg's Transition Model highlights that transitions whether anticipated or unexpected are shaped not only by external conditions but also by the individual's internal resources, coping strategies, and support systems. For returning doctoral graduates, this framework illuminates re-entry as an active process of meaning-making, through which they seek to re-establish coherence between who they have become abroad and who they are expected to be at home.

While Schlossberg's model explains how people navigate change, it does not specify what forms this change takes within the re-entry experience itself. To address this, the following section explores how readjustment unfolds among returning sojourners, focusing on its emotional, cognitive, and behavioural dimensions.

Psychological Dimensions of Re-entry

The psychological dimensions of re-entry extend the discussion of acculturation by examining how cultural and identity negotiations are experienced affectively, behaviourally, and cognitively (Szkudlarek, 2010; Fanari, Wright, and Foerester, 2021). While Berry's (1997; 2005) acculturation framework conceptualises adaptation in terms of cultural orientation and identity negotiation between home and host contexts, Ward *et al.* (2001) further develop this perspective by examining the psychological and sociocultural processes through which such adaptation unfolds. Together, these approaches illuminate how returnees navigate cultural belonging and identity transformation, while also highlighting the inner emotional, behavioural, and cognitive mechanisms through which these negotiations are lived and interpreted.

At an affective level, re-entry is shaped by emotional responses, coping, and well-being (Szkudlarek, 2010; Gray and Savicki, 2015). Lysgaard's (1955) U-curve model of adjustment and Gullahorn and Gullahorn's (1963) W-curve extension remain foundational in explaining the cyclical nature of adaptation, crisis, and recovery during cultural transitions, a framework discussed in more detail later in the section on the W-curve model. These models demonstrate that emotional reactions often follow a rhythm: initial enthusiasm gives way to frustration and confusion before eventual readjustment. However, later studies reveal that re-entry can provoke emotional distress equal to, or even greater than, the initial culture shock experienced abroad (Martin, 1993; Gaw, 2000; Merrill and Pusch, 2007). Returnees frequently experience feelings of disconnection and loss when the home environment and social networks they anticipate have altered during their absence (Sussman, 1986; Zikic, 2006; Fanari, Wright, and Foerster, 2021). As Storti (2001) observed, expectations of familiarity often intensify frustration when reality fails to match these assumptions. Berry (2005) further argues that successful psychological adaptation depends on the ability to integrate elements of both cultural contexts, suggesting that difficulties in balancing cultural continuity and change may heighten emotional stress during re-entry.

Recent empirical research further demonstrates that reverse acculturative stress upon return is significantly associated with lower life satisfaction and negative affect, particularly among women returnees, underscoring how emotional wellbeing during re-entry is closely tied to identity renegotiation and perceived social support (Alkhalaf, Al-Krenawi, and Elbedour, 2024). In this sense, the affective dimension of re-entry involves not only emotional upheaval but also a process of rediscovering belonging in a space that no longer feels entirely one's own.

From a behavioural perspective, re-entry involves renegotiating social practices and interactional norms. Research suggests that individuals who adapted successfully abroad may experience heightened behavioural incongruence upon return (Black *et al.*, 1992; Martin and Harrell, 2004; Geeraert *et al.*, 2022). The internalisation of host-culture norms can create tension in home contexts that expect continuity rather than change (Wielkiewicz and Turkowski, 2010; Savicki and Price, 2021). For returning academics in particular, such behavioural shifts may clash with institutional expectations that remain resistant to innovation or difference (Ward *et al.*, 2001; Szkudlarek, 2010; Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019).

Cognitively, re-entry challenges how returnees interpret home, identity, and belonging. Unlike departure, return is often assumed to be straightforward, an assumption that overlooks the cognitive dissonance generated when internal transformation meets external familiarity (Adler, 1981; Sussman, 2002). New values and perspectives developed abroad may conflict with

established norms, prompting reflection on how multiple cultural frames can be integrated into a coherent sense of self (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015). Empirical studies show that mismatches between expectations and reality strongly shape re-entry satisfaction and coping (Martin and Harrell, 2004; Szkudlarek, 2010; Mehreen *et al.*, 2025). Qualitative research on Indonesian returnees similarly highlights how gaps between expectations and lived realities contribute to identity tension, psychosocial stress, and the need to renegotiate belonging during reintegration (Andrianto, Ma, and Damayanti, 2020). Cognitive flexibility is therefore central to successful reintegration, enabling returnees to reinterpret familiar contexts without losing coherence in self-understanding (Martin, 1984).

These affective, behavioural, and cognitive dimensions are often conceptualised collectively through the ABC model of acculturation (Ward *et al.*, 2001), which has been extended to explain re-entry processes (Martin and Harrell, 2004). Together, they illustrate that returning home is not a simple reversal of departure but a psychologically complex and transformative experience.

Understanding Readjustment in the Re-entry Context

Building on the psychological and situational dimensions of transition discussed above, readjustment refers to the initial phase of adaptation that returning sojourners experience as they navigate life in their home country after studying abroad (Ward, Bochner and Furnham, 2001). This phase represents the early stage of re-entry, during which individuals attempt to re-establish familiarity, continuity, and functional engagement with everyday social and professional environments that may feel both familiar and unexpectedly altered.

Empirical research demonstrates that readjustment often involves negotiating new tensions between internationally shaped expectations and local realities. Studies focusing on academic returnees have repeatedly highlighted issues of readjustment, including difficulties in reconnecting with local academic cultures and professional expectations (Feng and Feng, 2009; Zweig, Fung, and Han, 2008; Yi, 2011). Zweig (2006), for instance, found that many Chinese returnees struggled to reintegrate into their native literary and scholarly communities after prolonged exposure to Western academic systems.

Gullahorn and Gullahorn (1963) argued that returnees' expectations play a decisive role in shaping their ease of readjustment, noting that difficulties often arise when individuals assume that home environments remain static during their absence. Similarly, Black, Gregersen, and Mendenhall (1992) observed that successful readjustment is more likely when returnees' expectations align with the realities of their post-return contexts. One recurring challenge lies in the tendency to compare life abroad with life at home. Kartoshkina (2015), through a mixed-

methods study of students returning from China, Mexico, Greece, Australia, and Spain, found that returnees frequently described their re-entry as bittersweet. Many expressed happiness at returning home but also a sense of loss over leaving behind friendships, autonomy, and lifestyles that shaped their identity abroad. Participants also reported frustration in communicating their experiences to friends and family, who often struggled to relate to their transformed perspectives.

These findings align with those of Christofi and Thompson (2007), who identified feelings of alienation and longing among returnees unable to fully reconnect with their home environments. Their phenomenological study of returnees from Cyprus, Russia, Germany, and Liberia revealed that many participants viewed their host countries as spaces of personal growth and self-realisation, leading some to consider returning overseas rather than re-establishing themselves at home. This emotional tension emphasises that readjustment is rarely linear or uniform; rather, it is marked by an interplay between nostalgia, belonging, and loss.

Institutional and Professional Reintegration

Re-entry extends beyond the initial phase of adjustment and involves a deeper and more complex process of reintegration. Where readjustment refers primarily to the early stage of outward adaptation, reintegration captures the longer-term social, professional, and psychological processes through which returnees re-establish themselves within their home environments. Reintegration requires not only re-engagement with familiar social and institutional structures but also reconciliation between the returnee's transformed perspectives and the realities of the home environment (Arthur, 2003; Hadis, 2005; Fitzpatrick, 2017). Many individuals find this process particularly challenging, as it entails navigating between continuity and change readjusting externally while negotiating internal transformation.

The literature indicates that reintegration occurs across several levels. At the institutional level, academic returnees must re-establish themselves within their employing universities, adapting to administrative expectations, teaching responsibilities, and research cultures (Jonkers and Tijssen, 2008; Chen and Li, 2019). At a broader professional level, reintegration involves building or renewing scholarly networks, accessing research funding, and contributing to both national and international academic communities. Finally, at the societal level, reintegration entails re-engagement with cultural norms and values, often filtered through the new worldviews developed during time abroad (Cassarino, 2004).

Reintegration is, therefore, a multi-layered process that may unfold in diverse ways. Some returnees remain physically rooted in their home environment while maintaining professional and emotional connections with their former host country; others detach completely or cultivate dual

belonging, engaging across both contexts simultaneously (Levitt and Glick Schiller, 2004; Engbersen and Snel, 2021). Conversely, some may feel alienated or professionally constrained, leading them to withdraw or even leave their positions if the home context fails to accommodate their transformed identities (Lazarova and Caligiuri, 2001; Chen and Du, 2023). These varied outcomes highlight that reintegration is not a singular event, but a continuing negotiation shaped by institutional, cultural, and individual factors.

Understanding reintegration as a multifaceted process provides a foundation for exploring the broader dynamics of re-entry. While reintegration emphasises the processes through which returnees re-establish roles and positions within institutional, professional, and social domains, the broader concept of re-entry encompasses the overarching psychological and cultural transition associated with moving from one sociocultural environment back to another. Examining reintegration within this wider re-entry framework therefore offers deeper insight into how returning scholars navigate change, confront constraints, and reconstruct a sense of belonging in their home context.

Models of Re-entry Adjustment

To understand the re-entry process, which is frequently discussed in the literature in relation to reverse culture shock, it is useful to begin with its key conceptual foundations. Westwood, Lawrence, and Paul (1986) describe re-entry as a continuum of experiences and behaviours encountered when an individual returns to their place of origin after spending a significant period in another cultural context. Time spent away is often sufficient to require emotional and psychological adjustment before the returnee can function optimally in a familiar yet altered environment. Despite its importance, re-entry preparation has received far less attention within international education than pre-departure orientation (Pierce, 2017).

Martin's (1984) seminal conceptualisation framed re-entry as a process of cultural adjustment filled with unexpected challenges, often rooted in the mistaken assumption that home will remain stable and unproblematic. Early work in anthropology, psychology, and international education (Adler, 1981; Sussman, 1986; Young, 2014) identified re-entry as potentially more difficult than initial cultural adaptation, given the emotional dissonance that can accompany returning to a familiar yet internally transformed setting. Subsequent studies confirmed that re-entry experiences vary widely across individuals, with some facing only mild discomfort and others experiencing prolonged distress or identity confusion (Sussman, 2002; Cox, 2008).

While earlier reviews noted limited theoretical development (e.g., Szkudlarek, 2010), research over the past decade has advanced considerably. Recent work has examined expectation reality

alignment and coping strategies (Presbitero, 2016; Savicki and Price, 2021), as well as the links between re-entry and knowledge transfer, identity reconstruction, and professional reintegration among academic returnees (Pikos-Sallie, 2018; Chen and Li, 2019; Pham and Saito, 2020). Other studies have explored re-entry under new global conditions, including disrupted mobility and health crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, which have reshaped mobility experiences and highlighted the importance of institutional and emotional support (Winkel, Strachan, and Aamir, 2021). Collectively, these contributions demonstrate that re-entry is best understood as a multidimensional process shaped by psychological, cultural, and institutional factors rather than a single stage of adjustment.

A range of theoretical frameworks have been employed to explain these experiences, including stage theories (Adler, 1975), adjustment curves (Lysgaard, 1955; Gullahorn and Gullahorn, 1963), and coping perspectives (Adler, 1981). Yet, as Kim (2001) observed, cross-cultural adaptation remains a complex process with no single comprehensive theory that captures the diversity of sojourner experiences (Church, 1982; Rohrllich and Martin, 1991). Within this evolving body of research, re-entry is increasingly conceptualised as a multidimensional process that integrates psychological adjustment, identity negotiation, and professional reintegration across time. Earlier sections have explored specific experiential dimensions of these processes; here, re-entry is framed more broadly as a theoretical lens that connects these elements within a continuous transition. Within this broader conceptualisation, reverse culture shock emerges as one of the key analytical lenses through which the emotional and psychological dimensions of re-entry have been examined. The following section therefore explores reverse culture shock in greater theoretical depth.

Culture Shock and Reverse Culture Shock

Building on the discussion of the re-entry process, the concepts of culture shock and reverse culture shock provide essential frameworks for understanding the psychological and emotional dimensions of returning home after an extended period abroad. These phenomena capture the disorientation that occurs when individuals move between cultural contexts and then re-encounter their own, highlighting that re-entry is not merely a physical return but a profound psychological transition (Szkudlarek, 2010; Van Gorp *et al.*, 2017). While culture shock typically refers to the difficulties experienced upon entering a new culture, reverse culture shock concerns the unexpected challenges of readjusting to one's home environment after prolonged exposure to a foreign setting (Gullahorn and Gullahorn, 1963; Uehara, 1986; Gaw, 2000). Presbitero (2016)

similarly defines reverse culture shock as a phenomenon closely related to culture shock but centred on the difficulties of re-adjusting to one's home culture following immersion abroad.

Early research by Lysgaard (1955) introduced the U-curve model, illustrating how sojourners' adjustment follows a trajectory of initial enthusiasm, crisis, and eventual recovery. Later, Gullahorn and Gullahorn (1963) extended this to the W-curve model, demonstrating that similar patterns occur during re-entry except that the distress of returning home is often more intense because it is unanticipated. In this view, reverse culture shock reflects the loss of familiar cues, social symbols, and roles that once shaped an individual's sense of belonging (Rohrlich and Martin, 1991). The emotional and cognitive reactions to these changes often manifest as confusion, frustration, and feelings of alienation, as returnees realise that both they and their home environment have transformed (Adler, 1981; Gaw, 2000).

Wilson (1988) conceptualised the re-entry process as a cycle of personal growth and development, characterised by reflection, re-evaluation, and integration. In this cyclical model, sojourners critically reassess their beliefs, values, and identities shaped abroad and then merge these perspectives with pre-existing cultural frameworks upon return. Within the context of reverse culture shock, this cyclical understanding highlights how emotional disorientation may coexist with developmental transformation, as individuals attempt to reconcile newly acquired perspectives with previously familiar cultural frameworks. This reflective integration process fosters deeper self-awareness and intercultural maturity (Taylor, 2017). As a result, re-entry can serve as a powerful period of transformation, yet also one marked by tension and uncertainty as individuals negotiate between their evolved identities and unchanged social expectations at home.

Empirical research consistently shows that returning home can be more difficult than adjusting to life abroad (Adler, 1981; Sussman, 1986). Returnees often report feelings of estrangement, loss, and disconnection from their surroundings, which are compounded by the limited understanding of friends and family who remained behind (Butcher, 2002; Allison *et al.*, 2011). Butcher (2002) likened this process to grieving, noting that returnees mourn not only the people and places they left behind but also the versions of themselves that existed in those contexts. Such findings emphasise that reverse culture shock is not simply a temporary phase but a critical stage of identity negotiation and emotional realignment.

Studies have further revealed that reverse culture shock is shaped by multiple contextual and relational factors. Thompson and Christofi's (2006) phenomenological research on Cypriot students who studied abroad for several years showed that re-entry distress was often triggered by internal change altered perspectives, habits, and self-perceptions as well as by shifts in the

external environment. Similarly, Jung, Lee, and Moral (2013) in a phenomenological study of Korean counselling professionals who returned to South Korea after obtaining their doctoral degrees in the United States, found that re-entry experiences were deeply shaped by institutional and cultural contexts. Their findings demonstrate that adjustment extends beyond individual psychological processes to include the social, professional, and organisational systems into which returnees reintegrate.

Recent studies in Asian contexts highlight how reintegration is mediated by structural and institutional factors. Chen and Li (2019), for instance, investigated Chinese academics returning to research institutions in China and found that reintegration was contingent upon organisational support and access to research networks. Likewise, Liu (2021) revealed that Chinese art educators returning from the United States faced administrative and interpersonal challenges that required reshaping their professional identities and pedagogical practices. Extending this discussion beyond Asian contexts, Kuzhabekova (2025) highlights how doctoral graduates trained in Global North institutions frequently encounter structural and cultural tensions when transitioning into domestic academic systems in the Global South, requiring ongoing negotiation between internationally acquired academic identities and locally embedded institutional expectations. Collectively, these studies reinforce that reverse culture shock should be understood not only as an individual psychological response but as a phenomenon shaped by broader institutional and socio-cultural dynamics.

Critical Perspectives on Stage Models of Re-entry

Among the earliest attempts to theorise the emotional trajectory of re-entry is the W-Curve Model developed by Gullahorn and Gullahorn (1963), which conceptualises return as a distinct and often destabilising phase of cross-cultural transition. As discussed earlier in relation to reverse culture shock, the W-curve proposes that adjustment follows a cyclical pattern involving initial excitement, subsequent disorientation, and gradual adaptation. Central to this framework is the idea that returnees' expectations shape their readjustment experiences, particularly when they discover that both they and their home environments have changed during their absence (Martin, 1984).

The W-Curve represents one of the earliest attempts to conceptualise the social and psychological processes associated with re-entry. However, rather than treating it as a definitive explanatory model, contemporary scholarship increasingly positions it as a historical starting point that opened scholarly debate about re-entry as a distinct phenomenon. Despite its historical influence, empirical research has offered limited support for the W-Curve hypothesis (Sussman, 2001; Cox,

2008). Subsequent critiques have emphasised that adjustment does not always follow a predictable or curvilinear trajectory. Adler (1981) proposed a flattened U-curve model, while Ward and Kennedy (2010) found that satisfaction levels fluctuate non-linearly across sojourns. Onwumechili *et al.* (2003) further challenged the assumption that cultural adjustment and readjustment are analogous processes, suggesting that the W-Curve lacks flexibility to account for diverse and context-dependent experiences. Moreover, the model overlooks how identity evolution and intercultural growth can lead to positive transformation rather than distress alone (Kim, 2001).

Recent scholarship has highlighted the need to consider how intersectional factors such as gender, culture, and institutional contexts shape re-entry. For example, Alandejani (2013), Alfurayh and Burns (2019) Almuarik (2020), and Alkhalaf, Al-Krenawi, and Elbedour (2024) found that Saudi Arabian women returning after doctoral studies abroad faced heightened challenges due to restrictive gender norms. Similarly, Butcher (2002) and Gaw (2000) identified themes of disenfranchised grief, social alienation, and identity conflict among returnees. These findings suggest that while the W-Curve provides an early conceptual framework for understanding re-entry, it must be reinterpreted through more nuanced, context-sensitive, and culturally grounded approaches.

However, the U-Curve model and its later adaptations have significantly influenced understandings of cross-cultural adjustment and re-entry. Research indicates that the adjustment process is shaped by a complex interaction of macro- and micro-level factors rather than following a uniform pattern (Ward *et al.*, 2001). Macro-level influences include societal structures, economic conditions, and national attitudes toward returnees (Schartner, 2013), whereas micro-level influences involve individual characteristics such as gender, personality, intercultural exposure, and length of stay abroad (Szkudlarek, 2010).

As demonstrated in this body of literature, both contextual and individual factors critically shape how returnees experience transition. From my engagement with these works, it becomes evident that re-entry cannot be understood in isolation from the broader cultural and institutional settings in which it unfolds. For instance, societies with limited interest to globally educated returnees or minimal institutional support often exacerbate re-entry stress (Alandejani, 2013).

Within this research, the aim is to offer a more in-depth and nuanced understanding of re-entry challenges and opportunities, grounded in participants' lived experiences rather than prescriptive stage models. This approach recognises that while traditional frameworks such as the U- and W-

Curves provide valuable conceptual foundations, the reality of re-entry is far more dynamic, contextually mediated, and personally experienced.

Experiencing Re-entry: Emotional and Social Challenges

While the theoretical models discussed above, such as the U- and W-Curves, offer important conceptual starting points, they tend to portray re-entry as structured and predictable. Such representations risk overlooking the emotional turbulence and nuanced psychological responses that characterise the lived experience of return. Moving beyond these generalised models, this section foregrounds the emotional and relational dimensions of re-entry, examining how returnees interpret and negotiate the process as ongoing, dynamic, and deeply personal rather than as a linear stage of readjustment.

Research consistently demonstrates that re-entry is accompanied by a complex mix of emotional responses, reflecting both the gains associated with international experience and the losses incurred through return (Szkudlarek, 2010). Kartoshkina's (2015) study of U.S. students returning from diverse international contexts illustrates this emotional uncertainty: while some participants reported comfort and fulfilment upon reuniting with family, others experienced grief, frustration, and a profound sense of loss for the independence, autonomy, and cultural engagement they had developed abroad.

Emotional Disruption and Sense of Loss

The emotional impact of re-entry is frequently described in terms of loss and mourning. Butcher (2002), in her study of East Asian students returning from New Zealand, conceptualised re-acculturation as a form of grieving, in which returnees must relinquish meaningful aspects of their lives abroad. This loss often extends beyond place to encompass personal growth, freedom, and transformed ways of being. Importantly, such grief is frequently alienated, as it is rarely recognised or legitimised by family members or wider social networks who expect return to be accompanied by satisfaction and success (Butcher, 2002). As a result, returnees may experience their emotional struggles in isolation, compounding the difficulty of adjustment.

This sense of emotional disruption is often intensified by a mismatch between expectations and reality. Returning home is commonly anticipated as a moment of familiarity and comfort; however, many returnees encounter environments that feel unexpectedly unfamiliar, generating confusion, disappointment, and emotional stress (Storti, 2001; Gaw, 2000). These emotional responses underline that re-entry involves not simply resettlement, but a reorientation of self in relation to a changed internal landscape.

Relational Tensions and Identity Repositioning

Beyond internal emotional responses, re-entry also unfolds through interpersonal and institutional relationships. Returnees frequently report feelings of alienation and uncertainty as they attempt to reconnect with family, friends, and colleagues whose expectations remain anchored in pre-departure identities. Exposure to new cultural, academic, and social contexts often reshapes values and perspectives, leading returnees to perceive familiar environments through a more critical lens (Wielkiewicz and Turkowski, 2010). This can produce a tension between attachment to home and frustration with its perceived limitations.

Empirical research highlights the relational consequences of these identity shifts. Fanari, Wright, Foerster (2021), in a longitudinal study of U.S. returnees, found that difficulties in communicating transformed perspectives frequently contributed to loneliness, emotional withdrawal, and prolonged psychological vulnerability. When returnees feel unable to articulate who they have become or encounter a lack of recognition from others, emotional distance and misunderstanding may emerge.

These challenges are particularly salient for doctoral and academic returnees, for whom re-entry also involves professional relationships. Pham and Saito (2020) show that Vietnamese academics returning from overseas study often experienced professional alienation when attempting to introduce pedagogical or research practices acquired abroad. Similarly, Pikos-Sallie (2018) identified reverse culture shock, institutional rigidity, and difficulties gaining professional legitimacy as significant sources of emotional and professional stress among Saudi academic returnees. In such contexts, alienation operates not only at the interpersonal level but also within institutional hierarchies that shape recognition, authority, and belonging.

A further dimension of this relational stress involves the presentation of the self. Christofi and Thompson (2007) describe how returnees are required to continually explain and justify their transformed identities, a process that can be emotionally exhausting when met with indifference or resistance. As Gu and Schweisfurth (2015) and Karakaş (2020) observe, the absence of social or institutional recognition can intensify feelings of frustration, isolation, and disconnection. At the same time, returnees may be expected to resume familiar social and familial roles, despite having developed greater independence and autonomy abroad. As Szkudlarek (2010) and Kartoshkina (2015) note, this tension often generates stress within family dynamics, reinforcing the “bittersweet” nature of return.

Collectively, these emotional and relational challenges illustrate that re-entry is not a simple return to normality but a deeply affective and socially embedded process of renegotiation.

Returnees must navigate loss, uncertainty, and shifting relationships while repositioning themselves within familiar yet altered social and professional environments. These challenges do not unfold in isolation; rather, they are shaped by broader structural conditions that may intensify or mediate re-entry experiences. The COVID-19 pandemic represents one such context, having reshaped re-entry trajectories and amplified experiences of uncertainty, isolation, and psychological vulnerability.

Global Disruptions and the COVID-19 Pandemic: Implications for Returnees

Building on the emotional and relational challenges of re-entry discussed in the previous section, the COVID-19 pandemic represents a critical contextual disruption that further reshaped and intensified return experiences for internationally educated graduates. While re-entry is typically associated with emotional, social, and professional adjustments, returning during a period of global crisis introduced additional layers of uncertainty and structural constraint (De Wit and Altbach, 2021; Haque and Rahaman, 2021; Zhang *et al.*, 2022).

The pandemic significantly altered the experience of international education itself. Higher education institutions worldwide shifted abruptly from in-person to remote learning, transforming the pedagogical, social, and intercultural dimensions traditionally associated with studying abroad. Research widely documents that the move to online teaching weakened experiential learning, disrupted on-campus engagement, and limited opportunities for intercultural interaction (Jensen and Marinoni, 2020; Liu and Shirley, 2021). For many students, this shift diminished the immersive aspects of international education that typically contribute to personal growth, identity negotiation, and the development of global perspectives.

Re-entry during the pandemic presented additional complexities. Many graduates returned amid prolonged lockdowns, mobility restrictions, and social distancing measures, all of which intensified feelings of uncertainty, emotional dislocation, and social detachment. These constraints hindered opportunities to rebuild relationships with family, friends, and academic networks, thereby extending the emotional distance between their host and home experiences. Studies report that returnees often described their home environments as both familiar and foreign an uncertainty heightened by the broader social and economic instability of the pandemic (Jin *et al.*, 2024; Zhang *et al.*, 2022).

Professional reintegration was similarly affected. The global economic downturn led to hiring freezes, reduced academic funding, and fewer research opportunities, creating additional barriers for internationally trained graduates seeking to apply their skills at home (Haque and Rahaman, 2021). Many returnees faced underemployment or temporary roles below their qualifications,

generating frustration and anxiety about future career pathways. He and Zhang (2023) further note that, during the crisis, internationally acquired skills were not always immediately valued, as institutions prioritised short-term stability over innovation.

The psychological toll of returning during such a period of global uncertainty was substantial. Jin *et al.*, (2024) document heightened levels of stress, anxiety, and depressive symptoms among returnees facing isolation, disrupted life plans, and reduced institutional support. The pandemic removed many of the emotional, social, and structural mechanisms such as peer networks, mentoring, and community activities that typically help returnees manage the complexities of re-entry.

The COVID-19 crisis therefore illuminated the vulnerabilities embedded within international mobility systems and emphasised the need for more resilient and equitable re-entry support structures. Mehreen *et al.* (2025) argue that the pandemic highlighted the importance of long-term institutional strategies that can sustain reintegration, enhance well-being, and harness the potential of internationally educated professionals during times of instability. This period also highlighted that re-entry experiences must be understood within broader social, cultural, and geopolitical contexts, rather than solely as individual adjustment processes.

Taken together, these pandemic-related disruptions reveal how re-entry challenges were not only intensified but also reconfigured under conditions of global crisis. Understanding these compounded pressures highlights the importance of examining how returnees actively adapted and developed coping strategies to manage uncertainty, emotional strain, and disrupted trajectories. The following section therefore turns to the ways in which returnees navigated re-entry through processes of adaptation and coping.

Adaptation and Coping Strategies

Having outlined the emotional, relational, and contextual challenges associated with re-entry including those intensified by the Covid-19 pandemic it is equally important to consider how returnees navigate and manage these experiences. Coping strategies play a central role in facilitating emotional stability and psychological adaptation during this transition (Sussman, 2001). Effective coping mechanisms not only ease immediate distress but also help individuals reinterpret their experiences and rebuild coherence between their transformed identities and the realities of home.

Personal qualities developed during international mobility, such as open-mindedness, resilience, and flexibility, cultivated in foreign cultural contexts, often become critical resources upon return

(Szkudlarek, 2010). Returnees who consciously employ these skills are typically better equipped to handle the emotional fluctuations and situational ambiguities that characterise re-entry.

Beyond individual resources, social support emerges as a key coping mechanism. Butcher (2002) emphasises the importance of connecting with others who share similar experiences, whether through alumni networks, re-entry workshops, or online communities. Such interactions foster empathy and validation, helping returnees feel understood and less isolated. Peer-based spaces allow returnees to exchange practical strategies for managing cultural dissonance, bridging the gap between their internal transformations and their external environments.

Reflective practices also serve as powerful tools for emotional adjustment. Activities such as journaling, writing personal narratives, or engaging in dialogue with mentors enable returnees to process their experiences more deeply. Savicki and Price (2021) found that reflective engagement helps individuals integrate the personal growth gained abroad with the cultural frameworks of their home context, promoting self-awareness and emotional coherence.

Expectation management represents another important dimension of coping. Kartoshkina (2015) and Wielkiewicz and Turkowski (2010) argue that returnees who anticipate potential challenges approach the process with greater resilience. By recognising that re-entry involves ongoing negotiation rather than simple resettlement, individuals can mitigate disappointment and reduce the psychological impact of unmet expectations.

In addition to individual and interpersonal strategies, institutional support plays a significant role in shaping coping outcomes. Universities and study-abroad programmes play a critical role by providing pre-departure orientations and post-return debriefings, and reintegration support services (Chen and Li, 2019). However, existing literature indicates that such support remains unevenly implemented, leaving many returnees to rely primarily on personal coping strategies (Szkudlarek, 2010; Pierce, 2017).

Ultimately, coping with re-entry is neither a linear nor uniform process. It reflects an ongoing negotiation between individual agency and structural conditions, shaped by emotional resilience, social context, and institutional responsiveness (Presbitero, 2016). Examining these strategies provides important insight into how returnees actively reconstruct belonging, continuity, and meaning following transformative international experiences.

Conclusion

In this chapter, I have critically reviewed literature relevant to international doctoral mobility, return migration, and re-entry, with particular attention to identity, culture, acculturation, and the

emotional and professional dimensions of reintegration. While existing research highlights the benefits of international education and knowledge circulation, it also reveals persistent gaps in understanding how returning doctoral graduates experience re-entry as a lived and negotiated process, particularly within under-researched contexts such as Algeria.

Drawing together theorisation of identity as dynamic and relational, alongside acculturation and transition perspectives, this review has established a conceptual foundation for examining re-entry as non-linear and contextually mediated. In addition, Transformative Learning theory has been used to illuminate how international study can reshape assumptions, values, and self-understanding, helping to explain why return may involve tension between an altered sense of self and unchanged social or institutional expectations at home. Considered together, these perspectives support an interpretive focus on meaning-making, identity negotiation, and the institutional conditions that shape returnees' reintegration.

The review further demonstrates that much scholarship remains concentrated on the period of study abroad, with comparatively limited attention to doctoral returnees' post-return realities, including reverse culture shock, belonging, identity disruption, and professional identity tensions within home institutions. Addressing this gap, the present study explores how UK-trained Algerian doctoral graduates interpret and navigate their re-entry experiences. The next chapter therefore outlines the methodological approach underpinning this study, explaining how IPA enables an in-depth examination of participants' sense-making in relation to identity, culture, and reintegration.

Chapter Four

Research Methodology

Introduction

In this chapter, I outline the research design, methodology, and data collection methods used to address the study's aims. It also explains the process of data analysis and the principles followed to ensure validity, rigour, and ethical integrity.

Once again, the study set out to explore the experiences of Algerian doctoral graduates returning home after studying in the UK. Given the exploratory nature of the study, IPA was adopted as the methodological approach. This is because it allows for a rich and detailed exploration of complex, under-researched phenomena by attending closely to participants' subjective experiences and the meanings they ascribe to them (Reid, Flowers, and Larkin, 2005). This study is situated within an interpretivist paradigm, privileging the voices of Algerian doctoral graduates to generate insights into how they made sense of their return and how this shaped their personal, academic, and professional trajectories.

As mentioned in Chapter One, the study was guided by the following research questions:

1. How do UK-based Algerian doctoral graduates experience their transition to Algeria, and what are the personal and professional implications of their return?
2. How do these graduates navigate the professional landscape in Algeria upon their return?
3. In what ways do their international academic experiences shape their contributions to academia, research, and professional practice in Algeria?

By addressing these questions, the study aims to deepen understanding of the re-entry phase and its implications for both individuals and the wider academic and professional landscape in Algeria.

Theoretical assumptions underpinning the study

In order to ensure coherence between philosophical positioning and methodological choice, this section outlines the ontological, epistemological, and axiological assumptions informing the study. The ontological and epistemological foundations of this study shaped its research design and guided the exploration of participants lived experiences. Ontologically, the study is based

on the belief that multiple realities exist, and that these realities are subjective and context-dependent (Creswell, 2013). Epistemologically, knowledge is understood as being co-constructed between the researcher and participants, with meaning emerging through dialogue and interpretation (Creswell, 2014), and this is my position in my study.

This position aligns with an interpretivist paradigm, which views reality as socially constructed and best understood by engaging closely with participants' perspectives in their own contexts (Holstein *et al.*, 2013; Merriam and Tisdell, 2015). Rather than seeking generalisable truths, interpretivism aims to uncover how people make sense of their worlds (Bryman, 2001). This orientation was crucial for my study, as it allowed me to investigate how Algerian doctoral graduates navigated their return home after studying in the UK. My interest was not in measurement or prediction, but in meaning-making; an emphasis that also underpins IPA. (see p.72)

Building on this interpretivist position, social constructivism further informed my approach, recognising that participants' experiences were shaped by cultural and institutional contexts, and that my interpretations were inevitably influenced by our shared background. Like my participants, I am Algerian, with Arabic as my mother tongue, and we share cultural and religious frames of reference as well as the common experience of pursuing doctoral study in the UK on a government scholarship. While this insider position facilitated rapport and cultural sensitivity, I remained aware that each participant's reality was unique and should not be assumed to mirror my own. Reflexivity was therefore central to the research process, ensuring that interpretations remained transparent, balanced, and respectful of participants' individuality, and this will be discussed further in the reflexivity section. (see p.76).

Axiology

In addition to ontological and epistemological assumptions, the study is also grounded in axiological considerations. Axiology acknowledges the role of values in qualitative research (Creswell and Poth, 2017). My values influenced how I engaged with participants and interpreted their accounts. I maintained ethical sensitivity by respecting each participant's unique narrative, avoiding judgmental language, and remaining alert to how my own assumptions shaped the interpretative process. By recognising the role of values and reflexivity, I aimed to ensure that participants' voices were represented authentically and with integrity.

Figure 1: Overview of the interrelationship Between the Building Blocks of Research (Grix, 2004, p.68).

Figure 1 illustrates the interrelationship between the key components of the research process and demonstrates how philosophical positioning informs methodological decision-making (Grix, 2004). I established a clear link between what I believed could be researched (ontological perspective), what could be known about it (epistemological position), and how it could be acquired (methodological approach). In this regard, my methodological approach, supported by specific ontological and epistemological assumptions, reflected my choice of strategy and the research methods I used in this study.

Research Design and Rationale

Having established the philosophical foundations of the study, this section now turns to the research design and the rationale underpinning methodological choices. Qualitative research design provided the overarching foundation for this study, ensuring coherence between the research aims, questions, and methodological decisions. As the primary researcher responsible of

data collection and analysis, I recognised the importance of selecting a design that would allow me to capture the depth and complexity of Algerian doctoral returnees' experiences. Drawing from scholars such as Yin (2009) and Schwartz-Shea and Yanow (2013), I understood research design as a logical and coherent process that connects empirical findings to the initial research questions.

In light of the study's focus on lived experience and meaning-making, a qualitative research design was adopted. This design was considered most appropriate for exploring how participants interpreted and navigated their return home, rather than for measuring outcomes or producing generalisable findings.

Qualitative Research Design

Within this overarching framework, qualitative research was positioned as the most suitable approach for investigating subjective experience. Qualitative research requires a clear position within a coherent methodological framework (Liamputtong, 2020).

Denzin and Lincoln (2003) conceptualise qualitative research as a situated activity that positions the researcher within the world and involves interpretive practices aimed at making sense of social reality. This perspective aligns with the present study, which acknowledges the subjective and contextual nature of participants' experiences.

Consistent with Merriam and Tisdell (2015), qualitative research was understood as an approach concerned with how individuals interpret their experiences, construct meaning, and make sense of their social worlds. Accordingly, in this study, I sought to understand how Algerian doctoral returnees interpreted their personal and professional transitions following their return to Algeria, rather than to measure outcomes or generate generalisable claims.

I embraced the flexibility and dynamism that characterise qualitative research, which enabled me to respond to issues introduced by participants during the semi-structured interviews. This method provided a structured yet adaptable design, allowing me to gather secure and meaningful data while remaining open to key ideas that evolved throughout the research process. Recognising that the intention of qualitative research is not to generalise findings but to explore phenomena in depth (Creswell, 2007), I designed my study to capture participants' lived experiences through semi-structured interviews.

As conducting my study, I was conscious and mindful of my role as a qualitative researcher, I was also an instrument of data collection. In relation to the implications of my role, as noted by Denzin and Lincoln (2003) and Merriam and Tisdell (2015) qualitative researchers play an active

role in knowledge construction, with interpretation shaped by reflexive engagement and sustained immersion in the data. By foregrounding the perspectives of Algerian returning graduates, I sought to provide a detailed account of their journeys, acknowledging that qualitative research values depth over breadth.

In line with Creswell's (2007) rationale for adopting qualitative methodologies, my choice was guided by the need to investigate a specific issue, engage with a particular population, and develop a deeper comprehension of the complexity of their experiences. I aimed to amplify voices that had not been extensively documented, thereby offering participants the opportunity to share their narratives while also addressing the inherent power imbalance between researcher and participant. Overall, qualitative research design provided an appropriate and coherent framework for addressing the study's aims and research questions. Within this qualitative research design, a specific interpretative methodological approach was adopted to support an in-depth exploration of participants lived experiences.

Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)

Having established the qualitative and interpretivist foundations of the study, this section introduces IPA as the methodological approach adopted and explains its philosophical foundations, strengths, and limitations. IPA was developed in the 1990s within health psychology (Smith, 1996) but has since been widely applied in fields such as counselling, education, and sociology (Noon, 2018; Rana and Smith, 2020). Its core purpose is to explore how people make sense of major life experiences, positioning participants as active sense-makers of their own worlds (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022). This approach is particularly suited to my study, which sought to understand how Algerian doctoral graduates interpreted and navigated their return home after studying in the UK. At the core of IPA lies a phenomenological concern with lived experience, making phenomenology the first conceptual foundation through which participants' accounts are approached and understood in this study

Phenomenology

IPA is grounded in three interrelated philosophical traditions phenomenology, hermeneutics, and idiography which together shape its analytic orientation. Phenomenology emphasises the study of lived experience and the meanings individuals attribute to events in their lives (Moustakas, 1994; Creswell and Poth, 2018). For this study, a phenomenological lens allowed me to focus on the emotions, reflections, and personal transitions of Algerian PhD returnees, representing their accounts as authentically as possible. Rather than seeking to generalise, my aim was to capture the richness of individual experiences and to present them in the participants' own terms.

Hermeneutics

It highlights the interpretive nature of understanding, and IPA explicitly involves a “double hermeneutic” where the researcher interprets how participants make sense of their experiences (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). This was especially relevant in my study, as my shared identity as an Algerian doctoral graduate created both insight and the need for reflexivity. I engaged iteratively with participants’ accounts, moving between parts and wholes (the hermeneutic circle) to reveal deeper meanings embedded in their narratives. While bracketing my assumptions entirely was not possible, I sought to manage them through critical self-awareness and open, non-directive interviewing.

Idiography

As a core of principles of IPA, idiography refers to the detailed examination of individual cases before moving to broader themes (Smith, 2004). This idiographic commitment shaped my decision to work with a small, homogeneous but diverse sample of Algerian PhD returnees. Each case was analysed on its own terms before identifying convergences and divergences across participants. This approach allowed me to highlight the uniqueness of each participant’s experience while situating these within broader shared contexts of reintegration.

In sum, IPA provided a coherent and flexible methodological framework for this study. Through phenomenology, I prioritised participants’ lived experiences; through hermeneutics, I engaged reflexively in interpreting their meaning-making; and through idiography, I balanced attention to individual voices with the identification of collective patterns. This integration enabled a holistic exploration of a complex and under-researched phenomenon: the re-entry of Algerian doctoral graduates into their home academic and social environments. The following section considers the methodological strengths of IPA and explains how these supported the aims of the present study.

Strengths of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis

IPA offers particular strengths for research focused on personal meaning-making. It is a participant-oriented approach that values subjective accounts and prioritises the exploration of lived experiences (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022). Rather than treating experiences as objective facts, IPA recognises them as shaped by individuals’ beliefs, histories, and social contexts (Willig, 2008). This orientation is crucial for the present study, which sought to understand how Algerian doctoral returnees made sense of their re-entry experiences across social and professional domains.

The strength of IPA lies in its integration of phenomenology, hermeneutics, and idiography. Together, these principles provided the conceptual tools needed to explore participants’ lived

experiences in depth while acknowledging both shared experiential patterns and individual distinctiveness. Phenomenologically, IPA attends closely to how experiences are lived and felt; hermeneutically, it recognises interpretation as central to understanding; and idiographically, it commits to detailed engagement with individual cases before considering points of convergence across participants (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022). This combination is particularly well suited to capturing the complexity of doctoral return, where experiences are both deeply personal and shaped by shared structural and cultural conditions.

Another key strength of IPA is its commitment to depth over breadth. Working with small, purposively selected samples allows for detailed exploration of participants' meaning-making processes (Smith and Osborn, 2008). For this study, the aim is not generalisation but to generate rich, in-depth insights that could illuminate the broader phenomenon of doctoral return. The flexibility of IPA further enabled responsiveness to participants' narratives while maintaining a systematic and transparent analytic process. While IPA offers significant methodological advantages, it is also important to critically acknowledge its limitations and ongoing debates within qualitative research.

Limitations and Critical Considerations of IPA

Despite its strengths, IPA is demanding and not without critique. The process of detailed, case-by-case analysis can be time-consuming and requires sustained analytic commitment from the researcher (Clarke, 2009). Some scholars have also questioned IPA's methodological rigour, suggesting that its interpretative flexibility may render it less systematic than other qualitative approaches (Sousa, 2008; Giorgi, 2011). Others note that while IPA generates rich interpretative accounts, it does not aim to identify causal explanations for experiences (Willig, 2013).

These critiques are acknowledged and understood as inherent to the interpretative nature of IPA rather than as methodological shortcomings. In this study, rigour was addressed through transparency at each stage of the research process, including detailed documentation of participant selection, interview design, data collection, and analytic procedures. Tables outlining participant characteristics and analytic steps further enhanced clarity and auditability.

Reflexivity also played a central role in addressing potential limitations. I explicitly acknowledged my positionality and dual role as both insider and outsider, critically reflecting on how my background and assumptions may have shaped interpretation (Goldspink and Engward, 2019; Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022). In addition, findings were grounded firmly in participants' voices through the use of verbatim extracts, enabling readers to trace the interpretative process and engage with the hermeneutic circle. This transparency invites readers

to evaluate the credibility of the analysis and to appreciate both participants' and researcher's sense-making.

Although IPA does not follow a rigid or fixed procedural framework, its interpretative and phenomenological orientation makes it particularly appropriate for the present study. It enabled a nuanced and contextually embedded exploration of return experiences and illuminated how Algerian doctoral returnees constructed, negotiated, and reflected upon the meanings of their transitions. Having critically considered both strengths and limitations, the following section explains the specific rationale for selecting IPA over alternative qualitative methodologies.

The Rationale for Choosing IPA

Within the broader landscape of qualitative methodologies, selecting an approach that aligned closely with the study's philosophical assumptions and research aims was essential. Many qualitative methodologies have been developed to explore individuals' experiences in educational settings, each offering unique perspectives. For my study, the open and explorative nature of IPA aligned closely with my aim to investigate how Algerian doctoral returnees made sense of their transition home. IPA's focus on describing, interpreting, and situating participants' meaning-making processes made it particularly suitable for capturing the personal and professional complexities of re-entry (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022).

The interpretivist assumptions underpinning IPA also matched my ontological and epistemological stance. I was interested not in testing hypotheses or producing generalisable findings, but in engaging with participants' subjective accounts to uncover how they experienced and interpreted their return. By working with a homogeneous but diverse group of Algerian PhD graduates, IPA enabled me to explore both individual distinctiveness and shared patterns across cases.

Before settling on IPA, I considered other qualitative methodologies. Narrative inquiry appealed for its emphasis on storytelling but is primarily concerned with the structure and form of narratives, whereas my focus was on the meanings underlying participants' words. Case study was also unsuitable, as my interest lay in lived experiences across a group rather than portraying each participant as a bounded case. Grounded theory was rejected because it seeks to generate theory, while my aim was not to build new theory but to understand the quality and texture of participants' experiences.

What ultimately drew me to IPA was its recognition of the active role of the researcher. Through the process of double hermeneutics, I interpreted how participants made sense of their lives, while

being reflexively aware of how my own background as a fellow Algerian doctoral student shaped the analysis. IPA's idiographic commitment also allowed me to engage deeply with each account before moving towards thematic synthesis.

While I acknowledge the value of other qualitative methodologies, IPA offered the closest alignment with my research aims. Its commitment to in-depth exploration, its recognition of the researcher's interpretative role, and its ability to illuminate the complexity of lived experience made it the most appropriate methodology for this study.

Reflexivity

Given the interpretative nature of IPA and its emphasis on researcher involvement in meaning-making, reflexivity formed a central component of the methodological process. Reflexivity involves recognising how the researcher's perspectives, assumptions, and positioning shape the research process and its outcomes (Probst and Berenson, 2014). In IPA, reflexivity is integral, as knowledge is produced through a double hermeneutic in which participants seek to make sense of their lived experiences, and the researcher, in turn, interprets those sense-making processes (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022). As such, reflexivity in IPA does not aim to render research objective; rather, it seeks to make the researcher's subjectivities visible and to understand how these may have shaped the collection and interpretation of data (Dean, 2017; Barton, 2020).

This understanding of reflexivity aligns with the view that qualitative analysis is necessarily interpretative and situated. Explicit acknowledgement of the researcher's personal positioning allows readers to appreciate why different researchers, or the same researcher at different moments, might arrive at different yet equally plausible interpretations of the same data (Brown, 2010; Berger, 2015). In this study, reflexivity therefore functioned as a means of enhancing transparency, interpretative awareness, and coherence, rather than as an attempt to eliminate subjectivity (Schwartz-Shea and Yanow, 2013).

From the outset of the study, I engaged reflexively by documenting my expectations, assumptions, and emotional responses in a research journal, and by actively comparing these reflections with participants' narratives during analysis. This ongoing reflexive practice supported awareness of potential bias and enabled me to refine interpretations as themes developed. My positionality was layered: as an Algerian doctoral student, Muslim, Arabic speaker, and scholarship holder, I shared several cultural and social characteristics with participants. These shared experiences facilitated rapport and trust, with participants often feeling that I could understand their experiences without extensive explanation. They also enhanced my

understanding to culturally embedded meanings, such as references to family obligations, religious practices, or scholarship-related pressures.

At the same time, I remained attentive to the potential risks associated with this insider positioning. Familiarity could have led to assumptions, taken-for-granted interpretations, or the overlooking of divergent experiences. To address this, I consciously adopted a questioning stance during interviews, using prompts and follow-up questions to encourage participants to articulate their experiences in their own words rather than relying on assumed shared understanding. This approach ensured that meaning was grounded in participants' accounts rather than my prior knowledge or personal experiences. In this sense, my insider position functioned both as a strength enabling depth and openness and as an analytic challenge requiring careful reflexive management.

Alongside this insider positioning, I also occupied an outsider role, as I had not yet experienced the process of returning to Algeria myself. This dual positioning required a balance between empathic understanding and critical distance (Goldspink and Engward, 2019). Drawing on both emic (insider) and etic (outsider) perspectives allowed for a co-constructive analytic process (Reid, Flowers, and Larkin, 2005), in which cultural nuance could be recognised without over-identification or projection.

To support transparency and analytic rigour, I practised partial bracketing by actively reflecting on and temporarily setting aside immediate preconceptions in order to attend more closely to participants' lived accounts (Larkin and Thompson, 2012; Nizza, Smith, and Kirkham, 2023). Verbatim quotations, detailed analytic notes, and iterative development of experiential themes further ensured that participants' voices remained central, while my interpretative role was made explicit. In addition, as a doctoral researcher, I remained mindful of the need to move beyond descriptive accounts towards deeper levels of interpretation, a challenge noted within IPA methodology (Smith *et al.*, 2009). This was addressed through repeated engagement with the data, reflexive note taking, and sustained alignment with IPA analytic principles throughout the research process.

Ultimately, reflexivity was not a peripheral consideration but a central component of this IPA study. By critically engaging with my dual position as both insider and outsider, I was able to produce an analysis that was empathetic, interpretatively rigorous, and grounded in participants' meaning-making.

Data Collection Methods

The data collection process was carefully structured to ensure depth and reliability in exploring the lived experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees. Following a pilot study to refine the approach, the main phase involved in-depth online interviews designed to capture nuanced insights consistent with the interpretative phenomenological framework. The following sections outline the pilot study and its role in refining the research design, followed by a detailed account of the semi-structured interview approach, the use of online interviewing, the development of interview questions, and the participant recruitment process.

Pilot Study

Before commencing the main interviews, I conducted a pilot study with three participants using Zoom and Microsoft Teams. The purpose was to test the clarity of the questions, the suitability of the recording tools, and the overall feasibility of the research design (Teresi, Stewart, and Hays, 2022). In the context of this study, the pilot also provided an opportunity to reflect on my role as an IPA researcher, particularly in relation to managing assumptions and engaging reflexively with participants' accounts (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022).

The pilot generated several practical and methodological insights. It highlighted potential challenges related to recruitment, allowed me to refine the wording and sequencing of interview questions, and reinforced the importance of setting aside preconceptions in order to engage more openly with participants' meaning making. Testing the interview schedule in advance is widely recognised as a key step in qualitative interviewing, enabling researchers to enhance sensitivity to participants' experiences and improve the quality of the data generated (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2018). The pilot interviews also increased confidence in the use of online platforms, confirming that participants were able to share detailed and reflective narratives in this setting.

Overall, the pilot study was invaluable in strengthening the design and preparing me for the main phase of data collection. By ensuring that the interview questions, recording tools, and analytic stance were fit for purpose, the pilot supported a more rigorous and reflexively informed approach to capturing the lived experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees. The practical insights gained through the pilot phase are discussed in more detail in the following section, which reflects on methodological learning and reflexive considerations emerging from these preliminary interviews.

Reflection on Pilot Interviews

I conducted three pilot interviews recruited through purposive sampling, with access facilitated by gatekeepers via Messenger. This approach enabled the selection of individuals who met the study's inclusion criteria and could provide relevant insight into the phenomenon under investigation, as outlined in the Participants and Recruitment section of the methods chapter.

Prior to the interviews, participants were contacted via email and provided with information about the aims of the research, the interview process, and the anticipated time commitment. Once participants agreed to take part, consent forms and participant information sheets were shared (see Appendix 2). Providing participants with clear information in advance reflects ethical qualitative practice and supports informed and voluntary participation (Orb, Eisenhauer, and Wynaden, 2001). Participants were also offered the option of receiving interview questions beforehand, which all three accepted, a strategy that supported comfort and preparedness in discussing personal experiences.

Conducting the pilot interviews generated important methodological insights. Interview duration varied according to participants' engagement with the questions, highlighting the flexible and participant-led nature of qualitative interviewing. Early analysis of pilot data informed refinements to the interview guide, including the removal of repetitive questions and the addition of a new question prompted by participants' responses. This aligns with Kvale and Brinkmann's (2009) view that pilot interviews are essential for refining interview structure and improving the quality of data generation.

Participants reported finding several questions engaging and were able to relate to them easily, often providing detailed and reflective accounts of their experiences. The pilot interviews also provided an opportunity to develop interviewing skills and identify effective strategies for establishing rapport prior to eliciting more personal narratives. This reflects Roulston and Choi's (2018) discussion of pilot interviews as a space in which researchers develop interactional competence and become more adjusted to how interview dynamics shape the depth and quality of participants' responses.

Rapport-building strategies were consciously employed during the pilot interviews, including beginning conversations with informal social talk and discussing shared contextual experiences. Establishing rapport in this way is recognised as central to qualitative interviewing, particularly when exploring sensitive or personal topics (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006; Mahama and Khalifa, 2017). Shared socio-cultural characteristics between myself and participants, including

gender, religious identity, and academic background, facilitated openness and trust. This insider positioning enabled sensitivity to culturally embedded meanings, while also requiring careful reflexive awareness to avoid assumptions.

At the same time, I remained attentive to the complexities of insider–outsider positioning. While shared experiences supported rapport, participants did not always disclose highly personal information, reinforcing the importance of not assuming familiarity or shared understanding. Adopting a reflexive and questioning stance helped ensure that meaning remained grounded in participants’ own accounts rather than my prior experiences (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022).

All pilot interviews were conducted online, with participants choosing their preferred time and language. English was selected by all participants, reflecting their professional roles as lecturers in English departments, although occasional expressions in Algerian Arabic were used naturally. The online format proved effective in facilitating rich and extended interviews, supporting previous research indicating that online qualitative interviews can enable depth, flexibility, and participant comfort when appropriately managed (Archibald *et al.*, 2019).

Overall, the pilot interviews strengthened both the interview design and my preparedness as a qualitative and IPA researcher. They supported methodological refinement, enhanced reflexive awareness, and increased confidence in facilitating participant-led narratives during the main data collection phase. Building on these insights, the main phase of data collection employed semi-structured interviews, which are discussed in detail below.

Semi-Structured Interviews

In alignment with the interpretative phenomenological framework outlined earlier, semi-structured interviews are qualitative interviews guided by a flexible schedule of open-ended questions, allowing the interviewer to probe, follow up, and adapt sequencing in response to participants’ meaning-making (Brinkmann, 2014). This format allows participants to articulate their experiences in their own words while enabling the researcher to explore issues in depth and attend closely to participants’ sense-making processes.

Semi structured interviews were selected as the primary method of data collection because they aligned closely with the study’s aim of exploring how Algerian doctoral returnees interpreted their transition experiences upon returning home. This method enabled participants to reflect on their experiences within the personal, social, and professional contexts in which they lived and worked, supporting the generation of rich, detailed, and contextually grounded accounts.

Capturing such meanings was central to the study, as the focus was not simply on outcomes of return, but on how participants understood and navigated their transitions.

The one-to-one, semi-structured format was particularly appropriate for this purpose, as it allowed participants to speak openly without the influence of others and to elaborate on aspects of their experiences that they considered significant. This approach is consistent with qualitative research principles, which emphasise depth, flexibility, and participant-led narration (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015). By privileging open-ended questions and follow-up prompts, the interviews facilitated nuanced insight into participants' lived experiences and meaning-making processes.

Other qualitative options were considered but were less suitable for this study. Focus groups are group-based discussions that generate data through interaction between participants; they can be valuable for exploring shared norms and collective meanings. However, they may inhibit disclosure of sensitive experiences and are vulnerable to group dynamics, including dominant voices shaping the discussion and quieter participants contributing less (Sim and Waterfield, 2019). Given the personal and potentially sensitive nature of re-entry experiences, and the study's emphasis on individual sense-making, focus groups were not considered the best fit.

Structured interviews involve a fixed set of questions asked in the same order and wording, producing data that is more standardised and comparable across participants. While useful for consistency, this format limits opportunities to follow participants' meanings as they emerge and can constrain responses within predetermined categories, reducing interpretative depth. This rigidity is not well aligned with IPA, which depends on the exploration of nuance, context, and participant-led elaboration (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009).

Unstructured interviews are highly open conversations with minimal guidance, offering maximum flexibility. However, this openness can result in interviews that are uneven across participants and may generate unfocused data that does not consistently address the research questions. For this study, some structure was necessary to ensure coverage of key areas while still allowing participants to narrate their experiences in their own terms.

On this basis, semi-structured, one-to-one interviews offered the most appropriate approach: they provided sufficient guidance to ensure relevance and coherence, while retaining the flexibility needed to elicit rich, detailed narratives and support in-depth interpretative analysis consistent with IPA (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009; Willig, 2013). Having established the rationale for semi-structured interviewing, the following section explains the practical decision to conduct interviews online and reflects on the methodological implications of this choice.

Online Interviews

All interviews were conducted online via Microsoft Teams and Zoom, as participants were located across different Algerian cities while I was based in Scotland. Online interviewing was also a practical necessity in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic, which normalised the use of digital platforms for qualitative research (Lobe, Morgan, and Hoffman, 2020). This mode of data collection is widely recognised as enabling flexibility and access, particularly when participants are geographically dispersed, while also reducing time and financial costs associated with travel (Archibald *et al.*, 2019). In this study, the online format also allowed participants to take part from familiar and comfortable environments, which can support ease and openness during qualitative interviewing (Archibald *et al.*, 2019).

Most participants agreed to take part in online interviews, as travelling across different Algerian cities would have been both time-consuming and financially challenging. This mode of participation was familiar to many, as several had previously engaged in online interviews during their doctoral studies in the UK. A small number of participants, however, chose to keep their cameras switched off. One participant was unwell, another felt uncomfortable being on camera, and a third was situated in a shared family space where privacy was limited.

While the absence of visual cues restricted access to body language and other non-verbal expressions, I adapted my interviewing approach by paying closer attention to vocal tone, pauses, and hesitations, and by using follow-up questions to support participants' meaning-making. Such adaptations are recommended in online qualitative interviewing to compensate for reduced visual interaction and maintain depth of engagement (Sullivan, 2012; Lo Iacono, Symonds, and Brown, 2016). Existing research supports the view that, when managed reflexively, online interviews conducted without video can still generate rich and meaningful data (Seitz, 2016; Wakelin, McAra-Couper, and Fleming, 2024). Although interpretative limitations were acknowledged, this methodological compromise was considered necessary in order to maintain participant comfort, privacy, and trust, and to uphold the ethical principle of prioritising participants' autonomy and wellbeing. As outlined in the consent process, participants agreed to have their voices digitally recorded and retained full autonomy over whether to use video during the interview.

At the same time, I remained attentive to the ethical and relational challenges associated with online interviewing, particularly the potential difficulty of identifying emotional distress without physical co-presence and access to full non-verbal cues (Deakin and Wakefield, 2014). To address this, participants were reminded that they could pause or stop the interview at any time, and interviews were conducted in a conversational and supportive manner. Such an approach

aligns with guidance within IPA, which emphasises sensitivity, reflexive awareness, and care in engaging with participants' lived experiences, particularly when discussing potentially emotional or personal topics (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022).

Overall, the use of semi-structured online interviews aligned closely with the aims of IPA by enabling a flexible yet focused exploration of participants' lived experiences. The one-to-one online format supported participant-led narratives, respected individual autonomy, and allowed for close engagement with meaning-making processes, ensuring that participants' voices remained central to the research process.

Interview Questions Development

Consistent with IPA's emphasis on participant-led meaning-making, the development of interview questions aimed to encourage reflective and experiential narratives. The interview questions were developed through a combination of methodological considerations, insights from the literature, and piloting. The starting point was the study's overarching aim: to explore the lived experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees, with attention to their social, cultural, and professional reintegration. To ensure that the interviews encouraged rich and detailed accounts, the questions were deliberately framed in an open-ended style, privileging "how" and "why" formulations. In qualitative research, such wording is essential because it avoids leading participants into predefined categories and instead invites them to reflect, elaborate, and construct meaning in their own terms (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022; Lim, 2025). This approach is particularly consistent with Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis, which seeks to facilitate participant-led narratives and in-depth engagement with lived experience (Willig, 2013).

In designing the interview schedule, I drew on examples from published theses, prior qualitative studies, and themes identified in the literature review, adapting and tailoring them to the particular focus of my research. For example, rather than asking participants to confirm whether they had encountered a specific challenge, I used broader formulations such as: "*How would you describe your home transition after your sojourn in the UK?*" Such wording gave participants the freedom to interpret the question according to their own circumstances, thus generating richer insights than would have been possible through closed or confirmatory phrasing.

To explore feasibility, clarity, and flow, three pilot interviews were conducted with participants recruited through purposive sampling, as discussed earlier in the Pilot Study section. Insights gained during these pilot interviews, including participants' ease in responding and the limited need for clarification, indicated that the questions were generally clear, accessible, and aligned with the study's aims. The pilot process also highlighted areas for refinement: one overlapping

question was removed, and additional probes (for example, “*Can you say a bit more about that?*”) were incorporated to encourage elaboration where responses were brief. Such iterative refinement of interview questions is widely recognised as a key function of piloting in qualitative research (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009).

The pilot interviews also supported the development of an effective interviewing strategy. In particular, beginning interviews with informal conversation helped to establish rapport and ease participants into more personal reflection, an approach that is recognised as central to eliciting rich and reflective qualitative data (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006; Roulston and Choi, 2018). This was especially important given my dual positioning as both an insider and outsider to the participants’ experiences. Having established the interview design and questioning approach, the following section outlines the participant recruitment strategy used to identify individuals able to provide rich experiential accounts.

Participants Recruitment

In keeping with the interpretative phenomenological framework underpinning this study, participant recruitment was guided by purposive selection aimed at identifying individuals who shared key experiential characteristics while allowing for meaningful variation across cases. Qualitative research depends on participants who can provide detailed accounts of their lived experiences (Creswell, 2013). In IPA, the aim is to recruit a reasonably homogeneous sample so that both shared and divergent experiences can be explored in depth (Smith and Osborn, 2003; Smith, flowers, and Larkin, 2009). Sample sizes are typically small, as the focus is on detailed, idiographic analysis rather than generalisation (Pietkiewicz and Smith, 2012).

For this study, the sample consisted of 18 Algerian doctoral graduates who had successfully completed their PhDs in the UK, returned to Algeria, and begun teaching in different universities. Recruitment took place through Facebook, Twitter, and email, where I shared a short description of the study. Initial participants then introduced me to colleagues who also met the criteria, making snowball sampling a useful and efficient supplement (Alase, 2017).

Inclusion criteria were based on three main conditions: participants had to be Algerian, hold a UK doctoral degree, and have spent at least two months in Algeria after returning. These criteria ensured that participants could reflect on their reintegration experiences both personally and professionally.

The study’s focus was not on generating generalisable findings but on capturing the complexity of returnees’ lived experiences. A homogeneous but diverse sample in terms of individual

transition journeys allowed for a nuanced exploration of how Algerian PhD graduates made sense of and navigated their return home. Figure 2 provides an illustrative example of the recruitment process, showing a snapshot of participant interaction and initial engagement during recruitment, and serves to contextualise how access to participants was negotiated in practice.

I hope you are doing well Dear
I am a PhD student conducting my research on Algerian sponsoree student returning back home

I am interested in their social and academic experiences

I was wondering if you are one among this sample population

I would be happy if you can take part

In my research 🌸

Sounds so interesting. Thank you so much for reaching out to me. I would be aming this sample soon InshaAllah but not sure when. I am graduating in summer. Not sure if I'll have anything to contribute with this year if you're looking for the experiences you mentioned when i am back home

I would be in this sample*

I am happy to help though

Thank you so much for taking th time to reply.
Belated Congratulations 🌸🌸
Wish you more success.
Please, do you know others or friends that already got back home and strated teaching

That would be helpful

10/02/2023 16:06

Sure. There is [redacted]

[redacted] as well

Yes fortunately I could reach [redacted] just recently sent her a text, but I couldn't reach [redacted]

Oh i see

Figure 2: Screenshot of Participant Interaction

An illustrative example of the recruitment process is shown in Figure 2 above. The interaction began when a potential participant was approached and initially expressed interest in the study. At the time, they had not yet returned to Algeria or begun teaching, making them ineligible to participate at that point. However, they were interviewed later after meeting the study's eligibility criteria. This demonstrates how flexibility and persistence in recruitment were vital for ensuring an appropriate sample.

Additionally, during this interaction, the participant suggested referrals to others who might meet the study criteria, highlighting the role of snowball sampling in reaching a geographically dispersed population. Such referrals proved crucial in overcoming recruitment challenges and broadening the pool of eligible participants.

Participant Profile Overview

Participants name	Gender	Age	Civil status	Period stayed abroad	Return year	Period stayed unemployed	Occupation	Country studied	Teaching period	Interviewed on
Hiba	Female	32	Single	5 years and 5 months	2020	5 months post-return	University English lecturer	UK	2 years and 4 months	02/03/2023
Mohamed	Male	33	Married	5 years	2020	1 year and 8 months post-return	University English lecturer	UK	1 year and a half	16/03/2023
Ghizlene	Female	32	Married	5 years	2020	immediately started her career	University English lecturer	UK	2 years and 7 months	09/02/2023 And 10/02/2023
Manel	Female	31	Single	5 years	2022	immediately started her career	University English lecturer	UK	8 months	18/04/2023
Hanaa	Female	32	Married	4 years	2020	3 months post-return	University English lecturer	UK	2 years and 6 months	10/02/2023
Insaf	Female	32	Married	5 years	2021	10 months post-return	University English lecturer	UK	1 year and a half	02/06/2023
Ahmed	Male	29	Single	4 years	2022	3 months post-return	University English lecturer	UK	3 months	16/02/2023
Akram	Male	32	Married	4 years and a few months	2019	immediately started his career	University English lecturer	UK	3 years and a half	08/05/2023
Autumn	Female	29	Married	4 years and 8 months	2022	9 months post-return	University English lecturer	UK	8 months	14/05/2023
Yasmine	Female	30	Married	4 years	2020	2 years post-return	University English lecturer	UK	7 months	07/05/2023
Amani	Female	30	Married	4 years	2020	1-year post-return	University English lecturer	UK	2 years	17/02/2023

Wahiba	Female	31	Married	5 years	2021	2 weeks post-return	University English lecturer	UK	1 year	17/04/2023
Karim	Male	32	Single	4 years and a half	2020	1-year post-return	University English lecturer	UK	2 years	01/03/2023
Nawel	Female	31	engaged	Four years and 6 months	2022	immediately started her career	University English lecturer	UK	1 year and a half	03/06/2023
Amine	Male	30	Single	Nearly 4 years	2022	5 months post-return	University English lecturer	UK	5 months	07/02/2023
Samar	Female	32	Married	5 years and a half	2021	6 months post-return	University English lecturer	UK	1 year	24/01/2023
Maya	female	31	Single	5 years	2021	5 months post-return	University English lecturer	UK	1 year	01/02/2023
Kenza	female	31	Single	4 years and six months	2021	8 months post-return	University English lecturer	UK	1 year	03/02/2023

Table 2: Participants Profile Table.

Participants Profile Table Explanation

The table provides an overview of the participants in this study, who are all scholarship holders engaged in academic mobility programme as part of an initiative by the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and the British Council. As part of this programme, participants were contractually required to return to Algeria and take up teaching posts in English departments. Further contextual detail regarding the structure of this scholarship scheme, including age criteria and pre-sessional preparation, is discussed in Chapter Two.

Many participants returned during or shortly after the COVID-19 pandemic, which shaped aspects of their reintegration experiences, particularly in relation to administrative processes and credential recognition. This shared structural context provided a coherent experiential backdrop while allowing for meaningful variation across individual transitions. Consistent with the interpretative phenomenological approach, the focus was not on institutional policy itself, but on how participants made sense of their return within these structural conditions.

Facing the Recruitment Challenge: Insights from the Field

The initial recruitment of participants represented one of the most challenging stages of the study. It required identifying and contacting Algerian doctoral graduates who had completed their PhDs in the UK and returned to Algeria, many of whom were balancing university teaching alongside substantial academic and personal commitments. Such recruitment challenges are well documented in qualitative research, particularly when working with professionally engaged and geographically dispersed populations, where access, availability, and responsiveness can be unpredictable (Newington and Metcalfe, 2014).

Recruitment began through informal academic networks. I initially contacted a friend via Facebook who had completed her PhD in the UK and returned to Algeria. Although I did not interview her due to ethical considerations and concerns that prior familiarity might influence the depth or openness of disclosure, she acted as a key informant by facilitating access to other potential participants. Such reliance on gatekeepers and existing networks is a common strategy in qualitative research when studying specialised or hard-to-reach populations (Chamberlain and Hodgetts, 2022). Individuals were then purposefully selected based on the study's inclusion criteria, focusing on government-sponsored Algerian doctoral graduates who had completed their PhDs in the UK and returned to teach in Algerian universities.

In total, more than forty potential participants were contacted directly via Messenger following recommendations from academic contacts. Of these, eighteen met the eligibility criteria and agreed to take part in interviews. Several individuals were excluded because they had not yet completed their doctoral studies or had returned to Algeria but had not started teaching due to ongoing bureaucratic delays. Additionally, three individuals initially agreed to participate but did not attend the scheduled interviews. Non-response and attrition at this stage reflect challenges commonly reported in qualitative recruitment processes and should be understood as part of the practical realities of fieldwork rather than as methodological shortcomings (Phillips, 2014).

Once individuals expressed interest, contact details were exchanged to allow the distribution of participant information sheets and consent forms. Despite careful screening, recruitment remained constrained by factors beyond the researcher's control, including workload pressures, employment delays, and limited availability. These challenges shaped both the final sample size and the pace of data collection but also reinforced the importance of purposive sampling and flexibility when working with information-rich cases in qualitative inquiry (Patton, 2015). With the final sample confirmed and interviews completed, the next stage involved a systematic and idiographically oriented analysis of participants' accounts in line with IPA principles.

Steps for IPA Analysis

The aim of the analysis was to gain an in-depth understanding of participants' lived experiences by engaging closely with their accounts and interpreting the meanings they ascribed to them. Following Smith, Flowers and Larkin's (2022) guidance for novice researchers, I adopted a stepwise approach while remaining reflexively aware that IPA is an iterative and flexible process.

Step 1: Reading and Rereading

The interviews were transcribed via Zoom transcription. I knew that IPA necessitates a 'semantic record of interview: a transcript documenting all uttered words by all participants' (Murray and Wilde, 2020; Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022). I reviewed the transcripts while listening to the audio. Ongoing listening enabled me to better understand each participant's perspective and rectify any technology-related inaccuracies in capturing that experience. While reading and re-reading, I highlighted key phrases and/or statements that immediately stand out as particularly meaningful, emotional, or reflective of the participant's experiences (See Appendix 5). It helped me engage with the data deeply.

Stage 2: Exploratory Noting (EN)

At this stage, I delved deeper into the insights provided, I focused on capturing relevant descriptions and references from their narratives. To manage the substantial volume of transcript data, I organised my notes into a structured table using Microsoft Word, where I began adding exploratory comments in the appropriate sections. As I sought to extract abstract meanings related to their reintegration experiences, some of my notes served as descriptive summaries of the Information, while others involved a more profound analysis, all the while striving to stay true to the participants' realities. This particular process allowed me to immerse myself in their worlds, recognising the complexities of their journeys as they navigated the challenges and opportunities of returning home after studying abroad. Reflecting on this stage, I felt a profound connection to the text, appreciating the rich descriptions of the participants' lives and the unique contexts they encountered upon returning to Algeria. As I engaged with their accounts, I began to notice recurring themes and patterns.

Step 3: Constructing Experiential Statements (ES)

In this phase, I used exploratory statements (ES) to condense the transcript and exploratory notes data. To facilitate my analysis, I added a column to the existing table, aiming to capture the essence of the participants' words at this level (See Appendix 6). There were moments when I found myself leaning towards more descriptive accounts, prompting me to be more mindful of my focus on interpretation. Recognising the importance of my perspective within the

'hermeneutic circle' (Nizza, Smith, and Kirkham, 2023; Vicary and Ferguson, 2024). I acknowledged my role as an interpreter in the process. As I worked on developing the exploratory statements, I frequently revisited the transcripts, stage 2 notes, and emerging statements to ensure that my interpretations were well-supported by the data.

Step 4: Searching for Connections Across Experiential Statements (ES)

In this step, I focused on collecting experiential statements by establishing conceptual connections through listing and mapping. I created a document on my laptop to compile the emerging themes from the interviews, allowing me to view them all easily. Effectively, I needed to search for ways to connect these themes and produce a structure that highlighted the most fascinating and significant aspects of the participants' experiences. To explore these connections, I employed two primary strategies. First, I compiled a chronological list of all the topics and then examined the list to rearrange the themes into clusters of related topics. Some themes acted as magnets, drawing in other associated themes. After typing out the list, I kept it organised within the document, which enabled me to visually examine the relationships between the developed themes on my laptop.

Step 5: Moving to the Next Case

In this phase, I moved on to the next transcript, repeating the procedure with careful attention to detail. It was essential to approach each case on its terms, respecting its unique context and experiences. As I worked on the second transcript, I made a conscious effort to bracket any concepts or insights from the first case to honour the individuality of the new transcript. This approach aligns with the idiographic focus of IPA, allowing for a fresh examination of each participant's experience. I recognised that my prior findings could influence my interpretation, shifting my "fore-structures" in the process. To adhere to the principles of hermeneutics, I needed to remain open to the development of new themes with each subsequent case (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009). By following these procedures diligently, I aimed to ensure that the richness of each participant's narrative could come to the forefront. This iterative process was repeated for every case, allowing me to build a comprehensive understanding of the experiences shared by the Algerian doctoral returnees.

Step 6: Looking for Patterns Across Cases

The primary aim of IPA is to gain insights into the experiences of participants (J. A. Smith, 2015). In this step, I focused on identifying common Personal Experiential Statements (PETs) within their narratives, aligning with this overarching goal. To facilitate this, I consolidated all the topic tables into a single document and carefully reviewed them to explore potential connections

between the PETs. My objective was to establish general patterns that could be applicable across all participants while remaining mindful of both strong and weak connections (See Appendix 7 and 8). The selection of Group Experiential Statements (GETs) was guided by their frequency in the data, the richness of supporting evidence, and their capacity to shed light on various aspects of the participants' experiences, as suggested by Smith *et al.* (2022). This process led to the identification of distinct GETs, which I will discuss in the forthcoming chapters (See Appendix 9). Once these were established across all cases, I continued to write up the results, ensuring a coherent presentation of the findings. In summary, I have outlined the procedures for analysing the data to develop a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon from the perspectives of the participants.

Principles to Ensure IPA Validity

Validity in IPA is essential to maintaining the rigour and credibility of the research process. This section introduces the key principles that underpin IPA validity, outlining the strategies used to ensure that findings authentically represent participants' lived experiences while adhering to methodological standards.

Credibility

The most challenging issue to a qualitative research study's credibility, according to Patton (2002), was attempting to impose one's interpretation on the unfolding event rather than recording the participants' experience. I used a pilot study before data collection, as it was believed to enhance the credibility of qualitative research (Padgett, 2008). The use of pilots also enabled the identification of ethical and other significant practical difficulties, such as the sampling technique, and provided an opportunity to resolve specific issues that could otherwise impede the main project (Kelly, 2007).

Therefore, I needed to remain genuine to the respondents' viewpoint to preserve credibility. Additionally, I had to ask pertinent questions while listening carefully. Robson (2002) emphasised the importance of researchers being able to ask appropriate questions while also listening attentively, in order to avoid misinterpretation of data and to capture the essence of the phenomenon under study. In applying this to my own research, I sought to remain open to new information without bias and to be attentive to participants' expressions, effects, and moods.

Transferability

Transferability refers to the extent to which research findings may be applicable to other settings (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Creswell (2009) argued that the concept of generalisability is seldom

used in qualitative research, since the aim is not to generate universally applicable conclusions but rather to develop rich and in-depth insights into a specific phenomenon, often with small sample sizes. Similarly, Scotland (2012) highlighted that the knowledge produced within the interpretive paradigm is often fragmented and context-specific, which poses challenges for transferring insights across different contexts. The nuances and specificities of each situation strongly shape how experiences are understood, thereby limiting the extent to which findings can be applied to wider populations or settings.

In the context of this study, which examined the experiences of eighteen Algerian doctoral returnees from the UK, these considerations were particularly relevant. Each participant's journey was influenced by their individual backgrounds, doctoral trajectories, and the socio-cultural contexts in which they sought to reintegrate. While the findings provide valuable insights into the challenges and achievements of these returnees, the circumstances of their reintegration may not be directly applicable to other individuals or groups. This points out to the importance of recognising the localised and situated nature of qualitative research findings and their implications for broader contexts. By acknowledging these limitations, it becomes possible to appreciate the richness of the data while remaining cautious about drawing overly broad conclusions that risk overlooking diversity in experience.

In line with the qualitative orientation of IPA, Yardley (2008) proposed four overarching criteria for evaluating the quality of qualitative research, which can be used to demonstrate how IPA addresses concerns about rigour and validity:

Sensitivity to context

My sensitivity to the context of the interviews was evident in the way I approached and appreciated the interactions during the sessions. For IPA interviews, I recognised that skill, awareness, and commitment were essential, as the quality of analysis depends on the richness of the data collected. Generating strong data required a heightened sensitivity to the interview process, which meant demonstrating understanding, ensuring that participants felt at ease, recognising interactional challenges, and carefully navigating the dynamics of the researcher-participant relationship.

This attentiveness was not only crucial during the interviews but also extended into the analysis phase. To understand how each participant made sense of their experiences, I paid close attention to the nuances of their shifting narratives. I was mindful that the credibility of an IPA study rests

in large part on such context sensitivity, which is often assessed indirectly by readers or examiners.

In practice, I prioritised creating an environment in which participants felt comfortable sharing their personal experiences. One of the first steps was confirming their preferred language of communication, whether Arabic, French, or English. All participants opted for English, as they had studied in the UK and recognised the practical benefits of transcription in this language. Nevertheless, I reassured them that they could switch to Arabic at any point if it enabled them to express themselves more fully. This flexibility allowed participants to articulate their experiences authentically and to share the complexities of their reintegration. I also reminded them of their right to withdraw at any stage, reinforcing a sense of trust and ethical commitment.

By listening attentively and encouraging openness, I sought to foster a safe and supportive atmosphere, enabling participants to provide richer and more nuanced accounts of their journeys as Algerian doctoral returnees navigating the challenges of reintegration into their home country.

Commitment and Rigour

Commitment in qualitative research can be demonstrated in several ways. Within the context of IPA, I recognised that attentiveness to participants during data collection and a careful, sustained engagement with each case were essential. To conduct effective in-depth interviews, I prioritised creating a welcoming environment that allowed participants to feel at ease and encouraged them to share their experiences openly. I also demonstrated commitment through the rigorous handling of data, transcribing interviews verbatim and engaging in repeated readings to capture the subtleties and nuances of participants' accounts as faithfully as possible.

Transparency and Coherence

Transparency in qualitative research involves clearly documenting the stages of the research process. To ensure transparency in this study, I provided a detailed account of participant selection procedures, the development of the interview schedule, the conduct of interviews, and the analytical steps undertaken. This was further supported with tables outlining participant information the scheduling process, and the stages of analysis, which offered readers a clear and systematic view of how the research was conducted.

The coherence of qualitative research can be judged in multiple ways, with much of the evaluation lying with the reader of the final report. In this study, coherence was demonstrated through methodological alignment, as the use of IPA was consistent with the ontological and epistemological assumptions underpinning the research. Employing the double hermeneutic

enabled me to interpret how participants themselves made sense of their experiences, while maintaining an idiographic focus ensured that individual cases were carefully considered before moving towards more general themes. Reflexivity was integral to this process, as I consistently reflected on my assumptions and preconceptions. By acknowledging and disclosing my background, assumptions, and beliefs early on, I clarified my position as the researcher and strengthened the overall coherence of the study.

Importance and Impact

The fourth overarching principle outlined by Yardley (2008) relates to the impact and importance of qualitative research. She argued that regardless of how rigorously a study is conducted, its true validity lies in whether it conveys findings that are fascinating, relevant, or useful to the reader. This principle is equally applicable to IPA, where the researcher's goal is to generate insights that extend beyond description and offer meaningful contributions.

In my research, I sought to ensure that the findings carried both impact and importance by foregrounding the relevance of participants' experiences. The themes were carefully selected to highlight not only individual narratives but also the broader implications of these accounts for understanding reintegration after studying abroad. My aim was to present insights that resonate with readers and contribute to the discourse on the challenges faced by Algerian doctoral returnees.

To strengthen the relevance of the findings, I engaged with existing literature to situate the participants' accounts within broader debates on international education and migration. This process demonstrated how the study's insights could inform future research, policy, and practice, while also underscoring their applicability to wider discussions in the field. Ultimately, my intention was for the research to meet academic standards while also offering meaningful contributions to the understanding of returnees' lived experiences, thereby enhancing its overall impact and importance.

Ethics consideration

According to Smith, Flowers, and Larkin (2009), undertaking ethical research is an active effort. This indicates that the researcher's ethical knowledge and practice require analysis and reconsideration at various points throughout the research process; when applying for ethical approval, this was a relevant consideration (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2009; Willig, 2013). In this respect, I submitted an ethics application form that was approved by the ethics committee of the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) (See Appendix 4). However, it is significant to

acknowledge that ethical issues can arise at any phase of a study project. Respect for the participants and settings is required, as Creswell (2014) indicated.

For qualitative researchers, preserving the highest ethical standards while planning their studies is an ethical requirement that must be fulfilled. Given that qualitative researchers are often in much closer proximity to their participants than quantitative researchers, they must exercise greater caution regarding ethical issues (Wa-Mbaleka, 2019). In line with IPA, studies frequently investigate personal experiences, which can lead to participants experiencing feelings of strangeness, embarrassment, and anger, presenting various ethical difficulties for researchers (Noon, 2018). The following actions were implemented and adhered to: I provided an information sheet to participants along with a consent form for them to sign, and I ensured that data from interviews and transcripts were securely stored and scheduled for destruction after five years when the research was completed. Participation was voluntary and free from coercion.

Furthermore, I considered that participants have the right to know about the research and the freedom to participate or withdraw at any time. The research followed ethical guidelines designed to ensure that it was valued and mitigated potential risks to the recruited participants. It was also important to note that I kept the data confidential to uphold ethical research standards. Additionally, the British Educational Research Association (BERA) (2018) outlined a set of guidelines aimed at preventing any potential harm resulting from an investigation. The research design was crafted to put participants at ease and avoid being demanding, thereby preventing discomfort or anxiety. Before initiating data collection, I revealed any possible harmful effects that might arise from the study. Both anticipated and unanticipated harms were addressed during the data collection process, with individual rights taking precedence over any other advantage. I also considered the availability of participants to ensure that they were not overwhelmed.

Consent

According to Creswell (2013), phenomenological research participants require written participation permission. Furthermore, collecting and analysing data for qualitative research can be time-consuming and complicated; that is why the Institutional Review Board (IRB) must be provided with a thorough and detailed informational background before the research is conducted (Willig, 2013). In this regard, Creswell (2012) claimed that, since qualitative data collection involves extended periods of data collection obtained from participants and recording detailed personal viewpoints, the researcher must provide an institutional review board with a detailed description of the intended procedure.

In addition, I issued a consent form and interview guide that was emailed to the participants. When a potential respondent agreed to be interviewed, I provided them with a copy of the Consent Form (See Appendix 1) to sign before the first interview session and interview questions (See Appendix 3). I made sure that participants understood the information sheet and consent form before they signed it. I believed that the current research causes no harm to the recruited participants as it has followed ethical guidelines, which aim to hinder any probable threats to the participants.

Furthermore, interviewers were advised of their right to review the interview transcripts after each interview to ensure that the content accurately reflects their thoughts, feelings, and opinions and to allow each to add, clarify, or omit any comments they chose. When debriefing the participants during the interview sessions, I made sure to inform them that a summary of this research would be submitted to them when this project was complete. The participant had the right to change their mind and withdraw consent at any time. In this concern, information about the participants would only be accessible to me and the team supervising the study (identities, audio records). Participants were informed that their information would be kept private.

Human Subjects' Safety

Protecting human research subjects has always been regarded as an important duty of the researcher, especially for an IPA researcher (Alase, 2017). I recognised that IPA researchers should do everything possible to preserve study participants' rights, dignity, and privacy. I ensured that I never violated the participants' privacy, adhering to all participant protection and privacy considerations throughout the study.

In this regard, I acknowledged the importance of securing and preserving qualitative data. As the controller of the study dataset, I took measures to secure the data obtained. Charlick *et al.* (2016) advised several steps for securing research data. For the safety and protection of the participants, I planned to delete any video, audio, or taped information after it had been transcribed. I also ensured that a safe and durable data storage system was in place for this study. The information gathered was de-recognised and stored on a protected server (UWS) OneDrive that required a password. Each participant was given a unique pseudonym, and I ensured that no connection was made between this pseudonym and any identifying information.

During transcription, participants were referred to by pseudonyms, and I informed participants that direct quotations from the transcripts would be included in the data analysis. As a result, no

one other than the research team would be able to recognise them, and any identifying characteristics from the data collection were omitted from the transcripts.

Conclusion

This chapter has outlined the research design, methodological framework, and methods employed in this study. It introduced IPA as the guiding methodological approach, highlighting its suitability for exploring participants' lived experiences and the interpretative processes through which meaning is constructed. The chapter also detailed the research population and sampling strategy, clarifying the rationale for participant selection in relation to the study's focus. Furthermore, it described the use of semi-structured interviews as the primary data collection method and explained the analytical procedures applied to interpret the data. Ethical considerations were addressed throughout, demonstrating the study's commitment to responsible and reflexive research practice.

Building on this methodological foundation, the following chapter presents the analysis of the data, exploring the experiential themes that emerged from participants' accounts and examining how these illuminate the lived experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees.

Chapter Five

Findings and Discussion: Personal Journeys of Return

Introduction

In this chapter, I respond to the first set of group experiential themes coming out by data, which centre on participants' personal experiences of returning to Algeria after completing doctoral study abroad. Across their accounts, return was not experienced simply as a physical relocation, but as a complex and emotionally charged process through which participants negotiated familiarity and difference, continuity and change. I show that reintegration was shaped by profound internal shifts as they attempted to make sense of themselves within social and cultural environments that felt simultaneously known and newly unfamiliar.

The findings presented in this chapter are organised around three group experiential themes: "Cultural and Social Re-adaptation", "Personal Growth", and "Psychological Wellbeing and Coping in Re-entry". Within these themes, participants illustrate how their return journeys were experienced as deeply personal processes of sense-making, through which they interpreted disruption, reflected on change, and renegotiated their identities.

To support interpretation, this chapter begins with brief participant profiles that situate each account within its academic and personal context. These profiles provide a foundation for understanding the experiential depth and diversity underpinning the analysis. I then include a dedicated section explaining the analytic movement from participant accounts to interpretation, outlining how individual Personal Experiential Themes (PETs) were developed and subsequently integrated into Group Experiential Themes (GETs). In keeping with the principles of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis, participants' voices remain central, while their experiences are interpreted in relation to wider theoretical and scholarly conversations on return, identity, and re-adaptation.

Participant Profiles

This section provides an overview of the participants involved in the study. Each profile outlines the participants' academic backgrounds, their experiences studying abroad in the United Kingdom, and their professional journeys upon returning to Algeria. These profiles offer context for understanding the personal and academic challenges faced by returnees as they navigate the complexities of reintegration in Algerian universities.

Hiba

Hiba, 32, earned her PhD in modern languages and applied linguistics from a university in southern England. She returned to Algeria in 2020 amidst the difficulties caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Due to pandemic-related delays, the academic year was postponed, forcing her to wait five months to finalise the documentation necessary for securing her position as a university lecturer in an English department in eastern Algeria. With 28 months of teaching experience, Hiba continues to adapt to the Algerian academic environment, applying her international experience to her role.

Mohamed

Mohamed, 32 and married, completed his PhD in southern England. In 2020, he returned to Algeria for a family vacation, but the COVID-19 outbreak prevented him from returning to England to complete his final tasks. Due to the closure of airports, Mohamed was unable to retrieve his diploma, attend the graduation ceremony, or complete academic responsibilities. After waiting a year and eight months, he secured an English literature lecturer position at a university in north-central Algeria in 2021. In addition to his teaching responsibilities, Mohamed has authored numerous articles and recently published a book.

Ghizlene

Ghizlene, a woman in her thirties and married, earned her PhD in narrative research with a focus on the identity of foreign language students from a university in the Midlands, UK. After graduating, she returned to Algeria during the COVID-19 pandemic and immediately secured a position as an English lecturer at a university in western Algeria. Currently, in her third year of teaching, Ghizlene remains engaged with her students and integrates her narrative research into her approach to teaching language and identity in a globalised context.

Manel

Manel, 31 and unmarried, holds a PhD in applied linguistics from a university in southern England. She returned to Algeria in 2022 and promptly secured a lecturer position in the eastern region, where she gained seven months of teaching experience. Before her return, Manel held an associate fellowship at an English university and taught at a primary school, instructing students in both Arabic and English. Currently, she teaches and supervises master's students, contributes to international academic journals, and manages the English language programmes at her institution.

Hanaa

Hanaa earned her PhD in education and cultural studies, which she completed in three years and

ten months at a university in southwestern England. After returning to Algeria during the COVID-19 pandemic, she took up the role of teaching several subjects, including research methodology, research ethics, cultural studies, and language and culture. In addition to her teaching, Hanaa supervises students and conducts various academic and non-academic workshops. Her multidisciplinary approach reflects the breadth of her international experience.

Insaf

Insaf, 32 and married, earned her PhD from a university in northeastern England. She returned to Algeria after completing her studies and currently holds a lecturer position in the English department at a university in northeastern Algeria. Insaf has been teaching for eight months, though her reintegration was complicated by bureaucratic challenges, including paperwork delays involving both the UK and Algerian institutions. Her experience highlights the administrative hurdles faced by many returning scholars.

Ahmed

Ahmed, 29 and unmarried, earned his PhD in applied linguistics from a university in southern England. Upon returning to Algeria in 2022, Ahmed began a three-month teaching position in the southern region. However, administrative delays with his diploma delayed his ability to secure a permanent teaching position straightforward. Despite these challenges, Ahmed is dedicated to applying his knowledge of applied linguistics to improve English education in Algeria.

Akram

Akram, 32 and married, completed his PhD at a university in southeastern England. In 2019, he began teaching at the English department of an eastern Algerian university immediately after earning his PhD. With three and a half years of teaching experience, Akram has actively contributed to his department by integrating his international academic background into the curriculum.

Autumn

Autumn, 29 and married, specialises in post-colonial feminist literature. She earned her PhD from a university in central England and returned to Algeria in 2022. Due to bureaucratic delays, Autumn experienced a period of unemployment before beginning an eight-month teaching assignment in western Algeria. Her expertise in feminist literature adds depth to her teaching and research, positioning her as an emerging voice in the study of gender and post-colonialism in the Algerian academic landscape.

Yasmine

Yasmine, 30 and married, holds a PhD in history from a university in southeastern England. After completing her PhD viva remotely due to the COVID-19 pandemic, she returned to Algeria and is currently a lecturer at a university in northern Algeria. Yasmine teaches academic writing and American literature to master's students, bringing her historical perspective into the classroom and promoting interdisciplinary research among her students.

Amani

Amani, 30 and married, earned her PhD in post-colonial literature and comparative studies from a university in northern England. After the COVID-19 pandemic delayed her return, Amani finally arrived in Algeria in 2020 and took up a position as a university lecturer. Despite pausing her career for a year due to familial responsibilities, Amani now has two years of teaching experience. Her focus on comparative literature and post-colonial theory continues to shape her academic contributions in Algeria.

Wahiba

Wahiba, 31 and married, holds a PhD in education with a research focus on global citizenship within English as a foreign language classroom. After completing her studies in northeastern England, Wahiba returned to Algeria, though she faced delays in securing a teaching position due to administrative issues related to her diploma. Despite these challenges, she is now lecturing in the English department of an eastern Algerian university and continues to integrate global perspectives into her teaching.

Karim

Karim, 32 and unmarried, earned his PhD in southeastern England. For the past two years, Karim has taught British literature, literary theory, and comparative literature at a university in northeastern Algeria. Although bureaucratic delays prevented him from securing a teaching position for nearly a year after his return, Karim has since established himself as a key figure in his department, focusing on interdisciplinary approaches to literature.

Nawel

Nawel, 30 and engaged, completed her PhD in southeastern England after four years of study. She is now an English lecturer at a university in northeastern Algeria, where she teaches at various academic levels and supervises master's students. Nawel's contributions to teaching and research reflect her commitment to modernising English language education in Algeria.

Amine

Amine, an unmarried man in his thirties, completed his PhD in southern England in three years. He faced a nine-month delay in securing employment after returning to Algeria due to bureaucratic issues. His expertise in bilingual education and language acquisition continues to inform his work, as he seeks to expand language education opportunities for students in Algeria.

Samar

Samar, 32 and married earned her PhD from a university in northwestern England. She returned to Algeria in 2021 during the COVID-19 pandemic and initially lived in her hometown before relocating. Samar now teaches at an English department, working with students of various proficiency levels. Her ability to adapt to different academic environments has made her a valued member of her department.

Maya

Maya, 30 and unmarried, holds a PhD from a university in southeastern England. After facing delays in returning to Algeria due to COVID-19, Maya was unemployed for five months before securing a teaching position at a northern Algerian university. With one year of teaching and supervision experience, Maya is passionate about cross-cultural communication, aiming to equip her students with the tools they need to thrive in a globalised world.

Kenza

Kenza is a 31-year-old single woman. She began teaching at an Algerian university in the northern region nearly six months ago. However, before starting her position as an English language lecturer, she had to wait for her PhD corrections to be approved and her diploma to be processed. The entire process took eight months to finalise, delaying her paperwork and job placement until the Ministry of Higher Education granted her the position.

From Participant Accounts to Group Experiential Themes

The participant profiles presented above introduce the individuals whose lived experiences form the empirical foundation of this study. Together, these accounts underpin the analysis presented across the two findings chapters. At this point, the thesis moves from descriptive contextualisation of participants to an interpretative engagement with their narratives, focusing on how the experience of returning to Algeria was understood, negotiated, and given meaning across personal, social, cultural, and professional domains.

While the full analytical procedures are outlined in detail in Chapter Four, a brief explanation is provided here to orient the reader as the interpretative analysis begins. In line with the principles

of IPA, analysis proceeded idiographically, with each transcript examined in depth to develop PETs that captured how individual participants made sense of their re-entry experiences (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022). Following this case-by-case analysis, patterns of convergence and divergence were explored across participants, resulting in the development of GETs that reflect shared experiential meanings while remaining grounded in individual accounts (Nizza, Smith, and Kirkham, 2023).

This analytic movement from PETs to GETs reflects IPA's commitment to balancing attention to individual lived experience with interpretative engagement at a group level, recognising both convergence and nuance across cases (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022). Examples illustrating the development of PETs and GETs are provided in Appendix (7 and 8) offering transparency in the analytic process. The analysis that follows therefore moves beyond individual description to interpret how re-entry was experienced and negotiated by Algerian doctoral returnees within shifting cultural, institutional, and professional contexts.

GET1: Cultural and Social Re-adaptation

This group experiential theme captures participants' lived experiences of re-engaging with their home environment after doctoral study abroad. In this study, culture is understood not as a fixed national entity but as a pattern of everyday meanings, values, practices, routines, and social expectations through which participants make sense of belonging and identity (Geertz, 1973; Holliday, 2011). This theme therefore focuses on how returnees experienced the re-negotiation of familiar social norms, institutional practices, and interpersonal relationships, and how these encounters made previously taken-for-granted aspects of home feel unfamiliar, challenging, or re-evaluated. The accounts presented here illuminate how cultural re-adaptation was experienced as both a practical and emotional process, shaped by shifts in identity, expectations, and social recognition upon return. So far, I have framed cultural and social re-adaptation as lived and layered; this first subtheme examines how participants navigated everyday transitions and cultural reconnection on return.

Subtheme 1: Navigating Transition and Cultural Reconnection

In this subtheme, participants are showing me how the process of return unfolded through encounters with everyday practices that felt newly visible or unexpectedly challenging. Rather than smoothly resuming familiar routines, participants described moments in which ordinary interactions such as navigating administrative systems, accessing services, or responding to social expectations became sites where change was felt most acutely. What I can see across the accounts is that these experiences prompted heightened awareness of previously taken-for-granted norms,

revealing how time abroad reshaped participants' perspectives on belonging, identity, and social participation. Through these encounters, the familiar appeared reconfigured, inviting participants to renegotiate their relationship with their home environment.

In the quote below, Ghizlene described how ordinary routines became unexpectedly frustrating and emotionally charged:

“But after you get used to a different, a different style of living in a different education system, and you might find that again Strange, though you've been through it for your whole life. But just that cut has me has made me realise many things and see the differences between the contexts. So the transition was not always happy, and was not always sad I had moments where I wish to go back. And until now I still think of my life back... So, having an appointment with the doctor would sound different. Staying in the queue would sound different, would look different. So these are amongst the things which annoyed me at the beginning. Yeah. As I felt a bit. It's not well organised as before.”

Ghizlene's account suggests that re-entry was experienced through subtle yet persistent disruptions in everyday practices. Activities such as queuing or arranging medical appointments appear to function as symbolic points of comparison, highlighting how her expectations of organisation and efficiency had shifted during her time in the UK. Her repeated use of the word “*different*” indicates an ongoing process of sense-making, in which previously taken-for-granted routines became objects of evaluation. This irritation can be understood as an emotional response to a misalignment between Ghizlene's transformed internal standards and the familiar systems she encountered upon return. This reflects what Ward *et al.* (2001), Thomson and Christophi (2006) and Agha (2021) describe as reverse culture shock, where re-entry challenges arise not because the environment has fundamentally changed, but because the individual has.

In this study, as discussed earlier in chapter three reverse culture shock is understood as a form of re-entry disorientation in which emotional discomfort emerges as returnees attempt to re-engage with everyday practices, relationships, and institutional routines that now feel misaligned with their reshaped identities (Sussman, 2002).

Similar experiences of disruption in everyday environments were described by Autumn, who articulated a deeper sense of disorientation, extending beyond routines to her emotional relationship with place:

“When you come back home again. you're like, this is not home. Because things have changed, you know, new buildings, the roads change, you know, sometimes

like if you go to an administration they say we no longer have it here you need to go elsewhere so you feel like you're trying again to navigate your way... at a very, very micro level at the level of your own home. ... you feel like stranger in your own home. I Literally felt strange in my own home and then I realised okay 'UK city' is my home now."

Autumn's narrative illustrates the spatial and emotional dimensions of cultural re-adaptation. Her references to "*new buildings*" and altered administrative systems suggest that changes in the physical and institutional environment intensified her sense of disconnection. However, the disruption she describes extends beyond material change. The phrase "*a stranger in my own home*" signals a deeper rupture in her sense of belonging, indicating that what felt unfamiliar was not only the environment but her relationship to it. As discussed earlier in chapter three, culture in this study is understood not as a fixed national entity but as a system of meanings and everyday practices through which individuals orient themselves in the world (Geertz, 1973; Holliday, 2011). From this perspective, culture becomes most visible precisely when it no longer functions effortlessly within daily life. Autumn's difficulty in "*navigating her way*," even within her own home, reflects a moment in which previously taken-for-granted cultural practices lose their coherence, prompting a more conscious engagement with everyday cultural practices. Her realisation that the UK city now felt more like "*home*" suggests that belonging had become associated with predictability, familiarity, and emotional ease rather than geographical origin. This experience resonates with scholarship on re-entry and identity shift, which highlights how returnees often reassess their attachment to home culture after internalising alternative ways of living abroad (Ward *et al.*, 2001; Sussman, 2002; Wielkiewicz and Turkowski, 2010). Autumn's account thus demonstrates how cultural reconnection during re-entry can involve not only adaptation, but also a sense of loss, uncertainty, and re-negotiation of what "*home*" comes to mean.

Hanaa echoed similar struggles, describing her re-entry as more challenging than her initial adaptation abroad:

"Not only was it hard to readapt again, which is home culture readaptation process. I thought that adjusting to the UK was easier for me than re-adapting back to everything back home. The routine changed, everything changed."

Hanaa's account illustrates the paradox frequently noted in re-entry literature: that returning home can be more demanding than adapting to a new cultural environment (Adler, 1981; Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015; Karakaş, 2020; Alkubaidi and Alzahrani, 2020; Geeraert, Ward, and Hanel, 2022). However, beyond confirming this pattern, her emphasis on "*routine*" offers deeper insight into the lived texture of re-entry. Cultural disruption was not experienced as dramatic cultural

rupture, but through the subtle destabilisation of everyday practices that once felt taken for granted. The repetition of “*everything changed*” signals not only external alteration, but an internal recalibration of familiarity. What had previously been taken for granted now required conscious negotiation. In this sense, re-entry reflects what Ward, Bochner, and Furnham (2001) describe as a shift in cultural competence, where exposure to alternative systems reshapes one’s baseline expectations of normality. Hanaa’s narrative therefore suggests that re-entry is cognitively demanding because it requires the re-learning of home through a transformed self. Her struggle was not with Algeria as a nation, but with the re-alignment between a reconfigured identity and unchanged social rhythms.

In contrast, some participants described smoother transitions rooted in strong cultural and familial continuity. Amani noted:

“I didn’t struggle as much as I thought I would. My family was incredibly supportive, and I didn’t feel too disconnected... I was happy to be back with people who understood me, people who shared my background and culture. Sure, there were things I missed from my time abroad, but being home gave me a sense of belonging that I didn’t have while I was away.”

Amani’s account reflects how strong familial support can ease the challenges of reintegration. Her emphasis on being “*understood*” and surrounded by people who “*shared*” her background suggests that home functioned as a space of cultural and emotional familiarity, allowing her to reconnect without the sense of disruption described by other participants. In line with the study’s conceptualisation of culture as lived through shared meanings and everyday practices rather than fixed national traits (Geertz, 1973; Holliday, 2011), Amani’s experience points to continuity rather than rupture in her cultural re-adaptation.

While she acknowledged missing aspects of her life abroad, her narrative indicates that these losses did not outweigh the sense of belonging reestablished through family support. This aligns with Liu’s (2024) findings that strong familial networks can significantly mitigate re-adaptation difficulties by providing emotional stability and recognition. In contrast to participants such as Autumn and Hanaa, who experienced disorientation and emotional distance, Amani’s smoother transition highlights how cultural alignment and relational support can reduce the intensity of reverse culture shock and facilitate a more contained re-entry experience (Ward *et al.*, 2001; Sussman, 2002).

Similarly, Mohamed explained:

“In terms of culture, I didn't actually, you know, feel the transition, because I am already a member in the Arabic Islamic Algerian culture. So actually, I didn't I didn't find any problems with the transition; the cultural, social transition.”

Mohamed's account points to a strong sense of cultural continuity and how familiar meanings, values, and everyday practices continued to orient his sense of belonging after return. His emphasis on already being a “*member*” of Algerian cultural and religious life suggests that re-entry did not require a substantial renegotiation of the routines and norms of his daily life.

However, not all participants who reported relative cultural continuity experienced re-entry as entirely smooth. Karim's reflections introduce a more ambivalent and relational dimension to cultural reconnection:

“I think I wouldn't use the word smooth, definitely I wouldn't use that word, but it wasn't... extremely difficult. It was challenging... I think that's the term to use challenging also because of expectation, because your family, you know, expects you to be this person, and probably not that person anymore, or some aspects of you have changed... I think, the difficult part is just to be the person that you are now not the person that you were, because you cannot be the person that you were, and I think, being that is the person that they actually do not know entirely.”

Karim's narrative reintroduces tension, but in a distinctly relational form. His account centres on the difficulty of being recognised as the person he has become rather than the person others expect him to be. This highlights how cultural re-adaptation is mediated through relationships and processes of social recognition, rather than through unfamiliar cultural practices alone. The challenge Karim describes is not only internal but interpersonal, rooted in the disjuncture between his transformed sense of self and the expectations of family and community.

Consistent with the study's understanding of culture as lived and enacted through everyday relationships and shared meanings, Karim's experience suggests that cultural continuity does not necessarily guarantee an uncomplicated return. While the cultural environment itself remained familiar, the social roles through which identity is acknowledged had not shifted in response to his personal change. Interpreted through Sussman's (2002) work, this illustrates how reverse culture shock can emerge through relational misalignment, where returnees struggle to negotiate changed identities within largely unchanged social expectations.

Across these accounts, cultural and social re-adaptation emerged not as a simple process of returning to a familiar cultural environment, but as an ongoing negotiation of meaning, identity, and belonging shaped through everyday interactions. Consistent with the study's conceptualisation of culture as a dynamic system of meanings and practices (Geertz, 1973; Holliday, 2011), participants' narratives illustrate how re-entry involved reinterpreting ordinary

routines, relationships, and social expectations through newly developed perspectives acquired abroad. Rather than representing a linear adjustment, re-entry appeared as a transitional process in which participants renegotiated their sense of self within contexts that were simultaneously familiar and newly experienced. These findings extend existing understandings of reverse culture shock by demonstrating that disruption was not limited to national cultural differences but also emerged through relational expectations, institutional practices, and everyday micro-interactions. In this sense, cultural re-adaptation is interpreted here as a process of identity re-positioning, where returnees actively reconstructed their place within evolving cultural and professional landscapes. This contributes to re-entry scholarship by highlighting how cultural transition operates through lived everyday practices, revealing the subtle yet significant ways in which identity transformation becomes visible through routine encounters after return.

GET 2: Personal Growth

This group experiential theme captures how international doctoral study shaped participants' personal development through expanded perspectives, heightened social awareness, and adaptability. Previous research has shown that prolonged international study can prompt significant personal transformation, encouraging self-awareness, independence, and intercultural sensitivity beyond academic skill development (Georgiev, 2014; Marginson, 2014; Karakaş, 2020; Savicki and Price, 2021). Across participants' accounts, personal growth was described as an outcome of sustained engagement with new cultural, social, and academic environments, where individuals were required to reassess assumptions, manage unfamiliar responsibilities, and negotiate difference in everyday life.

However, participants' narratives also reveal that such growth did not translate seamlessly into the post-return context. Rather than functioning as an unproblematic resource, personal development acquired abroad often complicated re-entry, as newly formed values, behaviours, and expectations clashed with familiar social, cultural, and professional norms at home. In this sense, personal growth was experienced as both enabling and destabilising, echoing wider literature that conceptualises return not as a simple reintegration but as a shift of identity shaped by prior transformation (Gaw, 2000; Sussman, 2002; Fanari, Wright, and Foerster, 2021).

The two subthemes that follow, "Broadened Perspectives and Social Growth" and "Building Resilience and Independence", reflect the profound impact of their international experiences on their personal lives, shaping their outlook and equipping them with the confidence to navigate complex professional and personal landscapes upon their return. This Group experiential theme

highlights how these changes not only influenced their sense of self but also their ability to contribute meaningfully to their communities and professional environments.

Subtheme 1: Broadening Perspectives and Social Growth

I learnt from the data that a key dimension of personal growth experienced by participants was the broadening of their perspectives and the development of social competence. Exposure to diverse cultures, academic systems, and ways of thinking during their time abroad reshaped their worldviews, equipping them with skills and insights that extended beyond academia. Upon their return, participants described how this newfound perspective enriched their social interactions, allowing them to engage more thoughtfully with their communities and contribute meaningfully to societal discourse. Their narratives illustrate how the intersection of international experiences and local reintegration fostered both personal and social growth, highlighting the transformative potential of navigating life between different cultural contexts.

Participants consistently highlighted how their experiences in the UK contributed significantly to their personal growth, reshaping their perspectives and enhancing their social competence. This growth was not described as a simple outcome of academic success, but as a broader transformation involving emotional maturity, intellectual development, and increased self-awareness.

This can be read in Samar's reflection on her personal transformation following her return. In the extract below, she described how her time in the UK reshaped her sense of self, emotionally and intellectually:

“So when I came back for good. I grew as a person emotionally, intellectually. I am not the person who went to the UK in 2016. That's obvious”.

Samar's statement captures the depth of personal change she experienced, positioning growth as a fundamental shift in identity rather than a gradual improvement. Her assertion, “*I am not the person who went to the UK,*” shows a difference between past and present selves, suggesting that her doctoral journey abroad reshaped how she understood herself at a core level. Rather than framing development as improvement within a stable identity, Samar narrates transformation as a reorientation of self-understanding.

Her emphasis on emotional and intellectual growth reflects how sustained immersion in a different cultural and academic environment prompted heightened self-awareness and a reassessment of previously taken-for-granted assumptions. Read through a transformative learning lens, this account illustrates a reconfiguration of meaning and self-understanding that

emerges through prolonged engagement with unfamiliar contexts and ways of thinking (Mezirow, 1997).

Building on this, Wahiba's narrative offers a more emotionally layered account of return, highlighting how personal growth was intertwined with uncertainty and loss. She described her return to Algeria as marked by mixed emotions:

“When I first arrived in Algeria, I mean, it was a mixture of feeling sadness and happiness. Happiness because I'm going to see my family after being far—I mean, for a long time, especially with COVID. They didn't see them for more than a year. ... I was so happy and excited to meet them again. But at the same time, sad because I left... my second family back home in the UK”.

Wahiba's account highlights the duality of returning home. The joy and anticipation of reuniting with family, heightened by the prolonged separation during COVID-19, coexisted with feelings of sadness and loss at leaving behind the strong social bonds she had formed abroad. This blend of emotions reflects the complexity of re-adaptation, where the excitement of reconnecting with one's origins is tempered by a profound sense of disconnection from a recently adopted cultural home. Her reference to her “*second family*” in the UK underlines the depth of her integration into the host culture and the friendships she developed. This connection made her departure more emotionally challenging, suggesting that re-adaptation is not merely a return to the familiar but a process of reconciling the dual identities formed during her time abroad.

Wahiba's reflection on becoming “*more independent and responsible*” further illustrates the transformative nature of studying abroad. Living alone and managing her own affairs fostered a strong sense of autonomy that she carried back to Algeria, while sustained engagement within a multicultural environment broadened her perspective and heightened her awareness of cultural diversity and inclusivity. In contrast, Wahiba described Algerian society as relatively homogeneous, a perception that generated a subtle but persistent tension between her expanded worldview and the cultural norms she encountered upon return. This tension reflects wider findings in the re-entry literature, which suggest that returnees often experience resistance when newly acquired forms of openness, autonomy, and intercultural awareness sit uneasily within familiar social contexts that have remained largely unchanged (Thompson, 2007; Landon *et al.*, 2017; Khanal and Gaulee, 2019; Savicki and Price, 2021).

The emotional weight of Wahiba's narrative also reveals how broader contextual factors, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, intensified the complexity of the re-adaptation. Extended physical separation from family not only deepened her attachment to life in the UK but also rendered her

return Algeria more bittersweet. This juxtaposition of joy and sorrow highlights the complex, layered nature of returnee experiences, where emotional and personal dimensions are deeply interwoven.

Such accounts resonate with scholarship highlighting how postgraduate study abroad shapes personal and professional identities through sustained exposure to unfamiliar academic, social, and cultural environments (Austin and McDaniels, 2006; Castelló *et al.*, 2017). These experiences often prompt individuals to reassess values, expectations, and ways of relating to others, fostering forms of growth that extend well beyond academic achievement.

Samar's narrative further stresses this process of transformation. As she reflected, "*I am not the person who went to the UK,*" a statement that captures personal growth as a fundamental shift in identity rather than a gradual accumulation of skills. Her account echoes Mezirow's (1997) theory of transformative learning. In the sense that learning is a process through which exposure to disorienting experiences challenges previously taken-for-granted assumptions and reshapes meaning perspectives. The growth Samar described illustrates how the process of living abroad extends beyond academic achievement, reshaping individuals' values, priorities, and interpersonal skills. This transformation not only equips returnees with a broader worldview but also enables them to navigate their reintegration with a renewed sense of self.

While Samar and Wahiba foreground growth through emotional awareness and openness, Akram's account offers a contrasting perspective that exposes the limits of personal transformation within constraining home environments. He described his return as marked by a persistent sense of misfit:

"It was difficult...and I didn't really adapt so quickly. I felt that's a piece I have... that doesn't really fit into the environment where I was supposed to. That's a feeling that I still have until nowadays, due to many things—due to the work environment that is not exactly what I expected to be, due to the financial reasons... If you look to dream big in Algeria, that's not really going to help. And this is one of the issues... I still see myself not quite fitting to the process here"

Akram's narrative captures the emotional dissonance and frustration that can accompany re-adaptation, particularly when professional realities fall short of expectations. His vivid metaphor of being a "*piece that doesn't really fit*" reflects a profound sense of misalignment with his environment. This feeling, which persists over time, illustrates the long-lasting psychological impact of unmet expectations and systemic barriers. His account stresses two key challenges: financial constraints and systemic limitations in the educational sector. The financial struggles he

describes, including the inability to “*dream big*,” point to structural issues that restrict opportunities for upward mobility, adding to his dissatisfaction. The disconnect between his aspirations and the constraints of his role as a university teacher further deepens his sense of alienation. Akram’s perception of his role as merely an “*implement*” of governmental directives reveals a lack of agency, exacerbating his feelings of frustration and disempowerment. This aligns with findings by Alanedjani (2013), Karakas (2020), and Le Ha and Mohamad (2020) who emphasise that returnees often struggle when their professional and cultural expectations clash with the realities of their home environment. Furthermore, Gaw (2000) identifies such misalignment as a significant contributor to reverse culture shock, particularly in cases where systemic limitations prevent returnees from applying the skills and perspectives gained abroad.

Despite these challenges, Akram’s narrative underscores his enduring sense of responsibility as a teacher, even as he remains critical of the structural limitations of the system in which he works. His account reveals a persistent tension between his professional values and the institutional constraints that restrict meaningful agency, illustrating how re-entry can involve not only cultural readjustment but an ongoing struggle to reconcile transformed academic identities with inflexible local structures. In this sense, Akram’s experience offers a poignant example of the emotional and professional complexity that can characterise reintegration for returning scholars.

In contrast, Amine described personal growth as both internally transformative and externally validated. Reflecting on his PhD journey, he stated:

“I’m more mature. If you ask me, in terms of my personality, I think I became more calm and collected, wiser, and sure. In terms of academia, I would say yes, it grew up. I’ve gone up the academic ladder. I think now I can see things with more clarity, thanks to the whole PhD journey I spent in the UK. I think it made me a better person wise and academia-wise. I feel that, to be honest with you. I feel I know things way better than so many people in Algeria, particularly where I work. They keep asking, ‘Oh, he must know such things because he’s got a PhD from the UK.’ It’s good to feel that acknowledgement. It’s good to see someone recognising your potential, your abilities, and the good stuff about you... I’ve become more mindful of my language when talking to people... I managed to break my silos”.

Amine’s reflections reveal a profound transformation of both personal and professional identity through his PhD journey in the UK. He describes becoming “*more mature, calm, and collected*,” gesturing a deep internal growth cultivated by navigating the challenges of an international academic environment. His assertion of becoming “*wise and academia-wise*” highlights the intertwined nature of his personal and professional development, where the clarity gained during

his studies reshaped his sense of self and approach to academia. The external recognition he receives in *Algeria* “he must know such things because he’s got a PhD from the UK” further reinforces his professional identity, offering validation and a sense of pride, while subtly acknowledging the societal prestige attached to international qualifications. His heightened cultural sensitivity, reflected in his mindfulness of language, and his ability to “break silos” point to significant interpersonal growth, likely influenced by exposure to a multicultural setting. These experiences collectively highlight the transformative impact of his PhD, enabling him to blend self-assurance, academic competence, and social adaptability into a cohesive, redefined identity.

These dimensions of Amine’s account align closely with Pikos-Sallie (2018), who highlights emotional resilience, increased self-confidence, and reflective clarity as key outcomes of postgraduate mobility, as well as with Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva (2019), who emphasise how international doctoral trajectories foster the integration of scholarly competence with personal adaptability. In this sense, Amine’s narrative illustrates how international doctoral study can support the development of a cohesive professional identity grounded not only in academic achievement but also in interpersonal awareness and self-assurance. His reference to breaking silos also mirrors the observations of De Wit and Altbach (2021) discusses how returning students often break away from old habits, fostering greater collaboration and inclusiveness.

Amine’s reflections on his PhD journey and its transformative impact on his personal and professional identity are echoed in Ahmed’s narrative. Ahmed also described significant personal growth during his time abroad:

“So I kinda grew there, I became. I think I became more mature. So I lived on my own. I, you know, started reading more, and the journey itself. It’s, you know, you know, I became what is called critical. So I mean, I got a PhD. You know. So I think I grew as a person”

Ahmed framed his growth through increased independence, critical thinking, and self-confidence, developed through living alone and engaging deeply with academic work. His account aligns with transformative learning theory, where exposure to unfamiliar contexts prompts reflection and re-evaluation of assumptions (Mezirow, 1997). Yet his emphasis on humility alongside confidence signals ongoing identity negotiation rather than closure.

Ahmed’s account complements Amine’s in highlighting the transformative effect of living independently and engaging with diverse academic perspectives. His statement, “*I became more mature,*” underscores the emotional and intellectual growth that comes from navigating a new

cultural and academic environment. Living on his own and cultivating a habit of critical reading contributed to his self-awareness and intellectual independence, resonating with Curtis and Ledgerwood (2018) findings that studying abroad fosters critical thinking, autonomy, and personal development. The narratives highlight the profound personal changes experienced by returnees, as they adapt to new environments, challenge their assumptions, and develop skills that extend beyond academic achievement. Furthermore, this transformation aligns with Knight (2020), who highlights that sustained engagement with unfamiliar academic and cultural environments provides fertile ground for personal and intellectual growth. Furthermore, the ability of returnees to apply these insights upon reintegration reflects the lasting value of international education in shaping broader perspectives and fostering social competence.

Similarly manel' s account vividly illustrates the personal transformation she experienced as a result of her time in the UK. She reflects:

“How I change! You grow up. You're no longer the same little naive girl. But you went to the UK at the beginning...you start thinking because you analyse things differently. You live differently, you eat differently. You develop your own system that is separated from the rest. Why? Because, from my perspective, once in Algeria, we're very family oriented in that. it's the family system that drives us. It's not your system. It's the way your mom and dad sets it up for you. It's not the way you set it up for you. But then, once you are in the UK, you are responsible for making your own decisions. You're responsible for choosing the way you live, the way you think, the way you behave, the way you do everything about your life when and how and why. So once you do that, you develop, as I said, your own self... social awareness about things. You're no longer your thinking to be... driven by others. It's driven by your own way of analysing things. So that was something people like noted about me, that I might be going, for them, I became much more critical when it comes to the way I live. So instead of accepting things and taking things for granted, I actually started asking questions... 'Why does it have to be me?’”

Manel's narrative powerfully illustrates how international doctoral study facilitated a shift from socially prescribed modes of living towards self-authored ways of thinking and being. Her repeated emphasis on “*developing your own system*” captures a movement from family-driven decision-making towards individual agency and reflexive self-governance. By contrasting Algerian family-oriented norms with the autonomy required in the UK, Manel frames personal growth as a process of learning to take responsibility for one's choices, values, and behaviours.

Her account reflects more than independence in a practical sense; it signals the emergence of critical consciousness. The transition from “*accepting things and taking things for granted*” to

actively questioning “*why does it have to be me?*” demonstrates a reorientation towards reflexive reasoning and critical engagement with social expectations. This aligns with Tran and Pham (2015) and Kartoshkina’s (2018) observation that studying abroad often fosters self-reliance and critical thinking as individuals navigate unfamiliar environments without established support structures. Manel’s growing “*social awareness*” and questioning stance also highlight the relational consequences of personal transformation. The fact that others “*noticed*” her change indicates that her newly developed self-awareness disrupted familiar interactional patterns upon return. This suggests that personal growth did not occur in isolation but rather reshaped her positioning within family and community contexts. In this sense, transformation became visible, and at times unsettling, to those around her.

From a theoretical perspective, Manel’s narrative closely reflects Mezirow’s (1997) transformative learning theory, in which exposure to disorienting experiences prompts critical reflection on previously unexamined assumptions. Her account illustrates how living abroad destabilised taken-for-granted cultural norms and enabled her to reconstruct meaning on her own terms. Importantly, this transformation did not end with return; instead, it continued to shape how she negotiated belonging and authenticity in Algeria.

Likewise, Ahmed complements Manel’s narrative, stating:

“I’m way more confident now than I was back then because, like, I have a PhD, and I have a nice salary here. My life is on point. Sometimes I feel that I’m ahead of others, but I also remind myself to stay humble.” His journey exemplifies how the experience of studying abroad not only provided academic and professional credentials but also instilled a deeper sense of self-assurance and personal achievement. Ahmed further noted, “It gave me more confidence. It kind of pushed me.”

Ahmed’s narrative reveals a profound shift in his self-perception following his international experience, particularly in the way he associates confidence with tangible achievements like earning a PhD and securing a stable salary. His assertion, “*I’m way more confident now than I was back then because, like, I have a PhD, and I have a nice salary here. My life is on point,*” reflects a sense of pride in his accomplishments, suggesting that academic and professional milestones became important reference points through which he evaluated personal growth. This aligns with Marginson (2014), who argues that international education reshapes not only skills but how individuals position themselves in relation to others and assess their own worth.

His comparison to others, as expressed in “*Sometimes I feel that I’m ahead of others,*” indicates a reflective evaluation of his current position relative to his peers. This recognition of his

achievements underscores a reconstructed sense of identity, where he now views himself as capable and accomplished. However, his acknowledgment of the need to “*stay humble*” introduces a dynamic tension between pride and self-awareness. This duality highlights an ongoing negotiation of values as he navigates the implications of his transformation.

Ahmed’s reflections suggest that the international experience was not only about academic success but also about internal growth and resilience. His sense of being “*pushed*” signifies the challenges and opportunities that shaped his ability to adapt, reflect, and redefine his understanding of success. This reflects Mezirow’s (1997) conceptualisation of transformative learning as a process through which individuals reconstruct meaning and self-understanding through critical reflection on experience. For Ahmed, the journey abroad facilitated not only professional achievement but also a deeper understanding of himself, emphasising the interplay between external accomplishments and internal introspection.

The narrative highlights the lasting impact of the international experience on Ahmed’s identity. While he derives confidence from his tangible successes, his reflection on humility reveals a more profound self-awareness. The duality of pride and humility underscores the transformative nature of his journey, illustrating how external achievements catalyse internal growth. Through his reflections, Ahmed provides a nuanced perspective on the relationship between personal growth and professional accomplishment, revealing the enduring influence of his experience abroad.

Viewed collectively, these narratives illustrate that personal growth following international doctoral study was neither uniform nor linear. While participants such as Samar and Wahiba described growth as a reconfiguration of self, marked by emotional awareness and expanded perspectives, others such as Akram highlighted the limits of personal transformation when confronted with constraining professional and institutional contexts. In contrast, Amine, Ahmed, and Manel articulated growth through strengthened autonomy, confidence, and critical self-positioning, often accompanied by heightened visibility and difference upon return.

Across these accounts, personal growth emerged not simply as an individual outcome of studying abroad, but as a relational and contextual process shaped by how transformed identities were recognised, resisted, or negotiated within home environments. This variation underscores that growth was lived differently depending on participants’ social positioning, professional contexts, and the extent to which newly acquired ways of thinking could be sustained after return.

Subtheme 2: Building Resilience and Independence

In this subtheme, participants are showing me how resilience and independence were developed through the demands of international doctoral study and subsequently mobilised during re-entry. Rather than framing resilience solely as emotional endurance, participants narrated it as an active and learned process involving persistence, self-reliance, and confidence in one's judgement when navigating personal, social, and institutional constraints. Participants also suggest that independence extended beyond practical matters, such as living alone or managing daily responsibilities, but as the development of personal agency and the ability to sustain one's values and practices despite resistance. Together, these accounts illustrate how resilience and independence were forged abroad and tested upon return, shaping how participants responded to challenges and negotiated their place within home contexts.

Ghizlene's account illustrates how resilience and independence were enacted through sustained persistence and confidence in her professional judgement following return. Reflecting on how others perceived her transformation, she explained:

“Everyone sees you a different person... the way you talk, how independent you are, how much you always seek knowledge. Even people who don't know you say there is something special about this person.”

These observations show that personal transformation was not only internally experienced but also socially recognised. Ghizlene positioned herself as someone who had developed a strong sense of self-direction and confidence, attributes established through her doctoral experience abroad.

This resilience became particularly visible when her values and ways of working were challenged. When she encountered resistance to her research-informed practices, she chose not to retreat:

“I never gave up... I resisted that. I was convinced that what I was doing was research-based, not something traditional. I had my own arguments to justify myself.”

Ghizlene's narrative positions resilience as an active and agentic process rather than passive coping. Her insistence on continuing to use pedagogical approaches grounded in research reflects strong academic confidence and professional independence. Even when faced with resistance, she sustained her practices, demonstrating what Tu and Nehring (2020) describe as returnees' efforts to assert internationally acquired knowledge within resistant institutional contexts. Her account also shows how independence extended beyond professional life; when family members questioned the time she spent learning, she reframed this engagement as a form of personal

wellbeing, describing it as “*like a psychotherapy session.*” In this sense, resilience was mobilised across both professional and personal domains, allowing her to maintain practices aligned with her values despite social pressure.

Amine’s reflections further illuminate resilience and independence as capacities developed through experience rather than inherent traits. Reflecting on his doctoral journey in the UK, he described how independence and resilience emerged gradually through sustained engagement with challenge:

“I think the whole PhD journey in the UK made me a stronger and more independent person. Before, maybe in Algeria, I was a bit dependent. But now I’ve fully developed this sense of autonomy. I believe in people’s autonomy, that you can do things by yourself despite the struggles, despite the hurdles. You still get over them. And that’s what makes you resilient...For me, resilience is not something you are, it’s something you become. I wasn’t resilient before. I’ve learned to be resilient through experience. This resilience and autonomy were shaped by the UK environment”

Amine’s account explicitly frames resilience as a “*process of becoming*” rather than an inherent personal quality. By contrasting his earlier self with who he has “*become,*” he positions resilience as something developed through repeated encounters with difficulty rather than something he possessed in advance. This understanding echoes re-entry scholarship that conceptualises resilience as a learned and contextually shaped capacity, developed through prolonged exposure to challenge rather than as a fixed individual trait (Agha, 2021; Winkel, Strachan, and Aamir, 2022).

His emphasis on autonomy and self-reliance highlights how international study fostered confidence in his ability to navigate obstacles independently. Importantly, Amine situates this transformation within the UK academic environment itself, suggesting that resilience emerged through ongoing negotiation with unfamiliar institutional expectations, academic pressures, and everyday demands. Rather than positioning resilience as innate and describing it as “*learned through experience,*” he presents personal growth as environmentally shaped and relational, aligning with research that emphasises the role of international academic contexts in cultivating adaptive capacities through sustained engagement with complexity and uncertainty (Coleman, 2015; Prince, 2019; Deardorff *et al.*, 2023).

In contrast, Akram's account foregrounds the limits of resilience when transformed identities encounter constraining structural conditions upon return. Reflecting on his professional environment, he explained:

“This is not the perfect environment that you should be working in... there are difficulties and struggles that certainly hinder academic and research progress.”

Akram's narrative highlights how systemic constraints restricted intellectual freedom and professional fulfilment, producing a persistent sense of misalignment between his aspirations and institutional realities. Despite this disappointment, his continued engagement within academia reflects a form of constrained resilience, shaped less by agency than by endurance. His experience aligns with research showing that returnees often struggle when their professional expectations clash with rigid institutional systems that limit the application of internationally acquired knowledge (Tu and Nehring, 2020; Pham and Saito, 2020).

Collectively, the accounts of Ghizlene, Amine, and Akram illustrate how resilience and independence were developed through international study but enacted in distinct ways upon return. While Ghizlene's resilience was expressed through persistence and academic confidence, and Amine's through internalised autonomy and self-belief, Akram's narrative reflects a more constrained form of resilience shaped by structural and institutional limitations.

GET 3: Psychological Well-being and Coping in Re-entry

This group experiential theme sheds light on the emotional and psychological challenges faced by Algerian doctoral returnees as they transitioned back into their home environment. Participants' accounts indicate that re-entry was accompanied by varying levels of emotional stress, psychological vulnerability, and the need to actively cope with familiar yet demanding social environments. Rather than a discrete phase, adjustment appeared as an ongoing process shaped by how participants interpreted their return and sustained a sense of self after transformation abroad (Adler, 1981; Szkudlarek, 2010). Consistent with re-entry work, gaps between expectations and experience amplified distress (Rogers and Ward, 1993; Geeraert, Ward, and Hanel, 2022). With this focus on wellbeing as an ongoing process, the first subtheme examines how participants coped with the transition and its emotional toll.

Sub-theme 1: Coping with Transition and Emotional Toll

In this subtheme, participants are showing me how they experienced and managed the emotional toll of re-entry, revealing marked variation in coping strategies and psychological outcomes. Through their accounts, participants appear to be highlighting that emotional adjustment was not

uniform; while some described adopting proactive, solution-oriented approaches that supported their wellbeing, others narrated experiences of cumulative overload or a perceived restriction of personal agency. Importantly, these variations were not experienced in isolation from broader social and relational contexts, including gendered expectations that shaped how emotional strain was lived and negotiated. What I can see in participants' responses is that psychological wellbeing during re-entry was shaped less by the objective presence of challenges than by how individuals interpreted, negotiated, and made meaning of these changes. This pattern echoes re-entry scholarship suggesting that emotional outcomes are mediated by meaning-making processes rather than challenges alone (Adler, 1981; Gu, 2015; Van Gorp *et al.*, 2017).

For some participants, coping was closely tied to a sense of agency and intentional meaning-making. Insaf, for example, framed her return as challenging but manageable, emphasising the importance of mindset and self-directed adaptation:

“So I would consider my transition to be not too bad... it was with difficulties, because the change is huge...However, it's about how you react to those differences that matters... I just look at the positive sides always, okay. And I try to make changes myself.”

Insaf's emphasis on “*how you react to those differences*” underscores the central role of personal agency in managing the challenges of re-adaptation. While acknowledging the significant changes she faced, including differences in pedagogical and broader cultural perspectives, her choice to focus on “*positive sides*” reflects a resilience that aligns with Sussman's (2002) findings on proactive coping strategies. Sussman emphasises that focusing on actionable solutions and maintaining an optimistic outlook enables returnees to better manage the emotional and practical difficulties of reintegration. Furthermore, Insaf's determination to “*make changes herself*” demonstrates an active engagement with her environment, aligning with Chen and Li (2019), who found that returnees who adopt a solution-oriented approach are better equipped to overcome the psychological and social challenges of reintegration. By framing her transition as a process of adaptation and growth, Insaf illustrates how embracing challenges with positivity can foster resilience and ease the transition back into one's home culture. Her narrative serves as an example of how returnees can navigate the complexities of re-adaptation by focusing on self-efficacy and constructive action, highlighting the potential for personal growth even amidst significant challenges.

In contrast, other participants described emotional stress arising from the convergence of multiple demands during re-entry. Yasmine's account vividly illustrates how psychological distress

emerged when academic, personal, and cultural expectations collided. Reflecting on the period following her return, she explained:

“My submission happened a month before my wedding day... then my viva happened a week after Ramadan... I entered married life under very challenging circumstances... I was tired, exhausted, and strained... I started having major panic attacks.”

Yasmine’s account provides a demonstrative example of the emotional and psychological toll of re-adaptation, she faced the convergence of personal, professional, and cultural demands. Her narrative reveals how the intersection of significant life events; marriage, the fasting month of Ramadan, and the completion of her PhD impaired her mental and physical exhaustion. She described herself as “*tired, exhausted, and strained,*” reflecting the overwhelming nature of her circumstances. The cultural expectations placed upon her as a new bride in Algeria, coupled with the pressure to adhere to traditions, added to her emotional stress. This aligns with Berry’s (2005) acculturation theory, which highlights the stress experienced by individuals navigating multiple cultural expectations. Yasmine’s mention of “*panic attacks*” and “*struggling to finish her final submissions*” underlines the psychological impact of balancing these overlapping responsibilities, illustrating how re-adaptation is not merely a cultural process but a deeply personal and emotional one. This experience can be understood through Sussman (2011) psychological transition cycle, which conceptualises re-entry as a period of identity destabilisation in which individuals struggle to reconcile transformed self-concepts with renewed social and cultural demands. From this perspective, Yasmine’s emotional exhaustion reflects not merely situational stress, but a deeper tension between competing role expectations at a moment when her personal, professional, and cultural identities were simultaneously in flux. Her account illustrates how re-entry can provoke heightened anxiety and emotional imbalance when returnees are required to perform continuity in contexts that no longer fully align with their internalised sense of self.

While Yasmine’s narrative highlights the overwhelming pressure of balancing personal milestones with professional demands, Maya’s experience sheds light on the emotional toll of navigating restrictive societal norms and intrusive cultural expectations upon her return to Algeria:

“It was very, very hard... I transitioned from having a life of my own... But when I came back to Algeria, it’s family life again... you can’t really do whatever you want.”

Maya's narrative highlights the psychological stress of returning to a restrictive social environment after experiencing autonomy abroad. Her reflection on transitioning from a self-directed routine to a family-centered lifestyle highlights the challenges of reintegration. The statement, "*It was hard. It was very, very hard. I think I got into some sort of depression,*" reveals the emotional toll of adapting to cultural norms and expectations she had outgrown during her time in the UK. This gendered dimension of re-entry is well documented in the literature. Studies by Alandejani (2013), Almuarik, (2019), Alfurayh and Burns (2020), and antal and Alzhrani (2020) show that women returnees often experience re-adaptation as particularly challenging due to heightened social norms, expectations surrounding marriage and modesty, and restrictions on personal autonomy. Maya's experience reflects these findings, as her distress emerged not only from the process of returning home but from navigating gendered cultural norms that conflicted with the independence she had developed during her time abroad. Alkhalaf, Al-Krenawi, and Elbedour (2024) further demonstrate that highly educated women frequently experience re-entry as a site of tension, where academic success coexists with persistent gender norms that limit its social recognition. Maya's account therefore illustrates how re-adaptation can involve not only cultural adjustment but also gendered identity negotiation, contributing to emotional stress and feelings of constraint during reintegration.

Maya's narrative also reflects Adler's (1981) re-entry theory, which identifies a period of psychological disorientation as individuals reconcile their transformed sense of self with the unchanged cultural norms of their home environment. The interplay between her personal growth abroad and the limitations imposed by societal expectations highlights the nuanced emotional challenges faced by returning scholars. Yasmine and Maya stories underscore the emotional and psychological complexity of re-adaptation, particularly for women navigating restrictive cultural norms and societal pressures. Her experience emphasises the need for tailored support systems that address the unique challenges of reintegration, including mental health resources and initiatives to challenge traditional gender roles. This narrative adds depth to the broader discourse on re-adaptation, illustrating how personal autonomy developed abroad can clash with cultural expectations at home.

A further layer of gendered negotiation emerged in Samar's account, illustrating how re-entry challenges were shaped not only by emotional stress but by the renegotiation of cultural expectations surrounding gender roles and autonomy. Samar reflected on how her perspectives on women's roles had fundamentally shifted following her time abroad:

“My perspectives of a female life have changed... I used to have a regular Algerian female mentality... now I believe that no one should have to do anything she doesn't want to... I believe we are 50/50 partners... cooking and cleaning are not my duties. And I don't miss an opportunity to remind my family of that or my sister, my younger sister.”

Samar's reflections introduce a more explicit reconfiguration of gender identity, revealing how international mobility reshaped her understanding of female roles, autonomy, and relational expectations. Her statement that she previously held a “*regular Algerian female mentality*” but now rejects traditional assumptions about gendered duties illustrates a process of critical identity renegotiation rather than simple personal change. Within the study's conceptualisation of identity as dynamic and relational (Hall, 1996; Jenkins, 2008), Samar's narrative suggests that exposure to alternative cultural frameworks enabled her to question previously internalised norms and reconstruct her sense of self through new interpretative lenses.

Her insistence on redefining partnership roles as “50/50” and challenging expectations surrounding domestic responsibilities highlights how cultural identity transformation is enacted through everyday practices and relational negotiations. This reflects scholarship demonstrating that women returnees may experience heightened tension when transformed gender identities conflict with established social expectations (Szkudlarek, 2010; Alandejani, 2013; Jung, Lee, and Moral, 2013; Alfurayh and Burns, 2019). Samar's active resistance can be understood as a form of identity assertion, where emotional labour emerges through the ongoing need to justify and defend newly adopted values within familiar social environments. Rather than simply adapting to existing norms, her narrative illustrates agency in reshaping cultural meanings, reinforcing the idea that re-entry is a process of continuous negotiation between personal transformation and collective expectations.

Autumn's account further illustrates how gender norms may shape emotional wellbeing and professional agency during re-entry. She described how restrictions within her personal relationships affected her ability to engage professionally:

“I faced the problem because I had this plan, with one of my colleagues, in the UK who happen to have also a PhD in the same area of mine. And he thought, okay, let's work together to publish a book... it was going to be published...but My husband said no. I cannot allow you to work with a man... why do you have to work with a man?”

Autumn's account further illustrates how emotional wellbeing during re-entry can be shaped by relational and structural constraints that limit the enactment of newly developed identities. Her

statement that she was prevented from working with male colleagues highlights how gendered expectations extended beyond social norms into professional participation, influencing both her sense of agency and belonging. Rather than representing a simple interpersonal disagreement, this experience reflects a deeper tension between the autonomy cultivated through international mobility and culturally embedded expectations surrounding gender roles. Within the study's conceptualisation of culture as a system of lived meanings and practices (Geertz, 1973; Holliday, 2011), Autumn's experience demonstrates how re-entry involves renegotiating everyday practices through which identity is enacted and recognised.

The restriction she describes may be understood as a disruption to her emerging professional identity, particularly as it challenges her ability to apply skills and collaborative practices developed abroad. The emotional impact therefore emerges not only from the restriction itself but from the mismatch between her transformed self-understanding and the relational expectations imposed upon her. Similar dynamics are identified in studies of women returnees navigating conservative environments, where autonomy gained through overseas education may be constrained by social norms governing gender interaction and professional visibility (Alandejani, 2013; Winkel, Strachan, and Aamir, 2021). Autumn's narrative suggests that coping during re-entry may involve ongoing negotiation between internal change and external limits, highlighting how emotional wellbeing is deeply tied to recognition and validation within social relationships.

Across their accounts, Insaf, Yasmine, Autumn, and Samar illustrate that emotional wellbeing during re-entry was shaped less by the objective presence of challenges than by how participants negotiated transformed identities within relational and cultural contexts. Importantly, these negotiations were not gender-neutral but were structured through gendered expectations operating at relational, cultural, and institutional levels. For female returnees in particular, reintegration extended beyond academic adjustment to include intensified social scrutiny, domestic expectations, and relational constraints that intersected with their professional identities. While male participants' challenges were more frequently framed around institutional workload or organisational pressures, women's narratives revealed how personal autonomy, marital roles, and professional participation became key sites of contestation.

Insaf's account foregrounds agency and intentional meaning-making, demonstrating how proactive interpretation supported psychological stability despite significant change. In contrast, Yasmine's experience highlights cumulative overload, where simultaneous personal, academic, and cultural demands disrupted her capacity for adaptive coping and intensified emotional stress. Autumn's narrative introduces a relational dimension, showing how gendered expectations may

constrain professional participation and create tension between internal transformation and external recognition. Similarly, Samar's account reflects a more explicit identity renegotiation, where resistance to traditional gender norms illustrates the emotional labour involved in asserting newly developed values within established social frameworks. These accounts therefore suggest that re-entry can be understood as a process of gendered identity negotiation rather than a neutral transition. The emotional toll described by participants was shaped not only by returning home but by the expectation to re-embody culturally sanctioned forms of femininity after internalising alternative gender norms abroad. In this sense, re-entry functioned as a space where global academic mobility intersected with local gender systems, producing distinct psychological pressures for women.

Collectively, these accounts suggest that re-entry is not simply an adjustment process but an ongoing negotiation of belonging, autonomy, and identity continuity, reinforcing re-entry scholarship that emphasises the relational and interpretative nature of psychological adaptation (Adler, 1981; Sussman, 2002; Gu, 2015). By conceptualising reintegration through this gendered lens, the analysis moves beyond describing emotional distress to illustrating how cultural expectations surrounding marriage, domestic responsibility, modesty, and professional interaction actively structured women's coping processes and wellbeing, positioning gender as a central organising dimension of post-return adjustment.

Subtheme 2: The Impact of COVID-19 on Emotional Wellbeing

In this subtheme, the participants are showing me how the COVID-19 pandemic fundamentally reshaped the emotional atmosphere of re-entry. What I can see across the accounts is that COVID-19 did not merely add practical difficulty to return trajectories; rather, it intensified separation, disrupted anticipated endings, and provoked unexpected forms of psychological endurance. Participants' narratives reveal how prolonged uncertainty, forced immobility, and delayed closure altered how they understood themselves, their relationships, and their capacity to cope.

Ghizlene's experience vividly illustrates the emotional toll that the COVID-19 pandemic exerted on returning scholars. For her, the pandemic amplified the challenges of being physically distanced from her family, a circumstance she initially perceived as challenging. Reflecting on her prolonged separation, she expressed disbelief at her endurance:

“Because I'm very, very attached to my family and my home... But living away from them and leaving for a good period... especially because of COVID, 2 years and 3 months. I never thought I could do it and now I'm thinking like how did I survive? How did I survive without them?”

Ghizlene's repeated questioning "*How did I survive?*" captures a moment of retrospective meaning-making. Rather than describing resilience as something she consciously possessed at the time, her reflection suggests that resilience was recognised only after the experience had passed. This indicates a shift in self-understanding, where she moves from viewing herself as emotionally dependent on proximity to family toward recognising an unexpected capacity for endurance and autonomy. The pandemic context appears to have acted as a catalyst for this transformation, forcing her to navigate sustained uncertainty and isolation without the emotional resources she previously relied upon.

At the same time, Ghizlene's account reveals the emotional cost of this endurance. Her astonishment at having "*survived*" underscores how psychologically demanding the separation was, even as it later became a source of self-redefinition. This aligns with research showing that international students experienced heightened psychological stress during the pandemic, particularly due to isolation and prolonged separation from support systems (Fanari, Wright, and Foerster, 2021). Ghizlene's narrative thus reflects a dual process: emotional vulnerability alongside the gradual emergence of resilience, illustrating how the pandemic reshaped both her emotional experience and her sense of self.

Yasmine's narrative reveals a different, yet related, pattern of disruption during the pandemic, one characterised less by separation alone and more by cumulative psychological overload. Describing the period shaped by COVID-19, she explained:

“Unfortunately during those two years COVID happened, so it kind of turned everyone's life upside down... I would describe a very strange two years, where I struggled on so many levels, mentally, academically, personally, to adapt with everything that was happening and all the changes. And then I kind of felt the need to go back home as soon as I could”.

Unlike Ghizlene's account, which centres primarily on emotional distance from family, Yasmine's narrative highlights how multiple domains of her life became entangled during the pandemic. Her reference to struggling "*on so many levels*" suggests that academic progress, mental health, and personal stability could no longer be managed separately. Instead, these pressures accumulated, producing a sense of sustained stress rather than a single identifiable challenge.

From this perspective, Yasmine's return appears less as a planned or anticipated transition and more as a response to emotional and psychological saturation. Her expressed "*need to go back home as soon as I could*" reflects a search for containment and stability in the face of prolonged

uncertainty, rather than a readiness for re-entry. This experience resonates with Adler's (1981) observation that re-entry is often precipitated by emotional exhaustion rather than preparedness, particularly when individuals are navigating unresolved stressors. Yasmine's account illustrates how COVID-19 transformed re-entry into a coping response, where returning home functioned as a strategy for regaining equilibrium rather than the culmination of a completed overseas experience.

Mohamed's account highlights a further psychological consequence of the pandemic. His return to Algeria for a short family visit coincided with the outbreak of COVID-19, leaving him unable to return to the UK to complete the final stages of his academic journey:

“The thing which stopped me from going back to the UK was COVID-19, and then I was very patient, waiting for COVID to end, so I could go back to England. Finish with all the final procedures... attending the graduation ceremony, bringing the books back...”

Mohamed's reference to “*waiting*” captures the frustration of a disrupted timeline. His narrative suggests that re-entry occurred before he felt psychologically prepared. Attending graduation ceremony, completing procedures, returning books carry symbolic weight. These moments represented closure, recognition, and the formal completion of an important transition. Their absence left his return feeling incomplete, contributing to a persistent sense of interruption between the UK and Algeria.

Unlike participants who returned with a clearer sense of completion, Mohamed's re-entry was shaped by disruption and unfinished transitions. This experience aligns with Sussman's (2002) observation that sudden interruptions to expected routines can deepen re-entry difficulties, particularly when individuals are unable to bring psychological and symbolic closure to their time abroad. The inability to complete these final stages also mirrors Adler's (1981) argument that re-entry distress is often linked to emotional exhaustion and unresolved transitions rather than readiness to return.

Mohamed's experience further reflects research on pandemic-related mobility disruption, which shows that prolonged uncertainty and disrupted timelines heightened emotional stress and complicated adjustment processes (Zhang, Zeng, and Zhang, 2022). For Mohamed, returning without completing these final academic and institutional rituals meant that re-adaptation involved not only reconnecting with home but also managing a persistent sense of incompleteness. His account illustrates how COVID-19 transformed re-entry into a fragmented

process, where return occurred in the absence of closure, complicating both emotional adjustment and identity reorientation.

Such accounts illustrate how COVID-19 magnified the emotional challenges of transitioning home. It disrupted participants' sense of continuity, left them without the opportunity to fully celebrate their academic achievements, and forced them to navigate re-entry without the psychological closure they might otherwise have had. As Gaw (2000) argues, re-entry is not merely a physical return but an emotional and psychological process that requires resolving one's past experiences. For Mohamed, the pandemic created an additional obstacle to this resolution, leaving an emotional imprint that shaped his broader experience of re-adaptation. Participants also described the compounded challenges of navigating quarantine and adapting to a rapidly changing environment.

Across their accounts, Ghizlene's, Yasmine's, and Mohamed's narratives demonstrate how the pandemic reshaped re-entry trajectories in distinct yet interconnected ways. Ghizlene's experience foregrounds endurance and the retrospective recognition of resilience, as prolonged separation prompted a re-evaluation of her emotional capacity and independence. In contrast, Yasmine's account highlights cumulative psychological overload, where academic, personal, and emotional pressures converged, transforming re-entry into a search for stability rather than a planned transition. Mohamed's narrative introduces a further dimension, illustrating how pandemic disruptions produced a sense of suspended closure, where the inability to complete expected academic rituals prolonged feelings of incompleteness and delayed emotional transition. Together, these accounts show that COVID-19 did not simply delay or complicate return but fundamentally reshaped how re-entry was experienced, negotiated, and emotionally processed. Rather than a linear movement from host to home context, return became entangled with uncertainty, interruption, and ongoing adjustment, reinforcing the complex and contextually mediated nature of re-entry experiences.

Conclusion

In this chapter, I have examined the personal reintegration experiences of UK-based Algerian doctoral graduates, tracing how return was lived as both a deeply transformative and emotionally complex process. Participants' narratives revealed that re-entry was not a simple return to familiarity, but a negotiation between who they had become abroad and the cultural, familial, and social expectations that awaited them in Algeria. Feelings of reverse culture shock, disconnection, and frustration emerged not merely as adjustment difficulties, but as indicators of identity shifts that were no longer fully aligned with previously taken-for-granted norms.

Across accounts, I observed that personal growth acquired abroad intensified, rather than eased, the challenges of return. Expanded perspectives, critical awareness, and intercultural competence sometimes amplified participants' sense of difference within their home environments. Yet these same developments also functioned as internal resources. Participants drew upon increased self-confidence, reflexivity, and emotional maturity to renegotiate their roles within families, communities, and wider social contexts. Reintegration, therefore, unfolded as a dynamic process of identity reconstruction rather than restoration.

A cross-case reading suggests that the findings highlight the dual nature of personal reintegration: it was marked by emotional stress and cultural tension, but also by renewed purpose and self-definition. Return did not signal regression; instead, it required participants to actively integrate transformed aspects of self into environments that were not always immediately receptive. This underscores the importance of recognising reintegration as an ongoing psychosocial process that permits structured support, particularly for scholars returning from long-term international study.

This chapter contributes to existing scholarship on reverse culture shock by demonstrating that re-entry for UK-based Algerian doctoral returnees was not confined to national cultural adjustment, but unfolded across layered sites of belonging, including family relationships, everyday routines, and social expectations. The findings further show that culture operated not as a fixed national category, but as lived, relational, and context-dependent, becoming most visible when previously taken-for-granted practices felt unfamiliar. In doing so, this study reconceptualises reverse culture shock in postcolonial contexts, highlighting how return involves ongoing negotiation of belonging rather than simple cultural readjustment.

The following chapter turns to the professional dimensions of this journey. Building on the personal transformations explored here, it examines how participants navigated the academic and institutional landscape in Algeria, the structural barriers they encountered, and the ways in which their internationally shaped identities influenced their professional practices and aspirations.

Chapter Six

Findings and Discussion: Professional Reintegration

Introduction

This chapter explores the professional reintegration experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees as they re-enter academic roles within Algerian universities. Building on the previous findings chapter, which examined the personal, emotional, and cultural dimensions of return, this chapter shifts attention to participants' professional worlds and workplace encounters. As illustrated in chapter five, experiences of identity negotiation, emotional adjustment, and resilience do not end upon return; rather, they continue to shape how returnees interpret, navigate, and respond to professional demands.

Drawing on IPA and in-depth online interviews with eighteen participants, in this chapter I examine how returnees make sense of their professional re-entry in contexts that often differ markedly from the academic environments in which they were trained. Participants' accounts reveal both shared and divergent experiences, shaped by institutional cultures, collegial relationships, and structural conditions within Algerian higher education.

Across the findings, participants described difficulties adapting to local academic norms, including tensions with colleagues, heavy teaching workloads, limited institutional support, and persistent shortages of resources. Many also reflected on challenges related to professionalism and workplace practices, where differences in work ethics, communication styles, and administrative processes complicated reintegration. At the same time, returnees' international academic experiences had reshaped their professional identities, expectations, and values, sometimes bringing them into tension with local norms and practices.

In this chapter, I further highlight how participants attempted to negotiate these challenges through a range of strategies, including recalibrating expectations, selectively engaging with colleagues, focusing on teaching or research priorities, and drawing on international academic networks for support. By unpacking these experiences thematically, I illuminate the complex interplay between returnees' aspirations and the structural and cultural constraints of their professional environments, offering insight into the lived realities of professional reintegration after doctoral mobility.

GET 1: Academic Reintegration and Adaptation

This group experiential theme captures participants' lived experiences of re-entering academic workplaces following doctoral study in the UK. In this study, academic reintegration is understood not simply as resuming professional roles, but as an interpretative and relational process through which returnees negotiate professional identity, institutional expectations, and collegial relationships shaped by their international academic socialisation. This understanding of academic reintegration aligns with the work of (Jung, Lee, and Moral, 2013; Pham and Saito, 2020; Karakas, 2020). This theme therefore focuses on how participants encountered local academic norms, workplace cultures, and professional practices upon return, and how these encounters often rendered familiar academic environments sites of tension, frustration, or re-evaluation.

The accounts presented here illuminate academic reintegration as a layered and ongoing process, shaped by mismatches between participants' internationally informed expectations of academia and the realities of local institutional structures. Across narratives, returnees described navigating resistance to innovation, limited collaboration, heavy workloads, and perceptions of being "*different*" or "*too ambitious*," all of which influenced their sense of professional belonging and legitimacy within their institutions (Altbach, 2014; Alandejani, 2013; Kuzhabekova, Sparks and Temerbayeva, 2019; Alsulami, 2021). So far, academic reintegration has been framed as a negotiated and relational experience; the first subtheme examines how participants made sense of academic disconnect and tension in their interactions with colleagues.

Subtheme 1: Academic Disconnect and Tension with Colleagues

In this subtheme, participants are showing me how professional reintegration was experienced through everyday academic interactions with colleagues, where differences in pedagogical values, work cultures, and expectations became particularly visible. What emerges across these accounts is not simply disagreement over methods, but a deeper sense of misalignment between internationally shaped academic identities and locally entrenched norms. Similar to the re-entry disruptions discussed in the previous chapter, these professional encounters rendered familiar academic environments unfamiliar, prompting participants to reassess their roles, legitimacy, and sense of belonging within their institutions.

Hiba's account illustrates how this disconnect emerged through everyday academic interactions. Reflecting on her early return, she stated:

"I expected that, at least I find some active academics, some people who are very active in research, some academics who take initiatives, some academics who

share up some discussions. That wasn't the case. I was very very disappointed, and even when you talk to them about the academic line, what about training? What about conferences? What about seminars? What about talks? What about workshops? They will be like (surprised look) Hmm, Is that because you are new, you came from abroad that you have those ideas? But believe me, if you, when you spend one or 2 or 3 years here, you will stop being that ambitious”

Hiba’s account highlights a profound disconnect that emerges from a gap between her expectations of an active, collaborative academic environment and the indifference she encountered upon returning to Algeria. Hiba’s repeated references to “*active academics* and *taking initiatives*” reveal an internalised understanding of academia as collaborative and dynamic, an understanding shaped by her doctoral experience abroad. The emphasis on “*very very disappointed*” conveys the emotional intensity of this unmet expectation, suggesting that the absence of such practices was experienced not merely as organisational difference, but as a personal and professional let-down. The rhetorical question posed by her colleagues “*because you are new, you came from abroad*” subtly reframes her academic ambition as foreign and temporary. This positioning undermines her professional legitimacy and shows that innovation is tolerated only as a transitional phase rather than a valued contribution.

Such experiences resonate with Altbach’s (2014) argument that returning scholars often face resistance when attempting to introduce practices that diverge from established academic cultures. Similarly, Alandejani (2013) notes that returnees’ internationally shaped professional norms may be interpreted as threatening or inappropriate within local institutional contexts, leading to marginalisation rather than integration.

While Hiba’s account illustrates how internationally shaped academic expectations may be questioned or resisted within local institutional contexts, similar tensions emerge in Amine’s narrative through a different experiential pathway, where international training becomes the basis for intensified institutional demands rather than marginalisation. He stated:

“They give me so many modules to teach, they give me so many groups. I don't have time for writing articles, I mean my social life is getting smaller, and the circles getting tricked. And because of the academic world, I'm in, I'm just overwhelmed with the number of students I teach and the lessons you have to prepare when you have 4 different modules, so much I swear that's too much”.

Amine intensely describes the overwhelming academic and social pressures he faces upon re-entering the Algerian academic environment. His words highlight a substantial increase in workload, as his institution places an extremely high teaching burden on him, likely as a result of his international qualifications. This situation can be interpreted as reflecting an implicit

expectation that his international qualifications positioned him as particularly capable of absorbing heavy teaching demands. His description of being given “*so many modules*” and feeling “*overwhelmed*” suggests that institutional expectations may have been shaped by assumptions about the added capacity associated with studying abroad.

Similar dynamics have been identified in returnee research. Black, Gregersen, and Mendenhall (1992), note that internationally experienced professionals are often assigned intensified responsibilities upon return, as organisations presume, they possess superior adaptability and productivity, which can create significant adjustment strain. Likewise, Young (2014) observes that highly qualified returnees may be expected to compensate for institutional limitations or resource gaps, leading to increased workload pressures and emotional exhaustion. Amine’s account echoes these patterns, particularly in the way his international credentials appear to legitimise heavier demands rather than facilitate smoother professional integration.

His language becomes even more expressive with the phrase “*I swear that’s too much,*” which underscores his frustration and exhaustion. Unlike Hiba, whose ambition was questioned, Amine’s international training appears to have justified intensified expectations, positioning him as someone who should be able to absorb institutional shortcomings.

While Amine’s account reveals the intense workload pressures and high expectations placed on returnees, Hanaa’s narrative highlights a further dimension of academic disconnect, centred on institutional infrastructure and scholarly culture. She described her experience as follows:

“I told you about the fact that being... I was very motivated, and others didn’t have the same motivation the same mindset or the same ideas that I have for different projects. When I went back home, I discovered that they didn’t even have a research lab so that was a shock... I tried to work on an international cooperation and an international conference, but... I didn’t get a reply regarding any of them... Academically speaking, they are not as up to date with everything that is going on in academia as I thought they would, and that would raise... a lot of challenging discussions.”

In Hanaa’s reflection, she provides insight into the disconnect and professional isolation she feels as she re-enters the academic landscape in Algeria. Her words reveal an initial shock and disappointment upon discovering that the academic environment back home lacks the essential structures she had come to expect, such as a research lab, which she identifies as a basic resource for academic work. This discovery disrupts her initial enthusiasm, as she realises that the academic infrastructure and mindset at her institution do not align with her ambitions and the practices she encountered abroad.

Hanaa's attempt to initiate international collaborations and organise a conference further reflects her motivation to bring new academic practices into her workplace. However, the lack of response to her proposals suggests passive resistance from her colleagues and institution, reinforcing her sense of isolation. This experience reflects her realisation that her colleagues neither share her commitment to academic innovation nor engage with her level of motivation. Her laughter when recalling the absence of a research lab could be seen as a coping mechanism, acknowledging the stark reality of her situation while masking her disappointment.

Furthermore, Hanaa's mention of "*challenging discussions*" around methodology points to the gaps in academic knowledge she perceives between herself and her colleagues. These discussions, while not explicitly conflicts, become difficult as her colleagues are not as "*up to date*" on current academic developments. This phrase suggests a subtle frustration and disillusionment as Hanaa finds herself constantly needing to bridge the gap between her advanced knowledge and the practices of her local peers. Hanaa's narrative illustrates her process of making sense of an environment that feels academically stagnant compared to the active, resource-rich setting she experienced abroad. This gap leaves her in a complex negotiation between maintaining her professional standards and adjusting her expectations to align with a system that resists both her methodologies and her drive for academic advancement. This pattern resonates with Alsulami's (2021) findings, which suggest that institutional resistance to returning academics often emerges not through overt confrontation but through subtle forms of disengagement, delayed responses, or lack of institutional support. Similar to Hanaa's experience, participants in Alsulami's study described proposing new initiatives or collaborative practices that were met with silence or minimal engagement, creating feelings of professional isolation and questioning the feasibility of innovation within existing structures. In this sense, Hanaa's experience illustrates how resistance may operate indirectly, shaping reintegration through relational distance and organisational indifference rather than explicit rejection.

Following Hiba, Amine, and Hanaa's, narrative of infrastructural and academic resistance, Ghizlene's experience illustrates how sustained resistance can become deeply personal over time. She reflected:

“When I tried to apply new teaching approaches, like ones I'd learned in workshops abroad, some colleagues were openly dismissive. I remember one saying, ‘These methods might work over there, but our students aren't ready for this.’ I kept trying, but it was like hitting a wall. Over time, I realized they didn't just doubt the method; they doubted me as if I was the problem”

Ghizlene reflects on the personal impact of the resistance she faced. Her colleagues' ill-informed essentialist statement that "*our students aren't ready for this*" suggests a deep-rooted assumption that Algerian students would not benefit from or adapt to innovative teaching approaches, which reinforces a conservative outlook on education. Ghizlene's use of the metaphor "*like hitting a wall*" captures her frustration and highlights the emotional toll of this continuous dismissal, as her attempts to introduce new practices were repeatedly undermined. The shift from questioning the methods to doubting Ghizlene herself intensifies her sense of isolation, as the skepticism extends beyond her ideas to her capabilities as an educator. This form of resistance can be understood as a protective response to perceived disruption, where innovation is reframed as inappropriate or premature rather than valuable. Piko-Sallie (2018) notes that returnees who attempt to introduce pedagogical change are often positioned as *misaligned* with local academic cultures, particularly when their practices challenge established routines or hierarchies. In Ghizlene's case, the shift from questioning the new method to questioning *her* professional competence suggests that resistance operated not only at an institutional level but also at an interpersonal and identity level, intensifying her sense of exclusion.

Whereas Ghizlene's experience highlights the struggles of reintegrating within an environment resistant to new ideas and lacking essential academic resources, Mohamed's narrative provides a contrasting perspective. Unlike Hanaa's account, discussed above, who encounters resistance and frustration due to infrastructural and attitudinal limitations, Mohamed describes a supportive, obstacle-free environment where he feels unhindered in his teaching and professional activities:

"I am absolutely happy. nothing is challenging me, neither from the administration nor from the deans... I'm doing my work as properly as possible, without any obstacles during my teaching".

Mohamed's words reflect a rare sense of contentment and professional ease. Mohamed's repeated emphasis on "*nothing is challenging me*" and "*without any obstacles*" conveys a sense of ease and stability. The affective tone of "*absolutely happy*" and experiencing "*without any obstacle*" indicates a harmonious alignment between his expectations and the realities of his local academic environment. The absence of administrative barriers and conflict with colleagues allows him to carry out his teaching duties without the stress or frustration that others, like Hanaa's experience. Mohamed's account suggests a successful reconciliation of his professional identity with his work environment, illustrating how a supportive and well-aligned academic context can foster satisfaction and integration for returning scholars.

Mohamed's experience aligns with Richardson and McKenna (2002), Chen and Li (2019), and Geeraert, Ward and Hanel (2022), who emphasise that re-entry adjustment is shaped by the degree of contextual fit between returnees' expectations and their institutional environments. In contrast to participants who encountered misalignment or resistance, Mohamed's narrative reflects a sense of professional congruence, where organisational conditions enabled continuity rather than disruption. Similar to the smoother transitions described in these studies, his experience suggests that when institutional structures and interpersonal dynamics support returnees' professional positioning, reintegration may be experienced as stabilising rather than challenging. Mohamed's account therefore functions as a contrast case, illustrating that academic tension is not inevitable but contingent upon situational and relational factors within the workplace.

Conversely, Hanaa's reflection on collaboration captures the affective weight of institutional silence:

“Back in the UK, collaboration was almost second nature we'd work together on projects, discuss findings, share feedback. Here, though, I felt like every attempt to collaborate was met with silence. I even approached a colleague with a research proposal, and he just shrugged it off, saying, 'I prefer working alone; collaboration just complicates things here.' It's like, what's the point of my being here if we can't bring new ideas together?”

Hanaa's comparison between collaboration being *almost second nature* in the UK and being “*met with silence*” upon return reveals more than a difference in working styles; it reflects a profound disruption to her sense of professional belonging. The repeated emphasis on “*silence*” and the colleague's dismissal of collaboration as something that “*complicates things*” positions Hanaa at the margins of the academic community, where her preferred ways of working are neither recognised nor valued. From this perspective, collaboration functions not merely as a practice, but as a marker of professional identity. Drawing on Wenger's (1998) notion of communities of practice, Hanaa's exclusion from collaborative engagement can be understood as a form of peripheral positioning, in which limited participation restricts both her influence and her sense of legitimacy within the academic space.

This marginalisation has clear implications for how Hanaa understands herself within the institution. Her question, *what's the point of my being here*, signals a loss of professional meaning and purpose, suggesting that reintegration is experienced as an identity struggle rather than a technical adjustment. In line with Sussman's (2002) cultural identity model, Hanaa's account illustrates how professional identities shaped and validated abroad can become

destabilised upon return, as familiar markers of competence and contribution fail to translate into recognition in the home context.

The colleague's reported response "*I prefer working alone; collaboration just complicates things here*" further crystallises the cultural misalignment Hanaa encounters. The framing of collaboration as something that "*complicates*" suggests an academic environment oriented toward risk avoidance, individual autonomy, or bureaucratic containment rather than intellectual exchange. For Hanaa, this moment appears to confirm that collaboration is not merely unsupported but ideologically devalued, reinforcing her perception that her academic values are out of place.

These dynamics reveal how resistance to collaboration does not only constrain professional practice but also unsettles returnees' professional identities. As Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva (2019) note, the lack of a collaborative ethos in certain academic environments creates silos, further isolating returnees and diminishing their ability to reintegrate effectively. Hanaa's experience reflects a common internal conflict faced by many returnees where the aspiration to introduce innovative ideas is continually inhibited by the resistance or apathy of their peers.

While Hanaa's and Ghizlene's accounts highlight resistance expressed through silence, non-engagement, and the dismissal of new ideas, Manel's reflections highlight the interpersonal challenges she faced during her reintegration into the academic environment. She shares:

"To be honest, for teachers, they felt fear, they felt threatened by my existence. So they like, although I was like, so basically, I'm the least paid, the least... I have this status, but they still fear you".

Manel's account introduces a more interpersonal and affective dimension of academic resistance, where reintegration tensions are experienced not only through structural constraints or professional disagreement, but through perceived threat and insecurity within collegial relationships. Her description of colleagues feeling "*threatened*" by her presence reflects the power dynamics and resistance that often accompany the return of individuals with international experience. The repetition of "*they still fear you*" is particularly remarkable. It conveys an enduring emotional atmosphere rather than a one-off interaction, indicating that this sense of threat was sustained and embedded in everyday professional encounters. Importantly, this perceived fear persists despite Manel's marginal institutional position. Her emphasis on being "*the least paid*" and holding a low-status role complicates conventional assumptions about

power. Rather than authority producing threat, it is her international trajectory and embodied difference that appears destabilising to existing hierarchies.

Manel's narrative reveals how returnees may occupy an ambiguous positionality: formally subordinate, yet symbolically powerful. Her presence appears to unsettle colleagues by implicitly challenging established academic identities and norms, even when she lacks decision-making power. This reflects Wenger's (1998) notion of communities of practice, where newcomers or returnees re-entering a familiar community with transformed identities can be perceived as disruptive when their trajectories no longer align with dominant meanings and practices.

Manel's experience also reflects a deeper process of identity negotiation. While she has returned institutionally, her professional identity remains shaped by international academic norms, positioning her simultaneously as insider and outsider. In line with Sussman's (2002) cultural identity model, which highlights the interpersonal challenges returnees often face as their enhanced skills or global perspectives are viewed as disruptive to established hierarchies. This alignment also can be read in Alanedjani's (2013) which stresses that returnees frequently encounter resistance in environments where their qualifications or experiences are perceived as threatening rather than enriching.

Manel's narrative further illustrates how such dynamics can create a sense of alienation for returnees, who may find themselves navigating not only structural challenges but also interpersonal barriers to integration. Her experience highlights a critical aspect of academic reintegration: the tension between individual aspirations and the collective dynamics of academic workplaces, which are often shaped by embedded norms and resistance to change.

Taken together, the accounts of Hiba, Amine, Hanaa, Ghizlene, and Manel illustrate that academic reintegration was frequently experienced through various forms of resistance within local academic environments. While Hiba and Ghizlene encountered overt dismissal of their ideas and pedagogical approaches, Hanaa described resistance through silence, non-response, and the absence of collaborative engagement. Amine's experience highlights how excessive teaching workloads functioned as a structural constraint that limited his academic agency, while Manel's account reveals how resistance could become personalised, with her international background perceived as a symbolic threat rather than a resource.

Across these narratives, academic resistance was not experienced as a single or uniform barrier, but as a layered phenomenon operating at structural, cultural, and interpersonal levels. What connects these experiences is a recurring challenge to participants' professional legitimacy and

sense of belonging, where ambition was subtly discouraged, innovation was framed as impractical, and international experience was reinterpreted as disruption rather than value. Beyond organisational resistance alone, these tensions also reflect deeper clashes between internationally shaped professional identities and locally embedded understandings of academic practice. Participants returned with expectations grounded in collaborative research cultures, initiative, and professional reflexivity, which did not always align with institutional norms that prioritised stability, hierarchical relationships, or teaching-heavy roles.

This pattern resonates with Chen and Li (2019) and Chen and Du (2023) observation that the absence of a collaborative academic ethos can isolate returnees and constrain their reintegration. From an identity perspective, these accounts also align with Wenger's (1998) notion of misalignment between individual trajectories and community practices, in which returnees find themselves positioned at the margins of academic communities despite formal inclusion. From this standpoint, reintegration can be understood as a process of renegotiating membership and legitimacy within academic communities whose shared meanings remained relatively stable while participants' professional identities had transformed through international doctoral socialisation. This dynamic may also be interpreted as a form of professional reverse culture shock operating at the level of workplace culture, where differences in expectations around collaboration, innovation, and academic engagement generated identity-level tensions rather than purely organisational challenges.

At the same time, variation across accounts most notably Mohamed's contrasting experience of support and ease highlights that academic reintegration is contextually contingent rather than inevitable. These differences suggest that reintegration outcomes are shaped by departmental cultures, collegial norms, and institutional leadership rather than by returnee characteristics alone. Mohamed's smoother experience therefore illustrates that identity tensions emerge primarily where there is misalignment between professional self-concept and institutional expectations, reinforcing the interpretation of reintegration as an ongoing negotiation of professional legitimacy rather than a uniform adjustment process.

These tensions form the foundation for the next subtheme, which examines how participants responded to such challenges by recalibrating their expectations, professional identities and aspirations. Subtheme 2, "Managing Expectations and Academic Realities", explores how returnees negotiated the gap between their initial hopes for academic reform and the constraints of everyday institutional practice, and how this process reshaped their professional positioning over time.

Subtheme 2: Managing Expectations and Academic Realities

In this subtheme, participants are showing me how they made sense of the gap between their aspirations for institutional reform and the realities of working within the Algerian higher education system. Through their accounts, returnees are describing how expectations shaped during international doctoral study came into tension with rigid organisational structures, limited institutional support, and embedded academic cultures upon return. What I can see across these narratives is that managing expectations was not a one-off adjustment, but an ongoing and emotionally charged process through which participants negotiated what felt possible, sustainable, and meaningful within their professional roles. Rather than signalling disengagement, the recalibration of expectations appears to function as a way of preserving professional agency, wellbeing, and a coherent sense of self within constraining institutional contexts.

Hanaa's narrative reveals how managing expectations became a deliberate and emotionally charged strategy for coping with institutional resistance. In the extract below, she reflects on a moment of withdrawal from collective academic engagement towards a more self-directed professional focus:

“I just decided to give up and like, why am I doing this? If no one is interested in, is supported, then why am I bothering? I'm just gonna focus on myself. I'm gonna focus on my publications. I'm gonna focus on my intellectual development. And that's it.”

Hanaa's repeated use of decisive and self-referential language “*I just decided,*” “*I'm just gonna focus on myself*” suggests a turning point in how she positions herself within her professional environment. Rather than signalling apathy, this shift can be understood as a protective reorientation in response to persistent lack of institutional support. Her rhetorical questioning (“*why am I bothering?*”) conveys emotional exhaustion and disappointment, indicating that earlier efforts to contribute collectively were experienced as unrewarded or ignored. The movement from “*why am I doing this?*” to a narrowed focus on publications and intellectual development reflects a recalibration of professional goals, where agency is preserved by investing in domains that remain within her control.

What stands out here is that expectation management is not framed as failure, but as an adaptive response to structural constraints. Hanaa appears to be negotiating a boundary between aspiration and sustainability, choosing to preserve her professional identity by retreating from institutional reform rather than continuing to expend emotional labour in an unreceptive environment.

However, Hanaa’s narrative takes a positive turn later in her account when she reflects on how changes in academic staff introduced a more collaborative and supportive environment:

“This year, though, the academic staff changed, people are very young, people do want to work, and people are more welcoming of my initiatives. So that's why I'm working a little bit more”.

Here, the shift in tone is notable. The conditional phrasing “*this year, though*” signals a contextual change rather than a personal transformation, suggesting that motivation and engagement are contingent upon relational and institutional conditions. The repetition of “*people*” foregrounds the social dimension of professional reintegration, indicating that openness from colleagues functions as a catalyst for renewed involvement. This suggests that Hanaa’s earlier withdrawal was less about disengagement from collaboration itself and more about protecting her professional energy in an environment where collaborative practices were largely unavailable.

Hanaa’s account illustrates how managing expectations operates as a dynamic and relational process. Her experience shows that professional reintegration is shaped not only by individual resilience, but by the extent to which institutional environments signal recognition, reciprocity, and possibility. Similar patterns have been observed among internationally trained academics who return to rigid or under-resourced systems, where misalignment between expectations and institutional realities compels returnees to renegotiate their roles and ambitions (Khanal and Gaule, 2019; Karakas, 2020). In this sense, Hanaa’s experience resonates with wider scholarship showing that re-entry trajectories are shaped not only by individual resilience, but by the extent to which organisational environments provide affirmation, reciprocity, and scope for professional contribution (Geeraert, Ward, and Hanel, 2022).

Her earlier frustration with the lack of collaboration and academic infrastructure further reflects what Gu and Schweisfurth (2015) describe as a misalignment of pedagogical and professional norms, where practices internalised abroad cannot be meaningfully enacted upon return. Likewise, studies of academic returnees in Vietnam highlight how rigid workplace cultures and limited institutional openness can restrict innovation and contribute to professional disillusionment (Pham and Saito, 2020).

Maya’s narrative draws attention to a more practical, yet equally disorienting, dimension of professional reintegration. Maya reflects on this lack of support, stating:

“Even basic things I didn’t know how many hours teachers taught. So I actually had some wrong information. And no one corrected me.”

Maya's account shows how academic reintegration was experienced through everyday uncertainty and the emotional labour of navigating an unfamiliar institutional system without guidance. This absence of guidance left her feeling isolated, forcing her to independently seek out information and adapt to her role. The struggle to navigate such a system points to a lack of structured onboarding processes, which could otherwise ease the transition and provide a clearer understanding of institutional expectations. The phrase "*even basic things*" signals her surprise and disbelief, suggesting that she did not anticipate needing support for what she assumed would be routine professional information. This moment reveals how reintegration disrupted her sense of professional competence, positioning her not as an experienced academic returnee, but as someone left to figure things out alone.

Her admission that she had "*wrong information*" and that "*no one corrected me*" points to a silent institutional environment in which mistakes are neither anticipated nor supported. The absence of correction is particularly telling; it suggests not only a lack of formal mentorship but also a lack of informal collegial care. Rather than being guided into the institutional culture, Maya was required to self-navigate, heightening feelings of isolation and professional vulnerability. In this sense, her experience reflects a subtle yet impactful form of exclusion, where support is absent not through overt resistance, but through institutional neglect.

Similarly, Ghizlene's account highlights a deeper tension between her aspirations to drive curricular reform and the resistance she encountered within her institution. Initially optimistic about contributing to updates in the teaching syllabus, she explains,

"I thought that they might need me to update a little bit of the teacher syllabus, but the opposite has happened because they believe that this syllabus they use, doesn't need some shifts or some editions. Or edits, and that was the first clash, and since then I have stopped thinking of making a change, a, in a collective way, I focus on improving myself, improving my teaching practice and looking at the progress of my students, the students in my class."

Ghizlene's account shows how managing expectations unfolded as a gradual process of reorientation following an early moment of rupture. Her initial belief that her expertise would be welcomed "*they might need me to update a little bit of the teacher syllabus*" reveals an assumption of reciprocity, where international training would translate into institutional trust and openness. The phrase "*the opposite has happened*" marks a clear turning point, signalling not only disappointment but a fundamental misalignment between her expectations and the academic authority embedded within the institution.

What appears particularly significant is Ghizlene's identification of this moment as "*the first clash*." This wording suggests that the resistance she encountered was experienced as relational rather than procedural, positioning her professional identity in tension with an established pedagogical order. The institution's insistence that the syllabus "*doesn't need some shifts or some edits*" can be read as a rejection of change itself, but also as a dismissal of Ghizlene's legitimacy as a contributor to curricular knowledge. Similar dynamics have been observed among returnee academics whose pedagogical norms, shaped by international exposure, conflict with rigid local frameworks (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015; Pham and Saito, 2020; Alsulami, 2021).

In response, Ghizlene describes a decisive withdrawal from collective engagement "*since then, I have stopped thinking of making a change in a collective way*." This shift does not suggest disengagement from teaching, but rather a strategic narrowing of professional agency. By redirecting her focus towards "*improving myself, improving my teaching practice and looking at the progress of my students*," she appears to reclaim a sense of control and coherence within spaces that remain accessible to her. This movement reflects a form of identity negotiation, where professional commitment is preserved through individual practice rather than institutional reform (Wenger, 1998; Sussman, 2002; Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015).

Ghizlene's experience illustrates how expectation management is not simply about lowering ambitions, but about re-locating where meaningful professional action is possible. Her narrative resonates with research showing that returnees often recalibrate aspirations when confronted with inflexible academic cultures, choosing adaptive strategies that protect professional integrity while minimising emotional exhaustion (Khanal and Gaule, 2019; Karakas, 2020). In this sense, Ghizlene is showing me how professional reintegration involves ongoing negotiation between aspiration, recognition, and the structural limits of the local academic environment.

In contrast to Ghizlene's gradual recalibration of expectations, Manel's narrative reflects a more abrupt and emotionally charged encounter with the realities of academic life upon return. She shares:

"I have very high expectations in terms of everything—in terms of the system, in terms of the way people think sometimes—because I expected educated people with a higher degree. I expected a certain way of behaving from both, like teachers and students... I was slapped into the face... the idea was that I expected a certain level of education, a certain level of thinking, because we are in 2023. But I felt like my young students, who were born in the year 2000... they still have a mentality of someone who lived in 1985 or 1980. They still think the old way, in

the old fashion. They still believe that marks are their way of getting... they just want a degree, that's all what they think about".

Manel's narrative reflects the professional disillusionment that many returnees experience when their expectations, shaped by international exposure, clash with the realities of their home country's academic and professional systems. Her expression of feeling "*slapped into the face*" vividly captures her emotional reaction to the gap between her anticipated professional environment and the outdated practices she encountered.

Her critique of the focus on grades over intellectual growth among students highlights a broader systemic issue within the educational culture. This disconnect aligns with Almuarik (2019) findings that returnees often face cultural and professional misalignment, leading to frustration and a sense of alienation.

Furthermore, Manel's narrative illustrates the challenges of working within a system resistant to change. Her reference to students' "*mentality of someone who lived in 1985 or 1980*" underscores the generational and cultural gap she perceives, further amplifying her sense of disconnection. This critique also reflects her aspiration for a modernised and progressive academic environment, which she felt was not being met.

Manel's critique of students' focus on "*marks*" rather than learning further reveals a clash between instrumental and developmental understandings of education. Her frustration reflects an internalised commitment to critical thinking and intellectual growth, values often reinforced through international academic socialisation. Research suggests that such misalignments frequently lead returnees to experience frustration, alienation, and a questioning of professional purpose when institutional cultures prioritise credentialism over learning (Karakas, 2020; Khanal and Gaule, 2019).

Despite her disillusionment, Manel's narrative does not suggest withdrawal from teaching. Instead, her critique implies a continued investment in educational ideals, even as she recognises the constraints of the system. This tension reflects a form of negotiated professional identity, where commitment to pedagogical values persists despite limited structural support (Wenger, 1998; Sussman, 2002). In this way, Manel's experience shows how managing expectations involves holding onto professional principles while simultaneously confronting the emotional costs of working within environments resistant to change.

Together, these accounts illustrate that managing expectations was a dynamic and relational process rather than a linear adjustment. Participants such as Hanaa and Ghizlene described a

gradual recalibration of their professional aspirations, shifting from collective ambitions for reform towards more individualised strategies as a way of sustaining motivation within constraining institutional environments. Maya's experience further shows how unmet expectations were intensified by the absence of guidance and mentorship, rendering adaptation a largely solitary endeavour. In contrast, Manel articulated expectation misalignment as a deeply affective rupture, where professional values shaped through international exposure collided sharply with what she experienced as outdated pedagogical norms and limited intellectual engagement.

Across these narratives, expectation management emerged as a form of ongoing identity negotiation rather than resignation. Participants were not abandoning their professional values; instead, they were renegotiating *how* and *where* these values could be enacted within rigid organisational structures. This supports scholarship on return migration and professional identity, which emphasises that reintegration is shaped by institutional recognition, peer dynamics, and the perceived scope for meaningful action (Macklin and Bridges, 2012; Mackay, 2017; Khanal and Gaule, 2019; Karakas, 2020). Similar patterns have been observed among returnees in other Global South contexts, where misalignment between internationally acquired practices and local academic cultures constrains reform-oriented engagement (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015; Pham and Saito, 2020).

While this subtheme has focused on how returnees recalibrated their expectations in response to academic realities, the next GET shifts attention to what happened when participants attempted to act on their internationally informed practices. The following theme therefore examines Innovation and Resistance in Academic Practice, exploring how returnees navigated efforts to implement progressive teaching methods within environments that were often hesitant or resistant to change.

GET 2: Innovation and Resistance in Academic Practice

This group experiential theme captures how Algerian doctoral returnees attempted to translate internationally acquired pedagogical and academic practices in their post- return professional contexts. Innovation here is understood not simply as the introduction of new techniques, but as a relational and identity-laden process shaped by institutional norms, collegial responses, and perceptions of legitimacy. Participants' accounts reveal that efforts to innovate were often met with resistance rooted in entrenched practices and hierarchical academic cultures. At the same time, these accounts show how returnees navigated such resistance through persistence, adaptation, selective withdrawal, and reliance on alternative support structures. Together, the

narratives illuminate innovation as a contested practice, where professional integrity and identity are continuously negotiated within constrained institutional environments.

This GET is developed through two subthemes. The first examines how participants encountered and responded to resistance when implementing progressive teaching methods. The second explores how supportive networks and positive workplace relationships enabled returnees to sustain innovation despite local constraints.

Subtheme 1: Overcoming Resistance and Implementing Progressive Teaching Methods

In this subtheme, participants illustrate how attempts to introduce research-informed and student-centred pedagogies frequently generated resistance that extended beyond methodological disagreement. Rather than opposing specific teaching techniques alone, this resistance often challenged participants' professional authority, academic legitimacy, and expectations of their role as returning scholars. As the accounts of Ghizlene and Karim demonstrate, responding to such resistance required ongoing emotional, professional, and ethical negotiation, shaping how participants recalibrated their ambitions, enacted innovation, or constrained their practice within local institutional norms.

Ghizlene's account vividly illustrates this tension as she describes the challenges she encountered when introducing new teaching methods. She recalls,

“At university, there were 2 groups, first, staff used to make some challenging situation for me. Once I wanted to implement some of the teaching approaches I have developed in my research, and that has taken me some time for them to understand how I work.”

She later reflected on how she responded to this resistance:

“I did not back up, I resisted that, and I used the same system. I was convinced that I'm using something that is research-based, not something traditional.”

Ghizlene frames her department as divided into “*two groups*”, which suggests she experienced the workplace not as a unified team but as a socially segmented space where alignment could not be assumed. Her phrase “*challenging situation*” is noticeably vague, which implies that resistance was not always direct or formally stated, but enacted through everyday interactions that nonetheless accumulated as pressure. When she says it took “*some time for them to understand how I work*”, Ghizlene positions her own practice as something requiring translation and justification, as if her professional identity is being treated as unfamiliar or “out of place” within the local culture of teaching. The emotional labour here is subtle but heavy: instead of being evaluated on outcomes, she is negotiating recognition of the *way* she teaches.

This kind of pedagogical misalignment is consistent with work on returnees who attempt to recontextualise internationally shaped norms into institutions where established routines carry more authority than evidence-based innovation (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015; Pham and Saito, 2020). It also echoes the argument that re-entry is highly sensitive to host institutional climates where the same professional competence can be either validated or rendered marginal depending on departmental culture (Geeraert, Ward, and Hanel, 2022).

Her narrative later highlights persistence and resolve. Phrases such as “*I did not back up*” and “*I resisted*” indicate a conscious decision to maintain her approach despite opposition, suggesting that innovation becomes tied to her sense of professional integrity. The reference to continuing with “*the same system*” implies that her response to resistance was not withdrawal but endurance, as she sustained her preferred teaching practices in the face of pressure to conform. What appears to legitimise this persistence is academic rather than interpersonal: by framing her approach as “*research-based*” rather than “*traditional*”, Ghizlene constructs a hierarchy of credibility that anchors her confidence in her doctoral training. In this sense, she is not only defending a pedagogical method but also safeguarding a knowledge identity shaped through international doctoral research.

At the same time, this positioning can be read as double-edged. While invoking *research-based* practice offers Ghizlene internal validation, it may also sharpen relational boundaries between herself and colleagues whose practices are implicitly positioned as *traditional*. This helps illuminate why innovation often provokes resistance, not necessarily because change is rejected, but because it unsettles existing professional identities and hierarchies (Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019; Karakas, 2020). These tensions can therefore be understood not simply as resistance to pedagogical technique, but as a clash between differently constituted professional identities one shaped through international doctoral socialisation and research-oriented norms, and another embedded within locally established academic hierarchies. In this sense, what is being negotiated is not merely method, but legitimacy: whose knowledge counts, under which professional framework, and with what institutional authority. Ghizlene’s experience therefore shows that resistance is not only pedagogical but relational, and that maintaining professional integrity in return contexts often involves navigating the emotional and identity costs of standing apart.

Karim’s narrative, however, shows how repeated resistance can push returnees toward containment and self-silencing rather than overt resistance.

This experience aligns closely with Karim's reflections, which also capture the professional and emotional dilemmas of attempting to introduce progressive ideas into a resistant institutional culture. He shares,

“Each time I tried, I got the same reaction resistance, and sometimes even criticism. At some point, I had to question, ‘Is it worth it? Do I just adjust and conform?’ I started keeping my ideas to myself, just to avoid the constant pushback. It’s sad because I feel like I’m holding back my potential”.

Karim's account illustrates how repeated exposure to institutional resistance can gradually reshape a returnee's professional orientation. His reflection captures a moment of internal conflict, where initial motivation to introduce new methods gives way to doubt and self-questioning. The shift in his language from intention “*I thought I could make a real difference*” to hesitation “*Is it worth it?*” suggests an emerging sense of uselessness, as professional ambition becomes tempered by the emotional cost of sustained opposition. Rather than open confrontation, Karim describes a process of withdrawal, choosing to “*keep his ideas to himself*” as a protective strategy. This withdrawal can be understood not as disengagement, but as a pragmatic response to an environment perceived as unreceptive to change.

Karim's experience reflects a negotiation between his internationally shaped professional identity and the limits imposed by local academic culture. His decision to self-censor indicates an effort to preserve emotional wellbeing and professional stability, even at the expense of innovation. This aligns with research suggesting that returnees may scale back aspirations when institutional resistance undermines the legitimacy of their knowledge or expertise (Pham and Saito, 2020; Karakaş, 2020). Karim's narrative thus reveals how resistance operates not only externally, through overt criticism, but internally, shaping how returnees regulate their aspirations and reposition themselves within constrained professional spaces. Here, the clash of professional identities becomes internalised: rather than openly confronting institutional norms, Karim negotiates his internationally shaped academic self through strategic control, illustrating how identity negotiation may shift from resistance to self-regulation over time.

Together, Ghizlene's and Karim's accounts illustrate that resistance to pedagogical innovation is experienced not only as a structural constraint, but as an ongoing emotional and identity-related negotiation. While both participants encountered similar forms of opposition when attempting to introduce research-informed practices, their responses diverged in meaningful ways. Ghizlene's persistence reflects an effort to preserve professional integrity by anchoring her practice in the legitimacy of research-based knowledge, whereas Karim's withdrawal and self-censorship reveal

the cumulative emotional toll of repeated rejection. These contrasting responses suggest that coping with resistance is not uniform but shaped by how sustainable individuals perceive their agency to be within their institutional contexts.

This variation echoes research showing that returnees often moderate their ambitions over time, not due to a lack of commitment, but as a pragmatic response to entrenched norms and limited institutional receptivity (Kartoshkina, 2015; Alsulami, 2021). At the same time, both narratives reinforce the argument that returnees function as intermediaries between global academic practices and local institutional cultures, carrying the potential for innovation even when that potential is constrained (Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019). What becomes visible here is the dual challenge of sustaining motivation while navigating environments that may not readily recognise or accommodate internationally shaped professional identities.

Importantly, these accounts also point beyond resistance itself, raising questions about the conditions under which innovation can be sustained rather than silenced. This leads directly to the next subtheme, which explores how supportive networks and positive workplace relationships can mitigate resistance, provide professional affirmation, and enable returnees to maintain a sense of purpose and continuity in their academic practice

Subtheme 2: support Networks and Positive Workplace

In this subtheme, participants are showing how professional networks and supportive workplace relationships functioned as key enabling conditions for sustaining motivation, innovation, and professional identity after return. In contrast to the resistance and isolation described in the previous subtheme, these accounts illuminate how connections formed during international doctoral study continued to provide emotional reassurance, academic legitimacy, and alternative spaces for collaboration. What emerges across these narratives is that support networks were not peripheral, but central to how participants navigated professional reintegration and maintained a sense of academic continuity.

Ahmed, reflected on how his network now spans multiple countries, stating,

“I have a network of international friends. For example, if I visit the Philippines, Thailand, Bulgaria, Norway, England, Germany, or France, I will have a friend there. I also developed an academic network with my supervisor, professors, other Algerian students, and international peers.” Although Ahmed acknowledged he had not extensively published post-PhD, he credited these networks with keeping him inspired and connected to academia, highlighting their role in maintaining his motivation and ambition to contribute further to the academic field”.

What Ahmed emphasises here is not simply the existence of professional contacts, but a sense of relational continuity and accessibility. His repeated reference to “*I will have a friend there*” suggests that these networks are experienced as emotionally secure and personally meaningful, rather than purely instrumental. This framing positions networking as a form of social anchoring that transcends geographic location, enabling Ahmed to sustain a sense of belonging to an international academic community even after returning to Algeria.

Ahmed’s narrative can be understood as reflecting an effort to preserve academic identity continuity following re-entry. Rather than locating his professional self solely within the institutional structures of his home university, he appears to orient himself towards a transnational academic space where recognition, exchange, and legitimacy remain available. This is particularly significant given his acknowledgement that he has not yet published extensively post-PhD. In this context, networks function less as immediate career accelerators and more as sources of motivation, reassurance, and future possibility. His academic identity, therefore, remains forward-looking and relationally sustained rather than stalled by local constraints.

These experiences align closely with Williams and Baláz’s (2008) concept of *network capital*, which highlight how the mobility of highly skilled individuals fosters the development of both social and professional ties. Such networks not only enhance personal growth but also serve as conduits for the exchange of knowledge, collaboration, and global perspectives. For Ahmed, these networks appear to mitigate the potential isolation often associated with return, offering alternative sites of academic engagement that coexist alongside his local professional role. Similarly, Gu (2015) argues that international mobility encourages intercultural competence and fosters relationships that extend beyond academic settings, creating a foundation for lifelong professional and personal connections.

While Ahmed’s account highlights networks as a source of continuity and motivation, Autumn’s narrative illustrates how these connections are actively mobilised as professional capital within both local and international academic spaces.

“Networking now when I want to organise a conference, you know, I feel like because the UK is such a multicultural place, it's a hub of research. There is a culture of research there. So I've got loads of networks in there. That now I could refer to or use, you know, to boost my academic career here... the people I met in the UK who happen to be Algerians and they are all part of this scheme and they now they made it home. We've got networks as well. So you see it helps, it helps a lot.... I had 2 different resources and it helped me with you know networking, okay, establishing okay this kind of network vast network not just on a local or a

national level, but you can say international because I've met people in the UK who are from India, from Poland from different parts of the world. And also they are helping me locally or what we call national, nationally on a national level because these people came back as well and now we exchange information”.

Autumn’s account extends the role of networks beyond emotional support, positioning them as *actively mobilised professional resources*. When she refers to networking “*when I want to organise a conference*”, she frames her international connections as practical tools that enable academic action rather than symbolic affiliations. Her emphasis on being able to “*use*” these networks to “*boost my academic career here*” suggests that they function as mechanisms for sustaining professional momentum within the Algerian context.

Her description of the UK as “*a hub of research*” and a place with “*a culture of research*” implicitly contrasts with the institutional environment she returned to, where such infrastructures appear less accessible. In this sense, international networks become compensatory, allowing her to maintain practices and ambitions shaped during her doctoral studies. Networking thus operates as a means of preserving continuity in her professional identity across contexts.

Autumn also distinguishes between “*two different resources*”: international academic connections and networks of Algerian returnees who studied in the UK. These overlapping networks create both global reach and local relevance, enabling ongoing exchange of information and collaboration. Her repeated assertion that “*it helps a lot*” highlights the affective reassurance and professional confidence these networks provide alongside their instrumental value.

This account aligns with Williams and Baláz’s (2008) notion of *embedded knowledge*, where relationships formed through mobility continue to shape professional practice after return. It also reflects De Wit’s (2008) argument that international exposure generates enduring intellectual and relational resources that can be reactivated across settings. Together with Ahmed’s narrative, Autumn’s experience illustrates how networks function not only as sources of motivation, but as enabling conditions for sustaining innovation and professional agency after return.

Mohamed’s account offers a contrasting perspective on support networks, foregrounding the role of *locally embedded collegial relationships* rather than primarily international ties. He explains:

“I do have a very good network with teachers here, at Algerian university... we are working together... we are about to settle an English language school... My experience helps build a very good network with my colleagues, who are now either teaching in England or even globally.”

Unlike Ahmed and Autumn, who emphasise networks formed during mobility as sustaining links to global academia, Mohamed situates his sense of support within *national and institutional collaboration*. His repeated use of “we” signals collective orientation and shared purpose, suggesting that his reintegration was facilitated by a workplace environment receptive to cooperation. The planned establishment of an English language school reflects not only professional ambition but also confidence in institutional feasibility, indicating alignment between his expectations and the local academic context.

At the same time, Mohamed’s reference to colleagues “*teaching in England or even globally*” shows that his networks are not confined to national boundaries. Rather, his account illustrates how international and local networks intersect, enabling him to translate global experience into concrete institutional initiatives at home. In contrast to participants who relied on external networks as alternatives to unsupportive workplaces, Mohamed appears able to *activate* his networks from within the institution itself.

This experience resonates with research suggesting that when returnees encounter supportive departmental cultures, transnational capital can be more readily embedded into local practice (Chen and Li, 2019; Geeraert, Ward, and Hanel, 2022). Mohamed’s narrative thus highlights how the presence of collegial trust and shared goals can significantly shape the extent to which international experience is converted into sustained professional action.

In combination, the accounts of Ahmed, Autumn, and Mohamed illustrate that support networks function as *relational infrastructures* through which returnees sustain motivation, legitimacy, and professional continuity after return. While Ahmed and Autumn emphasised international networks as sources of inspiration and professional reassurance in the face of institutional constraint, Mohamed’s experience demonstrates how locally grounded networks can enable collective action and institutional development.

Across these narratives, networks are not experienced as passive remnants of time abroad, but as *actively mobilised resources* that shape how returnees navigate professional uncertainty and pursue innovation. These findings align with work on network capital and embedded knowledge, which highlights how relationships forged through mobility continue to influence professional trajectories long after return (Williams and Baláž, 2008; De Wit, 2008). Importantly, the effectiveness of these networks appears contingent on institutional context: where workplaces are receptive, networks enable collaboration and reform; where resistance persists, they function as alternative spaces of validation and continuity.

While these supportive networks offered important resources for sustaining professional engagement after return, they did not remove the structural and administrative barriers embedded within the higher education system. The next GET therefore shifts attention from relational support to the institutional conditions shaping reintegration. “Bureaucratic and Credential Challenges” explores how returnees encountered administrative inefficiencies, credential recognition issues, and procedural obstacles that constrained professional progress despite their qualifications and experience.

GET 3: Bureaucratic and Credential Challenges

This theme captures how Algerian doctoral returnees experienced bureaucratic processes and credential recognition as significant obstacles during professional reintegration. Despite holding advanced international qualifications, participants frequently encountered administrative delays, opaque procedures, and inconsistent institutional requirements that complicated their return. Navigating these bureaucratic systems was not only time-consuming but emotionally taxing, often generating frustration, uncertainty, and a sense of stalled progress.

Alongside bureaucratic barriers, participants also described difficulties in securing recognition for their doctoral degrees and the skills acquired abroad. In several cases, international credentials were questioned, undervalued, or misaligned with local academic expectations, forcing returnees to repeatedly justify their expertise and professional legitimacy. These experiences shaped how participants understood their position within the academic system, affecting both confidence and professional identity.

The subthemes “Navigating Bureaucratic Barriers” and “Credential Recognition Challenges” explore how returnees made sense of these institutional encounters and the persistence required to move forward. In combination, this theme highlights how systemic inefficiencies and recognition gaps complicated reintegration, revealing a tension between the potential value returnees bring and the institutional structures that constrain their professional trajectories.

Subtheme 1: Navigating Bureaucratic Barriers

In this subtheme, participants are showing me how bureaucratic systems were experienced as ongoing, everyday obstacles that shaped their professional reintegration. Rather than appearing as isolated administrative tasks, bureaucracy emerged as a persistent condition that constrained motivation, delayed progress, and complicated returnees’ attempts to settle into their academic roles.

Amani's account underscores the persistent struggle with bureaucratic inefficiencies and coordination issues in her workplace. She shares:

“I'm still struggling in terms of, I love teaching, I enjoy teaching. I love the students.”

Amani's account underscores the emotional and professional toll of navigating disorganised bureaucratic systems. While she expresses a deep passion for teaching, stating, “*I love teaching, I enjoy teaching. I love the students,*”. However, this positive orientation is immediately followed by her admission that she is “*still struggling*”, suggesting that her enthusiasm is tempered by the frustrations of adapting to institutional inefficiencies. Amani's enjoyment of teaching coexists with an environment that makes everyday professional functioning more difficult. Bureaucracy here is lived as something that sits in tension with her vocational commitment, slowly wearing down professional satisfaction rather than overtly negating it. This experience reflects findings that bureaucratic inefficiencies often produce emotional fatigue and a sense of stagnation among returnees, even when intrinsic motivation remains strong (Alsulami, 2021).

While Amani's experience highlights the emotional toll of bureaucratic friction, Insaf's account draws attention to how institutional inefficiencies translate into concrete workload pressures:

“Shortage of teachers makes us teach for long hours than we should.”

Insaf frames bureaucracy through the lens of staff shortages and excessive teaching hours. Her statement that “*shortage of teachers makes us teach for long hours than we should*” positions bureaucracy as a structural condition rather than a procedural inconvenience. The issue is not paperwork, but how institutional disorganisation redistributes responsibility onto individual academics. Insaf's experience shows how bureaucratic failure becomes embodied through exhaustion and overextension. The absence of adequate staffing forces returnees to absorb institutional shortcomings, leaving little space for research, reflection, or pedagogical innovation. This aligns with literature suggesting that returnees are frequently expected to compensate for systemic gaps due to assumptions about their resilience and capacity (Karakas, 2020).

While Insaf highlights the burden of structural overload, Nawel's account introduces a more nuanced experience shaped by workplace relationships. She shares:

“deja jina galona kech ma3andkom ideas, (when we came they already start asking for our ideas), you are welcome to share your ideas, 3tina afkarkom, meda bina nhasno (give us your ideas, we would love to enhance the level..), they encourage us).”

Nawel’s narrative offers a contrasting perspective by illustrating how supportive collegial environments can mitigate bureaucratic challenges. Her younger colleagues’ openness “*you are welcome to share your ideas*” highlights recognition and inclusion, allowing her to navigate institutional systems with greater confidence. This openness reflects a workplace culture that values fresh perspectives and collaborative efforts, which Nawel finds empowering and validating. Her experience aligns with studies of Alsulami (2021) and Yi (2011) which highlight the importance of institutional culture in facilitating the successful integration of returnees. A collegial environment fosters not only professional growth but also a sense of belonging, enabling returnees to maximise their expertise effectively.

However, Nawel’s experience also reveals the complexities of navigating generational dynamics within academia. While her younger colleagues embraced her ideas, she encountered resistance from more traditional professors, particularly regarding research concepts. She explains: “*bessah keyen haka clash fel ideas...bessah, (but there was a clash of ideas...but..)*” suggesting that while disagreements emerged, mutual respect ultimately allowed for diverse viewpoints to coexist. This duality in Nawel’s narrative reflects a nuanced process of reintegration, where collaborative opportunities coexist with generational tensions. Such experiences are consistent with findings by Zikic (2006), who note that returnees often act as bridges between traditional and progressive academic practices, fostering innovation while respecting institutional norms.

Kenza’s account returns attention to the frustrations caused by unclear systems. She shares:

“When I used to go to the ministry and tell them I have finished, and things like that. The instructions are not always as clear. So you always have to talk to so many people to get one inference that should have been available from the beginning. So that would be what annoys me the most”

Her account highlights the inefficiencies and complexity of bureaucratic processes, which create unnecessary hurdles for returnees seeking to complete post-PhD formalities. The need to “*talk to so many people to get one inference*” reflects a systemic lack of organisation and transparency. Here, bureaucracy is experienced as mentally exhausting and time-consuming, requiring constant interpretive effort. Kenza’s narrative also reveals how these inefficiencies detract from the reintegration experience, turning what should be a straightforward process into a time-consuming and mentally suffering. The lack of readily available information exacerbates the frustration of

returnees who are eager to transition into their professional roles but find themselves entangled in administrative red tape. This aligns with findings by Karakas (2020), who note that unclear procedures and inconsistent communication in bureaucratic institutions are common challenges for academic returnees, often leading to delays and frustration.

Amine's account further extends this picture by illustrating how bureaucratic complexity becomes a labour-intensive process managed almost entirely by the returnee. He shares:

“I struggled to get recruited because we had to go to the ministry, get things legalise ... authenticated and go to university taking the envelope and taking it to the head of department up within your recruitment”

Amine describes recruitment as a process involving multiple layers of authentication and physical movement between institutions. His account of “*taking the envelope*” from one office to another conveys bureaucracy as fragmented and decentralised, with coordination displaced onto the individual. This experience positions Amine not as a supported academic but as a logistical agent responsible for stitching together disconnected institutional processes. Bureaucracy is lived here as continuous self-navigation, diverting time and energy away from teaching and research. Such experiences reinforce findings that returnees often bear the burden of institutional fragmentation, which can delay professional integration and contribute to a sense of inefficiency and fatigue (Alsulami, 2021).

Together, Amani's, Nawel's, Kenza, and Amine narratives highlight the critical role of institutional culture and workplace dynamics in shaping the reintegration experiences of returnees. While systemic barriers like bureaucracy pose significant challenges, a supportive and open-minded workplace can mitigate these difficulties, enabling returnees to navigate their roles with greater confidence and impact. These insights stress the need for reforms that not only address systemic inefficiencies but also cultivate inclusive and collaborative academic environments that maximise the potential of returning scholars. The next subtheme builds on this by examining how bureaucratic complexity becomes particularly consequential when tied to credential recognition and equivalence, further affecting returnees' sense of legitimacy and progress within Algerian academia.

Subtheme 2: Credential Recognition Challenges

In this subtheme, participants reflect on how the process of obtaining equivalence for their foreign qualifications was lived as a significant obstacle, shaping the pace and direction of their early

reintegration experiences. Rather than being perceived as a straightforward administrative requirement, credential recognition was lived as a prolonged and uncertain process that delayed professional entry, disrupted career trajectories, and, for some, unsettled their sense of academic legitimacy.

Karim's account illustrates how credential recognition was experienced as a layered and time-intensive process, marked by repeated delays and a lack of institutional clarity. He explains:

“The first thing you need to do is to get the equivalence of the diploma... it still took two months to receive my own certificate... That website was not functioning well. I couldn't upload all the documents... for reasons I'm still unaware of, it took them two and a half months to process my equivalence.... By that time, the Human Resources department at the ministry told us we couldn't be appointed because the doors shut. We had to wait for the new academic year. A colleague of mine and I had to wait for a whole year to start.”

Karim's emphasis on duration brings to light time as a central feature of his experience. The waiting period does not appear as a single interruption, but as an accumulation of delays that gradually postponed his professional entry. This sense of uncertainty intensifies when he describes the malfunctioning equivalence platform, noting that *“for reasons I'm still unaware of”* his application took months to process. Such phrasing suggests not only frustration, but a loss of control and predictability, positioning the bureaucratic system as difficult and inaccessible. The consequences of these delays become more pronounced when institutional timelines intervene. Here, Karim's doctoral qualification temporarily loses its functional value. Despite having completed his PhD, he is unable to enter the academic workforce, experiencing what can be understood as a suspension of professional identity.

Karim's experience resonates with findings by Alsulami (2021) who highlight how credential recognition challenges often undermine the potential contributions of returning scholars. The delays in equivalence validation not only impede their ability to begin their professional roles but also create emotional and financial stress, exacerbating the difficulties of reintegration. For returnees who bring internationally recognised expertise, such barriers represent a missed opportunity to influence their skills in ways that could benefit the local academic system. Beyond structural inconvenience, Karim's repeated references to waiting to include the moment when *“the doors shut”* and the need to *“wait for a whole year”* suggest that time itself becomes an experiential burden, reshaping how progress and belonging are perceived during re-entry. Rather than marking a clear transition from doctoral completion to professional integration, the prolonged delays appear to place him in an in-between state, where achievement does not immediately translate into recognition. This temporal disconnection highlights how bureaucratic

processes can transform return into a prolonged period of uncertainty, requiring returnees to continuously renegotiate their sense of professional legitimacy and forward movement.

Mohamed faced similar challenges, particularly due to the disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. He shares:

“I had to wait for nearly a year for my diploma to come back. Due to COVID-19, the administration at my UK university was working from home, so they couldn’t actually print the diploma and send it to me. By the time I received it, I missed the recruitment date, which meant I had to wait nearly 16 or 17 months to find a job.”

Mohamed’s experience demonstrates the duality of navigating systemic challenges while striving for personal agency. The delay in receiving his diploma, caused by the administrative disruptions at his UK university during the COVID-19 pandemic, left him in a prolonged state of professional uncertainty. Such prolonged uncertainty has been identified in repatriation research as a critical stressor during re-entry, particularly when career progression becomes contingent upon bureaucratic or institutional timelines (Black, Gregersen, and Mendenhall, 1992; Presbitero, 2016).

His reflection, “*Due to COVID-19, the administration at my UK university was working from home, so they couldn’t actually print the diploma and send it to me,*” encapsulates the compounded frustrations of external circumstances beyond his control. This delay, which culminated in a missed recruitment deadline, extended his unemployment to nearly sixteen or seventeen months, underscoring the tangible consequences of these bureaucratic inefficiencies. The COVID-19 pandemic has been widely recognised as intensifying structural vulnerabilities within international education systems, exposing returnees to delays, uncertainty, and institutional bottlenecks beyond their individual agency (UNESCO, 2021).

The emotional and financial stress of this period is evident, as Mohamed recalls relying solely on personal income to sustain himself, a challenge he describes as “*very hard.*” This highlights the vulnerability of returnees who must navigate the intersection of global disruptions and local bureaucratic timelines. Re-entry scholarship consistently notes that periods of enforced waiting and institutional ambiguity can heighten psychological stress and financial precarity, particularly for early-career academics (Szkudlarek, 2010; Presbitero, 2016).

Despite these obstacles, Mohamed’s narrative also reveals a remarkable resilience and adaptability. His proactive approach to this downtime, “*I was trying to fill the time by writing more... We started writing the book during that period,*” demonstrates an ability to transform an otherwise challenging period into one of productivity and intellectual growth. This adaptive

reframing aligns with conceptualisations of agency during re-entry, where individuals reinterpret structural constraint through reflective meaning-making processes (Mezirow, 1991).

This account reflects not only the systemic barriers faced by returnees but also their capacity to reframe adversity as an opportunity for personal and professional development. Mohamed's story illustrates the complex interplay between external systemic pressures and internal resilience, emphasising the need for support systems that mitigate the effects of such delays. It also highlights the untapped potential of returning scholars, whose adaptive strategies can contribute significantly to their professional fields when given adequate institutional backing and timely processes. These narratives also reveal a remarkable capacity for adaptability among returnees. Faced with financial and career uncertainties, participants like Mohamed and others directed their energy into academic pursuits, using the waiting period to write, reflect, and prepare for future roles. This resilience underscores the untapped potential of returning scholars, who, despite systemic barriers, continue to demonstrate a commitment to personal and professional growth.

However, not all returnees shared the same experience. Ahmed, reflecting on his equivalence process, offered a contrasting narrative:

“I had to wait for my diploma to come, and then you have to do the equivalent procedures, you go to Algiers, you know the story, but it was smooth I guess, it wasn't that complicated.”

In contrast to the prolonged disruption described by Karim and Mohamed, Ahmed presents credential recognition as largely unproblematic. He characterises the process as “*smooth*” and “*not that complicated*”, language that noticeably lacks emotional intensity. This suggests that equivalence procedures did not become a defining moment in his reintegration, remaining peripheral rather than disruptive to his professional trajectory.

However, Ahmed's use of tentative phrasing such as “*I guess*” introduces a degree of caution, implying that the process may not have been objectively efficient but simply non-obstructive in his case. His account highlights how bureaucratic systems can fade into the background when they do not impede progress, shaping reintegration through relative invisibility rather than crisis. This variation reflects broader findings that credential recognition processes are inconsistently experienced, producing uneven outcomes for returnees depending on timing, institutional handling, and individual circumstances (Zweig, Fung, and Han, 2008; Karakaş, 2020).

At the same time, Ahmed's narrative suggests that the absence of disruption may itself influence how reintegration is remembered and narrated. Unlike participants for whom bureaucratic delays

became emotionally salient turning points, Ahmed's experience appears to normalise administrative procedures as routine and expected aspects of return. The phrase "*you know the story*" may indicate an implicit acceptance of bureaucratic processes as culturally familiar, positioning them as part of the anticipated landscape rather than a source of disorientation. In this way, smooth progression allows professional identity to continue uninterrupted, illustrating how the impact of institutional systems becomes most visible when they obstruct, rather than facilitate, transition.

Kenza describes an extended waiting period of approximately eight months before she could begin her role, attributing the delay to finalising diploma corrections and awaiting ministry approval. She explains:

"It took about eight months for me to finalise everything, and for the ministry to give me my position. So I was kind of jobless for all of that time"

However, Kenza also reflects on this gap positively, noting,

"It gave me the time to readjust to my family, to the dynamic of everyday, to my neighbourhood again."

Kenza's account reflects a more uncertain encounter with credential recognition, shaped by delay but actively reinterpreted. She describes being "*kind of jobless*" for approximately eight months, positioning this period as one of professional suspension. The phrasing conveys uncertainty and interruption rather than intentional pause.

Yet Kenza reframes this delay as an opportunity for personal and social readjustment, noting that it allowed her to reconnect with family, everyday routines, and her neighbourhood. Through this reinterpretation, bureaucratic delay becomes integrated into a broader process of resettlement rather than experienced solely as loss. Kenza's account reflects adaptive meaning-making, where waiting is absorbed into the wider work of re-anchoring herself at home.

Her experience underlines how structural obstacles are lived differently depending on personal positioning and social context. While delays in credential recognition remain a significant barrier to professional progression, Kenza's narrative illustrates (Rickleby, 2019; Pham and Saito, 2020) conceptions related to how returnees may negotiate these disruptions in ways that preserve emotional coherence and continuity

Taken together, these accounts show that credential recognition was not experienced as a uniform administrative task, but as a situated phase of professional reintegration shaped by timing, institutional coordination, and individual positioning. For participants such as Karim and

Mohamed, prolonged delays suspended professional momentum and generated uncertainty and financial pressure. In contrast, Ahmed's smoother experience illustrates how bureaucratic systems can remain largely invisible when they do not obstruct progress, while Kenza's account highlights how periods of delay can be reinterpreted as part of broader processes of personal and social readjustment. Across these narratives, bureaucratic procedures emerge not merely as technical requirements but as mechanisms that actively shape returnees' sense of agency, continuity, and professional belonging at a critical point in re-entry (Zweig, Fung, and Han, 2008; Karakaş, 2020; Pham and Saito, 2020). While this subtheme has focused on administrative barriers surrounding credential recognition, the next GET turns to how returnees pursued professional growth after formal reintegration, particularly within contexts marked by limited institutional and material resources. "Professional Growth and Resource Constraints" examines how academic ambition was sustained, adapted, or constrained within these environments.

GET 4: Professional Growth and Resources Constraints

This group experiential theme explores how professional growth following return was shaped not only by participants' desire to contribute, but also by the structural constraints within which that contribution had to unfold. Across accounts, returnees did not describe professional development as a linear progression built upon their international doctoral training. Instead, growth emerged as a negotiated process mediated by limited institutional resources, infrastructural constraints, and the disruptive context of COVID-19.

Participants articulated a strong sense of responsibility to apply the expertise and academic practices developed abroad. For many, returning home was accompanied by an internalised obligation to contribute meaningfully to Algerian higher education, particularly within knowledge-based institutions. This aligns with scholarship suggesting that academic returnees often experience a perceived duty to "give back" and translate their international capital into local impact (Lazarova, 2014; Rosen and Zweig, 2005). However, participants' narratives also reveal that such aspirations were frequently constrained by structural realities that limited the full representation of their skills.

The findings resonate with research indicating that the professional trajectories of returnees are highly contingent on institutional environments. While internationally trained scholars possess transnational human capital capable of driving innovation and reform (Lam and Rui, 2024), the translation of that capital depends heavily on local infrastructures, material resources, and organisational cultures (Chen and Li, 2019; Karakaş, 2020). Within the Algerian context

described by participants, resource scarcity, limited teaching infrastructure, and pandemic-related disruptions complicated the process of consolidating professional growth after return.

This GET therefore examines how participants made sense of their professional development within conditions of constraint. It unfolds across three interconnected subthemes: first, the application of experiences and skills acquired abroad; second, the impact of limited resources and teaching infrastructure; and third, the additional layer of professional disruption introduced by the COVID-19 pandemic. The following subtheme explores how participants understood and enacted their responsibility to apply their international training within Algerian academia.

Subtheme 1: Application of Experiences and Skills

In this subtheme, participants are showing me how their international doctoral experiences were not only transformative at a personal level but became resources they sought to actively apply within the Algerian academic context. What emerges across these accounts is not simply skill acquisition, but a reshaping of professional self-understanding, where confidence, academic positioning, and ethical responsibility are reconfigured through exposure to alternative academic cultures.

Kenza reflects on how her academic and professional experiences in the UK contributed to her self-confidence and intercultural competence. She shares:

“I think a bit more self-confidence just being put with people from different nationalities, people with higher qualifications. So, dealing with doctors and professors, and talking about serious things like research. I really like how in the UK they appreciate, you know, any type of contribution. They don't belittle, you know, students... they always point to the good things, and then they try to help you improve the not-so-good things, whereas here they always focus on the bad... constructive criticism that I gained in the UK—it has helped with my self-confidence; I think it has helped me develop... intercultural competence.”

Kenza's narrative illustrates the transformative impact of studying abroad on personal and professional development. Her increased self-confidence stems from engaging with diverse, highly qualified individuals and participating in academic discussions where her contributions were valued.

The contrast she draws between the constructive feedback practices in the UK and the more critical approach in her home country highlights the role of academic culture in shaping professional attitudes. Kenza's appreciation for feedback that balances strengths and areas for improvement reflects the importance of fostering a growth-oriented environment, which she associates with her enhanced ability to critically engage in academic and professional contexts.

Furthermore, her explicit mention of “*intercultural competence*” underscores the broader impact of exposure to diverse nationalities and cultural practices during her time abroad. This aligns with Deardorff (2006), who defines intercultural competence as the ability to interact effectively and appropriately with individuals from different cultural backgrounds, a skill increasingly valued in globalised academic and professional settings.

While Kenza’s transformation centres on confidence and communication, Akram’s account positions research as the primary site of application. He reflects:

“One element that I can think of is research; one way that I can transform or transmit from my own experience to Algeria is doing research the right way,”

Akram’s language signals a strong moral and highlights the centrality of research in bridging the gap between his exposure to global academic practices and the realities of the Algerian context. This insight reflects not only his awareness of the systemic limitations of local research practices but also his commitment to addressing these challenges through the application of rigorous and ethical methodologies.

The phrase “*doing research the right way*” suggests a critical evaluation of the standards and practices he encountered abroad compared to those prevalent in Algeria. His use of “*the right way*” signifies a clear delineation between practices he perceives as effective and those that may lack rigour or accountability in the local context, this reflects a sense of transformation in Akram’s understanding of research not just as an academic activity, but as a vehicle for knowledge transfer and meaningful change.

This narrative also points to a broader identity reconstruction. By framing research as a tool for “*transmitting*” his experience, Akram positions himself as a conduit between global academic norms and local needs. This aligns with the concept of returnees as agents of change, where individuals bring back not only technical skills but also a mindset shaped by international exposure. Akram’s desire to transform Algerian research practices suggests a dual focus; improving the system while also finding personal fulfillment in the process of contributing to institutional growth.

Akram’s reflections highlight the emotional and intellectual investment in his role as a researcher. The use of terms like “*transform*” and “*transmit*” implies a sense of responsibility, as if the knowledge and skills he gained abroad come with an obligation to share and apply them. This aligns with Mezirow’s (1997) transformative learning theory, which emphasises that profound experiences lead to critical reflection and a redefinition of one’s role in the world. Akram’s

emphasis on research as a transformational tool underscores his belief in its potential to create meaningful and sustainable change.

In essence, Akram's narrative encapsulates the interplay between personal transformation and professional responsibility. His reflections not only demonstrate the enduring impact of his international experience but also reveal how this transformation shapes his aspirations and approach to navigating the Algerian academic landscape. By emphasising research as a mechanism for bridging global and local practices, Akram situates himself as a change-maker committed to leveraging his experiences for the betterment of his home-country context.

A shared thread across Kenza and Akram's narratives illustrate that applying international experience is not a simple act of transfer. It involves re-enacting new feedback philosophies, research standards, and academic commitments within environments that may not fully share those orientations. In this sense, professional growth after return is both aspirational and negotiated, shaped by how transformed identities are enacted within existing institutional structures. This interpretation aligns with research suggesting that returnees' professional trajectories are deeply mediated by institutional cultures and peer dynamics, which can either validate or constrain the application of internationally acquired knowledge (Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019; Geeraert, Ward, and Hanel, 2022). The following subtheme explores how limited resources and teaching infrastructure further constrained participants' ability to translate international experience into everyday academic practice.

Subtheme 2: Limited Resources and Teaching Infrastructure

In this subtheme, participants are showing me how material and infrastructural conditions significantly shaped the application of their internationally acquired pedagogical practices. What becomes visible across these accounts is that innovation was not only negotiated at the interpersonal level, but also structurally constrained by the absence of technological tools, adequate facilities, and institutional support. The professional self that participants developed abroad often depended on environments where resources enabled experimentation, interaction, and critical engagement. Upon return, however, these possibilities were mediated by scarcity.

Mohamed reflects on this disparity, contrasting his teaching experiences in the UK with those in Algeria:

“Honestly speaking, it is very challenging, but because that depends on the environment... So, when I was teaching in England, we had the means. We had the technology means... we had the data shows, and everything was set... Here, in Algeria, unfortunately we don't... sometimes we don't have data shows. And then,

if we have data shows, we don't have electricity... So you find the students... very lost sometimes... trying to find out about the characters by simply imagining.

Mohamed's account paints a vivid picture of the infrastructural deficiencies that challenge the teaching process in Algeria. His mention of the absence of basic tools like projectors "*data shows*" and even electricity reflects systemic issues that impede the integration of modern teaching methods. In contrast, his experience in the UK demonstrates how access to resources enhances the learning experience. The availability of tools such as multimedia aids allows for creative and interactive teaching approaches, such as using cinematic adaptations to teach literature, which engages students more deeply with the material. This disparity between environments illustrates how resource scarcity in Algerian universities can constrain innovative teaching practices and limit educators' ability to make lessons engaging and accessible. The reliance on personal resources to supplement institutional deficiencies adds an additional burden on educators, reflecting broader systemic challenges in the Algerian higher education system. As highlighted by Lam and Rui (2023) and Wang *et al.* (2024), a lack of infrastructural support not only diminishes the quality of education but also demoralises educators, who often struggle to deliver effective teaching under such constraints.

Mohamed is not merely describing poor facilities; he is making sense of how environmental scarcity reshapes his capacity to inhabit the professional identity he developed abroad. The gap between intention and application becomes a structural, not personal limitation.

Also, Manel's reflections highlight the significant resource constraints that hinder effective teaching and academic practice. She shares:

"We don't have good working conditions... teaching using a data show in amphe theatres, and the number of students is tremendous. So sometimes I have, like, 175... I couldn't find any data show... I had to find alternatives. I had to send them stuff before. I'm asking them to use their phones for the presentation... During my first semester I had 4 modules, and imagine having about 175 in each. I corrected over 1200 papers. That was overwhelming, that was demotivating. That was getting on me... Another thing... staff development, we do not have any programme... to advance your thinking, to advance your professional skills. We don't know how... everyone thinks about their own benefit."

Her account reveals the challenges of adapting to a resource-deprived teaching environment. The absence of basic teaching aids, such as data projectors is not only about equipment; it symbolises the failure of the teaching practices she had internalised abroad. Her need to rely on students' phones signals improvisation under constraint, a form of adaptive resilience, yet one that operates within structural scarcity, and the overwhelming number of students in large lecture halls "*up to*

175 per class” illustrate the systemic barriers that limit the effectiveness of pedagogical practices. Her language shifts when she describes the workload as “*overwhelming*”, “*demotivating*”, and “*getting on me*”. The repetition intensifies the emotional weight of the experience. The burden is not framed as temporary adjustment, but as energy exhaustion “*wasted energy*”. This suggests that resource limitations and excessive teaching demands are not neutral logistical issues; they affect professional morale and identity sustainability. The absence of “*staff development*” introduces a further layer. Manel is not only describing infrastructural poverty but developmental stagnation. Her phrase “*to advance your thinking*” signals an aspiration toward intellectual growth, which she experiences as unsupported. In this sense, resource constraints extend beyond physical tools to include academic and institutional investment. This aligns with Lam and Rui (2023), who argue that resource scarcity in developing higher education systems constrains not only delivery capacity but also the professional growth trajectories of academic staff. Similarly, Altbach (2011) notes that structural underinvestment undermines innovation and contributes to academic demoralisation, particularly in postcolonial contexts where global standards are expected but local systems remain under-resourced.

Likewise, Maya’s reflections provide a detailed account of the inadequate teaching conditions she encountered upon returning to her academic role. She shares:

“You don't get any of this here... we don't even have data shows in every room... So you just go with the board and the pen, and that's it... but also the heating... it doesn't do anything... it's very cold when we're teaching... the conditions were quite bad, and we had to go on a strike for things to be a bit better.”

Maya begins with “*you don't get any of this here*”, immediately constructing a comparison between what was once normalised abroad and what is now absent. Maya’s description of having to rely on outdated tools like “*the board and the pen*” illustrates the significant resource gaps in her academic environment. The lack of data projectors and modern teaching aids creates a disconnect between her expectations, shaped by her experiences abroad, and the realities of her home institution.

Her description of poor heating conditions further highlights the challenging physical environment for educators. Teaching in cold classrooms not only affects the comfort of educators and students but also reflects the broader neglect of basic infrastructure. Such conditions contribute to professional dissatisfaction and demotivation,

Maya’s mention of going on “*strike*” conveys a deeper symbolic frustration of academic staff and the lengths they must go to in order to advocate for basic improvements. This mirrors a

broader institutional pattern where structures exist but do not operate effectively. The result is not only inconvenience but professional demoralisation. Teaching in cold classrooms affects concentration, engagement, and morale, reinforcing a sense of institutional neglect. Her account resonates with Lam and Rui (2023), who argue that inadequate infrastructure constrains not only pedagogical innovation but also institutional morale.

Taken together, Mohamed, Manel, and Maya are showing that resource constraints operate across technological, workload, developmental, and even physical dimensions. While Mohamed emphasises infrastructural disparities, Manel foregrounds cumulative overload and demotivation, and Maya highlights embodied stress and collective frustration. Across their accounts, resource scarcity emerges not as a minor inconvenience but as a structural condition shaping the extent to which internationally acquired skills can be enacted locally. This aligns with Lam and Rui (2023), who argue that institutional resource deficits constrain returnees' ability to translate global knowledge into practice.

These narratives suggest that professional growth upon return is mediated not only by motivation or competence, but by the material and institutional conditions within which returnees operate. As Altbach (2011) notes, under-resourced systems often limit innovation irrespective of individual capability, reinforcing that reintegration is structured by institutional affordances and constraints (Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019). These structural limitations form part of the broader landscape shaping reintegration, a landscape further complicated by the disruptions introduced during the COVID-19 pandemic. The next subtheme explores this temporal dimension of professional challenge.

Subtheme 3: Navigating Professional Challenges Amidst COVID-19

In this subtheme, participants are showing how the pandemic did not simply interrupt academic routines, but reshaped professional expectations, student engagement, and educators' sense of pedagogical responsibility. What appears across these accounts is that COVID-19 functioned as an additional layer of reintegration complexity, compounding already existing structural constraints and forcing returnees to recalibrate both their expectations and their practices.

Ahmed's account vividly captures the struggles caused by the pandemic-era hybrid learning model, which left students academically unprepared and educators overwhelmed by the gaps in learning. He reflects:

“I think another and another challenge is the students themselves, because, like everybody, is, this desperate, doesn't study and then the level is very low. Maybe because of the COVID era, because they've been studying hybrid.”

Ahmed elaborates further on the impact of these challenges on student performance, noting:

“Their levels are very low, and they they found it hard to understand, and in the tests and exams, they get disastrous marks.”

Ahmed positions students’ “*very low*” level as a direct consequence of hybrid learning. The repetition of “*very*” intensifies his perception of academic decline, while the phrase “*maybe because of the COVID era*” suggests an attempt to rationalise rather than blame. He is not simply criticising students; he is interpreting their struggles within a broader structural disruption. When he later describes exam results as “*disastrous marks*”, the language conveys both professional concern and emotional stress. Adding to that, the long-term effects of hybrid and disrupted learning environments have created an academic divide that requires significant remediation efforts, adding pressure to educators already adapting to reintegration.

What Ahmed is showing here is the dual burden placed on educators: addressing foundational learning gaps while still being expected to deliver quality outcomes. This aligns with Haque and Rahaman (2021) who noted the psychological and logistical challenges faced by students and educators during the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly in adapting to hybrid learning models, and UNESCO (2021) stressed how the pandemic exposed existing vulnerabilities in education systems, leaving both students and educators struggling to meet expected outcomes. Ahmed’s account reflects this dual burden, where the lack of continuity in learning during the pandemic created long-term repercussions that educators must address. In Ahmed’s case, reintegration becomes intertwined with remediation. His professional role shifts from knowledge transmission to repair work, adding pressure to an already demanding transition.

Similarly, Autumn’s narrative reflects the professional challenges she faced as an educator amidst the disruptions caused by COVID-19, highlighting systemic inadequacies and their impact on her teaching. She states:

“I was baffled... they said, don’t have high expectations. They are the COVID generations... there was no like, things were not digitalised... there was no Moodle... people tried to navigate their way into it.

Autumn’s use of “*baffled*” signals a moment of rupture between expectation and reality. The phrase “*don’t have high expectations*” reflects not only advice from colleagues but a collective lowering of standards. She describes how the “*COVID generations*” of students, who experienced minimal academic engagement during the pandemic due to the lack of digital infrastructure like Moodle, struggled with their learning, forcing educators to lower expectations.

The institutional unpreparedness to digitise education placed additional burdens on teachers, who had to navigate and implement unfamiliar platforms through trial and error. This moment reveals a tension between her professional ideals shaped in a context where digitalisation and research culture were embedded and a local system scrambling to adapt.

This resonates with Pham and Saito (2020), who describe rigid institutional environments that struggle to absorb global pedagogical shifts, and with Karakaş (2020), who highlights how reform efforts often weaken in structurally unprepared settings. Autumn's narrative reflects both frustration and empathy; she critiques the system while recognising the constraints placed on students and colleagues.

Extending this tension further, Kenza's account brings together institutional absence and cultural shift. She explains:

“One of the main challenges was not having guidance as a new teacher... and the student code has changed... they are not as hard working... not as engaged... not as interactive... because they studied online”.

Kenza's narrative highlights the lack of institutional support for new teachers, which she described as one of her “*main challenges*”, pointing to a systemic failure to provide mentorship or structured resources. This left her to navigate her role independently, a stark contrast to the supportive environments she likely encountered abroad. On the student side, Kenza observes significant shifts in behaviour, noting that students were “*not as hard working,*” “*not as engaged,*” and “*not as interactive*” as she expected, attributing these changes to lenient policies and the lingering effects of online learning. What Kenza is showing is that COVID did not merely produce academic gaps; it reshaped norms of effort and accountability. Her reference to academic leniency reflects her frustration with what she perceives as a decline in academic rigour, which she feels undermines students' motivation and engagement. The repetition of “*not as*” underlines her disappointment and the dissonance between her expectations and the reality she encountered.

This aligns with research on pedagogical norm misalignment (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015), where exposure to different educational cultures recalibrates professional standards. It also aligns with Zhang, Zenf, and Zhang (2022), who report that returnees during the pandemic struggled to communicate transformed expectations within socially and institutionally disrupted contexts. For Kenza, reintegration involves negotiating whether to maintain internationally shaped expectations or adapt to altered local realities.

Taken together, these narratives illustrate that professional reintegration was shaped not only by institutional culture and material constraints, but also by global crisis disruptions that reshaped academic norms and expectations. Ahmed's account foregrounds the pedagogical burden of addressing learning deficits, Autumn's reflection reveals institutional unpreparedness and digital fragility, and Kenza's experience highlights shifts in student engagement and weakened mentorship structures. Across their accounts, the pandemic emerges not simply as a temporary interruption, but as a structural shock that recalibrated expectations, professional standards, and relational dynamics within the university.

Consistent with Haque and Rahaman (2021) and UNESCO (2021), the pandemic exposed and intensified pre-existing structural vulnerabilities. However, within this study, what becomes particularly visible is how such disruptions intersected with return. Participants were not only adapting to local academic cultures but doing so within systems undergoing instability and recalibration. Reintegration therefore appears as a layered process shaped by institutional culture, infrastructural capacity, and global crisis dynamics (De Wit and Altbach, 2021; Zhang, Zeng, and Zhang, 2022). COVID-19 did not merely delay adjustment; it reconfigured the terrain upon which adjustment unfolded. With this final subtheme, GET 4 has illustrated how professional growth and aspiration were continually negotiated against resource constraints, systemic fragilities, and contextual disruptions.

Conclusion

In this chapter, I have shown that professional reintegration for UK-based Algerian doctoral returnees is neither linear nor straightforward, but a negotiated and context-sensitive process shaped by structural constraints, institutional cultures, and participants' evolving professional identities. Through the analysis, I demonstrated how participants encountered systemic barriers including bureaucratic inefficiencies, credential recognition delays, limited resources, and resistance to innovation. These challenges revealed a persistent tension between the academic practices and expectations shaped abroad and the institutional realities they faced upon return.

At the same time, I have argued that reintegration was not defined solely by limitation. Across the subthemes, participants' accounts revealed resilience, self-awareness, and a sustained commitment to contributing meaningfully to Algerian academia. Whether through defending research-informed pedagogies, sustaining international networks, adapting creatively to resource limitations, or navigating pandemic-related disruptions, returnees continually negotiated their professional identities within complex and often restrictive environments.

What emerges from this chapter is a dual process: professional reintegration involved both friction and transformation. Structural inefficiencies limited immediate impact, yet participants' internationally shaped epistemologies, teaching philosophies, and research orientations continued to influence their practice in subtle but significant ways. I interpret these findings as demonstrating that returnees operate within a space of ongoing negotiation, where global academic capital must be recontextualised within local institutional logics.

Taken together, this chapter contributes to existing scholarship on academic return migration by demonstrating that professional reintegration is not simply a matter of institutional adjustment, but an ongoing negotiation of academic authority, professional legitimacy, and identity within structurally constrained environments. In line with the study's conceptualisation of culture and identity as relational and context-dependent, reintegration is shown to unfold through everyday institutional practices rather than abstract national-cultural difference. By situating returnees' experiences within the intersecting dynamics of institutional culture, bureaucratic governance, resource limitation, and crisis disruption, this study advances a more contextually grounded understanding of how internationally trained scholars recontextualise global academic capital within local institutional logics.

Overall, I have shown that the professional dimension of return cannot be understood simply as institutional adjustment. Rather, it represents a dynamic interplay between agency and structure, innovation and resistance, aspiration and constraint. These findings highlight the importance of institutional reform, clearer administrative pathways, and structured professional support to better harness the potential of internationally trained scholars.

In the next chapter, I move beyond the professional sphere to integrate these findings with the personal and cultural dimensions of return. The Synthesis chapter brings these dimensions together to offer a holistic interpretation of reintegration as an interconnected experience shaped by identity, belonging, institutional power, and transnational positioning.

Chapter Seven

Synthesis

Introduction

In this chapter, I argue and show that the personal and professional dimensions of return are at times hard to detach and separate from one another in participants' lived experiences. Therefore, I bring together the personal, cultural, and professional dimensions explored in the previous two findings chapters to provide a more integrated and analytically developed understanding of the lived experiences of Algerian doctoral graduates as they returned home. While earlier chapters examined these dimensions separately for clarity, this synthesis acknowledges that, in practice, participants did not experience return as divided into distinct emotional or professional categories. Rather, these layers were intertwined and mutually shaping.

Throughout this chapter, I draw on participants' accounts, as analysed in Chapters Five and Six, to interpret re-entry as a negotiation of belonging, identity, professional, and institutional positioning. In doing so, I move beyond thematic description and critically interpret what the findings collectively reveal about return as a dynamic and context-sensitive process. In line with scholarship on re-entry adjustment and return migration (Gaw, 2000; Karakaş, 2020; Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019), I show that return is shaped not only by personal adaptation but by structural conditions, academic cultures, and institutional power relations.

I also use participants' lived experiences to show that re-entry was an ongoing process rather than a discrete transitional phase. Personal growth, professional reintegration, and identity negotiation continued long after participants physically returned, shaping how they understood themselves, how they interpreted their institutional environments, and how they positioned themselves within Algerian academia. In this sense, return is conceptualised not as closure but as recontextualisation: a process through which internationally shaped academic identities are continuously negotiated within local institutions.

By bringing the two findings chapters into dialogue, this synthesis offers added analytical value. It demonstrates that the emotional toll described in Chapter Five cannot be fully understood without considering the institutional constraints explored in Chapter Six, and vice versa. The chapter therefore integrates personal and professional dimensions to show that reintegration is best understood as a layered experience shaped by identity, institutional culture, global mobility,

and structural limitation. Through this integration, the chapter develops a more nuanced interpretation of return that contributes to broader discussions on academic mobility and professional reintegration in Global South contexts. The chapter begins by revisiting re-entry as disorientation and self-reconstruction, before turning to professional negotiation, resilience, belonging, and transformation. It then explicitly addresses the research questions and outlines the re-entry as a layered negotiation.

Re-entry as Disorientation and Self-Reconstruction

Returning to Algeria after completing doctoral studies in the United Kingdom was rarely experienced as a straightforward homecoming. Many participants, expecting familiarity and continuity, instead reported feelings of strangeness, disconnection, and emotional distance. These accounts closely reflect patterns noted in studies of reverse culture shock (Gaw, 2000; Alkhalaf, Al-Krenawi, and Elbedour, 2024), where the values, habits, and expectations developed abroad no longer align easily with those at home. However, participants' narratives suggest that reverse culture shock was not simply a matter of national culture. Rather, it involved a layered disruption encompassing social expectations, professional norms, and everyday relational dynamics.

This sense of disorientation extended beyond emotional discomfort. It represented a deeper disruption of identity. As Marginson (2014) argues, international education often promotes self-formation, independence, self-awareness, and expanded perspectives. Participants' narratives illustrated this self-formation clearly. Many described becoming more confident, more critical, and more autonomous during their doctoral studies. Yet upon return, these transformed perspectives did not seamlessly reintegrate into their previous social and professional environments.

What appeared across accounts was a tension between continuity and change. Participants physically returned to familiar spaces, but they no longer experienced them in the same way. Social norms that once felt natural were now experienced as restrictive or misaligned. This resonates with Jenkins' (2008) understanding of identity as socially negotiated and relational. Once again, throughout my thesis, I argue that identity is not fixed but continually shaped through interaction and recognition. In participants' experiences, the difficulty lay not only in adjusting themselves, but in navigating environments that did not necessarily recognise or accommodate their transformed selves.

Participants also described feeling misunderstood within their communities. Some spoke about conversations where their international experiences were minimised or not fully understood. Others described subtle distancing, where they felt "*different*" without being able to clearly

articulate why. As discussed in Chapter Five (GET1), participants such as Ghizlene and Autumn articulated this through references to feeling “*strange*” despite being physically home. This uncertainty mirrors findings in re-entry literature, where returnees often report feeling simultaneously at home and out of place (Gaw, 2000; Zhang, Zeng, and Zhang, 2022). The home environment remains familiar, yet the self has changed.

Importantly, however, this disorientation was not constant. Over time, participants developed strategies to navigate these tensions. Some recalibrated expectations; others consciously chose when to assert new perspectives and when to remain silent. Reflection played a central role in this process. As illustrated in Chapter Five and Six through participants’ accounts of gradual adjustment and emotional reframing, coping involved selective adaptation rather than withdrawal. Rather than rejecting their home context, participants gradually developed more nuanced understandings of how to inhabit it differently. In this sense, re-entry marked not a regression, but a reconfiguration of identity.

Synthesising the findings suggests that re-entry involved a dual negotiation: re-anchoring cultural belonging in a context that had not changed at the same pace as the self, while simultaneously integrating new perspectives without abandoning local attachments. Reverse culture shock, therefore, was not only about discomfort. It was about identity recalibration. Participants were not choosing between “*UK identity*” and “*Algerian identity*” Rather, they were learning to hold both in tension.

Across participants’ accounts, re-entry appeared most challenging where internal transformation was most pronounced and external environments remained comparatively static. Those navigating simultaneous life transitions, such as Yasmine, whose return coincided with marriage, academic completion, and intensified cultural expectations, described cumulative emotional strain that exceeded cultural readjustment alone. Similarly, female participants who had developed increased autonomy abroad experienced heightened difficulty when transformed gender identities encountered persistent relational expectations, as reflected in Samar’s resistance to traditional roles and Autumn’s experience of professional restriction. Participants whose professional identities were strongly shaped by internationally internalised academic norms, such as Akram, also reported intensified tension when institutional cultures constrained autonomy or innovation. These patterned experiences suggest that reverse culture shock was amplified not merely by national cultural difference, but by the degree of dissonance between reconfigured identity and relatively unchanged social or institutional frameworks. A key finding across participants’ accounts is that re-entry difficulty was shaped less by national cultural difference

alone and more by the degree of identity misalignment between transformed selves and relatively unchanged institutional or relational environments.

This synthesis advances existing scholarship by reconceptualising reverse culture shock as temporary adjustment stress. Instead, it conceptualises re-entry as a dynamic process of identity renegotiation shaped by social recognition, cultural expectations, and professional positioning. This provides a more context-sensitive understanding of return in Global South academic contexts, where institutional and cultural structures may shift more slowly than individual transformation. What becomes analytically significant here is that these processes of emotional recalibration and identity renegotiation did not conclude at the personal level. Rather, they shaped the lens through which participants interpreted institutional culture and professional positioning upon return. In this sense, personal re-entry experiences formed the interpretive foundation for subsequent professional negotiation.

Navigating Professional Realities: Clashing Professional Identities and Institutional Culture

If re-entry at the personal level involved disorientation and self-reconstruction, the professional sphere intensified these tensions in more visible and structured ways. Upon returning to Algerian universities, participants did not simply resume academic roles; they entered institutional environments where their transformed professional identities encountered established norms, hierarchies, and expectations. Across the findings, it became evident that workplace tensions were not only about resistance to innovation or bureaucratic inefficiency. As discussed in Chapter Six (GET2 and GET3), participants such as Akram, Amani, Ghizlene, and Autumn described these tensions through experiences of hierarchical resistance, constrained autonomy, and limited institutional recognition.

Many participants returned with a strong sense of professional purpose shaped by their doctoral training in the United Kingdom. Their experiences abroad appeared to normalise research-informed teaching approaches, student-centred pedagogies, and expectations of innovation grounded in scholarly evidence. These practices became embedded within participants' professional self-understanding. However, upon returning to Algerian university contexts, participants frequently encountered institutional environments characterised by established routines, hierarchical dynamics, and resistance to pedagogical change. These challenges were not solely interpersonal but reflected broader structural conditions shaping academic work. Structural analyses suggest that Algeria's significant investment in higher education has produced a growing cohort of highly educated graduates, yet limited professional opportunities and systemic

constraints have contributed to outward mobility and brain drain (Nour, 2019). Within this context, participants' efforts to introduce innovation were shaped not only by local departmental dynamics but also by wider institutional pressures that constrained organisational receptivity to change. This pattern echoes the detailed accounts presented in Chapter Six, where attempts to introduce research-informed practices were experienced as both practical obstacles and challenges to professional legitimacy.

This tension can be understood through the lens of identity negotiation (Jenkins, 2008) and professional community membership (Wenger, 1998). Participants had internalised norms from one academic community and returned to another with different expectations of authority, collaboration, and pedagogical legitimacy. When their approaches were questioned or dismissed, the challenge was not simply practical. It became relational and symbolic. Their credibility, agency, and sense of belonging were implicitly tested.

Several participants described moments where attempts to introduce research-informed practices were met with scepticism or subtle resistance. As discussed in Chapter Six, Akram's account of departmental resistance, Autumn's experience of constrained collaboration, and Ghizlene's attempt to introduce curriculum reform which was met with institutional hesitation illustrate how these tensions were experienced not merely as disagreement but as challenges to professional credibility and academic authority. These encounters often left them questioning not only institutional openness but also their own positioning within the academic hierarchy. In this sense, professional reintegration required them to renegotiate how their expertise was recognised. As Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva (2019) argue, returnees frequently experience tensions when globally acquired knowledge meets locally embedded institutional logics. The tension arises not because one system is inherently superior, but because academic cultures operate according to distinct norms of legitimacy and authority.

The clash was therefore not simply methodological; it was academic. Participants' doctoral experiences had reshaped their understanding of what constitutes "*good teaching*" or "*rigorous research*." When these standards did not align seamlessly with local expectations, they experienced professional dissonance. Gu and Schweisfurth (2015) similarly note that pedagogical misalignment can occur when internationally trained academics return to environments where traditional norms hold institutional authority. In such cases, innovation may be perceived not as enrichment but as disruption.

At the same time, these tensions revealed important dimensions of agency. Participants did not uniformly withdraw; instead, they adopted varied coping strategies that allowed them to navigate

institutional constraints while preserving aspects of their professional identity. Some maintained persistence in introducing research-informed practices despite resistance, framing innovation as integral to their academic integrity. Others recalibrated their expectations, recognising the pace and limits of institutional change and focusing on achievable goals within their immediate spheres of influence.

For several participants, the classroom emerged as a micro-space of transformation, where student-centred or interactive teaching approaches could be sustained even when broader structural reform felt unattainable. This was evident in participants' reflections on sustaining student-centred practices despite broader institutional rigidity (see Chapter Six, GET2). In other cases, coping involved strategic adaptation, including managing expectations, temporarily withholding ideas to avoid conflict, or redirecting energy toward personal development, research activities, or supportive professional relationships. These strategies illustrate how returnees negotiated between aspiration and contextual realities, reflecting what Karakaş (2020) describes as adaptive negotiation, whereby individuals balance innovation with sensitivity to local institutional cultures. Rather than representing passive adjustment, these coping mechanisms demonstrate active sense-making processes through which participants sought to maintain purpose and agency while navigating environments that did not always recognise internationally shaped professional identities.

Within this study, reintegration emerges not as a passive return to familiar professional routines, but as an active and often unsettling process in which participants reassess their place, purpose, and expectations within local academic environments. The need to recalibrate aspirations, described across accounts, reflects a broader pattern in which internationally shaped professional identities encounter rigid institutional norms and limited organisational receptivity. This aligns with research conceptualising re-entry as a critical phase of professional and identity negotiation rather than simple adjustment (Black, Gregersen, and Mendenhall, 1992; Presbitero, 2016). Participants' accounts suggest that the frustration they experienced was not merely personal dissatisfaction, but a response to misaligned expectations and constrained opportunities for contribution, a pattern similarly observed among academic returnees in other contexts characterised by inflexible workplace cultures and resistance to change (Pham and Saito, 2020; Karakaş, 2020). In this sense, professional disengagement or strategic withdrawal can be understood not as failure, but as a recalibration of self in response to institutional limits, echoing work on identity negotiation during re-entry that emphasises how belonging, legitimacy, and professional agency are renegotiated over time (Sussman, 2002; Wenger, 1998).

Building on these adaptive responses, synthesising participants' accounts suggests that professional reintegration involved negotiating three interrelated tensions. First, the tension between autonomy and hierarchy. Doctoral training in the UK often emphasised independence and critical voice, whereas local institutional cultures sometimes prioritised seniority and established authority (Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019; Pham and Saito, 2020). Second, the tension between collaborative academic practices and more individualised institutional routines. Participants accustomed to collaborative environments sometimes encountered siloed practices upon return. Third, the tension between internationally shaped pedagogical approaches and locally embedded academic expectations, where research-informed and student-centred practices encountered established routines and hierarchical norms. These tensions were not always overt conflicts; rather, they often operated subtly through everyday interactions and implicit expectations, shaping the strategies participants adopted to sustain their professional agency.

Importantly, these clashes did not result in extensive rejection of local academic culture. Rather, participants described learning when to assert, when to adapt, and when to remain patient. Over time, many developed a more layered professional identity that accommodated both international and local logics. In this sense, professional identity was not replaced but expanded; reintegration became a process of holding multiple academic orientations in dialogue.

This integrated interpretation allows for a more nuanced understanding of workplace tension. Instead of viewing resistance as mere institutional backwardness, reintegration can be understood as an encounter between distinct professional cultures. The challenge for returnees was therefore not only structural but interpretive: making sense of how to remain authentic to their transformed academic values while functioning within systems shaped by different historical and cultural trajectories. Participants' experiences thus illustrate that professional reintegration is inseparable from identity negotiation, where personal transformation and professional expectation continually intersect. These professional tensions further illuminate that reverse culture shock in this context extended beyond national identity into academic and institutional cultures.

Reverse Culture Shock: Beyond National Culture

As discussed in Chapter Five (Subtheme 1, GET1), participants frequently described feelings of disorientation, alienation, and difficulty readjusting to everyday life upon return. These experiences were initially presented as emotional and cultural readjustment challenges. In this synthesis, however, I extend that discussion by clarifying that the “*culture*” in question was not

limited to national identity. Rather, participants were negotiating multiple cultural layers: national culture, workplace culture, academic culture, and professional norms.

Reverse culture shock, as described by Gaw (2000), involves difficulty readjusting to previously familiar environments. Yet participants' accounts suggest that the shock stemmed less from national identity itself and more from the misalignment between the academic and professional cultures they had internalised abroad and the institutional practices they encountered at home. For example, Hanaa's reflection on the disruption of "*routine*" illustrates how cultural difference was experienced through everyday practices rather than abstract national belonging. Similarly, Akram's frustration with hierarchical departmental dynamics and Autumn's experience of professional restriction reveal that the sense of "*strangeness*" often emerged in workplace interactions, administrative procedures, and pedagogical expectations.

These accounts suggest that reverse culture shock operated across relational and institutional sites rather than being confined to social or familial reintegration. The difficulty lay not simply in returning to Algeria as a national context, but in renegotiating participation within academic and professional communities whose norms differed from those internalised during doctoral training. In this sense, reverse culture shock in this study is best understood as layered and context-dependent, reflecting identity misalignment within multiple cultural domains.

A Journey of Transformation: Gratitude and Lasting Impact

As the synthesis unfolds, it becomes clear that participants did not interpret their return solely through the lens of difficulty. Alongside frustration, resistance, and structural barriers, there was a consistent narrative of gratitude and long-term transformation. In this section, I argue and show that gratitude was not a superficial emotional response, but part of a deeper reflective process through which participants made sense of their return and sustained their commitment to contribution.

Throughout the interviews, participants frequently described their doctoral experience in the UK as life-changing. This transformation extended beyond academic credentials. It involved shifts in thinking, confidence, reflexivity, and intercultural awareness. As Marginson (2014) argues, international education often facilitates self-formation, enabling individuals to develop independence and new ways of understanding the world. Participants' accounts strongly resonate with this notion. They returned not simply with degrees, but with altered epistemological orientations and heightened self-awareness.

Importantly, gratitude functioned as a stabilising force during reintegration. When participants encountered bureaucratic inefficiencies, professional resistance, or resource constraints, they often contextualised these challenges within a broader narrative of personal growth. Rather than interpreting difficulties as evidence of failure, they positioned them as part of a longer journey. This reflective stance mirrors Mezirow's (1991; 2000) account of transformative learning, where individuals reinterpret disruptive experiences in light of newly developed perspectives.

Gratitude also shaped professional behaviour. Participants frequently described feeling a sense of responsibility to “*give back*” to their country, departments, or students. This sense of obligation aligns with Lazarova (2014), who notes that returnees often feel compelled to contribute to national or institutional development. However, in this study, that contribution was not always framed as grand reform. Instead, it appeared in everyday practices: mentoring students, introducing new teaching approaches, maintaining research integrity, and modelling critical thinking. What emerges here is a reframing of return. Rather than viewing reintegration solely as a process of adaptation, participants increasingly interpreted it as an opportunity for meaningful influence. Even when systemic change was slow, they derived purpose from incremental impact. This reinforces the idea that transformation continued after return; it did not end with mobility.

The notion of lasting impact must also be understood relationally. Participants' influence was visible in student engagement, evolving classroom practices, and subtle shifts in collegial interactions. These forms of impact may appear modest in structural terms, yet they represent the translation of international experience into local practice. As Chen and Li (2019) and Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva (2019) suggest, returning academics often act as bridges between global and local academic cultures. In this study, that bridging role was evident not through immediate institutional reform, but through sustained professional commitment.

By integrating gratitude into the synthesis, I show that reintegration was not defined solely by tension. It was also characterised by reflective meaning-making and enduring professional purpose. Participants' journeys demonstrate that international doctoral study had a lasting influence on how they understood themselves, their responsibilities, and their roles within Algerian academia. This section therefore strengthens the broader analytical claim of the thesis: reintegration is not merely adjustment to constraints, but an ongoing process of transformation in which global experiences are reinterpreted and recontextualised within local realities.

Relating the Findings to the Research Questions

This study was guided by three interrelated research questions concerning the experience of transition, navigation of the professional landscape, and the influence of international doctoral

education on contributions to Algerian academia. Bringing the findings together allows for a clearer articulation of how these questions have been addressed, demonstrating that the processes of transition, adaptation, and contribution were deeply interconnected rather than discrete stages.

The first research question explored how UK-based Algerian doctoral graduates experienced their transition to Algeria and the personal and professional implications of their return. The study indicates that transition was neither linear nor confined to institutional reintegration; rather, it involved complex processes of emotional adjustment, identity negotiation, and cultural recalibration. Participants' accounts show that re-entry disrupted previously taken-for-granted assumptions about belonging and everyday practices. Experiences described by participants such as Ghizlene and Autumn reveal how familiar environments became newly visible through transformed expectations, where routine interactions with institutions or social norms generated feelings of disorientation or misalignment. These narratives illustrate that reverse culture shock operated across multiple levels, not only as national cultural readjustment but also through workplace practices, relational expectations, and everyday social interactions.

Emotional responses to transition varied considerably, reflecting individual meaning-making processes. For example, Insaf framed re-entry as challenging but manageable through proactive coping and intentional reframing, while Yasmine's experience illustrated cumulative emotional overload resulting from the convergence of personal, academic, and cultural pressures. Such variation demonstrates that the psychological impact of transition was mediated less by the presence of challenges themselves than by how individuals interpreted and negotiated their changing circumstances. Gendered dimensions further shaped these experiences. Narratives such as Samar's renegotiation of gender roles and Autumn's encounter with restrictions on professional collaboration reveal that re-entry often involved confronting tensions between transformed identities and persistent social expectations. These findings suggest that transition was fundamentally relational, involving ongoing negotiation between self-perception and external recognition within familial, social, and professional contexts.

The second research question examined how graduates navigated the professional landscape upon return. The findings indicate that navigation was characterised by strategic adaptation rather than passive assimilation. Participants described a process of negotiating institutional structures that did not always align with the academic norms or professional expectations developed during their doctoral training abroad. Accounts such as Akram's highlight the experience of professional dissonance, where aspirations for innovation or academic autonomy encountered structural limitations within local institutional environments. Rather than abandoning their professional

identities, participants engaged in incremental and context-sensitive forms of adaptation, selectively introducing new pedagogical approaches, redefining professional success, and building informal networks to sustain their work. Navigation therefore emerged as an ongoing process shaped by the tension between agency and constraint, where returnees continuously recalibrated their expectations while attempting to preserve elements of their internationally shaped academic identities.

The third research question explored how international academic experiences shaped participants' contributions to academia and professional practice. The findings demonstrate that contributions were often subtle and relational rather than immediately visible at structural levels. Participants described changes in their approaches to teaching, mentoring, feedback practices, and research engagement, reflecting shifts in epistemological orientation developed through international doctoral training. For example, narratives emphasising increased critical thinking, autonomy, and intercultural awareness suggest that global academic exposure reshaped how participants conceptualised their roles as educators and scholars. Although systemic constraints sometimes limited large-scale institutional change, participants continued to enact these influences through everyday professional practice. International academic capital therefore persisted in local contexts through incremental transformation of pedagogical and relational practices rather than overt institutional reform.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that the three research questions intersect through a central process of identity negotiation. Transition, professional navigation, and contribution cannot be understood independently; each reflects an ongoing effort to reconcile transformed personal and professional identities with institutional and cultural environments that often remained relatively unchanged.

Broader Implications

The findings carry implications for institutional policy, professional development structures, and broader understandings of academic mobility in Global South contexts. At the institutional level, participants' experiences demonstrate that reintegration cannot be assumed to occur automatically or simply as a natural consequence of return. As illustrated across Chapters Five and Six, the process of professional repositioning required sustained negotiation rather than seamless transition. Structured onboarding processes, transparent credential recognition mechanisms, and sustained professional development opportunities therefore become critical. In the absence of such institutional scaffolding, internationally trained scholars risk not only the underutilisation of

their expertise but also prolonged identity misalignment within academic communities (Wenger, 1998; Sussman, 2002).

The study further suggests that reintegration must be recognised as both professional and psychological. The identity tensions described throughout the findings indicate that mentoring schemes, peer support networks, and spaces for reflective dialogue could function as institutional sites of negotiated belonging. Such structures would not merely facilitate adjustment but would support the recontextualisation of global academic capital within locally embedded institutional logics (Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019). As the pandemic-related findings demonstrate, institutional fragility can intensify reintegration challenges, reinforcing the importance of adaptable and resilient higher education systems capable of responding to global disruption (Marginson, 2020; Pham and Saito, 2020).

At a broader level, the findings complicate dominant narratives of “brain gain” or “brain circulation.” The return of highly trained scholars does not automatically translate into institutional transformation. Rather, the absorption of global knowledge is mediated by organisational culture, structural readiness, and administrative flexibility. This perspective extends debates on internationalisation (Altbach, 2014; Knight, 2020) by foregrounding the relational and institutional conditions under which mobility leads to meaningful and sustained change. Importantly, the study underscores that reintegration should not be conceptualised solely as the responsibility of returnees. Reintegration is relational and structurally mediated. It unfolds within institutional cultures, generational hierarchies, and historically embedded governance systems. Recognising this relational dimension shifts analytical and policy attention from individual adaptation toward systemic reflexivity and institutional reform. Having addressed the broader implications, I now return to the core analytical claim of the chapter to further refine the conceptualisation of re-entry as layered negotiation.

Re-entry as Layered Negotiation and Ongoing Becoming

Drawing the personal, cultural, and professional dimensions together reveals that re-entry for UK-trained Algerian doctoral graduates cannot be understood as a discrete transition from one stable state to another. Rather, it emerges as a layered and context-sensitive negotiation that unfolds over time. The findings demonstrate that reintegration involved emotional recalibration, identity re-alignment, professional repositioning, and ongoing meaning-making. These dimensions did not occur sequentially. They intersected, overlapped, and at times intensified one another.

At the emotional and cultural level, participants' accounts reveal that familiarity did not guarantee ease. Expectations of comfort were often disrupted by subtle experiences of distance and misalignment, particularly in everyday routines and relational expectations (see Chapter Five, GET1, Subtheme 1). This confirms that reverse culture shock, as discussed earlier (Chapter Three) and elaborated in the findings chapters (Five), operates not only as emotional discomfort but as a disturbance of taken-for-granted meanings (Gaw, 2000; Alsulami, 2020). In participants' narratives, reverse culture shock was experienced less as dramatic cultural rupture and more as gradual recognition that they had changed in ways that represented familiar environments newly unfamiliar.

At the professional level, reintegration was shaped by structural constraints and institutional rigidity. Participants described navigating established routines, hierarchical dynamics, and bureaucratic processes that limited opportunities for innovation and slowed professional progression. These experiences suggest that the challenges encountered were not solely interpersonal but embedded within wider institutional structures that shaped how internationally trained academics could enact their roles.

The key findings of this study resonate with broader structural analyses highlighting governance challenges, limited professional prospects, and bureaucratic constraints as factors influencing mobility trajectories and shaping return experiences (Nour, 2019). However, the findings extend this literature by demonstrating how such structural conditions were experienced at the level of identity and professional legitimacy. Rather than representing isolated frustrations, these constraints formed part of a broader institutional environment within which returnees were required to recalibrate expectations and renegotiate their professional positioning, a process consistent with conceptualisations of identity as negotiated participation within communities of practice and as subject to cultural identity shift during re-entry (Wenger, 1998; Sussman, 2002).

This intersection helps explain why reintegration was described as both destabilising and enriching. Participants did not simply adapt; they recalibrated. They revised expectations, reinterpreted success, and refined their strategies for contribution. Their accounts illustrate what Mezirow (1991; 2000) conceptualisation of transformative learning, particularly the idea that perspective transformation involves ongoing critical reflection and reorientation of meaning frameworks. In this study, transformation did not conclude with the completion of doctoral study but continued through the process of return and contextual negotiation.

The synthesis also highlights the importance of understanding reintegration as a longitudinal and evolving process rather than a short transitional phase. Reintegration was not a singular event

confined to the first months of return. It unfolded across years, shaped by cumulative interactions, institutional experiences, and evolving self-understandings. A key finding of this study is that belonging was not restored automatically through physical presence; rather, it was gradually reconstructed through relational engagement, professional agency, and reflective meaning-making (Wenger, 1998; Jenkins, 2008).

This layered understanding advances the conceptualisation of return migration and therefore constitutes one of the thesis's key original contributions to knowledge. While earlier adjustment models have often conceptualised re-entry in terms of measurable outcomes or stages of successful or unsuccessful reintegration (Gullahorn and Gullahorn, 1963; Black, Gregersen, and Mendenhall, 1992; Ward, Bochner, and Furnham, 2001), more recent scholarship has argued that return should be understood as an ongoing process of negotiation unfolding within wider transnational networks (Gu and Schweisfurth, 2015). The original contribution of this thesis lies in demonstrating that re-entry among Algerian doctoral returnees is best understood not as cultural readjustment alone, nor as a simple stage of professional adjustment, but as sustained identity negotiation unfolding within structurally constrained academic environments.

Building on this latter perspective, the findings of this study demonstrate that return is characterised by continuous negotiation within structural and institutional boundaries, where agency and constraint coexist. Innovation and resistance operate simultaneously and belonging and dislocation are experienced in parallel. Similarly, research on professional identity development emphasises that identity formation is not linear but evolves through continuous negotiation between personal values, institutional cultures, and wider social expectations (Trede, Macklin, and Bridges, 2012; Mackay, 2017).

By bringing together the personal and professional findings, the synthesis reveals that reintegration is best understood as a process of ongoing identity negotiation rather than a completed transition. In line with conceptualisations of identity as continuously shaped through social participation and relational recognition (Wenger, 1998; Jenkins, 2008), participants did not return as fixed versions of who they had become abroad, nor did they simply revert to previous identities. Instead, they occupied an in-between professional position, drawing from globally shaped academic practices while operating within locally embedded institutional frameworks. This positioning reflects what Gu and Schweisfurth (2015) describe as sustained negotiation across transnational spaces, where return does not signify closure but continued reconfiguration. For many participants, this in-between orientation was not merely transitional; it became a sustained mode of professional existence.

Importantly, this study demonstrates that internationally trained doctoral returnees in the Algerian context navigate not only structural limitations but academic tensions. They carry with them pedagogical values, research ethics, and relational approaches that may not fully align with local academic traditions. The resulting tension is not simply institutional resistance; it reflects deeper differences in academic culture. As discussed earlier in this chapter, similar tensions have been observed when globally acquired academic practices encounter locally embedded institutional logics (Kuzhabekova, Sparks, and Temerbayeva, 2019). Recognising this academic dimension strengthens the analytical contribution of the study by shifting the focus from organisational inefficiency alone to culturally embedded understandings of academic legitimacy.

Using my participants' accounts, I therefore reframe return not as a question of individual resilience alone, but as a relational process shaped by institutional culture, historical conditions, and global-local interaction. Participants' resilience was not innate. It was cultivated through reflection, peer support, classroom engagement, and sustained commitment to meaningful practice.

Furthermore, the inclusion of the COVID-19 context adds additional complexity. Reintegration occurred within a period of global instability that intensified structural vulnerabilities. This temporal layer demonstrates that return must be understood within broader socio-political conditions rather than as a context-free psychological adjustment.

The findings of this chapter demonstrate that re-entry for Algerian doctoral graduates trained in the UK is multidimensional, prolonged, and shaped by intersecting dimensions. While this interpretation foregrounds negotiation and transformation, it is important to recognise that reintegration trajectories were not uniform. The extent of tension and negotiation was mediated by institutional positioning, timing of return, and access to support networks.

This synthesis strengthens the overall argument of the thesis, which contends that re-entry for UK-trained Algerian doctoral graduates is not a linear process of adjustment, but a multidimensional and identity-level negotiation shaped by institutional culture, structural limitation, and relational belonging. By moving beyond thematic description toward a more integrated interpretation of return as lived experience, the chapter demonstrates that the personal and professional dimensions of reintegration cannot be analytically separated without concealing how they continuously shape one another in practice. The chapter therefore provides the conceptual bridge necessary to understand reintegration not simply as adjustment, but as negotiated transformation within constraint.

A further key argument developed in this chapter is that internationally shaped knowledge does not dissolve upon return. Rather, it continues to inform teaching practice, research orientation, and relational engagement, even when structural constraints limit visible reform. In this sense, the impact of international education is subtle yet enduring, operating through incremental pedagogical shifts and sustained professional commitments rather than immediate institutional transformation.

Conclusion

In this chapter, I have drawn together the key findings of the study to demonstrate that re-entry is best understood as a negotiated, layered, and ongoing process. By integrating the personal, cultural, and professional dimensions explored in the previous chapters, I have shown that reintegration involves identity recalibration, professional repositioning, emotional resilience, and institutional negotiation. These processes unfold simultaneously and shape one another in complex ways. The synthesis clarifies that the experience of return for UK-trained Algerian doctoral graduates cannot be reduced to structural barriers or personal coping strategies alone. Rather, it reflects the interaction between transformed academic identities and institutional contexts that may not fully absorb them. Through reflection, persistence, and incremental agency, participants gradually reconstructed belonging and professional purpose.

The chapter also demonstrates that internationally shaped knowledge does not dissolve upon return. It continues to inform teaching practice, research orientation, and relational engagement, even when structural constraints limit visible reform. In this sense, the impact of international education is subtle but enduring.

Having integrated the personal and professional dimensions of the findings, the thesis now moves to its final stage. The General Conclusion chapter brings together the overall argument of the study, reflects on its theoretical and methodological contributions, and outlines implications for policy, institutional practice, and future research. It also revisits the central claims of the thesis in light of the integrated analysis presented here, situating the study within wider debates on academic mobility, return migration, and higher education development in the Global South.

Chapter Eight

General Conclusion

Introduction

In this concluding chapter, I draw together the overall argument of the thesis and restate what the study has shown about the re-entry experiences of Algerian doctoral graduates returning from the United Kingdom. I revisit the key findings across the personal, cultural, and professional dimensions of reintegration and clarify the study's contribution to knowledge within scholarship on international doctoral mobility, return migration, and professional reintegration in Global South contexts. I then outline recommendations arising from the findings, reflect on the limitations of the study, and propose priorities for future research. Finally, I offer reflexive reflections on the research journey, including the methodological value and demands of IPA, and the ways this doctoral process has shaped my development as a researcher and a future returnee

Summary of the Process

This study examined the re-entry experiences of Algerian doctoral graduates who completed their PhD studies in the United Kingdom and returned to reintegrate into the Algerian higher education system. It explored the personal, professional, and cultural dimensions of reintegration, with particular attention to how participants navigated identity transformation, institutional expectations, and the complexities of returning to familiar yet newly experienced environments. By focusing on an underexplored context, the research sought to deepen understanding of academic return migration and its implications for higher education development.

The research developed from a critical engagement with literature on international student mobility and return migration, which revealed limited attention to the lived experiences of doctoral returnees within North African contexts. This gap informed the refinement of the study's focus on Algerian PhD graduates, enabling a context-sensitive exploration of how globally trained scholars re-enter local academic systems shaped by distinct institutional and cultural dynamics.

A qualitative approach grounded in Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (Smith, Flowers, and Larkin, 2022) was adopted to capture participants' lived experiences and sense-making processes. Through semi-structured interviews with eighteen participants, the study explored how returnees interpreted their reintegration journeys and negotiated challenges related to professional legitimacy, cultural readaptation, and structural constraints within Algerian academia.

Taken together, the findings demonstrate that reintegration is best understood not as a simple process of adjustment but as a layered and relational process of identity negotiation. Participants' experiences revealed tensions between internationally shaped academic practices and locally embedded institutional norms, highlighting how reverse culture shock extended beyond national culture to include workplace practices, pedagogical expectations, and professional hierarchies. Despite encountering bureaucratic and structural challenges, participants exercised agency through adaptive strategies, incremental innovation, and ongoing recalibration of expectations.

By providing one of the first in-depth explorations of Algerian doctoral returnees, the study expands existing scholarship on academic mobility and return migration. It situates reintegration as an ongoing and contextually mediated process shaped by the interaction between global academic experiences and local institutional realities, offering insights that contribute to broader debates on internationalisation, identity negotiation, and higher education transformation in Global South contexts.

Contribution to Knowledge

This thesis makes an original contribution to scholarship on return migration by providing one of the first in-depth interpretative phenomenological analyses of the re-entry experiences of Algerian doctoral graduates. Drawing directly on participants' lived experiences, I argue that reintegration is not a singular or linear process of cultural readjustment but a layered and contextually mediated negotiation of identity unfolding across personal, professional, organisational, and academic domains.

By foregrounding participants' voices, the study challenges dominant assumptions within existing literature that frame reverse culture shock primarily as national cultural dissonance. Instead, participants' accounts demonstrate that reintegration is shaped equally by workplace cultures, institutional bureaucracies, pedagogical norms, and professional hierarchies, highlighting the significance of organisational and academic contexts in shaping return trajectories. This reframing extends current understandings of reverse culture shock beyond individual psychological adjustment toward a more relational and structurally embedded perspective.

Situated within broader debates on international academic mobility, this research addresses a significant empirical gap concerning international doctoral returnees, particularly within North African and wider Arab contexts. Existing studies have largely focused on selected national cases, such as Saudi Arabia (Alandejani, 2013; Alfurayh and Burns, 2020; Alsulami, 2021), with limited attention to other regions. By focusing on Algerian doctoral graduates, the study expands the

geographical and contextual scope of return migration research and highlights how local institutional cultures and structural conditions shape reintegration experiences.

Methodologically, the study contributes through its use of IPA, foregrounding participants' lived experiences and sense-making processes. This approach enables a nuanced exploration of identity negotiation, professional positioning, and meaning-making during re-entry, offering insights that extend beyond structural or policy-focused analyses.

In addition, the researcher's contextual familiarity with the Algerian academic environment facilitated culturally sensitive interpretation while maintaining reflexive awareness of positionality. This perspective supported deeper engagement with participants' narratives and contributed to a richer understanding of the relational and context-specific dimensions of reintegration.

Finally, this thesis contributes to broader debates on internationalisation and academic mobility by demonstrating that academic return is not simply the conclusion of mobility but an ongoing process of identity negotiation shaped by the interaction between globally developed academic perspectives and locally embedded institutional realities. In doing so, the study responds to growing calls within the literature to recognise marginalised and underexamined experiences within global higher education and to move beyond standardised narratives of international student mobility.

Recommendations Arising from the Study

Given the complexities identified in the re-entry experiences of Algerian PhD holders, several key recommendations emerge for policymakers and educational institutions:

Development of Tailored Support Programmes: There is a critical need for the creation of structured support programmes specifically designed for returning PhD holders. These programmes should include career planning services, mentorship opportunities, and workshops on navigating the local academic landscape. Such initiatives could significantly ease the transition and help returnees apply their skills more effectively within the Algerian context. For instance, mentorship programmes could pair returnees with experienced local academics who can guide them through the nuances of the Algerian academic system, thus fostering a smoother integration process.

Enhancing Institutional Support Structures: Universities should implement comprehensive onboarding processes for returning scholars, including orientations that address the specific challenges of re-entry. This could involve practical job previews, support in navigating

administrative procedures, and platforms for knowledge sharing that integrate returnees' international experiences into the local academic discourse. By incorporating returnees into collaborative research projects and international networks, institutions can maximise their global expertise to enhance academic outcomes locally.

Strengthening Policy Frameworks: The findings suggest the need for a more robust policy framework that recognises the unique contributions of returning PhD holders. Policymakers should consider developing incentives for returnees, such as research grants, collaborative opportunities with international institutions, and pathways for career progression that maximise their international expertise. Such policies would not only enhance the reintegration process but also contribute to the broader goal of internationalising Algerian higher education, positioning it as a competitive player in the global academic field.

Fostering Collaborative Networks: Encouraging collaborations between returnees and local academics can help bridge the gap between different academic cultures and practices. Establishing networks that connect returning scholars with their peers both in Algeria and abroad can promote ongoing professional development and enhance the overall academic environment. These networks can serve as platforms for sharing best practices, exchanging ideas, and co-authoring publications, thereby enriching the academic landscape with diverse perspectives.

Addressing Cultural and Professional Re-entry Challenges: Institutions should provide resources that help returnees manage the psychological and cultural aspects of re-entry, such as workshops on dealing with reverse culture shock and adapting to different academic expectations. Acknowledging the emotional dimensions of re-entry is crucial for supporting the overall well-being of returning scholars. Creating a supportive community within academic institutions, where returnees can share their experiences and challenges, can foster a sense of belonging and reduce feelings of isolation.

Challenges of the Study

While this study provides valuable insights into the re-entry experiences of Algerian PhD holders, it is important to acknowledge certain challenges and limitations that shaped the scope and outcomes of the research. These limitations, inherent to the study design, context, and methodology, highlight both the challenges faced during the research process and the opportunities for further exploration. Recognising these constraints is essential for situating the findings within a realistic framework and understanding their applicability and implications.

Access Challenges: One major challenge was accessing participants. The returnees were dispersed across various cities in Algeria, and the number who had completed their PhDs and returned was relatively small. Additionally, participants had to meet specific criteria: they needed to be actively teaching, not just waiting for job opportunities. This requirement further limited the pool of potential participants. Despite reaching out to many, several did not meet these criteria, either because they hadn't returned or hadn't started teaching yet. Moreover, two participants who agreed to take part unfortunately did not show up on the interview dates. Fortunately, some participants went above and beyond by helping to reach out to their colleagues and friends, which was instrumental in gathering a diverse range of perspectives.

Probing Due to Shared Context: During the interviews, there was a possibility that I might encounter difficulty probing questions related to the Algerian context with some participants. As we share the same cultural and institutional background, participants often assumed I already understood what they meant, leading to a lack of elaboration on some responses. This aligns with the observations of Brett and Wheeler (2022), who argued that it is more challenging to probe effectively when the interviewer and interviewee share a common context, as shared assumptions can hinder deeper exploration of certain topics. To avoid that, I have conducted semi structured interviews to help me probe.

Impact of COVID-19: Researching the COVID-19 pandemic added another layer of complexity. With restrictions on in-person meetings, I had to rely on virtual interviews, which may have affected the depth of our interactions. Despite these limitations, I adjusted my approach by creating a supportive, conversational online environment and by allowing participants more time and space to express themselves. These adaptations helped ensure that the data remained detailed, meaningful, and reflective of their lived experiences.

Lack of Data from Official Sources of Algeria: One notable limitation of this study was the lack of comprehensive data from official sources regarding the Algerian scholarship scheme. Despite my attempts to reach out to relevant institutions via email and formally request documentation, no responses were received. While this did not affect the integrity or depth of my findings, as the participants' narratives provided rich, firsthand insights into their experiences, having access to official records would have added an additional layer of understanding. Specifically, data on the number of scholarship recipients who returned and secured employment would have helped contextualise the broader impact of the scheme on reintegration and professional outcomes. This limitation highlights the importance of institutional transparency and

accessible records, which would not only enhance future research but also support a more comprehensive evaluation of such programmes' effectiveness.

Acknowledging these limitations helps contextualise the findings and underscores the need for continued exploration of re-entry experiences. Despite these constraints, the study remains a valuable starting point for deeper understanding and further research in this area.

Areas for Future Research Arising from the Research

Despite these limitations, this study provides a substantial contribution to understanding the re-entry experiences of Algerian PhD holders, offering new insights into the unique challenges and opportunities faced by this group. By addressing a significant gap in the literature, it has emphasised the complex interplay between personal, cultural, and professional dimensions of reintegration, while highlighting the resilience of returnees and the systemic barriers they navigate. These findings are not only relevant to Algeria but also contribute to the broader discourse on return migration and internationalisation in higher education. Reflecting on these findings, several exciting directions for future research emerge that could build on this foundational work:

Comparative Insights: It would be intriguing to see studies that compare the re-entry experiences of Algerian PhD holders with those from other countries. This could help identify both unique challenges and common themes across different contexts. Understanding how re-entry processes differ around the world could offer valuable lessons and best practices for improving support for returnees.

Long-Term Perspectives: Tracking returnees over several years could provide deeper insights into how their experiences change over time. This type of longitudinal study could reveal long-term trends and how returnees adapt and grow in their roles, offering a fuller picture of the re-entry journey.

Mixed-Methods Approaches: Combining qualitative and quantitative methods could offer a richer, more rounded view of re-entry experiences. While qualitative research captures personal stories and nuances, quantitative data can provide broader validation and general trends. A mixed-methods approach might help paint a more complete picture of what returnees go through.

Diverse Participant Criteria: For future research, it could be beneficial to include a wider variety of PhD holders from different roles and fields. It's also worth considering those who are still in the process of returning home, not just those who have already made the transition. This

broader approach could give us a fuller picture of the challenges and opportunities they face, as well as their hopes and expectations as they prepare for their return.

Support Mechanisms: Exploring how different institutions and support systems impact the re-entry experience could be useful. Research could focus on how universities and governments can better assist returnees through tailored programmes, mentorship, and resources, helping to create a smoother transition.

Effects of Global Events: Given the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on this study, examining how global events affect re-entry experiences could be insightful. Research could explore how crises influence the challenges and opportunities faced by returning scholars and how institutions can better support them during such times.

Expanding Geographic Focus: With more time and resources, it would be interesting to expand research to include other North African or Middle Eastern countries. This broader scope could enhance our understanding of regional trends and issues related to the reintegration of PhD holders.

By highlighting these avenues for future research, this study contributes to a more inclusive and dynamic understanding of the re-entry experiences of internationally educated scholars. Its findings lay the groundwork for actionable interventions that can empower returnees, enhance institutional practices, and ensure that the benefits of international education are fully realised within the home context. Ultimately, this research underscores the importance of embracing the complexities of re-entry, fostering a holistic approach to supporting scholars as they navigate their paths back home.

Dissemination of Research

Throughout my academic journey, I have actively shared my research across various platforms. I have delivered presentations at international conferences, participated in UWS seminars, showcased my work at the University of the West of Scotland's (UWS) Research Festival through poster presentation, and competed in the Three Minute Thesis (3MT) competitions at UWS and Skills Development Scotland (SDS). These experiences have refined my ability to convey complex ideas with clarity and impact while broadening the reach of my research among diverse audiences. Looking ahead, I am committed to transforming my thesis into a published book, aiming to contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and provide a valuable resource for scholars and practitioners.

Practical Engagement and Support Initiatives

My role as a student buddy at my university, where I assist international students in adjusting to life in the UK, has profoundly deepened my understanding of the challenges associated with transitions. This experience has highlighted the importance of providing tailored support to individuals navigating new cultural, academic, and social environments. Recognising the parallels between these challenges and those faced by students returning to their home countries, I was inspired by my research to take proactive steps in addressing these needs.

As part of this effort, I organised a workshop where I introduced key findings from my research and provided support to students preparing for their return home. This workshop created a platform for open dialogue, allowing students to share their concerns, ask questions, and receive guidance tailored to their specific re-entry challenges. The session equipped participants with practical strategies to manage their transitions and fostered a sense of community and shared understanding among attendees. Feedback from the workshop was overwhelmingly positive, with participants expressing greater confidence and preparedness for their return journeys.

Encouraged by the success of this initiative, I shared my experience with my line manager and suggested the development of a formal programme to assist students returning to their home countries. My manager was enthusiastic about the idea, acknowledging it as a unique and innovative approach to addressing an often-overlooked phase of international education. Such a programme could provide valuable resources, mentorship, and peer support, significantly easing the reintegration process and enhancing the overall well-being and success of returning students.

Furthermore, alongside my role as a student buddy, where I supported new international students in adjusting to university life, I actively participated in the Strategy 2030 Student Reference Group at UWS. This initiative allowed me to share valuable insights and perspectives drawn from my experience as an international student. Collaborating with the university in this group, I engaged in discussions that aligned to grow global impact. Specifically, I put emphasis on the importance of research like mine in understanding the nuanced experiences of international graduates and their reintegration processes. I proposed that universities, through tailored policies and initiatives, play a crucial role in supporting both outgoing and returning students, highlighting the value of fostering global academic mobility while addressing its long-term implications.

Through these experiences, I have seen firsthand how targeted support can make a meaningful difference. My research and practical engagement have reaffirmed the importance of holistic, student-centred interventions that address both the emotional and logistical aspects of re-entry.

These insights underscore the potential for institutions to play a transformative role in supporting the transitions of international students and returning scholars alike.

Reflections on using IPA

Upon reflecting on my experience with Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA), I acknowledge both notable advantages and limitations that are important to consider in the context of my research on the experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees. One of the most significant strengths of IPA is its capacity to provide a vivid and empathic representation of participants' experiences, which is crucial for understanding the complex realities faced by individuals transitioning back to Algeria after studying abroad. This methodology allows for the creation of engaging narratives for each returnee, capturing the nuanced challenges and opportunities they encounter during their reintegration process.

The impactful quotes derived during the analysis phase have profoundly influenced my understanding, prompting continuous contemplation and interpretation throughout the writing and analytical procedures. Each participant's story adds depth to the overarching narrative of returning home, enriching the exploration of how their international experiences shape their identities and professional paths upon re-entry.

Moreover, IPA's primary merit lies in the transparency of the results, which are solidly grounded in the data collected from these doctoral returnees. This transparency not only enhances the trustworthiness of the findings but also encourages readers to engage in the hermeneutic circle. This engagement enables them to comprehend the sense-making efforts of both the participants and myself as the researcher. Such involvement is particularly important in my study, as it fosters a deeper appreciation of the personal and collective narratives that emerge from the participants' experiences. Ultimately, this contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of international education on their lives.

However, I also recognise certain limitations inherent in my use of IPA. The intensive nature of the analysis phase posed significant challenges, necessitating careful time management throughout the research process. Achieving a thorough analysis while remaining mindful of overall project timelines proved to be a delicate balance. Despite these challenges, the insights gained through this qualitative approach have been invaluable in illuminating the complexities of the reintegration experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees and underscoring the importance of their voices in the discourse on international education.

The intensive characteristics of IPA's analysis phase required an iterative methodology, often necessitating my return to transcripts and earlier analytical phases, particularly when handling a larger sample size. This dedication to comprehensive analysis, essential for reaching saturation, resulted in delays in the completion of my thesis. Moving forward, I recognise the need to combine analytical depth with practical scheduling constraints.

Furthermore, the analytical procedure became progressively challenging, especially when engaging with a substantial sample of participants under time constraints. This complexity required a heightened level of concentration and organisation, presenting distinct obstacles throughout the research journey.

While IPA provided a profound and insightful analysis of participants' experiences, the inherent demands and limitations of the methodology shaped the direction of my research. I aim to enhance the balance between analytical depth and practical timelines. Recognising these factors not only fosters my development as a researcher but also improves the quality and trustworthiness of future studies.

Reflections on Personal and Professional Growth

At the beginning of this thesis, I quoted a statement that has inspired and guided me throughout this journey: "A PhD can be completed by anyone with a certain degree of intelligence and, importantly, the commitment necessary to persevere through challenges" (Grix, 2004, p.11). This sentiment resonated deeply with me as I embarked on my doctoral journey, reminding me that while intelligence is important, it is the qualities of resilience, determination, and adaptability that truly define success in such a transformative process.

As Grix aptly notes, this commitment must also be accompanied by an open and enquiring mind, a willingness to take criticism, and the ability to listen and learn from others. These words have remained a guiding principle throughout my PhD experience, shaping how I navigated both the academic rigours and personal challenges of this journey. Reflecting on these qualities, I realise how pivotal they have been not only in overcoming obstacles but also in embracing growth and self-discovery during this transformative chapter of my life.

This study has been both a personal and academic endeavour, shaping my understanding of the obstacles and opportunities associated with re-entry. Engaging with the experiences of others has prepared me for my upcoming return to Algeria, enhancing my ability to anticipate the adjustments and contributions I can make. I hope that this work inspires future research and policy

initiatives aimed at supporting the next generation of returning scholars, enabling them to thrive upon their return.

The experiences and insights shared by the participants underscore the transformative power of academic mobility. Internationalisation has become a cornerstone of modern higher education, providing scholars with opportunities to engage with diverse ideas, innovative research methods, and global networks (Altbach and Knight, 2007; De Wit *et al.*, 2015). These experiences extend beyond academic growth they reshape professional identities, broaden perspectives, and foster a deeper understanding of different cultures. For many, including myself, the time spent abroad is not just about acquiring new knowledge; it is about evolving as individuals and professionals in ways that are both profound and enduring.

However, I am also mindful that returning home can be just as challenging as the journey abroad. As I prepare for my re-entry into the academic landscape of Algeria, I anticipate navigating a range of adjustments, from cultural re-adaptation to aligning my newly acquired skills with local academic expectations. Like many of the participants in this study, I expect to encounter the occasional disconnect between the advanced approaches learned abroad and the practices and structures at home. These challenges reinforce the importance of viewing internationalisation as a two-way process: one that involves both outward mobility and the equally critical support needed upon return.

To fully realise the benefits of internationalisation, institutions and policymakers need to invest in the reintegration phase of returning scholars. Providing targeted support, such as mentorship programmes, tailored onboarding, and opportunities to engage with international peers, can make a significant difference. These resources not only ease the transition but also enable returnees to maximise their global experiences to enrich their home institutions. Although I have not yet returned, I can already see how valuable such support will be in helping me bridge the gap between my international experiences and the local academic environment, empowering me to contribute effectively to my field.

Returning scholars have the potential to be catalysts for change. They bring back innovative teaching methods, new research perspectives, and a global network of contacts that can benefit their home institutions. They can serve as bridges between their countries and the wider academic community, fostering cross-border collaborations and enhancing the international profile of their institutions. As I prepare for my return, I am eager to share my experiences and insights from abroad, contributing to a broader dialogue on the value of global academic engagement.

Supporting returning scholars requires more than facilitating adjustment; it involves recognising the academic, professional, and relational value they bring back to their home institutions. Reintegration is not merely a personal transition but a structurally mediated process that shapes how global academic experiences are translated into local practice.

By foregrounding the lived experiences of Algerian doctoral returnees, this thesis demonstrates that return is not the conclusion of mobility but a new phase of negotiation, contribution, and identity recalibration. In doing so, it reframes internationalisation as a full mobility cycle one that extends beyond departure and requires sustained institutional engagement upon return.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

School of Education and Social Sciences

Research Informed Consent Form

Title of the study: “**Home and Away: The Lived Experiences of UK-based Algerian Doctoral Graduates on Returning Home to Algeria.**”.

Ethics Approval Number: 18017

Researcher`s name: Amina Manal Zidi

Researcher Email: B00376487@studentmail.uws.ac.uk

Informed Consent

This is a consent form for a PhD research project Titled: **Home and Away: The Lived Experiences of UK-based Algerian Doctoral Graduates on Returning Home to Algeria.** It is a research project at the University of the West of Scotland carried out by a PhD student Amina Manal Zidi. By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and instruction sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the Information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time up to three months after completing the study without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication resulting from this work will not identify me personally.	
I consent to the processing of my personal information (age, sex, and contact details) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I understand in the event of the researcher having a follow-up question with two weeks of the interview, I give permission to be recontacted by email to consider that specific question.	
I agree to have my voice digitally recorded.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

Signatures:

Name of participant: Name of researcher: Amina Manal Zidi

Date: Date:

Signature: Signature:

Appendix 2

School of Education and Social Sciences

Participant Information Sheet

Title of the study: “Home and Away: The Lived Experiences of UK-based Algerian Doctoral Graduates on Returning Home to Algeria.”.

Introduction

Amina Manal Zidi, a PhD candidate at the University of the West of Scotland in the school of Education and Social Sciences I am conducting this research project as a part of my degree.

Research Aim

The primary aim of this study is to explore the lived experiences of UK-based Algerian doctoral graduates upon their return to Algeria. The study seeks to understand how these individuals navigate the complex process of reintegration, both professionally and personally, and to identify the factors that influence their experiences.

Research Objectives

- To explore the personal, professional, and cultural challenges faced by returning Algerian doctoral graduates.
- To understand the coping mechanisms and strategies employed by these graduates to navigate the challenges of reintegration.

- To assess the impact of their return on the academic and research landscape in Algeria

What will you do in this research project?

The participation in this research study is voluntary and those of you who choose to be take part will have the right to withdraw up to three months once the data is analysed without penalty of any form, bearing in mind that no notifications or justifications are required for your withdrawal. In addition, you have the option to refuse to answer any question(s) to which you do not wish to provide a response regarding it (them). Moreover, if there is a question that you are unsure of, you should inquire further for clarification. In the event that you encounter a problem, you have the option of requesting that the recording be halted. As you have the option to request to terminate the interview if you believe that, you will be unable to continue it.

When you agree to take part in this study, you are than required to do a semi-structured interview that will last between 60 to 90 minutes, and will have open questions, which required more discussion, explanation and expanded answers. In the event of the researcher having a follow-up question with two weeks of the interview, you give permission to be recontacted by email to consider that specific question.

Why have you been invited to take part?

Your participation is kindly required in this study, since you were a fully funded Algerian student by the Algerian government, obtained a Ph.D. degree from the UK and have returned back to Algeria. The aim of the present study is to shed light on the lived experiences upon your home return. Thus, your participation will have an appreciated contribution to the proposed study project.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no potential risks to you in participating in this study, except devoting some time to the interview. Bear in mind that all provided data are anonymous and you can choose to skip or not to answer questions that bother you in any way.

What will happen to the information in this research project?

All sort of information and data collected from the participants will be completely anonymous and firmly confidential. They will be in a password-secured laptop and securely stored within the locked office at the university or my locked room. They will be disposed of six months after the end of the project.

What will happen next?

If now you are happy to take part and willing to proceed, first you will have to sign a consent form to confirm your participation. I am very grateful yet thankful for your involvement. Once this study is completed, report on its findings will be available on request for those who wish to read more about it.

Thanks for your patience in reading through these Information, if you have any questions/concerns, during or after the data collection process, contact details are available, or if you wish to contact an independent person for further details please contact:

Supervisor: Pr. Colin Clark Researcher Contact Details:

School of Social Sciences Miss Amina Manal Zidi, PhD candidate University of the West of
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Appendix 3

School: Education and Social Sciences – Paisley Campus.

Research Study Title: Home and Away: The Lived Experiences of UK-based Algerian Doctoral Graduates on Returning Home to Algeria.

Researcher's Name: Amina Manal Zidi.

Semi-Structured Interview Questions Draft

Interview Questions List:

Background information

1. Can you please tell me about yourself and your background (family, job, Profile)?
2. How long have you stayed in the UK?
3. How long have you spent in Algeria since you returned from the UK?
4. For how long are you working in university in Algeria?

Socio cultural and personal experiences

1. How would you describe your home transition after your sojourn in UK?
-Could you recall your experience when you first arrived in Algeria? How would you describe your feeling? (Happy, unhappy, shocked)
2. On returning to Algeria, how do you feel you have changed as a person?
-Were you socially accepted?
-can you tell me if people in Algeria notice this change? What was their impression?

3. In what ways has study abroad impacted your new life?
 - a) Socially
 - b) Your worldview
 - c) Your attitudes towards others.
4. What do you think have you gained from your study abroad programme?
5. Can you tell me if you have experienced any social and personal challenges?

Academic experiences

6. How would you describe your readjustment to the new workplace? Are the working conditions appealing?
7. Could you tell me if you have experienced any challenges that hampered your reintegration into your work place?
8. Have you tried to implement and transfer the previously acquired knowledge to the new work environment?
 - If yes, how?
 - Was it useful?
9. How have these gains influenced your life and career over time? What do they believe have been the most profound changes personally and professionally?

Secondary list of questions:

1. If you have any challenges, what are the coping strategies you have used to adjust to the work environment?
2. How your transnational experience did affects the way that you work as a lecturer now?
3. Can you tell me if you have established a good network with your colleagues?
 - How did these university members perceive you?

4. Was your experience valued? /undermined?
5. Are you maintaining contact with other Algerian doctoral students' returnees?
6. -If yes, how do you view your re-entry compared to them and others with the same experience? What is common in your experiences?
7. What would you recommend to other doctoral students' returnees?
8. Is there anything else that you think would be important for me to know in understanding the experience of return home after the sojourn in UK?
9. Do you have any question for me, and is there anything important that we have not already discussed?

Appendix 4

21/06/2022

Dear Amina Manal Zidi,

Your application 18017: An Interpretive phenomenological Analysis Investigation on the Lived Experiences of Algerian Sponsored Doctoral students upon Home

Return”, submission reference 15403, has been approved, with conditions, by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. You may proceed with your study provided

your supervisor confirms in writing that you have met the conditions outlined below:

Title Comment

Where will the proposed research take place?

Discuss the most efficient and realistic plan with your supervisors

Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)

As required, add a justification for the research, drawing from your knowledge of relevant literature

Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)

You say participants can withdraw at any time. What about once you have analysed and written up the results? Set a time limit in consultation with your supervisors.

Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)

Your sampling isn't clear. How will you choose the eight participants? Are they the only people funded through that scheme? Or is there a bigger population that you then need to take a sample from? If there are only eight, then you aren't studying a sample, you are studying the population. Further, it isn't clear who will take part in your pilot study. Discuss with your supervisors and provide clarity on these issues.

Please explain/justify your intended sample size:

As indicated above, it would be may to get a sense of the wider population.

How many PhD students are funded in this way? Discuss with your supervisors.

Please explain/justify your intended sample size:

You are saying ten participants now but you said eight earlier. Be consistent or clear.

Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:

Beginning analysis during the data collection process is an option within the qualitative paradigm. Discuss with your supervisors.

Please explain how you will analyse,

present/disseminate the data you intend to

collect:

You MUST add any proposed dissemination here and duplicate the information in the PIS to ensure that potential participants are giving informed consent.

Remember, also, dissemination activities that may take place during the process of research.

Please explain how you will analyse,

present/disseminate the data you intend to

collect:

This section asks how you will disseminate the data/results. Please provide details.

Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire

or Interview Schedule

Question three seems odd because I think you are asking 'are you the same person after returning home?', but you use third person. Consider changing.

Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire

or Interview Schedule

In consultation with your supervisors, review the questions for clarity and plain language, defining terms as necessary e.g. will everyone know what sojourn means?

Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire

or Interview Schedule

It isn't clear why you are asking them to commit time for interview before and after their return. I don't think you made this clear in the methodology above. It is

particularly unclear because your questions before their return are written in past tense, as if they had already had the experience and have returned home. Can you make this clear. Also maybe consider whether two phases are necessary, given you are asking people to give up their time to participate. If you think it is necessary, justify in the section where you outline your project.

Please provide details of how you will

obtain this consent and the information you

Make sure that you encourage potential participants to ask any questions and provide mechanisms for doing this.

Page 1 of 2

will provide to potential participants to

allow them to make an informed choice

about whether or not to participate in your research.

Please provide details of how you will

obtain this consent and the information you

will provide to potential participants to

allow them to make an informed choice

about whether or not to participate in your research.

See previous comment about saying they can withdraw at any time.

Please provide details of how you will

obtain this consent and the information you

will provide to potential participants to

allow them to make an informed choice
about whether or not to participate in your
research.

You need to give them the participant information sheet and consent form
BEFORE you ask them to agree.

Please upload a copy of the Participant
Information Sheet(s)

Consider with your supervisor whether there might be any other identifying data
that should be protected (locations, personal characteristics job descriptions
etc). If so, note this on the application and consent form, with detail on the PIS
of how you will do this.

Please upload a copy of the Participant
Information Sheet(s)

You have said on the PIS that follow-up interviews might be required but you
don't say this anywhere on your ethics application. As with the pilot study and
other things mentioned here, there needs to be consistency across all parts of
your ethics application. Please make required changes.

Please upload a copy of your Consent
Form(s)

Your consent form is inconsistent with the rest of your application. Here you are
saying they can withdraw up to one month after taking part. Make sure that all
information is consistent across the ethics submission.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's
approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Page 2 of 2

Appendix 5

Text example for analysis step 1

“.....So I had lots of difficulties, I also I also. I always remember. That's, the this is the first shock, but I used to give my hands to people whenever I meet them in the street for asking. This is completely Algerian, and this is completely Arab. And then I started, you know, integrating with the English society. Back to the question the transition in Algeria. Actually, I found the transition at the beginning very normal, because the thing which stopped me going back to the UK was COVID-19, and then I was very patient, waiting for Covid to end, so that's I go back to England. Finish with all the final, you know, procedures in terms of getting my diploma attending the graduation ceremony. Bringing the books back to the University library, and so on. Saying goodbye to people, and so on and so forth. And then I found myself in Algeria. I had to accept. You know, I was actually busy because my father was sick. And I. He suffered from pancreatic cancer. So I have to be with him. I had to carry him to the doctor, and to the hospitals, and so on, and so forth. And then I started looking for, you know, a job because I can't stay without Job forever. And then I started, you know, doing the equivalence and waiting for my designation, recruitment,

13:05:15 Okay.

13:05:15 So in terms of culture, in terms of culture, I didn't actually, you know, feel the transition, because I am already a member in the Arabic Islamic Algerian culture. So actually, I didn't I didn't find any problems with the transition; the cultural, social transition.

13:05: 35 Okay. And you said that. You had like, kind of culture shock when you have, When you went to the Uk. And after, like you returned to Algeria, did you have this?

13:05:50 Actually, actually, it wasn't. It wasn't a culture shock. I studied about the British culture which history in advance. It was just a, The transition was not actually smooth at the beginning, mainly because most of the people who are in England don't speak the RP, so they do have a accent which is the Cockney. So I found it a little hard to understand the language spoken by people in the streets. I also didn't know, but when I meet people I just need to say, Hi! Or Hello! Instead of giving my hand. That was Algerian, and it was, you know, unintentional. So I did it without the intention, but then I started adapting, and the adaptation didn't take time. Honestly!"

Appendix 6

Emergent Personal Experiential Themes: Autumn's Transcript Extract

Transcript Excerpt	Exploratory Notes (Descriptive, Linguistic, Conceptual)	Emergent Personal Experiential Themes (PETs)
<p>"It was very emotional... I cried because I made it home with that Dr. title, but things had changed so much."</p>	<p>Reflects mixed emotions of pride and disorientation upon return. The repetition of 'I cried' emphasises the duality of her emotions. Tension between personal achievement and changes in familiar spaces.</p>	<p>Emotional Rollercoaster of Achievement and Alienation</p>
<p>"I noticed my nieces and nephews didn't recognize me... I felt like I was missing something."</p>	<p>Highlights a disconnect from family due to prolonged absence. The use of 'didn't recognize me' emphasises feelings of loss. Explores how physical absence impacts familial ties and personal identity.</p>	<p>Familial Disconnect and Identity Displacement</p>
<p>"In the UK, I felt settled... I knew the streets, but back home I felt lost, even in my neighbourhood."</p>	<p>Captures a shift in her sense of home and belonging. Contrasts 'settled' with 'lost' to highlight the reversal of comfort. Examines how home and belonging are redefined through lived experiences abroad.</p>	<p>Redefining Home and Belonging through Reverse Cultural Adjustment</p>
<p>"People said, 'You've changed.' I used to be shy, but now I'm outspoken and confident."</p>	<p>Highlights personal growth and transformation. Repetition of 'changed' reflects an emphasis on identity shifts. Explores how international experiences reshape self-perception and interpersonal relationships.</p>	<p>Personal Growth and Transformation through International Experience</p>

<p>"Students here don't value education... They take it for granted because it's free."</p>	<p>Reflects disappointment in students' lack of appreciation for education. Phrases like 'take it for granted' convey frustration. Examines the disconnect between access to education and student engagement.</p>	<p>Frustration with Students' Lack of Interest Toward Education</p>
<p>"In the UK, students were more proactive... Here, I have to force students to engage with the material."</p>	<p>Stresses contrasting teaching experiences between Algeria and the UK. Words like "force" emphasise the difficulty of motivating students. Explores the challenges of adapting pedagogical approaches to a different context.</p>	<p>Adapting Teaching Strategies to Engage Reluctant Students</p>

Appendix 7: Mapping PETs to GETs

GET	Subthemes	Participants and PETs
Cultural and Social Re-adaptation	1. Navigating Transition and Cultural Reconnection	<p>Autumn: “I felt like a stranger in my own home.”</p> <p>Ahmed: “Relearning cultural norms was harder than I thought.”</p> <p>Samar: “The shift from UK life to Algerian life was overwhelming.”</p>
Personal Growth	1. Broadened Perspectives and Social Growth	<p>Hiba: “Living abroad changed how I view the world.”</p> <p>Mohamed: “I gained so much from meeting people from diverse cultures.”</p> <p>Amani: “My experiences taught me how to relate better to others.”</p>
	2. Building Resilience and Independence	<p>Karim: “Living on my own in the UK taught me resilience.” Autumn: “I became more independent through my struggles abroad.” Yasmine: “I learned to rely on myself during hard times.”</p>
Psychological Wellbeing and Coping in Re-entry	1. Coping with Transition and Emotional Toll	<p>Samar: “Adapting back home was mentally exhausting.”</p> <p>Kenza: “I had to develop coping mechanisms to manage the stress.”</p> <p>Insaf: “The transition wasn’t just physical, it was emotional.”</p>
	2. The Impact of COVID-19 on Emotional Wellbeing	<p>Maya: “Isolation during quarantine added another layer of stress.”</p> <p>Hanaa: “COVID made an already hard return much worse.”</p> <p>Karim: “Being cut off from friends and support systems during the pandemic was emotionally exhausting.”</p>

Appendix 8: Mapping PETs to GETs

GET	Subthemes	Participants and PETs
<p>Academic Reintegration and Adaptation</p>	<p>1. Academic Disconnect and Tensions with Colleagues</p>	<p>Hiba: “My ideas were dismissed as ‘foreign.’”</p> <p>Amani: “There’s a clear divide between returnees and locally trained colleagues.”</p> <p>Karim: “Integrating into the academic culture was harder than expected.”</p>
	<p>2. Managing Expectations and Academic Realities</p>	<p>Manel: “The academic environment is rigid and lacks innovation.”</p> <p>Wahiba: “I was disappointed by the lack of collaboration among colleagues.”</p> <p>Akram: “I had to adjust to different expectations here compared to abroad.”</p>
<p>Innovation and Resistance in Academic Practice</p>	<p>1. Overcoming Resistance and Implementing Progressive Teaching Methods</p>	<p>Samar: “Introducing workshops met resistance from colleagues.”</p> <p>Yasmine: “I implemented active learning techniques despite skepticism.”</p> <p>Maya: “Teaching methods I learned abroad faced pushback.”</p>
	<p>2. Support Networks and Positive Workplace Environment</p>	<p>Ahmed: “Having supportive colleagues made the transition easier.”</p> <p>Hanaa: “Collaborating with like-minded colleagues helped me adapt.”</p> <p>Samar: “A positive work environment allowed me to thrive professionally.”</p>

Bureaucratic and Credentialing Challenges	1. Navigating Bureaucratic Barriers	<p>Hanaa: “Getting the required documents was an exhausting process.”</p> <p>Akram: “The bureaucracy slowed down my reintegration.”</p> <p>Kenza: “The administrative hurdles made everything harder.”</p>
	2. Credential Recognition Challenges	<p>Amine: “Having my qualifications recognized took months.”</p> <p>Mohamed: “The constant need to prove myself was frustrating.”</p> <p>Autumn: “Credentialing processes were unnecessarily complicated.”</p>
Professional Growth and Resource Constraints	1. Application of Experience and Skills	<p>Samar: “My international teaching experiences enhanced my classroom methods.”</p> <p>Karim: “I used my UK-acquired skills to improve local teaching practices.”</p> <p>Insaf: “My training abroad made me a better educator here.”</p>
‘	2. Limited Resources and Teaching Infrastructure	<p>Wahiba: “We lack even basic teaching resources.”</p> <p>Amine: “The infrastructure here doesn’t support quality teaching.”</p> <p>Yasmine: “It’s challenging to innovate with such limited resources.”</p>
	3. Navigating Professional Challenges Amidst COVID-19	<p>Ahmed: “COVID disrupted everything and made reintegration harder.”</p> <p>Kenza: “The pandemic highlighted the gaps in our academic system.”</p>

